

A Neural Network-Based Multi-Label Classifier for Protein Function Prediction

Shahab Tahzeeb

Dept. of Computer & Information Systems Engineering
NED University of Engineering & Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
stahzeeb@neduet.edu.pk

Shehzad Hasan

Dept. of Computer & Information Systems Engineering
NED University of Engineering & Technology
Karachi, Pakistan
shasan@neduet.edu.pk

Abstract-Knowledge of the functions of proteins plays a vital role in gaining a deep insight into many biological studies. However, wet lab determination of protein function is prohibitively laborious, time-consuming, and costly. These challenges have created opportunities for automated prediction of protein functions, and many computational techniques have been explored. These techniques entail excessive computational resources and turnaround times. The current study compares the performance of various neural networks on predicting protein function. These networks were trained and tested on a large dataset of reviewed protein entries from nine bacterial phyla, obtained from the Universal Protein Resource Knowledgebase (UniProtKB). Each protein instance was associated with multiple terms of the molecular function of Gene Ontology (GO), making the problem a multilabel classification one. The results in this dataset showed the superior performance of single-layer neural networks having a modest number of neurons. Moreover, a useful set of features that can be deployed for efficient protein function prediction was discovered.

Keywords-gene ontology; molecular function term; multi-label classification; neural network; protein function prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

Understanding proteins' functions plays a vital role in acquiring insights of the molecular mechanisms operating in both physiological and ailing medical conditions. As a result, this understanding substantiates the discovery of drugs in different diseases [1]. However, predicting protein functions is an arduous task. The fact is markedly implied by the incredibly large number of unannotated protein entries hosted by the most comprehensive protein database, the Universal Protein Resource Knowledgebase (UniProtKB) [2]. This is mainly due to the reliance on traditional experimental annotation techniques carried out by molecular biologists. The gap between reviewed and unreviewed protein sequences is widening due to the data deluge from high-throughput state-of-the-art sequencing techniques [1, 3-5]. The pressing demands for computational methods on the functional annotation of proteins have paved the way for significant contributions by computer science researchers. Many computational techniques employing machine learning for functional annotation of proteins have been utilized in the literature. The principal difference between various approaches lies in the set of

features pursued by different investigators. This section presents a brief summary of some of the most prominent efforts in this area.

An ensemble of Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) was proposed in [1], where each DNN worked on a different set of features from the dataset. The predictions of different DNNs were then voted to arrive at the final protein function prediction. A DNN for the hierarchical multilabel classification of protein functions designed to perform well even with a limited number of training samples was presented in [3]. In [4], a DNN was introduced to learn features from word embedding of protein sequences, based on the concept of Natural Language Processing (NLP), using sequence similarity profiles as additional features to locate proteins. Authors in [5] established the efficacy of exploiting any interrelationships among different functional terms. For instance, different functional classes were found to coexist with some proteins suggesting a mutual relationship. Furthermore, a quantification model of these relations was proposed, using a functional similarity measure and a framework to capitalize on it for the eventual prediction of protein functions. A classification technique based on a neural network coupled with a Support Vector Machine (SVM) was demonstrated in [6], utilizing a bi-directional Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network to generate fixed-length protein vectors out of variable-sized sequences and deal with the challenges posed by the variable length of protein sequences. In [7], protein sequence motifs were used to build a deep convolutional network and predict protein function, while the authors claimed to have built the best performing model for the cellular component classes. The significance of Protein-Protein Interaction (PPI) and time-course gene expression data as powerful predictors for the prediction of protein function was shown in [8]. A method, called Dynamic Weighted Interactome Network (DWIN), was proposed, that in addition to PPI and gene expression data, took also into account information related to protein domains and complexes to improve the prediction performance. In [9], clustering was applied on a PPI network for the prediction of protein function. A protein graph model was shown in [10], constructed of protein structure, with each node representing a cluster of amino acid residues. However, the idea of using an accuracy metric for evaluation is generally misleading. In [11], an active learning approach was explored for the prediction of

protein function using a PPI network. This method operated in two phases: Spectral clustering was used to cluster the PPI network followed by the application of the betweenness centrality measure for labeling within each cluster, and then the labeled protein data were used by a classification algorithm. Associations between functions in a PPI network were used in [12], stating that multiple function labels assigned to proteins were not independent and their coexistence could be used effectively to predict protein function. A deep semantic text representation was presented in [13], with various pieces of information extracted from protein sequences such as homology, motifs, and domains. Protein function prediction was carried out using a consensus between text-based and sequence-based methods. In [14], a classifier using cumulative iterations was proposed, based on its semantic similarity with the term Gene Ontology (GO). Each prediction was followed by updating and optimizing scores of characteristic terms in the set of GO annotations, which, in turn, led to improved future predictions. The dissimilarity of protein functions, rather than conventional similarity measures, was used in [15] to segregate rare and frequently occurring classes of functions. This technique worked well for imbalanced datasets.

The notable contributions cited above are just a handful of numerous praiseworthy efforts towards the prediction of protein function. These endeavors differ in terms of the protein information utilized by the corresponding systems and the computational or time complexities of the classification models. The current paper presents a neural network-based multi-label classifier for the prediction of protein function by training and testing several neural networks on a large dataset [16]. The results indicate that a neural network with a single hidden layer achieved remarkable prediction performance with nominal computational complexity. This makes its implementation viable on systems with modest hardware capabilities. Consequently, the time required for the classification task is in the order of seconds.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Dataset

The dataset adopted from [16] includes 121,378 protein instances. These labeled protein examples were extracted from UniProtKB [2], a comprehensive worldwide repository of protein information. These protein entries pertain to 9 bacterial phyla, namely Actinobacteria, Bacteroidetes, Chlamydiae, Cyanobacteria, Firmicutes, Fusobacteria, Proteobacteria, Spirochaetes, and Tenericutes. Each instance in the dataset had 9,890 features. These features included the sequence of amino acids making up the corresponding protein, compositions of amino acids, dipeptides and tripeptides; compositions of five groups of amino acids, i.e. aliphatic, aromatic, positively charged, negatively charged, uncharged, and various structural and physiochemical properties derived from the amino acid sequence. In addition, some features quantify conjoint triads. A conjoint triad is a unit of three successive amino acids such that each amino acid in the unit belongs to one of the seven groups formed on the basis of the dipole and volume scale [17]. These characteristic values indicate the strength of interaction between the amino acids of these 7 groups. The feature set also contains pseudo amino acid compositions for the corresponding

protein. As suggested in [18], these numbers overcome the loss of sequence order effect in a protein caused by considering just plain amino acid compositions. Moreover, there are also 541 motifs included in the features. These are small segments in proteins' tertiary structure that are frequently found in different proteins. These similar patterns are associated with the structural or functional roles of proteins.

There are 1,739 binary labels associated with each protein instance. These labels correspond to GO terms belonging to the Molecular Function (MF) category. The GO is a categorization of biological functions using three broad classes, i.e. Molecular Function (MF), Cellular Component (CC), and Biological Process (BP), generally referred to as GO terms [19]. The molecular function term specifies a biochemical activity performed by a gene product, without taking into account the time and space dimensions of this activity. The enzyme is an example of the MF term. The CC refers to the location of the biochemical activity of a gene product in the cell. Ribosome and nuclear membrane are two such examples. BP, an all-encompassing term, defines a biological objective to which activities of various gene products contribute. Cell growth and maintenance serve as examples the BP term.

B. Data Preprocessing

The Comma Separated Values (CSV) files for 9 different bacterial phyla were combined to obtain a single Pandas' data frame object using the Pandas data analysis library in Python [20]. Duplicate rows were removed from the data frame, which was then converted to an array using the scientific computing library NumPy in Python [21]. The feature values were then scaled using the standard scaler available in the scikit-learn library in Python [22]. Data scaling was investigated using normalization and robust scaler, but these data scaling techniques proved inferior to the standard scaling technique.

C. Features Partitioning

The neural networks were trained on 3 sets of features. The objective of partitioning features into various subsets was to test the hypothesis that compositions of amino acids, dipeptides, and tripeptides are sufficient to predict protein functions. $F = \{F_1, F_2, F_3\}$ represented the set of features used to train different models, where F_1 was the entire set of 9,890 features, and F_2 was the set of 8,420 features that contained only compositions of amino acids, dipeptides, and tripeptides. The set $F_3 = F_1 - F_2$ contained 1,470 features consisting of various properties and characteristics derived from proteins as described in subsection A.

D. Neural Networks

A variety of neural networks was selected, differing in the number of hidden layers and neurons in each layer to train the protein function classification system on datasets corresponding to each feature set F_1 , F_2 , and F_3 . The experimental results are given in Section III. It was observed that the simplest neural network containing a single hidden layer demonstrated better performance on this dataset compared to neural networks having more hidden layers. The optimal number of neurons in this single hidden layer was experimentally determined to be just 5% of the total input and output neurons for feature sets F_1 and F_2 for the best performing

neural network. However, for the F_3 feature set, the optimal number of neurons in the single hidden layer of the best performing neural network turned out to be 50% of the total of input and output neurons.

Once the optimal number of neurons in a single hidden layer was determined, the addition of another hidden layer was utilized to observe any potential boost in performance. The number of neurons in the second hidden layer was chosen to be 50% of the first hidden layer. This was done to ensure that the network captured the most important features for prediction. Table I summarizes various single-hidden layer neural networks trained and tested on the F_1 feature set, i.e. the entire set of features from the dataset. The reference computer for all time and memory size measurements presented is a Core i7-8700 at 3.2 GHz 6-core processor.

TABLE I. SINGLE-HIDDEN LAYER MODELS TRAINED ON THE F_1 FEATURE SET

Model	Neurons ¹	Size (MB)	Training time (sec)	Prediction time (sec)
M1	1	16	1950	2.25
M2	5	77	2655	6.03
M3	10	154	3920	7.51
M4	15	232	4860	9.75
M5	25	386	8820	13.6
M6	50	773	12175	21.8
M7	75	1130	15400	31.6

1. Expressed as percentage of input + output neurons

Table II presents the M8 neural network with two hidden layers trained on F_1 . This model was constructed by adding another hidden layer to the best performing single-hidden layer neural network M2 to explore any performance gain. The second hidden layer had 50% neurons of the first hidden layer in an attempt to capture the optimal features best suited for the prediction task.

TABLE II. TWO-LAYER MODEL TRAINED ON THE F_1 FEATURE SET

Model	Size (MB)	Training time (sec)	Prediction time (sec)
M8	74	2120	5.52

Table III summarizes various single-hidden layer neural networks trained and tested on the F_2 feature set, i.e. the compositions of amino acids, dipeptides, and tripeptides in the protein sequence.

TABLE III. SINGLE-HIDDEN LAYER MODELS TRAINED ON THE F_2 FEATURE SET

Model	Neurons ¹	Size (MB)	Training time (sec)	Prediction time (sec)
M9	5	60	2760	5
M10	10	118	3480	6.31
M11	25	295	7920	11.1
M12	50	590	15000	17.8
M13	60	708	15855	20.4

1. Expressed as a percentage of input + output neurons

Table IV presents the M14 neural network containing two hidden layers and trained on F_2 . This model was developed by adding another hidden layer to the best performing single

hidden layer neural network M9, to investigate any improvements in the classifier performance. The second hidden layer had 50% neurons of the first hidden layer to exploit the predictors best suited for the prediction task.

TABLE IV. TWO-LAYER MODEL TRAINED ON THE F_2 FEATURE SET

Model	Size (MB)	Training time (sec)	Prediction time (sec)
M14	56	2050	4.76

Table V summarizes several single-hidden layer neural networks trained and tested on the F_3 feature set, i.e. features consisting of various properties and characteristics derived from proteins.

TABLE V. SINGLE-HIDDEN LAYER MODELS TRAINED ON F_3 FEATURE SET

Model	Neurons ¹	Size (MB)	Training time (sec)	Prediction time (sec)
M15	5	6	2750	1.33
M16	10	12	3200	1.58
M17	25	30	5200	2.92
M18	30	35	5270	3.05
M19	50	60	6630	4.20
M20	60	71	7320	4.59

1. Expressed as a percentage of input + output neurons

Table VI presents the M21 neural network having two hidden layers and trained on F_3 . This model was generated by adding another hidden layer to the best performing single hidden layer neural network M19 to discover any potential performance enhancement. The number of neurons in the second hidden layer was chosen to be 50% of the first hidden layer to capitalize on the features best suited for the classification.

TABLE VI. TWO-LAYER MODEL TRAINED ON THE F_3 FEATURE SET

Model	Size (MB)	Training time (sec)	Prediction time (sec)
M21	58	5720	4.64

For each network, we employed the *relu* activation for the hidden layers, the sigmoid activation for the output layer, the *he_uniform* kernel initializer for the hidden layers, and the Adaptive moment estimation (Adam) optimizer with a learning rate of 0.00001.

E. Performance Evaluation

Since a protein example in this dataset can be mapped to more than one binary label, the prediction of protein function is a multilabel classification problem. The dataset is also highly imbalanced due to the overwhelming number of negative examples for each label. Evaluation of such a classification model cannot simply rely on the accuracy of prediction [23, 24]. For example, if a negative class is abundantly prevalent among all examples in an imbalanced dataset, then a naive classifier predicting this class for all examples will easily achieve very high accuracy. The challenge of this inflated accuracy measure becomes aggravated in the case of multilabel classification of imbalanced datasets. This problem was

addressed by defining more meaningful performance measures, namely *precision*, *recall*, *F1 score*, *zero-one loss*, *hamming loss*, and *Matthews Correlation Coefficient*. These measures are defined here.

1) Precision

Precision is defined as the fraction of positively classified instances that are, in effect, positive. This gives a clear picture of a classifier's strength in predicting positive classes. Letting *TP* and *FP* respectively denote the count of true and false positives, *Precision* is calculated as:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (1)$$

The precision of *predict-majority-class-for-all* classifier is thus 0 judiciously penalizing for its shortcoming at predicting the positive minority class. However, any classifier that makes just one positive prediction and ensures its correctness would have 100% precision despite its failure to predict other positive examples. This calls for another classification metric, called *Recall*, also known as *sensitivity*.

2) Recall

Recall is defined as the fraction of positive examples in the dataset classified as positive. Letting *FN* denote the number of false negatives, the *Recall* is given by:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (2)$$

This measure penalizes a classifier that attempts to achieve high precision simply by making a few correct positive predictions.

3) F1 Score

Precision and recall are combined in a single performance measure called *F1 score*, which is their harmonic mean.

$$F1\ score = 2 * \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (3)$$

As the harmonic mean is biased towards lower values, *F1 score* can have a higher value only in the case when both precision and recall have high values. In multi-label classification, there are several ways to average the aforementioned performance metrics on all labels [25, 26]. These are the *micro* average, *macro* average, *weighted* average, and *samples* average as defined below. As usual, the *F1 score* is the harmonic mean of the corresponding precision and recall in each case.

4) Micro Average

This is calculated by counting the number of True Positives (TPs) across the entire set of target labels. If there are *N* samples in the dataset and each sample has *L* binary target labels, then the micro averages of *Precision* and *Recall* are calculated as:

$$Precision_{micro} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N*L} (Y_{pred_i} \wedge Y_{true_i})}{\sum_{i=1}^{N*L} Y_{pred_i}} \quad (4)$$

$$Recall_{micro} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N*L} (Y_{pred_i} \wedge Y_{true_i})}{\sum_{i=1}^{N*L} Y_{true_i}} \quad (5)$$

where *Y_{pred}* and *Y_{true}* are the predicted and actual target labels, respectively. The conjunction operator \wedge ensures the inclusion of only those label instances that are positive in both *Y_{pred}* and *Y_{true}*, i.e. TPs.

5) Macro Average

This averages the *Precision* and *Recall* scores of the individual target labels, giving equal weights to all of them.

$$Precision_{macro} = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{j=1}^L \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (Y_{pred_{ij}} \wedge Y_{true_{ij}})}{\sum_{i=1}^N Y_{pred_{ij}}} \quad (6)$$

$$Recall_{macro} = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{j=1}^L \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (Y_{pred_{ij}} \wedge Y_{true_{ij}})}{\sum_{i=1}^N Y_{true_{ij}}} \quad (7)$$

6) Weighted Average

This averages the *Precision* and *Recall* scores of the individual target labels, using the number of positive instances of each label in the set *Y_{true}* as their weight.

$$Precision_{weighted} = \frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^L w_j} \sum_{j=1}^L \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (Y_{pred_{ij}} \wedge Y_{true_{ij}}) * w_j}{\sum_{i=1}^N Y_{pred_{ij}}} \quad (8)$$

$$Recall_{weighted} = \frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^L w_j} \sum_{j=1}^L \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (Y_{pred_{ij}} \wedge Y_{true_{ij}}) * w_j}{\sum_{i=1}^N Y_{true_{ij}}} \quad (9)$$

where *w_j* denotes the weight, also known as the support of the *j*-th label.

7) Samples Average

It averages the *Precision* and *Recall* scores across the samples.

$$Precision_{samples} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\sum_{j=1}^L (Y_{pred_{ij}} \wedge Y_{true_{ij}})}{\sum_{j=1}^L Y_{pred_{ij}}} \quad (10)$$

$$Recall_{samples} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\sum_{j=1}^L (Y_{pred_{ij}} \wedge Y_{true_{ij}})}{\sum_{j=1}^L Y_{true_{ij}}} \quad (11)$$

This is the most faithful as well as the most conservative performance indicator of the multi-label classifier as it reflects, on the average, how well the classifier performed on each sample. Therefore, the sample averages were used to gauge the performance of the models.

8) Zero-One Loss

For a multi-label classification problem, this measure credits a prediction as correctly classified only when all labels are correctly classified. The loss is zero for a correct prediction. However, if the classifier fails to make a correct prediction even for just one target label, the corresponding loss is 1. It follows that the *zero-one* loss is truly a conservative and highly penalizing performance measure.

$$Loss_{0/1} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \prod_{j=1}^L (Y_{pred_{ij}} \oplus Y_{true_{ij}}) \quad (12)$$

The combination of the product operator \prod and the exclusive-OR operator \oplus ensures that any mismatch between *L* predicted and target labels generates a loss of 1 for any given sample. Otherwise, the loss is zero for a complete match between all predicted and target labels for a given sample.

9) Hamming Loss

This gives the fraction of all incorrectly predicted labels by quantifying the number of incorrect predictions of all labels rather than penalizing individual examples. Hence, if a multi-label classifier incorrectly predicts 1 out of 10 labels for a given instance, the hamming loss for that example is just 1/10 as compared to 1 in the case of zero-one loss. It follows that hamming loss is lenient compared to the stringent zero-one loss.

$$HL = \frac{1}{N*L} \sum_{i=1}^{NL} (Y_{pred_i} \oplus Y_{true_i}) \quad (13)$$

10) Matthews Correlation Coefficient

The Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) is a binary version of Pearson's correlation coefficient [27]. However, multiclass classification problems can also benefit from its extended version [28]. MCC compares ground truth and predicted vectors, considering all possibilities of prediction, i.e. True Positives (TP), True Negatives (TN), False Positives (FP), and False negatives (FN). Therefore, it gives a balanced evaluation of the performance of the classifier. The correlation coefficient lies in the range [-1, +1], with -1 for false prediction, 0 for random prediction, and +1 for correct prediction.

$$MCC = \frac{TP*TN - FP*FN}{\sqrt{(TP+TN)(TP+FN)(FP+TN)(FP+FN)}} \quad (14)$$

The MCC was calculated for every example and its average was used to assess the performance of the classifier on the entire dataset.

11) Consolidated Performance Metric

For the sake of an all-encompassing and more realistic comparison of performance, the aforementioned metrics were combined in a single Consolidated Performance Metric (CPM) as follows:

$$CPM = \frac{F1\ score * MCC}{Loss_{0/1} * HL} \quad (15)$$

The CPM was constructed in the higher, the better way.

III. RESULTS

Table VII shows the performance details of the neural networks (M1 to M21) as the samples averages of Precision (P), Recall (R), F1 score (F1), Zero-One Loss (ZOL), Hamming Loss (HL), MCC, and CPM.

A wide variety of neural networks was trained and tested on a large dataset of proteins. For feature sets F₁ and F₂, it was observed that 5% of the total input and output neurons in the single hidden layer networks exhibited better prediction performance than other single-layer models. These models were designated as M2 and M9, respectively. However, for the feature set F₃, the optimal count of neurons in the hidden layer emerged as 50% of the total input and output neurons. This model was designated as M19. The bar graphs in Figures 1-3 compare the CPM for various neural networks that work on a specific feature set. In each case, the best performing single-layer network was extended by adding a second hidden layer to assess any performance edge. Neurons in the second hidden

layer were the 50% of the first hidden layer to ensure that the most relevant features for prediction play their due role. The blue bars in Figures 1-3 represent the performance of the best performing single-layer networks, while yellow bars show the performance of 2-layer neural networks.

TABLE VII. PERFORMANCE OF NEURAL NETWORKS

Model	P	R	F1	ZOL	HL	MCC	CPM
M1	0.96	0.95	0.95	12.25	0.0159	0.9518	4.6423
M2	0.96	0.96	0.96	11.36	0.0120	0.9576	6.7437
M3	0.96	0.96	0.95	11.64	0.0122	0.9571	6.4028
M4	0.96	0.96	0.95	11.76	0.0122	0.9566	6.3341
M5	0.96	0.96	0.95	11.90	0.0123	0.9568	6.2100
M6	0.96	0.96	0.95	12.55	0.0129	0.9546	5.6016
M7	0.96	0.96	0.95	12.61	0.0132	0.9539	5.4442
M8	0.96	0.95	0.95	12.21	0.0128	0.9535	5.7959
M9	0.94	0.94	0.93	15.85	0.0173	0.9341	3.1681
M10	0.94	0.94	0.93	16.47	0.0179	0.9329	2.9429
M11	0.93	0.94	0.93	16.70	0.0180	0.9318	2.8828
M12	0.93	0.94	0.93	17.30	0.0186	0.9298	2.6873
M13	0.93	0.93	0.93	17.07	0.0183	0.9297	2.7678
M14	0.93	0.93	0.92	17.17	0.0188	0.9279	2.6446
M15	0.96	0.95	0.95	12.43	0.0129	0.9535	5.6492
M16	0.96	0.96	0.96	11.34	0.0117	0.9591	6.9396
M17	0.97	0.96	0.96	10.43	0.0108	0.9614	8.1935
M18	0.97	0.96	0.96	10.66	0.0110	0.9614	7.8709
M19	0.97	0.96	0.96	10.34	0.0107	0.9625	8.3516
M20	0.97	0.96	0.96	10.39	0.0108	0.9621	8.2310
M21	0.97	0.96	0.96	10.95	0.0114	0.9593	7.3775

Fig. 2. Neural networks' comparison on F₂ feature set.

Fig. 3. Neural networks's comparison on F₃ feature set.

F. Optimal Feature Set

The experiments also focused on exploring an optimal set of features for the prediction of protein function. As it was noticed, the F₃ feature set proved to be the best predictor for this multi-label classification. Figure 4 shows a comparison of the best-performing models for each feature set, where M19 on F₃ achieved the best performance.

Fig. 4. Performance comparison of the best performing single-layer models on different feature sets. F₃ proves to be the best predictor set.

G. Classification Threshold

The impact of the classification threshold on the performance of a classifier was examined. The models predict the probability of each target label associated with every instance. These probability values quantify the chance for a given instance to belong to a particular class. These probability values should be translated into binary labels 0 and 1 before the final evaluation of the model. This conversion to binary labels required a threshold or probability cutoff value below which all values are classified as class 0 and equal or greater values are classified as class 1. Classifier performance metrics are profoundly influenced by the choice of this threshold. The impact of the threshold is more pronounced for imbalanced datasets. As the examined dataset is skewed towards more negative examples of each label, the performance of the models was evaluated for various values of thresholds. Figures 5 and 6 show two example plots of samples averages of P, R, and F1

score for models M2 and M19, respectively, against a range of classification thresholds.

Fig. 5. Performance curves of M2 for the F₁ feature set. The choice of classification threshold plays an important role in improving the performance of the classifier.

Fig. 6. The Performance curves of model M19 for the F₃ feature set.

H. Confusion Matrix

The confusion matrix is a visualization of a classifier's performance, as it gives the count of TP, FP, TN, and FN class predictions.

Fig. 7. Confusion matrices of the best-performing model M19 for F₃. Only labels having support more than 1,000 are included.

Figure 7 presents the confusion matrices of select labels in the test dataset for the model M19 that performed best in the F_3 feature set. To highlight the strength of the classifier, only labels whose support exceeded 1,000 in the dataset were chosen

IV. DISCUSSION

The performance comparison of different neural networks on a large protein dataset showed that neural networks having a single hidden layer and a modest number of neurons achieved superior performance on this specific dataset than relatively more complex networks. The number of neurons in the single hidden layer was empirically determined. The rigorous experimentation revealed that only 5% of the total input and output neurons were adequate in single-hidden-layer models operating on F_1 and F_2 feature sets. However, this count was 50% for a single-layer model on F_3 . This disparity in the number of neurons was because these models for the F_1 and F_2 feature sets had 9,890 and 8,420 neurons, respectively, in their input layers. Therefore, even 5% of the total input and output neurons were adequate to effectively train the model for 1,739 labels. However, for F_3 , the number of input neurons was barely 1,470, and consequently, more neurons were needed for better prediction performance. This justifies a 50% count of neurons in the single hidden layer for this network. In any case, the training time, prediction time, and model size of these models were much better than those of other competing models. These models showed much better performance (F1 score: 0.96) compared to the deep learning ensemble [1] (F1 score: 0.79) on the same dataset. This was also achieved with a much lower computational complexity.

A. Best Predictors

The findings highlight the impressive role of the physiochemical properties and motifs in proteins, pseudo amino acid compositions, and other properties derived from the protein sequences in predicting protein functions. The proposed model for this feature set was extremely efficient as it had better performance and lower computational complexity.

B. Sufficiency of Amino Acid, Dipeptide, and Tripeptide Compositions

The results were suggestive of the sufficiency of amino acid, dipeptide, and tripeptide compositions in predicting protein functions. Although the performance metrics for this particular feature set had lower values than other feature sets, it can be used for a sufficient and tolerable approximation. This could save time spent in engineering features from existing features of the dataset consisting of bare compositions of amino acids, dipeptides, and tripeptides.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study culminated in two significant findings regarding the examined protein dataset. The first one pertains to the exceptional performance of single-layer neural networks on this dataset, although the number of neurons in this single hidden layer must be empirically determined as a percentage of the total input and output neurons in the network. The simple design of this single-layer model requires minimal computing resources. This model showed a performance improvement of

more than 16% over two-layer neural networks operating on the F_1 feature set. The corresponding performance improvements for the F_2 and F_3 features set were 20% and 13%, respectively. This study could play a substantial role in the prediction of protein function, due to the tremendous predictive power of some physiochemical properties of proteins, their pseudo-amino acid compositions, motifs in proteins, and some other significant characteristics. The bare compositions of amino acids, dipeptides, and tripeptides provide a reasonably high level of approximation of protein functions. This could be useful in cases where researchers want to have an approximate idea of protein functions just from the amino acid sequence rather than extracting and relying on many other properties of proteins.

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A Numerical Investigation of the Free Flow in a Square Porous Cavity with Non-Uniform Heating on the Lower Wall

Lilia Saidi

Laboratory of Industrial Technologies
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Ibn Khaldoun University of Tiaret
Tiaret, Algeria
saidililia@hotmail.fr

Said Mekroussi

Laboratory of Industrial Technologies
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Ibn Khaldoun University of Tiaret
Tiaret, Algeria
said.mekroussi@univ-tiaret.dz

Sahraoui Kherris

Laboratory of Mechanical Engineering, Materials and
Structures
Faculty of Sciences and Technology
Tissemsilt University
Tissemsilt, Algeria
kherris.sahraoui@gmail.com

Djallel Zebbar

Laboratory of Mechanical Engineering, Materials and
Structures
Faculty of Sciences and Technology
Tissemsilt University
Tissemsilt, Algeria
djallel.zebbar@cuniv-tissemsilt.dz

Brahim Mébarki

ENERGARID Laboratory
University Tahri Mohamed Béchar
Bechar, Algeria
brahimo12002@yahoo.fr

Abstract-Natural convection in a steady state of incompressible air inside a cavity's porous with a heated low wall of a sinusoidal profile is investigated numerically in this paper. The upper horizontal wall is kept cold while the two sides are thermally insulated. The proposed physical model was developed and studied with two-dimensional conditions, using the finite element method and adapting the Darcy-Brinkman model. This paper examines the laminar natural convection in a square porous cavity for different Rayleigh numbers ($10 \leq Ra \leq 10^4$), aspect ratios ($0.25 \leq AR \leq 1.0$), and sinusoidal temperature amplitude ($0.25 \leq \lambda \leq 1.0$). Moreover, the variation effect of Ra , AR , and λ on isotherms, streamlines, and the mean and local Nusselt numbers has been presented and analyzed. The results showed that an increase in the sinusoidal thermal amplitude, mean Nusselt number, and AR reduced somewhat the Rayleigh number. This provided a solution in which the mean Nusselt number increased by increasing the sinusoidal thermal amplitude and the Rayleigh number. On the other hand, it decreases slightly by increasing the AR . In addition, the convection transfer mechanism is the main mode when the Rayleigh number is high. Thus, it was found that the Darcy number also has an effect on heat transmission. The obtained results were compared with those found in the literature and were found to be in good accordance.

Keywords-porous medium; natural convection; square cavity; spatially variable temperature; aspect ratio

I. INTRODUCTION

It is observed that the heat exchange can be improved by using porous media. The term "porous medium" is generally referred to the solid complex shape which contains cavities or interstitial voids accessible to a fluid. In a porous medium multiple physicochemical and transport phenomena take place. It was often considered as a homogeneous and isotropic medium, nevertheless, it was considered anisotropic in its mechanical and thermal properties in various practical applications. Indeed, the field of porous environments is a part of a very spacious and quite complex research area which requires detailed and reliable understanding and knowledge. For a scientific survey on porous media, see [1-9]. The interstitial fluid flow in a porous medium is caused by convective heat transfer. This type of convection can be caused by different natural forces like the gravity force and the variation in density caused by the temperature difference. Low-temperature gradients affect the mass and heat transport that occurs in a porous medium. This type of convection is particularly important in a wide range of industrial and natural

processes. It is present in the exchange of moisture between the soil and the atmosphere. As a result of the daily and seasonal temperature variation of the surface, it is also present in certain technical fields, but we can find it as well in some biological and biotechnological systems [10]. Recently, authors in [11] proposed a three-dimensional model to study the effect of external vibrations on the drying process of a porous material.

In order to contribute to a more scientifically satisfactory study of the mechanism of heat transmission in a porous medium, numerical studies using the finite element method where it uniformly heats one of the side walls have been reviewed in [12-13]. Other researchers [14-16] applied heat both uniformly and non-uniformly to the bottom wall, whereas the sides were kept at a constant temperature and the top wall was considered adiabatic. Their interest was to see the impact of thermal boundary conditions that are both continuous and discontinuous. The Rayleigh number and the Darcy number have a wide range of values. It was discovered that when the Rayleigh number grew larger, the convective transfer mechanism took over as the major mode of transfer and that the Darcy number has an effect on heat transmission as well. In a similar model, authors in [17] heated both sidewalls with sinusoidal temperature while making use of the Darcy-Brinkman-Forchheimer model. Another shape was tested by the authors in [18] who studied the impact of inclined and sinusoidally heated wall in the trapezoidal cavity. The flow and heat transfer also were affected by the inclination of the walls. Authors in [19] investigated the convection of an inclined porous cavity at various inclination angles. The laminar, monophasic, and steady flows of water and air through cracks with penetrable walls were investigated in [20]. In order to describe heat and mass flows in porous media the authors in [21] employed a CVFEM technique. Others heated the side wall differentially [22-26] and the results were quite similar. Authors in [27] used heat generation. They verified the impact of porosity and heat generation on the streamlines and isotherms. According to the authors in [28], the ratio of the cavity's length to its width greatly influences streamlines and isotherms. Authors in [29] numerically analyzed the influence of the aspect ratios with Rayleigh numbers smaller than 10^4 . They discovered that the heat transfer rate rises with the raising of the aspect of the cavity. However, the authors in [30] measured the partially heated porous enclosure and they observed that raising the aspect ratio causes the flow function to increase and the heat transfer rate to cut back on.

Although sinusoidal heating in porous surfaces has important implications for research and engineering, there are still gaps in this area. The purpose of the current study is to improve the thermal performance by using a new temperature function (4). It is much more logical, rational and realistic, it can be found in different natural and industrial processes, such as solar energy and cooling of electronic components, where thermal heating takes the form of a cosine function, that is to say, the heating is concentrated in the middle and then distributed to the periphery. We will examine bottom-heated heat transfer by natural convection. The cavity is cooled from above, while the side walls are adiabatic. The main objective is to test this function on heat transfer and streamlines as a function of the Rayleigh number, the magnitude of the

temperature profile, and the aspect ratio. Our results are compared with the ones in [16].

II. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

The finite element method was utilized in laminar, stationary and two-dimensional conditions. The natural incompressible air circulation within a cavity of height H and length L (see Figure 1), is simulated numerically. The cavity with impermeable walls is filled by an isotropic porous medium, homogenous and thermodynamically balanced with the saturating fluid, where the high temperature of the cavity is maintained cold (T_c). The low wall is sinusoidally heated (T_h), whereas the two vertical walls are considered adiabatic.

Fig. 1. Boundary conditions of cavity geometry.

In the present investigation, the interactions between mass and heat transfer (Soret and Dufour effects), as well as heat transfer by radiation, are neglected. However, the thermal and fluid's physical characteristics are expected to remain constant. Boussinesq's approximation stands. Using these hypotheses and the Darcy-Brinkman model, the dimensionless equations governing this problem are [27]:

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial X} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial Y} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial U \Omega}{\partial X} + \frac{\partial V \Omega}{\partial Y} = \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial X^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial Y^2} - \gamma \right) \Omega + \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial X} \frac{Ra}{Pr} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial U \theta}{\partial X} + \frac{\partial V \theta}{\partial Y} = \frac{1}{Pr} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial X^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial Y^2} \right) \theta \quad (3)$$

where, θ , γ , and Ω are the dimensionless temperature, the porosity parameter, and dimensionless vortices, respectively. The other physical parameters are mentioned in the nomenclature. The control parameters of this problem AR , Pr , Ra , and Da are defined as follows:

$$AR = \frac{H}{L}, \quad Pr = \frac{\nu}{\alpha}, \quad Ra = \frac{g K \beta H \Delta T}{\nu \alpha} = Gr.Pr,$$

$$\text{and } Da = \frac{K}{H^2}.$$

The stream function is defined as:

$$U = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial Y} \quad \text{and} \quad V = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial X}.$$

Dimensionless variables are now included in the dimensionless equations:

$$Y = y/H, X = x/L, V = v/V_0, U = u/U_0,$$

$$P = \frac{p}{\rho U_0^2}, \text{ and } \theta = \frac{T - T_c}{T_H - T_c}.$$

In order to improve the performance of heat transfer within the porous medium, we have studied a new function totally absent in the literature, and yet widely encountered in natural and industrial processes, where thermal heating takes the form of the cosine function, i.e. the heating is concentrated in the middle and then distributed to the periphery. The boundary conditions of the current research are:

For the vertical walls:

$$X = 0 \text{ and } 0 \leq Y \leq H, U = V = 0, \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial X} = 0$$

$$X = L \text{ and } 0 \leq Y \leq H, U = V = 0, \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial X} = 0$$

For the low wall:

$$Y = 0 \text{ and } 0 \leq X \leq L, U = V = 0,$$

$$\theta = \lambda(1 - \cos(2\pi x))$$

For the high wall:

$$Y = H \text{ and } 0 \leq X \leq L, U = V = 0, \theta = 0$$

The low wall is heated as the sinusoidal formula in (4).

$$\theta = \lambda(1 - \cos(2\pi x)) \quad (4)$$

In the level of this wall, the average and local Nusselt number are:

$$\overline{Nu} = \int_0^1 Nu(X) dX$$

$$\overline{Nu} = \int_0^1 Nu(X) dX \text{ and } Nu(X) = -\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial Y}$$

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the experimental stage, we created an appropriate grid for a numerical model of the natural convection of a square cavity filled with porous material and saturated with incompressible air. Four varieties of uniform grids were designed, namely 30×30, 40×40, 50×50, and 60×60. The values AR=1.0, λ=0.5, and Ra=1000 were fixed as well as the tested function introduced in [16]: $Th = Tc + \lambda \sin(2\pi x)$. We found that the evenly spaced 60×60 mesh grid is fine enough to be used throughout the simulation. Our own result of the mean Nusselt number was 12.03, however, the result found in [16] was 13.56, giving a good agreement between the two. Then, we calculated the Nusselt number using our function in (4), and we found 18.91, which is sufficiently larger than the one found in [16]. The isotherms, the streamlines and the local Nusselt number with fixed values of λ=0.5, AR=1.0 and varying values

of the Rayleigh number $500 \leq Ra \leq 1000$ can be seen in Figures 2-4. We have obtained the same results as in [16].

TABLE I. NUSSELT NUMBER COMPARISON

Reference	[13]	[31]	[16]	This study
$\overline{Nu_x}$	15.80	14.06	13.56	12.03

Fig. 2. Isotherms for AR=1.0, λ=0.5 and $500 \leq Ra \leq 1000$: (a) [16], (b) current study.

Fig. 3. Streamline isotherms for AR=1.0, λ=0.5 and $500 \leq Ra \leq 1000$: (a) [16], (b) current study.

The numerical results obtained from the development of laminar natural convection in steady-state when an isotropic porous medium fills the square cavity, assuming that the lower wall is heated in a non-uniform way whereas the upper wall is cooled to a consistent temperature and the two vertical walls are thermally insulated. As mentioned above, we fixed the Prandtl number, porosity and permeability values, while we tested various Rayleigh values, aspect ratios, and amplitudes of the sinusoidal temperature. The temperature distribution and streamlines due to the buoyancy force effect are analyzed numerically, for different shape ratios $0.25 \leq AR \leq 1.0$. In each cavity shape ratio, the influence of the temperature amplitude $0.25 \leq \lambda \leq 1$ and the Rayleigh number $10 \leq Ra \leq 10000$ were studied regarding heat transfer and streamlines. The current

line results are shown in Figures 5-7 and the isotherms in Figures 8-10. It should be noted that the streamline contours are defined by two symmetrical vortices that occupy the whole cavity and rotate clockwise and counterclockwise for all the cases of aspect ratio. The hot fluid is driven from down along the bottom heated wall, under the influence of buoyancy. Buoyancy leads to circulation inside the cavity. However, close to the cavity's center, the circulation is more important in relation to the boundary of the enclosure due to the condition of non-slip.

Fig. 4. Local Nusselt number. (a) [16], (b) this study.

Fig. 5. Streamlines for $10 \leq Ra \leq 10000$, $0.25 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, and $AR=1$.

Fig. 6. Streamlines for $Ra=10000$, $0.25 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, and $AR=0.5$.

Fig. 7. Streamlines for $Ra=10000$, $0.25 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, and $AR=0.25$.

Fig. 8. Isotherms for $10 \leq Ra \leq 10000$, $0.25 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, and $AR=1$.

Fig. 9. Isotherms for $Ra=10000$, $0.25 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, $0.25 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, and $AR=0.5$.

Fig. 10. Isotherms for $Ra=10000$, $0.25 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, $0.25 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, and $AR=0.25$.

The center of the two cells is almost in the middle. The distance between the center and the hot wall is less than that between the center and the cold wall. As the Rayleigh number rises, the center of the cells shifts to the middle of the bottom wall. As a result of the conduction mode's dominance, the circulation force is very weak. The impact of the Rayleigh number on natural convection flow is a critical parameter. The flow convection is insignificant when the Rayleigh number is low. Conduction is the primary mode of heat transmission in the cavity. However, we notice a slight modification on the streamlines when we change the value of the sinusoidal temperatures amplitude. The flow forces as well as the values of the function rise when the Rayleigh number is high, which explains why the flow rate also increases. The current lines are shown in Figures 5-7 for different shapes ratios. It is obvious that the flow force becomes powerful and that the convection heat transfer is the most dominant to conduction. The increase in the value of the aspect ratio generates an increase in the flow force. We observe that when the shape ratio is decreased, the two cells become depressed. When the aspect ratio is high, the flow velocity of the fluid is higher. As a result, when the

distance between the two cold and hot walls is short, the heat exchange rate in the cavity is higher. At low Rayleigh number values, the temperature distribution is in the form of three sets of undulations symmetrical with relation to the vertical median of the cavity. Its amplitude in the middle is higher with a higher temperature gradient by compared to the other two next to it. On the other hand, we see a slight upward stretch of the ripples as we increase the value of the sinusoidal temperature distribution amplitude. The flow force increases as a result of an increase in the Rayleigh number and the heat transfer by natural convection becomes more dominant than the conduction, which is greatly influenced by the decrease in the boundary layer at the level of the wall hot. We notice that the isotherms become denser near the hot wall and more uniform in the central areas due to the enhanced free convection effect with the increase in the Rayleigh number so that the heat transfer is intensified and the temperature contour thins and condenses at the bottom wall approximation while the ripple turns into plumes.

Figure 11 depicts the effect of Ra and λ on the local Nusselt number Nux at the lower wall. In Figure 11(a) we considered $AR = 1$ and $\lambda = 1$, and in (b) we considered $AR = 1$ and $Ra = 1000$. The plot shows the acquired local Nusselt numbers as a function of Ra and λ . The curves are negative and divergent on the two edges and increase their value while going towards the center $X = [0,4-0, 6]$. Then they concave to the vertical mean where $X = 0.5$. The Nux is positive when the heat is supplied from the cavity to the environment and negative when heat is supplied from the enclosure to the environment. It is also observed that the effect of the height/width ratio is really negligible on Nux . The latter, on the other hand, is very changeable depending to Rayleigh and the amplitude of the sinusoidal function.

Fig. 11. Local Nusselt number (a) for $10 \leq Ra \leq 10000$, $\lambda=1$, and $AR=1.0$, (b) for $0.25 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, $Ra=1000$, and $AR=1.0$.

Due to the effect of the heat transfer mode by convection, we can observe that as the Rayleigh number grows, so does the Nusselt number. Where we see that the curve takes a concave and in the middle it becomes sinusoidal and increases its amplitude when the value of Ra is increased. We can also see

this behavior when λ is increased, which is why λ has a significant impact on heat transmission at the level of the enclosure.

IV. CONCLUSION

The main objective of this paper was to study the impact of the sinusoidal temperature on the heat flow and the current lines in a porous cavity subjected to natural convection while varying the Rayleigh number, the amplitude sinusoidal temperature, and the cavity format ratio parameter. The two-dimensional finite element method permitted us to model the flow and heat transfer which allowed us to deduct the following:

- For all height/width ratio values, the current lines take the shape of two vortexes, hiding the entire cavity and the heat transfer occurs in the form of three sets of ripples.
- The sinusoidal thermal amplitude has a minor impact on the flow but has a significant impact on the heat transfer rate.
- When the Rayleigh number is high, the convection flow is dominated by natural convection.
- The flow and the heat transfer rate are intensified when the Rayleigh number increases.
- Increase in the Rayleigh number causes a decrease in the boundary layer.
- The relationship between the Nusselt and the Rayleigh numbers can be expressed as a power function.
- The Rayleigh number has a great influence on the flow and the heat transfer rate.

NOMENCLATURE

Cp	Thermal capacity	$J kg^{-1} K^{-1}$
g	Gravitational acceleration	$m s^{-2}$
H	Enclosure height	m
k	Thermal conductivity	$W m^{-1} K^{-1}$
K	Porous media's permeability	m^2
L	Enclosure length	m
p	Pressure	Pa
T	Temperature	K
x, y	Coordinates	m
α	Thermal diffusivity	$m^2 s^{-2}$
β	Thermal dilatation coefficient	K^{-1}
θ	Dimensionless temperature, $(T - T_c) / (T_h - T_c)$	
ρ	Density	$Kg m^{-3}$
ν	Kinematic viscosity, $\mu \rho_0^{-1}$	$m^2 s^{-1}$
ψ	Stream function	
Ψ	Dimensionless stream function	
γ	Porosity parameter	
AR	Aspect ratio, H / L	
Da	Darcy number, K / H^2	
Gr	Grashof number, Ra / Pr	
Nux	Local Nusselt number	

\overline{Nu}	Average Nusselt number
P	Dimensionless pressure, $p / \rho U_0^2$
Pr	Prandtl number, ν / α
Ra	Rayleigh number, $g K \beta H \Delta T / \nu \alpha$
U	Dimensionless velocity components in horizontal direction
V	Dimensionless velocity components in vertical direction
X, Y	Dimensionless coordinates, $(x/L), (y/H)$

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A Tri-band Planar Inverted-F Antenna with Complementary Split Ring Resonator and Reactive Impedance Surface for Wireless Application

Tejaswi Jadhav

Electronics Engineering Department
Walchand College of Engineering
Sangli, Maharashtra, India
tejaswi.jadhav@walchandsangli.ac.in

Shraddha Deshpande

Electronics Engineering Department
Walchand College of Engineering
Sangli, Maharashtra, India
Shraddha.deshpande@walchandsangli.ac.in

Abstract—In this paper, a compact, tri-band Planar Inverted-F Antenna (PIFA) using Complementary Split Ring Resonator (CSRR) and Reactive Impedance Surface (RIS) is presented for multiband application. The structure of the PIFA consists of a metallic CSRR and 5×6 periodic unit RIS cells, which accomplishes miniaturization and improves bandwidth and multiband. The RIS metamaterial plane lies between two substrates and acts as a loading function, reducing the volume of the antenna. The measured and simulated results are consistent for a manufactured prototype. The overall size of the antenna is 22.71×3.451×2.59mm. The PIFA shows a tri-band with an S11 < -10dB bandwidth of approximately 17.08% (2.26-2.67GHz), 5.14% (6.85-7.21GHz) and 19.44% (7.44-9.19GHz) under measurement. The antenna radiates a wave in a preset direction with realized gains ranging from 3.21 to 8.1dbi. The CSRR and RIS improve the performance of the antenna for WLAN, C-band, and X-band applications.

Keywords—complementary split ring resonator; gain; multiband; planar inverted-F antenna; reactive impedance surface; wideband

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid advancement of wireless applications, lightweight, low-cost, and often omnidirectional radiation pattern antennas are becoming increasingly popular. With its low profile and ease of implementation, the Planar Inverted-F Antenna (PIFA) is a good radiator for applications such as handheld communication, Global Positioning System (GPS), microwave sensors, Wireless Local Area Networks (WLANs), Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), etc.. The PIFA has been used in wireless networking applications, such as WLAN, RadioFrequency Recognition (RFID), and satellite navigation systems because of its low profile and light weight. Broadside coupled Split-Ring Resonator (SRR) inclusions in the magnetic superstrate were studied in [1] and a lower resonance frequency was utilized using a metamaterial-based dual-band in [2], an asymmetrical meander lines SRR [3], and a cross-coupled interlinked SRR based metamaterial [4]. The combination of the thickness and feed position substantially increases the bandwidth of the desired frequencies discussed in [5] and a cross-shaped slot with a T-shaped patch is used for wideband in [6]. A dual-band operation is addressed by additionally loading

an electrically small CSRR structure in [7]. A metamaterial-based RIS has been used in the slot-loaded patch for antenna optimization in [8]. A tri-band antenna was presented in [9] and a CSRR loaded multiple-input–multiple-output antenna with electrically small elements and reduced mutual coupling in [10]. A Fractal PIFA and SRR printed on a conductor-backed dielectric substrate were used to create an artificial magnetic conductor in [11, 12]. A four-port diversity-based multiband antenna with high element isolation was presented in [13]. A CSRR has been used for miniaturization including the ground plane in [14]. A rectangular CSRR for the PIFA using a branch line and quad-band elements was arranged properly to implement a four-element MIMO configuration in [15, 16]. Improved narrow bandwidth and size reduction of an antenna were discussed in [17, 18]. Three resonant modes using an F-T-shaped radiating structure by a trapezoidal feeding plate were presented in [19, 20]. The portable wireless device system referred to in [21] is small in size and multi-band. The antenna structure is built around capacitive slots, which allow the multi-band behavior described in [22]. A loop antenna loaded with a Coplanar Strip (CPS) line was added along with two switches that allow the antenna perimeter to be varied to cover 7 different bands [23]. The CPS line is combined with two switches to vary the antenna perimeter to cover 7 different bands, and an Artificial Magnetic Conductor (AMC) was used as the reflector plane in [24]. The PIFA is a built-in mobile antenna that compensates for polarization issues, narrow bandwidth, lower gain, and operates multiple frequency bands.

In this paper, the CSRR and the RIS metamaterial are used to reduce the antenna size while improving the impedance bandwidth and multiband application. The drawbacks of the PIFA are reduced with an optimization technique, and a new, advanced, low-profile, and effective design of a PIFA with CSRR and RIS for multiband operations is implemented.

II. THE PIFA

A. Conventional Antenna

The proposed tri-band PIFA using CSRR and RIS is shown in Figure 1. The overall dimensions of the antenna are 22.71 × 3.456 × 2.59mm, which allows its use in portable

Corresponding author: Tejaswi Jadhav

systems. The standard PIFA consists of only a metallic patch element positioned above a ground surface, a dielectric constant, a microstrip line feeding mechanism on the ground surface, and a short-circuiting pin. The basic characteristic of the antenna, is the form of the letter F in English, thus it is called the inverted-F antenna. The PIFA is attached to the antenna ground plane. The PIFA ground plane scale on the PCB board has average dimensions of 56.4mm×33.5mm with a 1.59mm antenna height of FR4 dielectric substrate ($\epsilon_r = 4.4$, $\tan \delta = 0.02$). The overall dimensions of the antenna substrate are 70×50 mm.

TABLE I. GEOMETRIC DIMENSIONS OF THE PROPOSED PIFAWITH CSRR AND RIS

Parameters	Value (mm)	Parameter	Value (mm)
Lp	22.71	Wp	3.45
Lg	56.4	Wg	41.68
Ls	4.6	Ws	2.1
Lf	4.6	Wf	2.1
B1	5.5	W1	1
B2	9	W2	1
G1	1.5	G2	1.5
a1	0.8	g1	0.34
a2	0.9	g2	0.28
h1	1.59	h2	1

Fig. 1. The proposed PIFA with CSRR and RIS.

The PIFA is made up of a metallic module that is mounted on the bottom side of the substrate. RIS is a periodic structure designed, which can significantly improve the bandwidth and radiation characteristics. As shown in Figure 1(b), The RIS substrate is made up of two-dimensional periodic metallic patches printed on a metal-backed high dielectric substance. The CSRR is etched on the metal-plane resonator. Figure 1(c) shows a schematic view of the rectangular CSRR.

B. PIFA with CSRR AND RIS

The metallic square unit structure is mounted on the top side of the dielectric material in the PIFA configuration (FR4).

The design of the RIS contains 5×6 periodic unit cells. The RIS uses episodic metallic square unit cells that are joined and organized one after another on a dielectric substrate. The surface of RIS is perpendicular to the plane. The lateral dimensions of the PIFA are almost the same size as the ground element for the PIFA configuration. Using the exact picture formulation will reduce the interaction between its image and the elemental source in the RIS. The RIS can enhance impedance bandwidth and reduce the size of the PIFA antenna. It is between perfectly electric and magnetic conductor (PEC and PMC) surfaces. For better impedance matching, the PIFA has a single side-feed spot.

The CSRR is a mirror image of an SRR in a metasurface resonator. It consists of two concentric metallic rectangles, each with a slit in the middle. A rectangular CSRR structure is engraved on the dielectric substrate of the proposed antenna, as shown in Figure 1(d). The widths of the rectangular inner and outer CSRR are W1 and W2 and the distances between the rectangular gap are G1 and G2. Therefore the gap between the rectangular CSRR is 1–1.5mm. The width of the metallic slot is between 0.9 and 1mm. The proposed PIFA with CSRR and RIS design parameter dimensions is described in Table I. A fixed metallic inverted-F patch on the top is adjacent to the substrate (h2) and a ground plane of the antenna is on the bottom side of the antenna substrate (h1). The rectangular patch is fed by an electromagnetically coupled microstrip feed line that is sandwiched between two FR4 dielectric substrates, each with a thickness h1 of 1.59mm and an h2 of 1mm. Figure 1(e) shows the front view (cross-section) of the modified PIFA with CSRR and RIS. The metamaterial unit cell has extracted relative negative permittivity at its resonance frequency.

III. DESIGN OF THE PROPOSED PIFA

A. Proposed Antenna Equation

The design of the PIFA is using the transmission line model, which has 3 essential parameters, resonance frequency (f_0), selection of a dielectric substrate (ϵ_r), and substrate height (h). The geometric radiating patch length (Lp), patch width (Wp), ground length (Lg), and ground width (Wg) have been calculated by using the mathematical model in [21]. The patch width (Wp) of the PIFA is:

$$Wp = \frac{c}{2f_0 \sqrt{\epsilon_{eff} + 1}} \quad (1)$$

The patch length (Lp) of the PIFA is calculated by:

$$L = \frac{\lambda_g}{4} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2. (a) Simulated return loss of PIFA with and without CRSS and RIS. (b) Simulated VSWR of PIFA with and without CRSS and RIS.

Fig. 3. (a) Measured and simulated Return Loss of PIFA with CSRR and RIS. (b) Measured and simulated VSWR of PIFA with CSRR and RIS.

Fig. 4. Surface current distribution of the proposed PIFA at (a) 2.4GHz, (b) 7GHz, (c) 9GHz.

B. Parametric Study

The PIFA with and without CSRR and RIS has undergone parametric analysis and the results of the simulation are presented in Figure 2. The study was carried out by placing metamaterial surfaces on an antenna dielectric substrate while keeping all other measurements stable. Figures 3(a) and 3(b) display the simulation return loss and VSWR of the PIFA, which is tuned to resonate at 2.45GHz, 7GHz, and 9GHz with the CSRR’s dimensions modified. All geometric dimensions of the inside and the outside rectangle of the CSRR are listed in Table I. As a result, the slit width was held at 1.5mm. The resonant frequency of the antenna decreased as the length of the rectangular CSRR increased. The antenna resonant frequency increased, multiband was generated by increasing the width of the CSRR and the distance between the two squares. The antenna was tuned for multiband by adjusting these parameters. The patch’s presence on the top of the CSRR

produced a lower than the actual patch’s resonant frequency. This behavior is observed for different CSRR parameters in the proposed study and is consistent with previous findings.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Return Loss

The PIFA shows a tri-band with an S11 <-10dB bandwidth of approximately 27.25% (2.1467-2.80GHz), 5.71% (6.70-7.10GHz), and 22.46% (7.30- 9.3214GHz) under simulated and 17.08% (2.26-2.67GHz), 5.14% (6.85-7.21GHz) and 19.44% (7.44-9.19GHz) under measurement respectively. Bandwidth, polarization, gain, VSWR, and return loss of the PIFA antenna were measured in a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA). The simulated and fabricated results obtained from the output parameters are presented in Figure 3(a)-(b). The developed antenna is demonstrating high impedance matching in mobile application. Table II represented the comparison of the PIFA with previous works in terms of geometric measurements, miniaturization, frequency spectrum, gain, and bandwidth.

B. Voltage Standing Wave Ratio

The Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR) of the PIFA is shown in Figure 3(b). The VSWR values at 2.4GHz, 7GHz, and 9GHz are almost 1.32, 1.92, and 2.07 respectively, which is very effective in the fabrication process. VSWR should lie in the range of 1 to 2, indicating best antenna performance. It has used the input power of an antenna transmitted to the patch, as well as better impedance matching.

C. Current Distribution

The current distribution of PIFA with CSRR and RIS is determined through HFSS simulations. Figure 4 indicates the surface current distribution of the PIFA to determine the current with the RIS and the ground surface. The ground surface disrupts the current distribution of PIFA, causing CSRR. As a result, the propagation of electromagnetic waves was controlled by the substrate layer, port excitation, and changes in resonant response. The current distribution of 2.4GHz, 7GHz, and 9GHz is shown in Figure 4.

D. Gain

For a handheld unit, the gain of the PIFA, as shown in Figure 5 is acceptable for a good multiband antenna. For operating bands 2.4, 7, and 9GHz, the PIFA gain is 8.1, 3.13, and 7.26dbi, respectively. The average gain of an antenna across its operating bandwidth for a quad-band is 6.16dbi.

Fig. 5. Measured gain of the PIFA with CSRR and RIS.

TABLE II. COMPARISON WITH PREVIOUS WORKS

Ref.	Size	No of bands	Operating frequency (GHz)	Gain (dBi)
[5]	25.6×26×3.57	3	2.09/3.74/5	2.05/2.32/3.47
[8]	34×17×8	3	0.94/1.79/2.46	0.4/1.7/1.1
[11]	16.5×11.5×5	3	2.4/5.2/5.8	4.44/4.91/4.94
[15]	90×42×7.5	4	1.15/2.42/3.6/5.3	1.45/1.6/3.56/4
[16]	18.35×16.4×4.0	3	2.1/2.6/3.5	2.73/3.84/4.8
[20]	25×11×8	3	2.4/5.2/5.75	1.6/2.3/4.4
[21]	26×20×1.6	3	2.4/3.5/5.8	2.24/2.8/2.6
Proposed	22.7×3.45×2.59	3	2.4/7/9	8.1/3.213/7.26

D. Radiation Pattern

Figure 6 indicates the E-Plane and H-plane antenna radiation patterns (Phi=0° and Phi=90°) simulated in HFSS. The electric or magnetic field of the PIFA affects the radiation pattern with CSRR and RIS.

Fig. 6. Radiation pattern of the X-Z and Y-Z planes of the proposed PIFA at 2.4, 7, and 9GHz.

The verified PIFA radiation patterns with metasurface for wireless applications are 2.4, 7, and 9 GHz. The wave path of the maximum antenna radiates along the Z-axis, and the wave port 1 exits the simulation. The radiation pattern of the antenna (co-plane and cross-plane) is illustrated in Figure 6 for $\phi = 0^\circ$ and $\phi = 90^\circ$ at 2.4, 7 and 9GHz. The radiation pattern of the PIFA (co-plane and cross-plane) in the $\phi = 0^\circ$ and $\phi = 90^\circ$ of the XY plane. Figures 7(a)-(b) show a photograph of the manufactured CP-PIFA with CSRR and RIS.

Fig. 7. Photograph of the fabricated PIFA with CSRR and RIS.

V. CONCLUSION

A compact, tri-band, PIFA with CSRR and RIS, suitable for WLAN, C-band, and X-band applications PIFA was presented in this paper. The PIFA has multiple bands with $S_{11} < -10$ and bandwidth of approximately 17.08%, 5.14%, and 19.44% measured at 2.4, 7, and 9GHz respectively. The antenna radiates a wave in a preset direction with realized gains ranging from 3.21 to 8.1dbi. The parametric analysis indicates that a small change in the rectangular CSRR has a significant impact on the antenna impedance mapping. It also increases the bandwidth and provides better gain with the same dielectric substrate and radiating patch. The benefit of the multiple bands on the PIFA is shown on the radiation pattern, broadband, impedance adequacy, and gain of their operating bandwidth.

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Automatic Diagnosis of Covid-19 Related Pneumonia from CXR and CT-Scan Images

Naresh Kumar

Department of Computer Science & Engineering
Maharaja Surajmal Institute of Technology
New Delhi, India
narsumsaini@gmail.com

Manish Gupta

Department of Computer Science & Engineering
Moradabad Institute of Technology
Moradabad, India
manishymca2007@gmail.com

Adeel Hashmi

Department of Computer Science & Engineering
Maharaja Surajmal Institute of Technology
New Delhi, India
ashashmi10@gmail.com

Ankit Kundu

Department of Computer Science & Engineering
Maharaja Surajmal Institute of Technology
New Delhi, India
ankitkundu93@gmail.com

Abstract-Covid-19 is a highly infectious disease that spreads extremely fast and is transmitted through indirect or direct contact. The scientists have categorized the Covid-19 cases into five different types: severe, critical, asymptomatic, moderate, and mild. Up to May 2021 more than 133.2 million peoples have been infected and almost 2.9 million people have lost their lives from Covid-19. To diagnose Covid-19, practitioners use RT-PCR tests that suffer from many False Positive (FP) and False Negative (FN) results while they take a long time. One solution to this is the conduction of a greater number of tests simultaneously to improve the True Positive (TP) ratio. However, CT-scan and X-ray images can also be used for early detection of Covid-19 related pneumonia. By the use of modern deep learning techniques, accuracy of more than 95% can be achieved. We used eight CNN (CovNet)-based deep learning models, namely ResNet 152 v2, InceptionResNet v2, Xception, Inception v3, ResNet 50, NASNetLarge, DenseNet 201, and VGG 16 for both X-rays and CT-scans to diagnose pneumonia. The achieved comparative results show that the proposed models are able to differentiate the Covid-19 positive cases.

Keywords-artificial intelligence; covid-19 detection; convolutional neural networks; deep learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Covid-19 epidemic has caused millions of deaths worldwide [1-4]. The detection of corona virus positive cases is done through RT-PCR tests which take approximately 2 days to give results [5-7]. It is very crucial to diagnose the positive cases at early stages and quarantine them instantly. The infection can also be identified by pneumonia in Chest X-Ray (CXR) or CT-Scan (CTS) images of the patients, which is a much faster process [8-10]. These images are analyzed by the experts to locate the infection, which may take time due to the large number of patients. An automated and accurate artificial intelligence-based system to locate the infection in the images can considerably speed up the process.

This work aims to help identify the Covid-19 pneumonia from CXR and CTS images. A deep learning approach has been used to build the models, i.e. Convolutional neural Networks (CovNets) including ResNet152v2, Xception, InceptionResNetv2, ResNet50, Inceptionv3, NASNetLarge, DenseNet 201, and VGG-16 for the classification of the images as corona virus positive or not. The models were trained with a dataset containing CXR and CTS images of covid and non-covid patients. Comparative analysis of all the models is performed using various metrics to determine the best approach.

In the recent studies, researchers have observed the bilateral relation of CXR and CTS images with covid-19. They have observed the imaging patterns on the CXR and CTS of the lungs for the diagnosis of nCov (novel coronavirus) infection [11]. Also, it was found that with the help of deep learning techniques it is possible to achieve much higher image classification accuracy from CXR and CTS images in the diagnostic process of corona virus. It has been observed that 4% of the patients had False Negative (FN) corona result when tested with the RT-PCR kit. The study in [12] was related to the sensitivity of the real time polymerase chain reaction and CTSs during diagnosis of nCov were acquired. The authors observed that the RT-PCR is less accurate and also its sensitivity is much lower than that of the CTS. Deep learning techniques provide much better results in the diagnosis process of acute pneumonia in CSRs [13] or CTSs [14, 15]. In [14], strong deep learning-based models have been used for the classification of CTS images. The authors have used the imaging patterns of the CTS images of lungs to differentiate the covid positive from the covid negative cases. However, their model achieved sensitivity under 90% and was unable to reach much accurate results. The authors in [15] built an automated system for the diagnosis and quantification of Sars-CoV-2 based on artificial intelligence. Their automated system generates an output giving the quantitative opacity and 3-

Corresponding author: Adeel Hashmi

dimensional output for opacities. Their model is more efficient against pixel spacing. In [16], a transfer learning-based system was developed for the diagnosis of Covid-19 from CXRs. From the above discussion and from [17, 18], it has been concluded that CXR and CTS images can be utilized for the early diagnosis of nCov positive cases.

In [19], the authors designed an automated ensemble system for the initial stage diagnosis of nCov from CXRs. They used two popular open-source datasets of CXR images for their research work. The first dataset was used for binary classification (i.e. Covid-Healthy and Covid-Positive) and the second dataset was used for multi-class classification (i.e. Covid-Healthy, Covid-Positive, Pneumonia-Positive, and Tuberculosis-Positive respectively). They used the pre-trained CovNet combination of EfficientNet, GoogLeNet, and Xception in their model. The results were summated and an absolute or relative voting was carried out to obtain the final decision. Comparative analysis of their proposed model was done with some other CovNets such as ResNet-152v2, DenseNet-201, InceptionResNet2, and VGG-16 to assess the capabilities of the model. Their model outshined all the above-mentioned CovNets in both binary and multi-class classification and achieved decent accuracy rates of 99.21% and 98.95% for multi-class classification and binary classification respectively. The authors of [20] proposed a metaheuristic-based automated system for the early diagnosis of nCov positive patients from CXR images. They have used CNN for their experiments along with SPEA-2 for the proper tuning of the model's parameters. They resized the dimensions of the images in the datasets to $259 \times 259 \times 3$, which is the optimal size of the input image for the model. They computed the probability score of each class and the one with the maximum value was taken as the final. The performance of the proposed model was compared to VGG19, VGG16, ResNet50, AlexNet, ResNet-34, InceptionNet, Xception, DenseNet 201, and GoogLeNet in terms of accuracy, F1 score, sensitivity, recall, and area under the ROC curve. Their proposed metaheuristic-based model performed well in multi-class classification and achieved accuracy of 99.97% and 99.13% on training and testing sets respectively.

In [21] the authors used a multi-class dataset and deep CovNet and Xception model for their image classification model. The performance was evaluated with SVM, random forest, back propagation network, adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference systems, CovNet, VGGNet, ResNet50, AlexNet, etc. They achieved accuracy of 97.40%. The authors in [22] proposed an automated system for pre-screening of covid, heart illness, and diabetes using machine learning models. For portability, they built an android application for early prediction or severity diagnosis at home without having to travel to clinics. They used three binary datasets, one for each considered disease. For the covid dataset they arranged the data in two groups, one group containing the data points regarding the countries having less than 10,000 cases and the other one for countries with more than 10,000 cases and marked them as 0 and 1 respectively. They applied the logistic regression on the training set in all the datasets. They also applied the cross validation technique to get the most optimized result from the model. They claimed that real-time diagnosis could be possible

with the usage of an android application, also it would help in tweaking or dropping updates in the future. The proposed model was compare with other ML models such as LR, J48, KNN, SVM, ANN, RF, and GB. Their model achieved an accuracy rate of 95%, 94.20%, and 87% on diabetes, covid, and heart disease datasets respectively. The authors in [23] developed an automated system named Dark CovidNet for the early screening of Covid-19 from CXR images. Their model gave a decent accuracy of 98%, but it was trained on a small dataset of 125 CXR images.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset

Open source datasets from GitHub repository and Kaggle, were used to train the above-mentioned models. The dataset in [24] is a 740MB dataset source containing 7252 CXR images (3612 CXR images of Covid-19 patients and more than 3600 non-covid CXR images), whereas [25] is a dataset containing 1000 CXR images of Covid-19 and healthy people (495 Covid-19 positive and 505 Covid-19 negative images), as shown in Figures 1-2.

Fig. 1. Visualization of a few non-covid CXR images.

Fig. 2. Visualization of a few covid CXR images.

Regarding CTS images, [26] is a 231MB dataset consisting of 2481 CTS images (out of which 1252 images are of Covid-19 patients and 1229 are from healthy people), whereas [27] is a dataset used to train the models on chest CTS images. It consists of 750 images of Covid-19 patients and healthy people (353 images of Covid-positive patients and 397 of healthy people). The utilization ratio of the complete dataset is 80:20, i.e. 80% of the complete dataset is used to train the model and the rest 20% is used for testing. Figure 3 depicts a few Computed Tomography (CT) images from the dataset of the people infected from nCov 2019, while Figure 4 illustrates the visualization of a few CT images of healthy people present in the dataset used to train the models.

B. CovNet (CNN) Overview

CovNet has very good performance in diagnostics, agriculture, and industry [28-33]. Figure 5 illustrates a general

architecture of a CNN having an input layer, two convolution layers, each followed by a pooling layer, followed by two consecutive fully-connected layers, and at the end there is a SoftMax activation function [34, 35].

Fig. 3. CT scan images of covid patients.

Fig. 4. CT scan images of normal patients.

Fig. 5. General architecture of the CovNet.

C. The Proposed Architecture

TABLE I. COVNET ARCHITECTURE UTILIZED FOR COVID-19 DETECTION

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
input_1 (InputLayer)	[(None, 224, 224, 3)]	0
conv2d (Conv2D)	(None, 224, 224, 32)	896
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 224, 224, 32)	0
activation (Activation)	(None, 224, 224, 32)	0
max_pooling2d (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 112, 112, 32)	0
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(None, 112, 112, 64)	18496
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 112, 112, 64)	0
activation_1 (Activation)	(None, 112, 112, 64)	0
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 56, 56, 64)	0
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)	(None, 56, 56, 128)	73856
dropout_2 (Dropout)	(None, 56, 56, 128)	0
activation_2 (Activation)	(None, 56, 56, 128)	0
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 28, 28, 128)	0
conv2d_3 (Conv2D)	(None, 28, 28, 256)	295168
dropout_3 (Dropout)	(None, 28, 28, 256)	0
activation_3 (Activation)	(None, 28, 28, 256)	0
max_pooling2d_3 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 14, 14, 256)	0
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 50176)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 64)	3211328
dropout_4 (Dropout)	(None, 64)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 1)	65

The utilized architecture is depicted in Table I. The model consists of convolution layers that extract possible characteristics from medical scans and feed them to the input layer, which is then followed by the pooling layer. The average pooling strategy of 2x2 is being used in this study, which minimizes or divides the feature mapping by 2 and transmits the output to the hidden or middle layer, which is masked behind the SoftMax activation function and comprises of pooling and convolution layers. The activation function aids the middle layer in selecting the best input based on the weights. The data processed by the middle layer are sent as input for prediction to the dense or fully-connected layer. Because it delivers the final classification or predictions, the dense layer is also known as the output layer.

III. RESULTS

The proposed models were implemented using keras. All the tests were run on a Google Colaboratory console with 12GB RAM and a Tesla K80 GPU. The validity of the CovNets has been examined in two stages. In the first stage, classification reports of the 8 CovNet models were produced for 500 epochs for both CXR and CTS images. After that, confusion matrices were constructed. After a comparison analysis of the models, the best method was identified. Table II compares the results of the proposed model with 8 standard CovNet models on the CXR test dataset. The Inception V3 outperformed the other CovNets in terms of accuracy, peaking at 9%. The Xception model, on the other hand, yields nearly identical prediction figures to the Inception V3 network and scores 2% lower in terms of accuracy, while it also gives 97%, 87%, and 89% specificity, sensitivity, and f1-score respectively. In terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and f1-score, the ResNet 50 network has the lowest prediction figures of 83%, 76%, 92%, and 81% respectively. The VGG16 model produces some incredible results, with accuracy, precision, sensitivity, and f1-score values of 92%, 86%, 98%, and 92%. The rest of the models produced similar findings, with the exceptions of DenseNet 201 and ResNet 152 V2, which produce significantly better results than the other two models (InceptionResNet V2, NASNetLarge CovNet model) in all metrics. In terms of overall statistics, the proposed model produced the best end prediction values when all of the measures were taken into consideration.

TABLE II. CXR RESULTS

Model	Metric			Accuracy
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	
NASNetLarge	0.89	0.83	0.86	0.86
DenseNet 201	0.94	0.82	0.88	0.89
ResNet 152 V2	0.91	0.85	0.88	0.88
Inception ResNet V2	0.86	0.80	0.83	0.84
ResNet 50	0.76	0.92	0.81	0.83
Xception	0.97	0.87	0.89	0.93
Inception V3	0.87	0.98	0.91	0.95
VGG 16	0.86	0.98	0.92	0.92
Proposed Model	0.96	0.95	0.96	0.98

The statistics of the models in diagnosing nCov illness from CTSs are shown in Table III. All of the models were developed using a binary classification data sample. With accuracy, specificity, sensitivity, and f1-score values of 93%, 98%, 92%,

and 96% on the CT testing data sample, the Xception model performed exceptionally well and delivered highly competitive figures. The VGG 16 and Inception V3 both provide 92% accuracy, however the rest of the metrics for both neural networks are 92%, 92%, 92%, and 93%, 97%, and 95% respectively, while NASNetLarge and ResNet produced the lowest prediction figures. The accuracy rates of DenseNet 201, InceptionResNet V2, and ResNet 152 V2, are all in the range of 80-90%. In terms of overall statistics, the proposed model produced the best possible end prediction values when all the measures were taken into consideration.

TABLE III. CTS RESULTS

Model	Metric			Accuracy
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	
NASNetLarge	0.75	0.79	0.77	0.77
DenseNet 201	0.89	0.79	0.79	0.81
ResNet 152 V2	0.88	0.83	0.86	0.86
Inception ResNet V2	0.75	0.99	0.84	0.83
ResNet 50	0.83	0.74	0.76	0.79
Xception	0.93	0.98	0.92	0.96
Inception V3	0.93	0.97	0.95	0.92
VGG 16	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92
Proposed Model	0.97	1.00	0.96	0.97

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

CXR and CTS images were employed in this study to overcome the lack of precision with real-time polymerase chain reaction tests for nCov illness diagnosis. CXR and CTS reports were employed as medical imaging procedures. CXR and CTS reports suggest certain prospective patterns (pneumonia) and have bilateral effects with nCov, according to a large number of research publications and detailed reviews [36, 37]. Manual testing of these medical photos on the other hand takes a long time and may culminate in diagnostic inaccuracy. Image categorization, speech recognition, and other applications benefit greatly from CovNets. All the CovNet models listed above have been correctly trained, and the parameters have been fine-tuned. The models were trained using a dataset with a substantial number of images. To assess the capabilities of all the aforementioned models, a thorough comparison was carried out using a variety of popular benchmarks such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Inception V3 and xception showed the highest accuracy of 95% and 93% respectively whereas in CTSs, Xception Inception V3 exhibited the highest scores (96% and 92% respectively). Both the CovNet models, i.e. Inception V3 and xception surpassed all the other models.

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R-SOR: Ranked Social-based Routing Protocol in Opportunistic Mobile Social Networks

Mohamad Alrfaay
Common First Year Deanship
Jouf University
Sakaka, Saudi Arabia
mhrifai@ju.edu.sa

Aref Kurd Ali
Faculty of Computer Science and Information Technology
Universiti Malaysia Sarawak (UNIMAS)
Sarawak, Malaysia
abhznk@gmail.com

Slim Chaoui
College of Computer and Information Sciences
Jouf University
Sakaka, Saudi Arabia
schaoui@ju.edu.sa

Halikul Lenando
Faculty of Computer Science and Information Technology
Universiti Malaysia Sarawak (UNIMAS)
Sarawak, Malaysia
cool@unimas.my

Saad Alanazi
College of Computer and Information Sciences
Jouf University
Sakaka, Saudi Arabia
sanazi@ju.edu.sa

Abstract—Exploiting social information to improve routing performance is an increasing trend in Opportunistic Mobile Social Networks (OMSNs). Selecting the next message's relay node based on the user's social behavior is a critical factor in attaining a high delivery rate. So, to ascertain the most efficient selection of the next relay, the correlation between daily social activities and the social characteristics in the user profiles can be exploited. In this paper, we consider the impact of the social characteristics on mobile user activities during certain periods of the day and then rank these characteristics based on their relative importance in order to be included in the routing protocol. These processes consolidate the proposed Ranked Social-based Routing (R-SOR) protocol to provide an effective way for data dissemination in OMSN. We use the real data set INFOCOM06 to evaluate the proposed protocol. The experimental results show that the proposed protocol has higher routing efficiency than flooding-based protocols such as Epsoc and Epidemic, prediction-based protocols such as PROPHET, and social-based protocols such as MSM and Bubble Rap.

Keywords—*opportunistic networks; mobile social networks; data dissemination; social-based routing*

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, smart mobile devices are present in all areas of human activity. They transform the ways of sharing data into a new paradigm of Mobile Social Networks (MSNs) [1-4]. MSNs combine the social features of users carrying mobile devices in the strategy for data delivery. In an Opportunistic Mobile Social Network (OMSN), the mobile nodes

communicate opportunistically and data forwarding occurs when they encounter each other. In other words, routes from the sender to the destination of a message are created dynamically, and any possible node can opportunistically be used for the next hop. For these reasons, data routing in such networks is a crucial challenge.

The Store-Carry-Forward (SCF) method was developed as a data forwarding mechanism in opportunistic networks. With the SCF mechanism, each node stores data packets in the buffer. When the node encounters another node, it forwards the duplicated data packets. As a result, network resources such as bandwidth and node packet buffers are consumed in large amounts. For this reason, selecting the appropriate relay is a major challenge and key issue in OMSN. In [5], the performance of different routing protocols in opportunistic networks is analyzed. For instance, epidemic routing protocols [6, 7] use a flooding-based principle for spreading copies of messages to newly discovered contacts. Prediction-based routing protocols, such as PROPHET [8, 9], use contact history between users to estimate nodes' delivery probability which characterizes the probability of successfully delivering a message to the destination from a local node. Social-based routing is an emerging research trend where researchers look for ways to use social information of individuals to assist routing as it has been found that people follow almost stable patterns in their social behavior [10].

Routing in mobile networks is a challenging issue [11], networks such as the Vehicular Ad-hoc Network (VANET) and

Corresponding author: Mohamad Alrfaay

the Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) require efficient routing protocols due to their dynamic topology [12, 13]. Exploiting long-term social features in a disruptive and varied network environment for routing is a fruitful approach [14-16]. Several social aware routing protocols have been proposed [17-19]. Social aware schemes exploit different social metrics such as centrality [20, 21], similarity [22], betweenness [23], and social ties and friendship [24]. A user's social profile contains a vector of several social features such as nationality, language, and topics of interest. These social features influence the social behavior and activity of the mobile user. For examples, persons of the same nationality contact each other more often, people having common interests and contacts do similar actions, individuals with common language tend to meet and talk with each other longer, etc. In addition, most people follow a stable pattern or routine in their daily life. Generally, humans have different social activities at different periods of the day. The influence of social features changes according to the day period. For example, most people who meet in the evening share the same nationality or similar affiliations.

The main objective of this work is to design an efficient forwarding scheme in order to achieve high delivery ratio and to decrease the network overhead. This is carried out by involving the ranking of social features with regard to a specific day slicing mechanism in the routing process. Our contribution is focused on designing a ranked social-based routing protocol which is referred to as R-SOR protocol that seeks to improve the performance of OMSNs by considering the regularity of users' social behavior and by exploiting the relative impact of the social features during each day period. The contributions made under the proposed scheme are:

- We define a set of social profiles which can be involved in the routing process of OMSN.
- We estimate the probabilistic behavior of social activities according to the dynamic changes over time with regard to the defined day periods. An algorithm for updating the nodes' periods is proposed for this purpose.
- An algorithm for ranking social features according to their estimated probabilities is proposed.
- We developed the proposed R-SOR algorithm by selecting the best relay node having the highest rank of social feature similar to that of the destination in the current day period.

In order to investigate the proposed R-SOR approach, we carried out experiments using the real data set INFOCOM06 [25] to explore the impact of different social features in different time periods. The result of the simulation experiments exhibits the efficiency of the R-SOR protocol, in comparison to 5 benchmark routing protocols, namely flooding-based protocols such as Epsoc and Epidemic, prediction-based protocols such as PRoPHET, and social-based protocols such as MSM and Bubble Rap.

II. RELATED WORKS

Generally, routing schemes in OMSNs can be classified into different categories such as flooding-based, mobility prediction-based, context aware, and social aware protocols.

The stability of human social preferences and the regular patterns that social behavior follows give the opportunity to develop information provision. Several social features have been exploited by the research community [24]. For example, the SimBet routing protocol utilizes two social features, similarity and betweenness, for the forwarding process [26]. The values of betweenness centrality and similarity for each node are estimated with the ego network analysis technique. Only local available information is considered. Messages are forwarded towards the node with higher betweenness centrality to increase the possibility of finding the potential carrier to the final destination. Concentrating load on centralized nodes in SimBet results in network congestion in these nodes. In [27], the authors propose the Bubble Rap protocol which exploits two social and structural metrics, centrality and community. In this scheme, nodes belong to different sized communities and have different levels of centrality which was denoted as rank. There are two ranking types for each node, the local ranking inside the node's community and the global ranking for the entire network. Both levels of ranking are used for forwarding data. Messages are forwarded to nodes having higher global ranking until a node in the destination's community is encountered. Then, the messages are forwarded to nodes having a higher local ranking within the destination's community. However, employing the community detection methods require network information collecting and results to exchanges which lead to an overhead increase in the networks.

The research in the utilization of multiple social features to develop effective social aware routing is gaining interest. The authors in [28], introduced the intelligent tree (Int-Tree) routing protocol which exploits social ties, community density, and similarity of interests to improve routing performance. Inter-community and intra-community communications were considered. For intra-community communications, the social ties between nodes are utilized to select the next forwarders. Authors in [29] exploited both offline and online user's social network information to propose a social-based forwarding strategy for opportunistic networks. They combined the dynamic online centrality and the detected centrality based on the contact history. Thereupon, the delivery ratio was increased and the message replication number was reduced.

Authors in [30] proposed the Multi-Layer Social network based Opportunistic Routing (ML-SOR) protocol that considered the dynamics in social structure and user behavior by exploiting 3 social features, namely node centrality, community structure, and the social ties. Offline temporal social information gained from nodes' encountering and online static social information acquired from social networks were utilized for the better selection of the next carrier. Authors in [31] proposed the Proximity-Interest-Social (PIS) routing protocol that considered 3 social factors, physical proximity, user interests, and user social relationships. These factors were used along with the slot time management mechanism and a copy control way to develop an effective forwarding scheme. Authors in [32] proposed a multiple social metrics-based routing protocol where 3 social metrics were exploited, centrality, social similarity, and social activeness. Forwarding decisions were made based on combinations of the impact of these three metrics and the correlation among them.

Authors in [33] proposed a social aware routing scheme which depends on the features of the opportunistic network. In this scheme, dependability ratio, usability ratio, and weight factor are calculated as weights of human activities to obtain the optimal cooperation nodes in the network. Authors in [34] proposed the fuzzy routing-forwarding algorithm (FCNS) which exploits comprehensive node similarity (social and mobile similarities) in opportunistic social networks. Information about the state of the network is collected and updated to evaluate the social and mobile similarities of the nodes in the network, and then the transmission preference for each node is calculated through the fuzzy evaluation. The forwarding strategy depends on comparing the transmission preference of the nodes where the node with higher transmission preference will be selected as a message relay. In addition, FCNS uses a feedback mechanism for more stable forwarding of the message in the network. The results showed good achievement in terms of delivery ratio and routing overhead.

Authors in [35] considered the context of social importance when exploiting social similarity to improve routing performance in mobile opportunistic networks. Context information are recorded in nodes' buffer and a relay node is selected if it has the most similar social behavior to the destination. Authors in [19] proposed a hybrid routing scheme to enhance the routing efficiency of the epidemic protocol by exploiting social properties. Degree centrality metric was used to adjust the Time To Live (TTL) value of the forwarded messages in the seeking of decrease the redundancy of Epidemic protocol. Thereupon, EpSoc forwards messages towards the nodes that have higher degree centrality values.

In contrast to these works where a limited number of social features and social activity patterns were considered in the implementation of the routing protocols, the proposed approach allows us to exploit all social characteristics available in a user's social profile. The proposed approach considers the mutual correlation between the importance of a social feature and the node's interactions in the network. As long as the impact of different social features and social activity patterns over time is an important issue we also rank them according to user's social activity during different periods of the day. For each time period, we recorded and updated node contacts and ranked the social features based on their impact. The details of the proposed protocol and the related algorithms are presented below.

III. THE R-SOR PROTOCOL

The R-SOR protocol is a social-based routing protocol that ranks social characteristics and exploits them for efficient message forwarding in OMSNs. Several social characteristics such as nationality, language, interest topics, membership, and hobbies can be stored in a user's social profile. Social behavior and activities of the people are a reflection of their social characteristics during their daily routine. For example, researchers with similar interesting research topics encounter each other and make a discussion for a long time during meeting activities, students with common hobbies tend to form groups and interconnect regularly in the campus, etc. These simple examples indicate that social features have an impact on

the individuals' social behavior during their daily routine. In Table I, the notations and definitions that will be used throughout the R-SOR protocol algorithms are summarized.

TABLE I. USED NOTATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

Notation	Definition
f_x	Social feature.
n_F	Number of social features.
F	Set of social features.
p	Day time period.
P_i	Set of day time periods where the node i encounters other nodes in the network.
N_i^p	Set of the encountered nodes by the node i at the day time period p .
C_{ij}^p	Number of contacts between node i and node j in the day time period p .
C_{i,f_x}^p	Number of contacts of node i with other nodes that share same social feature f_x at the day time period p .
w_{i,f_x}^p	Social feature contact weight of a given social feature f_x in the node i at the day period p .
$V_{f_x,j}^p$	Set of values of a social feature $f_x \in F$ in the node j at the day time period p .
f_{max}	Highest ranked social feature of destination in the current day time period.

A. Updating Nodes' Contacts Per Day Time Period

People have daily routines, they follow almost stable patterns of social behavior in their everyday life. To consider the development of the people's social behavior during the different time periods of their everyday life, we propose the slicing of the day into 6 time periods, each one 4 hours long, as depicted in Figure 1. This division in different time periods has been reported in [33, 36] and evolves social structures that reflect the different interactions that users have over different daytime periods. Each node records and updates the history of the nodes it encounters per time period, while roaming on the network. These contacts' information set will be exploited to rank the social features. Let C_p be the set of contact events during the day time period p , $p=1, \dots, 6$. A contact event c within a time period is characterized by the couple of contact nodes i and j and is denoted by $enc(i, j, c)$. The number of contacts of a node i with a node j during a time period p is calculated based on the following equation:

$$C_p^{ij} = \sum_{c \in C_p} enc(i, j, c) \quad (1)$$

where $enc(i, j, c) = 1$ if there is a direct connection between i and j at the contact event c , otherwise $enc(i, j, c) = 0$.

Hence, the total number of contacts of node i in the time period p is calculated as:

$$C_i^p = \sum_{j \in N_i^p} C_{ij}^p \quad (2)$$

where N_i^p denotes the set of nodes encountering the node i within the time period p .

Algorithm 1, shown in Figure 2 is used to update node contacts for each day time period.

Fig. 1. SOR social feature for a node over day periods.

```

Begin
1:  if node  $i$  encounters node  $j$ 
2:      get the current period  $p$ 
3:      if  $p \in P_i$ 
4:          if node  $j \in N_i^p$ 
5:               $C_{ij}^p \leftarrow C_{ij}^p + 1$ 
6:          else
7:              add node  $j$  to  $N_i^p$ 
8:               $C_{ij}^p \leftarrow 1$ 
9:          end if
10:     else
11:         add  $p$  to  $P_i$ 
12:         add node  $j$  to  $N_i^p$ 
13:          $C_{ij}^p \leftarrow C_{ij}^p + 1$ 
14:     end if
15: end if
End
    
```

Fig. 2. Algorithm 1: Pseudo-code of update node's periods.

B. Ranking Social Features

Mobile nodes have several social features stored in the user's profile. Each social feature available in the user's profile may have a single value, like the country feature, or multiple values such as the nationality and interesting topics. For every time period, the contacts with other nodes are recorded in the period contacts profile. Accordingly, the social features of each node are ranked according to the number of contacts with other nodes that are associated with the same social features. Let $F = \{f_1, \dots, f_{n_F}\}$ be the set of social features which can be associated to the nodes in the network, where n_F is the number of social features included in the ranking process, and let $V_{f_x, i}$ be the set of values that a social feature f_x can take at the node i , $x = 1, \dots, n_F$. For a given node i and a time period p , the number of contacts with other nodes that share the same social

feature f_x is counted and is denoted by C_{i, f_x}^p . This is calculated using:

$$C_{i, f_x}^p = \sum_{j \in N_i^p} p_{f_x}(i, j) \quad (4)$$

where $p_{f_x}(i, j) = 1$ if $V_{f_x, i} \cap V_{f_x, j} \neq \emptyset$. In other words, the number of contacts of the node i with regard to the social feature f_x is incremented by 1 when a node j encounters the node i if and only if at least 1 value of the concerned social feature is similar in both nodes. Accordingly, the weight of contacts associated with the social feature f_x of node i at time period p is calculated by:

$$w_{i, f_x}^p = \frac{C_{i, f_x}^p}{C_i^p} \quad (5)$$

It is worth noting that w_{i, f_x}^p is a measure of significance of a given social feature f_x and is referred to as social feature contact (SFC) weight. The main idea behind this work is to involve the values of the SFC weights in the ranking process of the social features which is ultimately used as input in the forwarding decision. To this end, the SFC weights of each node in the network are calculated and stored in ascending order in the node's profile. The social feature that has the highest SFC weight value is the top-ranked social feature and is considered as the most impactful on the message forwarding process. Algorithm 2 (Figure 3) is used to record and update the ranked vector of the social features.

```

Input:
 $i$  ← current node  $i$ 
 $p$  ← current period  $p$ 
 $N_i^p$  ← The set of nodes encountering  $i$  at time period  $p$ 
 $V_{f_x, j}^p$  ← The set of social feature values,  $f_x \in F, j \in N_i^p$  at the time period  $p$ 

Output:
 $w_{i, f_x}^p = 1, \dots, n_F$ 

Begin
for each node  $j$  in  $N_i^p$ 
    calculate  $C_{ij}^p$  (Algorithm 1)
    for each social feature  $f_x \in F$ 
        for each social feature value  $v_{f_x, j}$  in  $V_{f_x, j}$ 
            if  $v_{f_x, j} = v_{f_x, i}$ 
                 $C_{i, f_x}^p \leftarrow C_{i, f_x}^p + 1$ 
            end if
        end for
         $w_{i, f_x}^p = C_{i, f_x}^p / C_i^p$ 
    end for
end for
end
    
```

Fig. 3. Algorithm 2: Pseudo-code of ranking social features.

C. R-SOR Forwarding Strategy

The R-SOR protocol includes two steps before starting the message forwarding process. The first step is devoted to reap the patterns of the mobile user's social behavior in the corresponding day time period while the second step is to rank the SFC weights that will be involved in the forwarding decision. Based on the aforementioned description, every node ranks its social features per time period using the Algorithm 2. Algorithm 3 describes the proposed R-SOR algorithm for message forwarding. Let node i be the current node. If a node j encounters the node i , then at first, node j will be checked for the availability of the destination's top-ranked social feature in its social profile. If available, then the number of contacts regarding this feature in node j will be compared to that in node i . If the number of concerned contacts of node j is greater than that of node i , then the message will be forward to node j else node i will still carrying the message. A message forwarding will also occur if the destination's top-ranked social feature is available in node j but not available in node i .

Fig. 4. Forwarding process in SOR.

Figure 4 shows an example of the message forwarding process. Let S and D be the sender and destination pair nodes respectively, and let N1, N2, and N3 be the intermediate nodes which are candidates for the next forwarding process. Assume that in the current day time period, the top-ranked social feature for node D is the "language". Node S will select from the intermediate nodes (N1, N2, and N3) that have common languages, in this case nodes N1 and N3, will be selected. Node S will further choose the node that has the highest rank for language feature, in this example N3. The forwarding algorithm is shown in Figure 5 (Algorithm 3).

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Data Set

The dataset INFOCOM06 [25] was used for the simulations. This dataset is suitable for this study because of the viability of social characteristics of the mobile users. The

participants were asked for filling answers in a questionnaire about different social features. We obtained this social information and attached it as social profiles for the mobile users in our experiments. We exploited the 10 available social characteristics, namely nationality, studies, languages, affiliation position, city, country, stay, member and topics. In this dataset, 78 mobile iMotes have a wireless range of around 30 meters using Bluetooth technology for communication. The encountering nodes within the short range of the 78 nodes are saved and tracked.

```

Input:
i ← current node
p ← current period
d ← destination node
 $N_i^p$  ← Set of nodes encountering i at the time period p
 $V_{f_{max},i}^p$  ← Set of values of the  $f_{max}$  social feature at the current node i
 $V_{f_{max},j}^p$  ← Set of values of the  $f_{max}$  social feature at the encountering nodes  $j \in N_i^p$ 

Begin
1:  $w_{d,f_x}^p$  ← weight of contacts associated with the social feature  $f_x, x = 1, \dots, n_F$ , of the destination node d at time period p. (Algorithm 2)
2:  $f_{max}$  ←  $arg \{ \max_{f_x \in F} \{ w_{d,f_x}^p \} \}$ 
3:  $C_{i,f_{max}}^p$  ← Number of contacts of node i with other nodes that share same social feature  $f_{max}$ .
4: if node i encounters a node j
5:  $C_{j,f_{max}}^p$  ← Number of contacts of node j with other nodes that share same social feature  $f_{max}$ .
6: for each message in the buffer of the node i
7: if  $V_{f_{max},j}^p \neq \emptyset$ 
8: if  $V_{f_{max},i}^p = \emptyset \vee C_{j,f_{max}}^p > C_{i,f_{max}}^p$ 
9: forward the message to node j
8: end if
9: end if
10: end for
11: end if
end
    
```

Fig. 5. Algorithm 3: Pseudo-code of R-SOR forwarding algorithm.

B. Simulation Setup

The Opportunistic Network Environment (ONE) [37] was used to conduct the experiments and to evaluate the proposed protocol. ONE is a Java-based simulation program which is designed primarily for opportunistic networks. The performance of the proposed R-SOR protocol is compared with that of 5 benchmark routing protocols, namely Epidemic and EpSoc which are flooding-based routing protocols, PROPHET which is a prediction-based routing protocol and Bubble Rap and MSM which are social-based routing protocols. The simulation settings are summarized in Table II.

TABLE II. SIMULATION SETTINGS

Parameter	Value
Interface	Bluetooth
Number of nodes	78 short range devices
Transmission speed	2 Mbps
Mobility	Real trace data (INFOCOM06)
Buffer size	1, 2, 5, 15, 25, 35, 45, 55 MB
Routing protocols	R-SOR, Epidemic, PRoPHET, BubbleRap, EpSoc, and MSM
Message size	128 kB
Message frequency	1 message every 30 to 40s

In each experiment, we evaluate the performance of considered protocols based on the following metrics:

- **Successful delivery ratio:** it is the ratio between the number of delivered messages and the total number of created messages. The ideal value of the successful delivery ratio is 1.0. This is attained when all created messages are delivered to their destinations.
- **Overhead ratio:** It reflects how many redundant messages are transmitted to deliver one message. It simply reflects the transmission cost in a network.
- **Average latency:** it is the average of the time elapsed between message creation and delivery.
- **Average hop count:** it is the average number of hops that messages traverse to reach the destination.

C. Experiments and Results

To evaluate the performance of the R-SOR protocol and provide a comparison against the performances of the other protocols, message TTL and buffer size values are varied in the carried experiments. It is worth noting that TTL and buffer size have a crucial impact on the routing performance in OMSNs because of the opportunistic behavior of the mobile node communication and the use of the SCF mechanism for message passing. Figures 6-9 show the performance of the proposed R-SOR protocol compared to that of the other routing protocols in terms of delivery ratio, overhead ratio, average latency, and average hop count. The experiments were carried out for different TTL values around the values given in Table II (from 10m until 1.6 days). Figure 6 shows the delivery ratio performances of the different protocols with varying TTL. The Figure shows that for low-range TTL values (10m-1h), the delivery ratio performance of all the routing protocols are low, due to the fact that the TTL value of a dropped message is set to 0. Increasing the TTL value causes rising up the delivery ratio (from TTL value of 8h, we observe a certain saturation), due to the delivering of quite a lot of messages to the destinations. For higher TTL values (over 16h), the delivery ratio decreases slightly with further TTL increase. This is the result of the increased number of carried and ultimately dropped messages in the networks which affects negatively the delivery ratio. The Figure reveals that the R-SOR protocol outperforms all other protocols for TTL values higher than 8h. Hence, messages with high TTL value are more probably carried by nodes that have strong social relations enabling R-SOR to achieve higher delivery ratio. The R-SOR protocol considers the regular patterns of the users' social activity during their everyday life and carries out a ranking of the social

characteristics based on the encountering rate in each day time period. This finding strongly implies that the adopted raking strategy leads to the selection of the relay node that has higher probability to encounter the destination.

Fig. 6. Delivery ratio over TTL change.

Fig. 7. Overhead ratio over TTL change.

Figure 7 presents the relationship between the overhead ratio and TTL value. It can be seen that the R-SOR protocol outperforms the Epidemic, PRoPHET and Bubble Rap protocols and its superiority is obviously manifested at high TTL values (higher than 1h). In these scenarios, messages do not expire quickly, which enables the R-SOR protocol to update the contact profiles of the nodes and ultimately to rank the social characteristics in each day time period. The R-SOR protocol considers all social characteristics in the user's profile and ranks them according to the social activities of the mobile nodes for each period. As a result, nodes with strong social relationships with the destination node are chosen as relays. This reduces the number of intermediate nodes involved in the forwarding process and increases the likelihood of delivering the message, and consequently, the overhead ratio is decreased substantially. In addition, Figure 7 shows that the overhead ratio of the EpSoc and MSM protocols is lower than that of the R-SOR protocol. This can be explained by the fact that these protocols apply rigorously defined rules for selecting the next forwarder. Nonetheless, negative impact on the delivery ratio is pronounced as outlined in Figure 6.

Fig. 8. Average latency over TTL change.

Figure 8 shows that the higher the TTL-value, the higher the average latency for all protocols. It is worth noting that raising the TTL gives the messages the opportunity to traverse longer paths to reach their destinations. Hence, the higher the TTL value, the higher the average end-to-end delay. We see that the R-SOR protocol outperforms the others in terms of average latency, with the exceptions of Epidemic and EpSoc which are the most prominent protocols regarding this evaluation metric because of their flooding-based forwarding strategy. The Figure reveals that choosing the appropriate relay based on the social feature ranking increases the likelihood to encounter the destination, so messages are delivered in less time, and thus the effectiveness of the R-SOR protocol in terms of the average latency metric is confirmed. The performance evaluation of the protocols regarding the average hop count is shown in Figure 9. As the TTL increases, the hop counts increase for all protocols until they reach stable levels. The Epidemic protocol performance is affected by the TTL variation more than the other protocols because of its flooding-based forwarding strategy. The Figure shows that the R-SOR protocol outperforms the non-social-based protocols (Epidemic and ProPHET). The hop counts are reduced in R-SOR because exploiting social features limit the number of candidate relay nodes, as a relay node is only chosen if it has a similar value to the destination's top-ranked social feature. Comparing to social-based protocols (Bubble Rap, EpSoc, and MSM) the R-SOR protocol has a similar-to-slightly better performance

Fig. 9. Average hop count over TTL change.

In the following experiments the performance metrics are evaluated by varying the buffer size while the TTL value is set to a constant value (10 hours). This value is selected based on the evaluation of the previous experiments. All protocols have good performance for this TTL value. The message size is set to 128KB. Three levels of buffer size will be considered in this study, namely low level (1, 2, and 5MB), middle level (15, 25, and 35MB), and high level (45 and 55MB). It is worth noting that increasing the buffer size means increasing the capacity of messages a mobile node can carry.

Figure 10 shows the performance of the protocols in terms of delivery ratio with varying buffer size. It is obvious that increasing the buffer size leads to increased delivery ratios for all routing protocols. A higher buffer size enables the mobile nodes to store and carry more messages and ultimately to deliver them to the destinations. The Figure illustrates that the R-SOR protocol outperforms the other protocols with respect to the delivery ratio for all buffer size levels. Moreover, the Figure shows that the superiority of the R-SOR protocol over the others is better exhibited at low and middle buffer size levels. This can be explained by the fact that the R-SOR protocol manages the buffer size more efficiently than the other protocols. The R-SOR involves all the social characteristics of the mobile users and adopts the ranking algorithm to select the next relay node. This leads to forwarding messages only to nodes that provide higher likelihood to encounter the destination. Consequently, the R-SOR protocol will be an effective forwarding mechanism especially in resource-constrained opportunistic networks.

Fig. 10. Delivery ratio over buffer size change.

Figure 11 outlines the overhead ratio with varying buffer size value for all protocols. It is obvious that increasing the buffer size results in decreasing the overhead ratio in the OMSN as intermediate nodes are enabled to carry more messages for later delivery. The R-SOR protocol shows a low overhead ratio in the OMSN. It outperforms Epidemic, PRoPHET, and Bubble Rap protocols, especially for low buffer size levels. Moreover, the Figure shows that the R-SOR protocol slightly outperforms the EpSoc and MSM protocols due to the fact that they apply strict social-based forwarding decision rules. Nonetheless, the delivery ratio for these protocols is lower than that of the proposed R-SOR protocol as shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 11. Overhead ratio over buffer size change.

Figure 12 shows the performance of the routing protocols in terms of average latency with varying buffer size. It can be seen that increasing the buffer size results to an increase in the average latency. Consequently, the messages will have a larger end-to-end delay to reach the destinations. For low buffer size levels, it is observed that the R-SOR protocol has lower average latency than ProPHET, Bubble Rap, and MSM protocols while the Epidemic and EpSoc protocols outperform all protocols due to their flooding-based forwarding strategy.

Fig. 12. Average latency over buffer size change.

Fig. 13. Average hop count over buffer size change.

Exploiting users' social characteristics and ranking them based on the encountering rate in each time period enable the R-SOR to select the forwarder node that has the higher likelihood to deliver the message in a lower end-to-end delay. Increasing the buffer size above 25MB, R-SOR, PRoPHET, and Bubble Rap protocols achieve almost similar performance. They benefit from the ability to store more messages in the mobile nodes and they outperform Epidemic, EpSoc, and MSM. The average hop count evaluation results are shown in Figure 13. The Figure reveals that the R-SOR protocol achieves low hop count and outperforms the Epidemic and PRoPHET protocols due to the fact that only nodes that have similarity with the top ranked social feature of the destination will be selected for message forwarding. Hence, a low number of nodes will incorporate in delivering the messages in the OMSN and hence a low average hop count is attained. The achievement of the R-SOR protocol in terms of average hop count is close to that of the Bubble Rap and EpSoc protocols and is slightly higher than that of the MSM protocol. This is because the MSM protocol applies stricter rules in forwarding messages than the R-SOR protocol as it exploits multiple social metrics for relay selection which leads to the decrease of the intermediate nodes. However, as we mentioned before and as shown in Figure 10, this impacts negatively the performance in terms of delivery ratio, where the R-SOR protocol outperforms the MSM protocol.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the R-SOR protocol is proposed, which aims to enhance the routing efficiency in OMSNs. The R-SOR protocol ranks the social properties of the mobile users in an OMSN during day time periods, and exploits the impact of social features in order to develop a more efficient forwarding scheme. The empirical results using real data show that the R-SOR outperforms other benchmark protocols, namely flooding-based protocols such as Epsoc and Epidemic, prediction-based protocols such as PRoPHET, and social-based protocols such as MSM and Bubble Rap. Different evaluation metrics were used for performance evaluation and comparison, namely delivery ratio, routing overhead, average latency, and average hop count. Regarding future work, we plan to combine the ranking of multiple social metrics and to make use of the social characteristics of mobile users and Internet of Things (IoT) objects for efficient data dissemination scheme in a social IoT environment.

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Hardware Acceleration of Video Edge Detection with High Level Synthesis on the Xilinx Zynq Platform

Taoufik Saidani

Department of Computer Science
Faculty of Computing and Information Technology
Northern Border University
Rafha, Saudi Arabia and
Laboratory of Electronics and Microelectronics
Faculty of Sciences of Monastir
University of Monastir
Monastir, Tunisia
taoufik.saidan@nbu.edu.sa

Refka Ghodhbbani

Department of Computer Science
Faculty of Computing and Information Technology
Northern Border University
Rafha, Saudi Arabia and
Laboratory of Electronics and Microelectronics
Faculty of Sciences of Monastir
University of Monastir
Monastir, Tunisia
Refka.Ghodhbbani@nbu.edu.sa

Abstract—The study conducted in the current paper consists of validating an original design flow for the rapid prototyping of real-time image and video processing applications on FPGAs. A video application for edge detection with Simulink HDL coder and Vivado High-Level Synthesis (HLS) has been designed as if the code was going to be executed on a conventional processor. The developed tools will automatically translate the code into VHDL hardware language using an advanced compilation technique. This amounts to embedding processors on Xilinx Zynq-7000 System on-Chip (SoC) device in an optimal manner. This automated hardware design flow reduces the time to create a prototype since only the high-level description is required. The design of the video edge detection system is implemented on Xilinx Zynq-7000 platform. The result of the implementation gave effective resource utilization and a good frame rate (95 FPS) under 170MHz frequency.

Keywords—high-level synthesis; automated hardware design; co-design; Xilinx Zynq-7000

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past ten years, several architectures combining reconfigurable processors and/or circuits (Field Programmable Gate Arrays-FPGAs) have been proposed for the acceleration of the execution of increasingly complex applications [1]. Dedicated signal and image processing systems currently use either processors with general or dedicated use, wired solutions configured for specific circuits of the ASIC type, or a combination of these two. However, the conjugation of the increasing algorithm complexity and the large volume of data to process, usually with strong real-time constraints, requires performance that processors cannot provide [2]. Parallel processing can provide speed and programming flexibility, but at the expense of cost and complexity of implementation. In addition, the use of ASICs which offer more processing speed suffers from rigidity and expensive development. Indeed, adding a new functionality to a wired system will surely require a redesign of one or more ASICs and will increase cost [3]. The reconfigurable architectures represent an appropriate response,

they offer better performance than programmable architectures and more flexibility than wired solutions. They use reconfigurable logic components that allow the user to modify the architecture after manufacturing it in a software way, unlike the ASIC whose algorithms are wired in silicon [2, 3].

Video and image processing are now booming and playing an increasingly important role in our everyday life [4, 6]. The integration of embedded systems in the field of modern wireless communications allows us to respond quickly to its ever-increasing demands. The invention of the FPGA made possible the concept of reconfigurable material hardware for video and image processing systems. The traditional design of video and image system architecture around the FPGA does not allow high productivity [3, 4]. The latter can be improved by using a new design technique based on the Model Based Design (MBD) model [5]. Tools based on this technique are intended for embedded systems, the development of signal processing algorithms, the rapid integration of systems, and the analysis of the behavior of complex digital systems for a wide variety of cases. To resolve this constraint, many high level synthesis tools have been developed to take advantage of this technique to achieve FPGA rapid prototyping [3]. The FPGA with its great integration capabilities and reconfiguration is a key component in rapidly developing prototypes. In the objective of encouraging the wide distribution of this type of circuits, it is necessary to improve the development environments to make them more accessible to non-electronics experts [8, 9].

The current study consists in proposing and validating a design flow for the rapid prototyping of real-time image processing applications on FPGAs. It programs a model with HDL coder library as if the code was going to be executed on a Zynq 7000 [8, 14]. The developed tools will automatically generate the code into hardware language (VHDL) using an advanced compilation technique. This amounts to embedding processors in the FPGA in an optimal way.

Corresponding author: Taoufik Saidani

II. ACCELERATION OF THE PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

Figure 1 shows the functional diagram of the proposed system architecture. The design is applicable to both video and image processing since the input pixels are processed successively. For embedded video processing, the process requires mega pixels. It is built by a video block that can be programmed by adapted algorithms and thus accelerate complex and heavy (in terms of resources and execution time) algorithms on the integrated blocks of the Xilinx SoC platform. The output of the video and image systems is passed directly to a video processing block and a display component [10]. The various video and image processing accelerators in FPGA are implemented in platform systems of the Xilinx Zynq 7000 [5, 8].

Fig. 1. The proposed global diagram for video and image system architecture.

In the architecture shown in Figure 1, the Advanced Extensible Interface (AXI) interconnects the processor that transmits the input video to the video processing pipeline system. The USB camera shares the interfaces and communicates with the ARM processor. The frame data are stored in the memory controller. Once the video IP core finalizes the process on the frame, it is displayed via the HDMI display. The pipeline is continued for the next iterations [14].

III. MBD MODEL BASED DESIGN FOR VIDEO AND IMAGE PROCESSING

The MBD technique for FPGAs results from the need to design complex DSP systems which require specific arithmetic units such as the addition-compare-select unit for the Viterbi decoder. These specific computing units require a finer level of FPGA-based circuit optimization [11]. This level of optimization is generally associated with traditional digital design video and image processing system. Model-based design is essentially a way of describing how a system will interact with the analog world in real time. This FPGA prototyping technique consists of converting the model of the system in question from its mathematical formulation to an executable specification [12]. The MBD technique provides a common framework that involves different phases of the development process. This reduces the Time to Market needed to create a complete model. The associated design phases to this technique allow the designer to locate and correct errors before prototyping the system [13]. There are many tools available for designing FPGA systems using the MBD technique. Most of these tools take advantage of the standardized Unified Modeling Language (UML). These tools differ in the way they describe a system and define its characteristics. Some implementation techniques used by these

tools may be less effective than others. However, they guarantee rapid prototyping of the system ensuring time efficiency. The choice of a tool depends on many factors such as the level of flexibility, the availability of pre-built libraries/blocks, and the overall understanding of these blocks. Some UML-based tools are the Arti-Real time Studio, the I-logix's Rhapsody, MATLAB and Simulink Realtime workshop [9]. These tools are used for the design of an embedded multiprocessor environment.

The tools that allow the generation of HDL code for the FPGA can be classified into two categories, the block-based tools and those based on the C language of blocks that generate HDL code from the block diagram, which is then used by the synthesis tool hardware to implement the system design on FPGA. Most of these tools, such as Synplify DSP, Xilinx System Generator, DSP Builder Altera, and Simulink HDL Coder [5], are based on Simulink and MATLAB environment. These tools guarantee a high level modeling environment of signal processing algorithms. Blocks from the Simulink library are used with IP cores from FPGA suppliers to create HDL code specific to the platform in question. Tools such as the Simulink HDL Coder allow more flexibility to the designer, as they integrate MATLAB functions and m-block files. With these tools, the designer develops a Simulink model, then translates it to the FPGA environment. The second category of MBD tools uses C programming language to create an abstraction for the design of systems. Among these tools are the Mentor Graphics Catapult C and the Celoxica's Handel-C. The main motivation behind these tools is the Simulink HDL coder, which is commonly used for the implementation of embedded systems on FPGA [13].

Fig. 2. A complete solution for embedded vision.

Simulink HDL coder is an MBD tool that enables modeling, analysis, and simulation of systems. It gives a well-structured graphical environment for the designer that allows him/her to create system designs of a high level of complexity. In addition, this tool allows the user to create flexible custom blocks from MATLAB functions. The Simulink HDL coder allows the designer to create HDL code bit-precise and synthesizable from the model developed using Simulink blocks. The obtained HDL code can be synthesized and mapped to the target FPGA board using tools such as Altera Quartus II, Synplify, and Xilinx Vivado. The Simulink HDL coder has many built libraries [15]. Some of these predefined libraries include adders, multipliers, accumulators, integrators, multi-port switches, lookup tables, etc.

IV. MODEL BASED MDB DESIGN FOR FPGA PROTOTYPING

A typical MBD design flow for implementing FPGA-based video and image processing system is shown in Figure 3.

A. System Specifications

The design of any DSP block always begins with defining the design specifications. This definition represents an abstract way to describe the main function of the block. At the end of this step, different parameters are obtained, such as the type of input/output and the basic mathematical function of the block. We can always determine whether the design of the block can be reused or not [12].

B. Analysis of Design Needs

As mentioned above, the basic mathematical function of the block is determined in the specification phase. The next step in the design process is to identify the algorithm required for the implementation practice. This algorithm is chosen based on many factors such as complexity, duration of the calculation, and the resources used. The algorithm is then subdivided into functions [12].

Fig. 3. Model-based design for embedded vision.

C. Simulation and Modeling

In this step we convert the design specifications into a high-level model using MBD tools such as the Simulink HDL Coder and XSG. This step consists in representing the mathematic equations in the form of models. Libraries and blocks provided by the tool facilitate this representation. The resulting model is then tested by observing the output for the various test input signals. Despite the wide variety of features and blocks provided by Simulink, only certain blocks can be converted using its HDL conversion environment which means that the other blocks must be replaced or built using the primitive libraries of the HDL converter tools such as VHDL [12].

D. System Implementation

This is the most important step. It consists of an automatic generation mechanism which is provided by the MBD tools. The flow advisor tool provided by Simulink HDL Coder, helps checking the model compatibility for code generation, converting the floating point model to a fixed point model,

setting the clock, types of input/output data into the fixed point model, and data scaling. When the HDL code is generated, it can be synthesized using the Simulink HDL Coder tool. The latter supports simulation tools. It also supports the synthesis tools of Xilinx and Altera [14].

V. EXPERIMENTAL APPLICATIONS

A. Sobel Edge Detector

The Sobel operator allows to locally evaluate the norm of the two-dimensional spatial gradient of a grayscale image. The regions of strong local variations in intensity corresponding to the contours are amplified. Along the O_x and O_y axes, the Sobel operator approximates the directional derivatives using a convolution of the image $f(x,y)$ with 3×3 masks. We notice that the mask of the Sobel operator corresponds in fact to the application of a smoothing operation by the $(1 \ 0 \ 1)$ operator followed by the application of a derivation operation by the $(1 \ 0 \ -1)$ operator in the orthogonal direction. The 3×3 matrix is convolved with the image to calculate the approximated horizontal and vertical gradients G'_x and G'_y as follows:

$$G'_x = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -1 \\ 2 & 0 & -2 \\ 1 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$G'_y = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & -2 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

The approximate absolute gradient magnitude and the gradient angle of each pixel are shown by:

$$|G'| = \sqrt{G'_x{}^2 + G'_y{}^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\theta = \arctan\left(\frac{G'_y}{G'_x}\right) \quad (4)$$

B. Edge Detection Hardware Design Using Simulink

The proposed video edge detection hardware prototyping uses the Sobel filter algorithm, and it has been designed with the Simulink HDL coder toolbox, so this design can be inserted as an FPGA IP core within any video processing pipeline flexibly. This is followed by a detailed description of the proposed hardware architecture. Figure 4 presents the top-level module for video edge detection based on the Sobel filter. The "video From File" block obtains the input video for the video edge detection system from the directory. This input video is converted to frames. The frames are serialized to pixels. Since the pixel values are of double type, the "Convert" block is used. Pixel-streaming processing is performed by HDL implementations of image and video processing algorithms. Therefore, a pixel stream is created with the Simulink "serialize" blocks [12]. The inverse process at the output of video processing system is performed by a "deserialize" block to verify the output processed in image format. These two blocks are depicted in Figures 6 and figure 7 respectively.

C. Synthesis and FPGA Implementation

Finally, in the third step (Figure 8), the Simulink HDL Coder converts the video edge detection Software-Hardware model into AXI4 streaming bus compliant IP core in the form of HDL (VHDL) source code. To verify in real time the

functionality of this IP core in a practical environment, a Hardware-Software co-design (HW-SW) has been implemented directly on a Xilinx Zynq-7000 AP SoC XC7Z020-CLG484 FPGA running at 170MHz. Simulink HDL coder generates a Full Vivado project for the HW-SW. This

project can be implemented in the Xilinx Vivado tool (version 2019.1), with all the software and hardware peripherals. Also, the Color transform IP core and the Sobel core are connected across a single bus.

Fig. 4. Simulink HDL coder model for video edge detection.

Fig. 5. Simulink HDL coder model for video edge detection core.

Fig. 6. Frame pixel serialization.

Fig. 7. Frame pixel deserialization.

Fig. 8. HDL workflow for the video edge detection system.

The HLS tool allows the generation of stream interfaces incorporating the hardware accelerator (IP). Once the high level synthesis is completed, a compressed file (.zip) containing all hardware components is generated. This file is exported to the media Vivado packages to generate our SW/HW design. At this level, the Vivado tool constitutes a complete environment for the design of the finalized SW/HW architecture. The latter allows the installation of an on-board processor connected to one or several hardware accelerators through AXI interconnection buses specific to the selected platform. For example, in order to reset the IP core, one has to write 0x1 to the bit 0 of the IPCore_Reset register. To enable or disable the IP core, 0x1 or 0x0 must be written to the IPCore_Enable register.

Fig. 9. Software-Hardware interface via AXI4-Lite.

To access the data ports of the MATLAB/Simulink algorithm, read or write to the associated data registers. The

AXI4 Slave port to pipeline register ratio is selected as 35 in task 3.2 for this model. The default delay to read the AXI4 register is one clock cycle. Depending on the selected ratio and the IO connected to the AXI4 interface, register pipelining is introduced in the read logic of the AXI4 registers. For this model the AXI4 pipeline register ratio setting 35 is larger than all the readable AXI4 slave registers. The total readable AXI4 slave registers are 1, so no pipelining is added to the AXI4 register read back logic. Figure 11 shows the design created using the Xilinx's Vivado CAD tool.

Fig. 10. The AXI Zynq interface.

Fig. 11. HW/SW video edge detection architecture.

In Figure 11, the blue rectangle encircles the IP ZYNQ7 Processing System which represents the processor part of the Xilinx Zynq-7000 SoC. This IP is used to make the system configurations, such as configuring clocks and enabling the propagation of security status from ARM cores (the security state of the processor part) to the reconfigurable part. The rest of the blocks constitute the elements that are implemented in the reconfigurable part of the SoC. The black rectangle encircles the AXI Interconnect which allows the IPs to be connected to each other. The green rectangle surrounds the edge detection IPs with Sobel filters. The red rectangle surrounds the direct and reverse color transformation IP.

D. Resource Utilization

At the next step, we implemented our video processing system cores on Zynq-7020 SOC. The resources used are presented in Table I. Data values, instruction memories, and the firmware are stored in BRAM. The consumed LUTs and DFFs define the architecture of the processor including control signals, internal registers, and microcode. The optimum frequency for our proposed system core is approximately

170MHz and 95FPS for throughput. The complexity of the implemented design affects the resources of the utilized Zynq7000 SOC. The proposed design is performed for input resolution of 1080-1920 frames. The reconfigurable SOC platform using Vivado is approved by these results.

TABLE I. RESOURCE UTILIZATION AND MAXIMUM FREQUENCY FOR THE VIDEO SOBEL EDGE DETECTION MODULE

Maximum frequency	170 Mhz	
LUT-FF Pairs	3816.667	7.38%
LUTs as Logic	2727.667	5.12%
LUTs as Memory	648.6667	3.73%
Slice Registers	2465	2.32%
RAM 36/18	0	0
DSP48	0	0

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a high level model-based hardware design flow using MBD tools was presented. The proposed design flow was put by a video edge detection prototyping into a Zynq 7000 SoC board. Each step of the adopted high level synthesis

prototyping design, from the top level description to the hardware implementation, was described. The global design process can reduce the time of processing by 65%. The experimental results of the proposed video design based on Sobel edge detection reimburse the hardware constraints reducing the complexity for embedded video processing in FPGAs.

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Deadline Verification for Web Services Using Timed Automata

Yamen El Touati

Faculty of Computing and IT
Northern Border University
Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
yamen.touati@nbu.edu.sa

Abstract—Many computation tasks are made today on remote cloud platforms using web services. Beyond the advantages provided by such services, many new challenges arise. One of the challenging problems is ensuring that web services respect critical deadlines. This is a critical issue, especially for real-time systems that use remote web services. This paper aims to propose a framework for deadline verification using Timed Automata (TA).

Keywords—web services; deadlines; timed automata; verification

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last few years, most companies migrated to remote cloud-based services. In these systems, most of the communication is ensured via web services that offer quasi-unlimited resources and computational power. However, companies face new challenges concerning security [1-4] and timing constraints [9-11, 19]. A web service is a software system designed to support interoperable machine-to-machine interaction over a network [6]. They provide flexible and efficient solutions to the sharing of information between people and businesses [6, 20]. By nature, a web service can face many random interferences that can cause delays in the required tasks [12-15, 18]. In many cases, it is not easy to check whether the specification deadlines are respected. In general, this is because some web services are composed of many correlated tasks, where delays and timing are propagated according to a dynamic schedule. In this particular context, timed automata [6-10] are suitable for modeling the evolution of a system focusing on time constraints. These are presented as an extension of finite-state automata with clocks into location. Transitions can be executed when a linear constraint on clocks, called guard, is verified. This framework presents an interesting graphical interface combined with powerful computational power. Moreover, it is more suitable to solve verification problems using a timed automata framework than performing algebraic calculus, which may be difficult to resolve if the size of the system increases. This paper proposes a new method based on timed automata reachability checking in order to resolve the problem of deadline verification.

II. BACKGROUND OF TIMED AUTOMATA AND TIME TRANSITION SYSTEMS

\mathbb{R}_+ denotes nonnegative reals, $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ denotes the finite set of real-valued variables, and the circumflex (\sim) is used to denote an element of the set of operators $\{\leq, \geq, =, \neq\}$. A simple inequality over X is an inequality of the form $x \sim c$, where $x \in X$ and $c \in \mathbb{R}_+$. A rectangular predicate over X is a conjunction of linear inequalities over X . $C(X)$ denotes the set of linear predicates on X .

A. Timed Automata

A timed automaton [1,3] is a tuple $A = (L, l_0, X, \Sigma, E, inv, F)$ where:

- L is a finite set of locations (nodes)
- l_0 is the initial state
- X is a finite set of non-negative real valued clocks
- Σ is a finite set of actions or events (labels)
- $E \subset L \times C(X) \times \Sigma \times 2^X \times L$ is a set of transitions. $e \in E$, and $e = (l, \delta, a, R, l')$ is defined, where l is the start location, δ is the guard, a is the action, R is the set of clocks to reset, and l' is the end location
- $inv \in C(X)^L$ is a function that associates an invariant to each location
- $F \subset L$ is the set of final states

B. Semantic of Timed Automata

The semantic of timed automata $A = (L, l_0, X, \Sigma, E, inv)$ is given by a Time Transition System [2] $SA = (Q, q_0, \rightarrow)$, where:

- $Q = L \times \mathbb{R}_+^X$
- $q_0 = (l_0, 0)$ is the initial state
- $\rightarrow \subset Q \times (\Sigma \cup \mathbb{R}_+) \times Q$ is defined by:
 - $(l, v) \xrightarrow{a} (l', v')$ (discrete transition) if $\exists (l, \delta, a, R, \rho, l') \in E$ such that $\delta(v) = true$, and $vi = v[R \leftarrow 0][\rho]$ and $inv(l')(v') = true$
 - $(l, v) \xrightarrow{t} (l', v')$ (continuous transition) if $l = l'$ and $vi = v + t$ and $inv(l)(vi) = true$

It is noted that $(l,v) \rightarrow^* (l',v')$ in the case of a transition sequence of leading from (l,v) to (l',v') .

C. Reachability in Timed automata

A run of a timed automaton A is a path in S_A starting from l_0 . $[[A]]$ denotes the set of all runs in the timed automaton A . It is noted that $(l,v) \rightarrow^t (l',v') \rightarrow^a (l'',v'')$ is equivalent to $(l,v) \rightarrow_a^t (l'',v'')$. A state (l_i, v_i) is considered as *reachable*, if:

$$\exists (l_0, v_0) \rightarrow_{a_0}^{t_0} (l_1, v_1) \rightarrow_{a_1}^{t_1} (l_2, v_2) \rightarrow_{a_2}^{t_2} \dots \rightarrow_{a_i}^{t_i} (l_i, v_i)$$

where $(l_0, v_0) = q_0$. A run:

$$(l_0, v_0) \rightarrow_{a_0}^{t_0} (l_1, v_1) \rightarrow_{a_1}^{t_1} (l_2, v_2) \rightarrow_{a_2}^{t_2} \dots \rightarrow_{a_i}^{t_i} (l_i, v_i) \dots$$

starting from $q_0 = (l_0, v_0)$ is a *timed trace*, denoted as:

$$w = (a_0 = e_0, \delta_0) \rightarrow (a_1, \delta_1) \rightarrow (a_2, \delta_2) \rightarrow \dots (a_i, \delta_i) \dots$$

where w is a sequence of pairs (a_i, δ_i) , $a_i \in E$ is a transition, and $\delta_{i+1} \in \mathbb{R}_+$ is the delay between the two successive events a_i and a_{i+1} where: $\delta_0 = 0$ and $\forall i \geq 1$:

$$\delta_i = t_i - t_{i-1}$$

III. DEADLINE VERIFICATION IN WEB SERVICES

A web service can be modeled by a set of tasks with a timed automaton, where each location corresponds to a specific configuration in the web service's lifecycle. Transitions between locations correspond to a configuration change. Thus, locations can be considered as elementary subtasks to fulfill the entire web service. Some of these tasks may take a longer than expected time to be fulfilled. Since the sequence of tasks and their exact duration is not easy to tackle in these systems, it would be interesting to investigate a way to check whether any critical deadline was broken.

Fig. 1. Example of a timed automaton.

A. Checking Deadline in Timed Automata

Consider the example shown in Figure 1 and suppose that this timed automaton represents the behavior of a web service composed of 5 subtasks (those represented by locations L1 to

L5). It can be assumed that the deadline of this web service is 16 time units (t.u). Checking whether this deadline is respected is equivalent to checking if L3 is reached always before 16 t.u. In this case, L3 is always reached before 8 t.u, which means that the previous deadline is respected by the web service. To resolve this problem, a universal clock x_0 (a clock that is never reset) can be added and check if the constraint $x_0 \leq 15$ is always verified.

B. Generalization

This problem can be generalized for a timed automaton $A = (L, l_0, X, \Sigma, E, inv)$ as:

Given $A_1 = (L, l_0, X \cup \{x_0\}, \Sigma \cup \{d\}, E, inv)$ and $Deadline \in \mathbb{R}_+$, *Deadline* is respected if:

$$\forall l \in L, \forall v \in \mathbb{R}_+ \text{ such that } (l_0, 0) \rightarrow^* (l, v), v(x_0) \leq Deadline \quad (1)$$

C. Deadline Verification Steps

To ensure that property (1) is respected, this problem is transformed into a reachability verification problem as follows.

- A new derivative automaton is constructed $A_2 = (L \cup \{l_d\}, l_0, X \cup \{x_0\}, \Sigma \cup \{d\}, E \cup E_d, inv)$, such that:

$$E_d = \{(l, x_0 > Deadline, \{d\}, \{\}, l_d), l \in L - F\}$$

- The reachability of l_d should be checked. If l_d is reachable, then the deadline is not guaranteed to be respected by the web service.

The l_d location has the behavior of a typical dead state. Transitions are added from each nonfinal location to l_d , with the guard $x_0 > Deadline$, without any reset.

Fig. 2. Updated Timed Automaton with dead state and universal clock - l_d is not reachable

In the example shown in Figure 2, the suggested method is applied to proceed to deadline verification. Location l_d is reachable if the universal clock t_0 reaches the limit defined by the deadline, here 16. In this particular case, the location l_d is not reachable, which means that the web service satisfies the deadline constraint. However, if a more restrained deadline constraint is considered, e.g. $x \leq 6$, the transition guards leading

to l_d will have the form $t_0 > 6$, as shown in Figure 3. In this case, the location l_d is reachable from any non-final location. In general, if the location l_d is accessible from even a single location, then the deadline constraint becomes unsatisfied.

Fig. 3. Updated timed automaton with dead state and universal clock – l_d is reachable

```

automaton machine_test
  state_var: t0,t1, t2;
  synclabs: m;

loc L1: while true wait {t0'==1 & t1'==1 & t2'==1 }
  when t1>=5 & t1<=10 sync m do {t0'==t0 &
t1'==t1 & t2'==0} goto L2;
  when t1>=4 & t1<=8 sync m do {t0'==t0 &
t1'==t1 & t2'==2} goto L3;
  when t0>=16 sync m do {t0'==t0 & t1'==t1 &
t2'==t2} goto Ld;

loc L2: while true wait {t0'==1 & t1'==1 & t2'==1 }
  when t2>=2 & t2<=4 sync m do {t0'==t0 &
t1'==t1 & t2'==2} goto L4;
  when t0>=16 sync m do {t0'==t0 & t1'==t1 &
t2'==t2} goto Ld;

loc L3: while true wait {t0'==1 & t1'==1 & t2'==1 }
  when t2>=12 & t2<=15 sync m do {t0'==t0 &
t1'==t1 & t2'==2} goto L5;
  when t0>=16 sync m do {t0'==t0 & t1'==t1 &
t2'==t2} goto Ld;

loc L4: while true wait {t0'==1 & t1'==1 & t2'==1 }
;

loc L5: while true wait {t0'==1 & t1'==1 & t2'==1 }
;

loc Ld: while true wait {t0'==1 & t1'==1 & t2'==1 }
;

initially L1 & t0==0 & t1==0 & t2==0 ;
end

echo "-----Forward_analysis----- ";
machine_test.print("TA_text.txt",0);
Forward_Analysis=machine_test.reachable;
Forward_Analysis.print("Forward_Analysis_text.txt",0
);
Forward_Analysis.print;

echo "-----Ld Reachability----- ";
space_to_check=machine_test.{Ld&t0>16};
result
=machine_test.is_reachable_fb(space_to_check);
result.print("Ld_Forward16ReachableSpace0.txt",0);
result.print("Ld_Forward16ReachableSpace1.txt",1);
result.print("Ld_Forward16ReachableSpace2.txt",2);
result.print;

```

Fig. 4. Automata and computation of reachable space.

```

resulting_space = machine_test.{
L1 & t1 - t2 == 0 & t0 - t2 == 0 & t2 >= 0,
L2 & t0 - t1 == 0 & -t0 + t2 >= -10 & t2 >= 0 & t0 -
t2 >= 5,
L3 & t0 - t1 == 0 & t0 - t2 == 0 & t0 >= 4,
Ld & t0 - t1 == 0 & -t0 + t2 >= -10 & t2 >= 0 & t0 -
t2 >= 0 & t0 > 6,
L4 & t0 - t1 == 0 & -t0 + t2 >= -10 & t2 >= 2 & t0 -
t2 >= 5,
L5 & t0 - t1 == 0 & t0 - t2 == 0 & t0 >= 12};

```

Fig. 5. Reachable space.

For any web service modeled by a timed automaton, the problem of checking deadlines is decidable. By construction, checking the deadline respect on automaton A is equivalent to checking the reachability of l_d in automaton A_2 . If a transition is executed in Ed , then the universal clock x_0 exceeds the defined deadline, since the guard $x_0 > \text{Deadline}$ becomes true. Furthermore, the reachability problem is known to be decidable for general timed automata [1], ensuring that the verification of the deadline is decidable. The proposed method to check a deadline is structural. It is sufficient to add a new l_d location, a new universal clock, and as many transitions as the cardinality of the locations set.

The proposed method was applied to the examples in Figures 2 and 3 using the Phaver tool [17]. Phaver allows the computation of reachable space of timed automata. The automata and the computation of reachable space were defined, conforming to the Phaver syntax, as shown in Figure 4. The result reachable space is shown in Figure 5.

D. How to Respect Deadline Constraints

Some web services may not meet some deadline requirements. When the number of clocks/locations increases, it is difficult to determine what are the possible updates on the behavior of the system to converge to the requirements. It is interesting to find a solution that describes the required values of the clocks with respect to the deadline constraints by following the following steps:

- Mark all locations where l_d is reachable. This set is denoted as L_d
- $\forall l \in L_d$, update $inv(l)$ by adding the constraint $t_0 \leq \text{Deadline}$
- Foreach $l \in L_d$, perform a backward analysis considering the reverse automata and the new location environment [16]
- Merge all the reachable space.

The result of these steps is a new automaton where the l_d location is never reachable. The implementability of these new constraints on the web service can be checked by the developers or designers based on the new constraints obtained on locations and guards. Moreover, it could be a starting point to enhance and upgrade the web service considering the new constraints.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper focused on the problem of deadline verification for web services that could be modeled by timed automata. This framework offers the possibility to model the internal behavior of a web service with explicit consideration of timing constraints. The contribution of this paper is to propose a way to transform this problem into a reachability verification problem of a derived automaton. This new automaton is obtained by a structural and linear transformation. Future work consists of the generalization of this problem for a sequence of subtasks of a web service with multi-deadline constraints. Moreover, it is possible to tackle the deadline verification in the context of web service composition [4, 8]. In this case, it is necessary to deal with the synchronous composition of timed automata as modeling frameworks.

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An Evaluation of the Extreme Rainfall Event of 2010 over the Kabul River Basin using the WRF Model

Fehmida Rafi

U.S.-Pakistan Center for Advanced Studies in Water Mehran
University of Engineering and Technology
Jamshoro, Sindh, Pakistan
fehmidarafi850@gmail.com

Ghulam H. Dars

U.S.-Pakistan Center for Advanced Studies in Water
Mehran University of Engineering and Technology
Jamshoro, Sindh, Pakistan
ghdars.uspcasw@faculty.muet.edu.pk

Courtenay Strong

Department of Atmospheric Sciences
University of Utah
Salt Lake City, Utah, USA
court.strong@utah.edu

Kamran Ansari

U.S.-Pakistan Center for Advanced Studies in Water Mehran
University of Engineering and Technology
Jamshoro, Sindh, Pakistan
kansari.uspcasw@faculty.muet.edu.pk

Syed Hammad Ali

Glacier Monitoring and Research Center (GMRC)
Water and Power Development Authority (WAPDA)
Lahore, Pakistan
syedhammadali2001@yahoo.com

Abstract-Extreme precipitation events are among the most severe weather hazards. Knowledge about the spatial patterns underlying such events in the Upper Indus Basin is limited because estimating precipitation is very challenging due to the data scarcity and the complex orography. Numerical weather prediction models can be applied at a fine resolution to overcome this issue. The Advanced Research Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model version 3.8.1 was applied over the Kabul River Basin to simulate the temperature and precipitation of monsoon season 2010, i.e., 1st May to 16th September 2010. We considered the May month as a spin-up period. The initial and boundary conditions were derived from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, Climate Forecast System Reanalysis data. The model was set up by using two-nested domains with increasing horizontal resolution moving inward from 15km on domain d01 to 5km on domain d02. The simulations were compared with TRMM 3B42, and station data collected from the Pakistan Meteorological Department and Water and the Power Development Authority using bias, percentage bias, root mean square error, and Pearson correlation. The results revealed that the simulated precipitation was improved from d01 to d02. However, the model showed mixed results with overestimation of precipitation at some stations and underestimations at others. Simulated precipitation generally agreed better with TRMM than with station data. Overall, the results indicate that the WRF model can be used to simulate heavy precipitation in complex terrain.

Keywords-WRF-ARW model; Upper Indus Basin; Kabul River Basin; Pakistan; climate change

Corresponding author: Fehmida Rafi

I. INTRODUCTION

The Indus basin is prone to floods and has been hit by massive and destructive flood events in the past. The main causes of floods in various regions of Himalayan Karakoram and Hindukush (HKH) is the intense monsoon rainfall and the rapid snowmelt due to the rising temperatures [1-4]. Pakistan faced an unprecedented and most devastating flood in 2010, which inundated 100,000km², affecting more than 20 million people, with a death toll of 1,980 [5]. Many factors are responsible for the 2010 flood occurrence, however the primary cause was extreme monsoon precipitation [7, 8]. In the early July of 2010, a strong ridge of high pressure was developed over Russia, which moved southward and was combined with the monsoon track and the Phet cyclone [9, 10]. The combination of these three factors caused unprecedented rainfall in Pakistan. The northwestern parts of the country, especially Kabul River Basin (KRB), were struck first by the flooding event of 2010, which then traveled to the south, causing severe damage to houses, crops, and livestock [8]. Authors in [9] reported that on 29 July 2010, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) province received more than 200mm of rainfall, which caused severe flash floods. Many stations in KPK received more than 150% of their climatological monthly July rainfall on 29 July. The KRB is a data-scare region, and the lack of sufficient meteorological stations makes performing climate and hydrological studies very challenging [10].

Global Climate Models (GCMs) are basic tools that assess climate change, but their coarse resolution limits their utility

for studying hydrology processes that are sensitive to sub-grid scale variations in precipitation. The complex terrain in the mountainous areas exhibit variations at much finer scales than the grid spacing of GCMs. Therefore, Regional Climate Models (RCMs) are used to perform hydro-climate studies in complex terrain [11, 12]. Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) models can be applied at higher resolutions to overcome the data scarcity issue and enhance the knowledge of atmospheric variability. The WRF model has been used worldwide for different applications [13, 14], but its application to the Indus River Basin (IRB) or even Pakistan is minimal [9, 15].

Pakistan is among the top 10 countries affected by climate change. Extreme events due to climate change cannot be completely avoided [16, 17], but their impacts can be reduced by developing effective and efficient forecasting techniques through sophisticated tools. This study has been conducted to simulate the flood-producing rainfall event of 2010, which occurred in KRB by using the WRF model with a two-nested domain with a horizontal resolution of 15km and 5km. The event of 2010 is used as a case study to examine the applicability of the WRF model to simulate extreme precipitation events. The study will help in overcoming the lack of gauge data for forecasting heavy precipitation in complex terrains, such as KRB. We believe that this study will improve the understanding of the flood-producing rainfall event of 2010 and may serve as a baseline for the authorities to devise better strategies to reduce the adverse effects of heavy precipitation events.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Area

The Kabul River is a 700-kilometer long river which is located between 33°36' N - 36°55' N and 67°36' E - 73°54' E. The river starts from the Sanglakh Range of Hindukush Mountains in Afghanistan and enters Pakistan through Mohmand Agency, where it is first gauged at Warsak Dam, then passes through Nowshera and finally drains into the Indus River near Attock. It contributes about 10% to 20% of its annual flows to the Indus river system [17]. The total catchment area of the Kabul River Basin (KRB) is about 76,908km², out of which 14,000km² are located in Pakistan (Figure 1). The basin has elevation of 305-7690m [18]. Higher discharge in the river is observed in July and August due to the heavy rainfall and, due to the higher temperature of these months, glacier melting. The main cause of flooding in the region is the combination of rainfall and glacier melting [19]. The climate of the basin is semi-arid. The maximum temperature of 28°C is observed in June-August, whereas the mean minimum temperature is -6°C. Due to the complex terrain and the variation in elevation, precipitation varies throughout the basin. The maximum precipitation occurs during winters in the form of snowfall, with an average of 110mm [20, 21]. Chitral, Swat, and lower parts of the Kabul River experience the Indian summer monsoon, On the contrary, the Upper Kabul is influenced by western disturbances [17].

Fig. 1. Map of the two nested domains of WRF simulations at the Kabul River Basin (d01 = 6km, d02 = 2km).

B. WRF Model and Setup

In this study, the Advanced Research Weather Research & Forecasting (WRF) model [21] is used. The WRF model is a next-generation mesoscale numerical weather system, which is used for short-term weather forecasts and long-term climate simulations. The WRF has been developed by the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) in partnership with National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) and the US Department of Defense. The WRF model was set up by using two nested domains, domain 1 (d01) and domain 2 (d02) with increasing resolution moving inward from 15km to 5km grid spacing (Figure 1). The Lambert map projection type is chosen for both domains. The inner domain (d02) is centered over northwest Pakistan to represent KRB with two-way nesting. The simulation started at May, 1 at 00:00 hours and ended at September, 16 at 20:00 hours. The hourly simulated data were converted into daily data for the validation process. Initial and boundary conditions for the simulations were derived from the NOAA Climate Forecast System Reanalysis (CFSR) data [22], which has a 38km horizontal resolution. The research shows that the CFSR dataset performs well in simulating atmospheric changes over the HKH region [11, 22].

The WRF model is a non-hydrostatic model that has many options for physical parameterization schemes. The model is configured with the Noah Multi-Parameterization (Noah-MP) land surface model [23], Yonsei University (YSU) planetary boundary layer scheme [24], Thompson microphysics scheme [25], Rapid Radiative Transfer Model (RRTM) longwave radiation scheme [26], Dudhia shortwave scheme [27], surface layer scheme [28], and Betts-Miller-Janjic cumulus scheme [29]. All these schemes were applied for both domains, however the resolution of the inner domain (d02) is small enough to allow switching off the convective parameterization.

C. Model Validation

We evaluated the simulations with the station meteorological data obtained from the Pakistan Meteorological Station (PMD) and Water and Power Development Authority

(WAPDA). The daily data come from 11 stations, namely Balakot, Chitral, Drosh, Dir, Saidu-Sharif, Peshawar, Ushkore, Yasin, Phulra, BeshamQila, and Daggar. The WRF precipitation output was also assessed with the Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) 3B42 version 7 gridded precipitation data at a monthly time scale. TRMM is considered a reliable gridded precipitation dataset in the Himalayan Karakoram region. The TRMM dataset has the best performance among the other remote sensing datasets in the Indus basin [30]. Similarly, authors in [31] revealed that TRMM 3B42V7 is better than the other products when evaluated in the Hunza river. The WRF simulations were assessed by the percentage bias (PBIAS), root mean squared error (RMSE), and Pearson correlation coefficient (r), and bias.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (O_i - S_i)^2}{N}} \quad (1)$$

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (O_i - \bar{O})(S_i - \bar{S})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (O_i - \bar{O})^2 \sum_{i=1}^N (S_i - \bar{S})^2}} \quad (2)$$

$$Bias = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (S_i - O_i) \quad (3)$$

$$PBIAS = 100 * \left[\frac{\sum_i (S_i - O_i)}{\sum_i O_i} \right] \quad (4)$$

where S_i denotes the simulated values, O_i denotes the observed values and N is the number of days.

III. RESULTS

In this section, the WRF-simulated precipitation is evaluated by using the PMD meteorological data and the TRMM dataset.

A. Precipitation at Specific Location

This section compares the WRF predicted precipitation to values observed by gauges and TRMM. The main results for both domains are shown in Figure 2. The WRF and TRMM data were bilinearly interpolated to the 11 gauge stations. For the WRF data, interpolations were performed separately for the 15km data from d01 and the 5km data from d02. The WRF reproduced the precipitation from May, 1 to September, 16 at each station at 22 different resolutions. It was seen that more precipitation was simulated by the WRF model on 29 July in each station in both domains.

Fig. 2. Time series comparison between the WRF simulated precipitation (blue), observed gauge precipitation (red), and TRMM precipitation (green) for d01 (left column) and d02 (right column).

Before presenting the summarized statistics of the WRF performance, we begin with the specific results for July, 29, 2010, which feature exceptionally high precipitation totals as discussed in the Introduction. When the simulations of each station were compared for d01, the simulated rainfall on July, 29 was 55mm (Balakot), 65mm (Besham Qila), 27mm (Chitral), 47mm (Daggar), 58mm (Dir), 38mm (Drosh), 49mm (Phulra), 63mm (Saidu Sharif), 16mm (Ushkore), and 17mm (Yasin), with the highest rainfall predicted in Peshawar (120mm). Similarly, in domain d02 the rainfall predicted at each station was 46mm, 55mm, 22mm, 40mm, 84mm, 30mm,

53mm, 67mm, 10mm, and 12mm respectively, with the highest rainfall again predicted in Peshawar (153mm). On the other hand, the observed data show that the maximum precipitation recorded on July, 29 was 45mm, 128mm, 41mm, 99mm, 149mm, 61mm, 90mm, 187mm, 0mm, and 2mm for the same stations, with the highest rainfall predicted in Peshawar (274mm). In addition, when simulated precipitation and gauge data were compared for d01, it was found that the WRF model under-predicted the precipitation at all the stations on July, 29, whereas there was over-prediction at Balakot, Ushkore, and Yasin.

For the gauge data, the results showed that the PBIAS decreased in magnitude in domain d02 at Balakot, Chitral, Daggar, Drosh, Peshawar, Phulra, Saidu Sharif, and Ushkore, whereas it increased at Besham Qila, Dir, and Yasin. This means that the resolution increase from d01 to d02 lessened the bias against the gauge data for 8 stations and worsened the bias for 3 stations. On the other hand, when the simulated precipitation was compared with the TRMM dataset, it was found that there were 4 stations (Balakot, Peshawar, Dir, and Yasin) where the bias was decreased in magnitude on d02 and 7 stations (Chitral, Saidu Sharif, Ushkore, Besham Qila, Phulra, Drosh, and Daggar) where the bias was larger in magnitude on d02. Overall, the gauge data comparison provided a stronger indication of bias reduction on d02 than the TRMM data comparison. Similarly, when the WRF predicted precipitation was compared with the gauge data, the correlation between the simulated and the observed data varied for each station. The WRF showed a high correlation ($r \geq 0.5$) to 5 stations (Balakot, Chitral, Besham Qila, Dir, and Drosh), whereas the rest of the WRF results had a lower correlation with the station data. The highest correlation was observed in Besham Qila ($r = 0.8$) and the lowest in Phulra ($r = 0.2$). On the other hand, when the correlation was considered for the simulation precipitation and TRMM dataset, 8 stations (Balakot, Chitral, Yasin, Besham Qila, Dir, Drosh, Saidu Shaarif, and Daggar) showed high correlation to the TRMM dataset, whereas 3 (Peshawar, Ushkore, and Phulra) did not. The highest correlation was observed in Besham Qila and Peshawar with $r = 0.8$, whereas the lowest was observed in Phulra with $r = 0.3$. Overall, at each location, the correlations with station data were similar in domains d01 and d02.

Fig. 3. WRF precipitation percent bias against gauge data in domain d01 and domain d02.

To illustrate how the performance statistics were organized on the topography in each domain, Figure 3 shows the PBIAS of WRF simulated precipitation relative to gauge data as a function of elevation. The shape of the PBIAS graphs as a function of elevation was similar on both domains, and the largest magnitude biases were positive and occurred at higher-elevation stations above approximately 1500m. At all but one station, as shown in Figure 3, the PBIAS was smaller in d02, which shows that at all stations there was a smaller bias between modeled and observed precipitation in d02 as compared to d01. The PBIAS averaged -9% in d02 and 17% in

d01. The t -test was used to identify cases where the mean precipitation simulated by WRF differed significantly from the observed precipitation at the 95% confidence level ($p \leq 0.05$). For most gauge data, the null hypothesis of no difference in mean could not be rejected at the 95% confidence level. However, in domain d01, a significant difference in mean was found at 3 stations: Chitral, Drosh, and Ushkore. When the WRF predicted precipitation was compared with station data in domain d02, significant differences were found at Dir and Ushkore. For TRMM data, no significant differences were found in d01, and only 2 locations (Drosh and Besham Qila) had significantly different results in d02. The patchy significance of these t -test results indicates the encouraging performance of WRF, especially given that we assumed one degree of freedom per day (i.e. use of effective degrees of freedom reduced to account for autocorrelation would be less likely to reject the null). Table I lists the p values associated with the t -test comparing the mean WRF precipitation to gauge (TRMM) precipitation in d01 and d02.

TABLE I. P VALUES FOR D01 AND D02

Station	p-value d01 (TRMM)	p-value d02 (TRMM)
Balakot	0.12 (0.14)	0.3 (0.2)
Chitral	0.004 (0.7)	0.1 (0.3)
Dir	0.2 (0.2)	0.003 (0.2)
Drosh	0.002 (0.3)	0.9 (0.02)
SaiduSharif	0.7 (0.07)	0.8 (0.3)
Peshawar	0.8 (0.05)	0.6 (0.3)
Ushkore	0.0005 (0.06)	0.03 (0.6)
Yasin	0.86 (0.4)	0.4 (0.8)
Phulra	0.4 (0.5)	0.6 (0.3)
BeshamQila	0.3 (0.1)	0.1 (0.02)
Daggar	0.5 (0.6)	0.7 (0.4)

B. Multilocation Mean Precipitation

This section examines the precipitation averaged across the station locations for WRF, TRMM, and gauge data. WRF, TRMM, and gauge data were averaged at the 11 gauge location. WRF over-predicted the precipitation at some days and under-predicted at others (Figure 4). Similarly, it was observed that WRF under-predicted the average precipitation on July, 29 in both d01 and d02. The TRMM value for this extreme event was intermediate between the WRF and the station values (the station average precipitation for both domains on July 29 was 98mm, and the TRMM dataset indicate 76mm in both d01 and d02, whereas the WRF model simulated 50mm in d01 and 49 mm in d02).

IV. DISCUSSION

In this paper, the WRF model was used to simulate the precipitation of the flood-producing rainfall event of 2010. It was found that there were 3 heavy precipitation events observed during these 5 months, namely May 17, June 3, and July 29. The findings of the study revealed that the precipitation event of July, 29 was the main cause of the flood of 2010, which was consistent with [8, 9]. The results showed that the precipitation simulations were improved from d01 (15km) to d02 (5km), which is attributable to the increased resolution or the combination of the parameterization schemes,

which is consistent with [32], in which it was found that WRF simulates convective precipitation quite effectively using Noah LSM, which predicts both soil temperature and moisture. The findings are also consistent with [33], the authors of which found that at higher resolution the WRF model shows better results. The results of the study are similar to that of [34], in which it was found that complex terrains need higher resolution to accurately forecast precipitation.

The study showed that the WRF has a weak positive correlation ($r = 0.3$) with the observed data at high-elevation stations (Ushkore and Yasin). However, the WRF results tend to have a stronger positive correlation with the observed datasets at some of the low-elevation stations (e.g. Besham Qila and Peshawar). This is consistent with [34-36]. In addition, the WRF showed a higher overall correlation with the TRMM dataset than with the gauge data. The station-averaged precipitation indicated a mix between over-prediction and under-prediction. For the extreme event on July, 29, WRF's simulated precipitation (~50mm) was smaller than the TRMM (76mm) and gauge results (98mm). Discrepancies from observations may stem from not resolving subgrid-scale terrain effects or limitations of the chosen physical parameterization schemes [36]. The high-elevated stations showed more PBIAS except for Yasin and Dir station, where the WRF showed a low PBIAS of 3.8% in d01 and -18% in d02 in Yasin and -21% in d01 and -51% in d02 in Dir. In addition, the WRF showed less bias at the low-elevated stations except from SaiduSharif and BeshamQila stations where the model showed underestimation of precipitation, as large as -34%.

Overall, it was concluded that the WRF model performed well with higher resolution with slightly overestimation at some locations and underestimation at others, which is consistent with [38]. Hence, it can be said that WRF can be used to predict the extreme precipitation events over complex regions such as the Upper Indus Basin.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Kabul River Basin is an integral part of the Indus basin and has been frequently hit by massive floods in the past. The worst flood in KRB was the flood of 2010. It is expected that due to the climate change, the frequency and intensity of floods will increase in the future. This study was conducted to simulate the flood of 2010 by using the WRF model over the KRB. The findings of the study revealed that the WRF model was able to predict the extreme precipitation event of 2010. The overall favorable performance indicates that the one-month spin-up period was sufficient for short-term simulations. Two domains were used to simulate the precipitation over the region, and the result showed that the WRF model performed better in the higher resolution domain. It was concluded that the model proved to be useful for precipitation simulations in the HKH region.

Although the WRF model performed well in the KRB, substantial biases were found at some of the higher elevation stations. Continued work is thus needed on the sensitivity analysis of the WRF model, which is important for determining the optimal combination of physical parameterization schemes over the Upper Indus Basin. In addition, the WRF output

should be compared with other available satellite and remote sensing datasets in addition to TRMM to evaluate the effectiveness of the model performance.

Keeping in view the shortcomings of the GCMs over hilly and complex areas such as KRB, the RCMs are the best tools to perform modeling climate studies. This study showed that WRF was able to simulate extreme events over the KRB. Therefore, it could be suggested that the WRF model with the right combination of physical parameterization schemes, horizontal resolution, and nesting domain can be used to forecast similar future events in the complex and rugged terrain of the HKH region.

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Surface Finish Comparison of Dry and Coolant Fluid High-Speed Milling of JIS SDK61 Mould Steel

The-Hung Le

Faculty of Mechanical Engineering
Hanoi Vocational College of High Technology
Hanoi, Vietnam
hunglt@hht.edu.vn

Van-Bong Pham

Faculty of Mechanical Engineering
Hanoi University of Industry
Hanoi, Vietnam
phamvanbong@hau.edu.vn

Dung Hoang Tien

Faculty of Mechanical Engineering
Hanoi University of Industry
Hanoi, Vietnam
tiendung@hau.edu.vn

Abstract—This paper investigates the influence of dry high-speed milling on the surface quality of JIS SKD61 hard steel, compared to the conventional coolant fluid method. This research was conducted in a Super MC 500 high-speed CNC milling machine with a Hitachi coated carbide 20mm in diameter. High-speed cutting parameters such as cutting speed V , cutting depth t , and spindle speed S were considered as variants. The experiment was designed based on Taguchi's L9. Surface quality, including Ra and Rq , was measured using the Mitutoyo Surftest SV-210. A mathematical regression model was found for the average values of surface roughness through regression analysis for dry and coolant fluid conditions. The chosen high-speed milling parameters and the respective Ra and Rq values were obtained by ANOVA. The grey relation scores for wet and dry milling surface quality for cut depth, feed rate, and cutting speed were 0.7527, 0.7869, 0.6302, and 0.8167, 0.7199, 0.6040, respectively. The results showed that the feed rate had the greatest influence on the surface quality during the high-speed coolant milling of hardened steel, while the depth of the cut had the greatest influence on the surface quality during the high-speed dry milling process.

Keywords—SKD61; FGRA; surface roughness; high-speed milling

I. INTRODUCTION

JIS SKD61 (or AISI H13) alloy steel is a hot work mold steel, popular for its remarkable toughness, sufficient resistance to high-temperature fatigue, and high rigidity. In general, the manufacturing processes of extrusion die sets, hot forging, and casting dies include roughing, heat treatment, and machine finishing. This process is costly and time-consuming. The increasing pressure in the global economy forces the manufacturers to increase machining productivity while maintaining or improving product quality. The improvement of the cutting productivity and quality of high-speed cutting processes have attracted the attention of many companies and

researchers in recent decades.

The coolant fluid is essential when milling hardened steel or other difficult-to-machine materials, especially when machining at high speeds. The main effect of a coolant in milling is to reduce temperature and friction, prolong the life of the cutting tool, and improve the machining efficiency and surface quality [1-3]. Moreover, a coolant also has anti-corrosion and cleaning effects [4, 5]. Nowadays, with the continuous development of precision and ultra-precision machining, machined surface integrity is more important than cutting efficiency and tool life, especially for important components such as mold parts working in harsh environments. However, the effect of the coolant fluid on machined surface quality and its performance in the high-speed machining of hardened steels has not been given attention and compared with dry milling under the same machining conditions.

The cost of the coolant fluid can increase the total production cost by up to 15% [6]. Dry, near-dry, and MQL machining processes are viable alternatives to reduce this cost. Dry machining is now considered an excellent solution to minimize the negative impacts on human health and the environment. Therefore, dry or near-dry machining has attracted considerable interest among manufacturers and researchers [7]. Dry milling can offer significant advantages such as reducing pollutants in the air, water, or the earth, having less harmful effects on human health [20], and a significant cost reduction as there is no need to invest in cooling equipment, maintenance, operation, and handling coolant after machining [8, 9]. Dry milling processes can be applied to a wide range of materials, such as cast iron, carbon steel, alloy steel, and difficult-to-machine steels [10, 11]. However, in dry milling conditions, due to the large friction between the tool and the workpiece, the cutting temperature increases and causes increased wear of the cutting tool. Build of edge also appears more frequently [9], adversely affecting

Corresponding author: The-Hung Le

the quality of the machined surface. Although the further improvement of surface quality and the reduction of tool wear during dry milling has attracted the interest of many researchers, most of them focused on measures to offset the positive effects of lubricants through the optimal selection of cutting parameters, changing the geometry of the cutting tool, choosing the right tool material, improving the machine, etc. However, these studies have not mentioned or compared the main factors that affect surface quality between the wet and dry milling process.

This study examined the factors influencing the dry and wet high-speed milling of hardened steel on surface quality under the same machining conditions. Fuzzy Grey Relationship Analysis (FGRA) was applied to determine the influence of each factor on surface quality in the two different milling environments. Based on the experimental results obtained by the Taguchi L9 method, the FGRA processes were used to evaluate the main factors affecting surface quality. The dry and wet milling comparison provides excellent reference values to be applied to the machining processes and further improve the surface quality of high-speed milling of hardened steel.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. The Workpiece

The SKD61 hard steel, used as the workpiece specimen, was prepared in square blocks of 70×40×15mm dimensions. The chemical composition and mechanical properties of JIS SKD61 mold steel are demonstrated in Tables I and II.

TABLE I. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF JIS SKD61 HARD STEEL

C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Mo	Ni	Cu	V
0.349	0.582	0.720	0.001	0.001	5.59	1.18	0.062	0.036	0.573

TABLE II. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF JIS SKD61 HARD STEEL

Properties	Metric	Imperial (Psi)
Tensile strength at 20° C	1.200 ÷ 1.590MPa	174.000 ÷ 231.000
Tensile strength, yield at 20° C	1.000 ÷ 1.380MPa	145.000 ÷ 200.000
Reduction of area at 20° C	50%	50 %
Modulus of elasticity at 20° C	215 (Gpa)	31.200
Poisson's ratio	0.27÷0.30	0.27-0.30

Fig. 1. Super MC 500 high-speed CNC milling machine.

B. Machine and Cutting Tool

An MC50 high-speed machine, made by Foxconn Corporation and a Hitachi cutting tool with coated inserts were used for the experiment process (Figure 1).

C. Measurement Equipment

The surface roughness value for all experiments was determined as the average of three measurements at separate locations in the workpiece specimens using a Mitutoyo Surfrest SV-210. These average values are shown in Table III.

III. APPLYING GREY FUZZY RELATIONSHIP ANALYSIS

GRA is an effective statistical method to measure the approximation between objects using the grey relational level. The model has been successfully applied in many different fields [12-14]. The level of information in a GRA assists decision-making in difficult situations [15, 16]. An improved version of this method is the Fuzzy Grey Relationship Analysis (FGRA). This is an approach based on a fuzzy system developed on coefficients and grey relation levels. This model considers all the different criteria, including their importance and the uncertainty about the weights. In this work, FGRA was used to evaluate the effects of various factors from the cutting mode parameters on the machined surface quality in both dry and wet milling environments. The steps of the algorithm are described as follows:

- Step 1: When applying FGRA to determine the factors affecting surface quality in wet and dry milling, the reference matrix Y is established based on the surface roughness parameters obtained. $Y(1), Y(2), \dots, Y(n)$ correspond to the surface roughness values obtained by the experiments 1, 2, ..., n . The reference matrix with the surface quality in high-speed milling is described by:

$$Y = [Y(1) Y(2) \dots Y(n)] \quad (1)$$

The factors investigated in the high-speed milling process include inputs such as cutting speed, feed, wet milling, dry milling, etc. in the experiments. If the number of the investigated factors is m and the number of experiments is n , the comparison matrix is:

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} X_1 \\ X_2 \\ \vdots \\ X_m \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} X_1(1)X_1(2) \dots X_1(n) \\ X_2(1)X_2(2) \dots X_2(n) \\ \vdots \\ X_m(1)X_m(2) \dots X_m(n) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

- Step 2: Nondimensionalize original sequences. As the investigated factors (surface roughness) and the reference variables (depth of cut t , feed rate S , cutting speed V) have different dimensions, they must be nondimensionalized by [17]:

$$X_i(k)' = \frac{X_i(k) - \text{Min}[X_i(k)]}{\text{Max}[X_i(k)] - \text{Min}[X_i(k)]} \quad (3)$$

- Step 3: Calculate the cosine value of the fuzzy membership. In this study, the included-angle cosine method was adopted, which is not affected by the linear proportional relationship of the data. The similarity of the two factors

was determined by the included-angle cosine of the two factors, which was calculated by [18]:

$$R_1 = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n Y(k)X(k)}{\sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n Y(k)^2} \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n X(k)^2}} \quad (4)$$

- Step 4: The grey level relationship was calculated by [18]:

$$\xi_i = \frac{L\Delta_{max} + \Delta_{min}}{L\Delta_{max} + \Delta(k)} \quad (5)$$

This variant must be suitable for working conditions and resist any noise signal, as the values of dispersion coefficients may not accurately reflect the relationship between the investigated variants. The dispersion coefficient was calculated by [14]:

$$\Delta = \frac{1}{n.m} \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^n |Y_t(k) - X_{tj}(k)| \quad (6)$$

where Δ is the absolute error's mean. As $C = \frac{\Delta}{\Delta_{max}}$, the resolution factor was obtained as:

$$L \in \begin{cases} [C; 1.5 \times C]; & C < \frac{1}{3} \\ (1.5 \times C; 2C]; & C \geq \frac{1}{3} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

If $C < \frac{1}{3}$, then $L = 1.25C$. If $C \geq \frac{1}{3}$ then $L = 1.75C$.

- Step 5: The Euclidean distance was used to determine the difference between the comparison and reference matrices and increase the accuracy of the estimation processes. Therefore, the weight vector of the different elements in the reference matrix was defined by:

$$W = (W1, W2, \dots, Wj), \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (8)$$

The grey Euclidean R2 levels were calculated using [17]:

$$R_2 = 1 - 2\sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n [W\{1 - \xi_i(k)\}]^2} \quad (9)$$

- Step 6: Determine the fuzzy grey points. According to the fuzzy association coefficient, the grey relationship's level and grey relationship with the fuzzy correlation coefficient of the research variants were calculated by:

$$R = \sqrt{\frac{R_1^2 + R_2^2}{2}} \quad (10)$$

- Step 7: Ranking. Based on the magnitude of the grey relational grade, the impact of the investigated factors was ranked.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The experiment was designed based on the Taguchi orthogonal array [19] to reduce the number of experiments. Two responses, R_a and R_q , were analyzed simultaneously in both dry and coolant fluid environments. Cutting speed V , spindle speed S , and depth of cut t were chosen. Table III shows the high-speed milling parameters and results.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 2 and 3 depict a quality comparison of the workpiece surface in wet and dry milling, according to R_a and

R_q , respectively. The results show that the surface quality in dry is lower than in coolant fluid milling with the same cutting parameters.

TABLE III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

No	Variant code			Surface quality in flood cooling condition		Surface quality in dry condition	
	t	S	V	R_a (μm)	R_q (μm)	R_a (μm)	R_q (μm)
1	1	1	1	0.382	0.464	0.543	0.615
2	1	2	2	0.714	0.836	1.314	1.525
3	1	3	3	1.492	1.712	1.829	2.290
4	2	1	2	0.827	1.011	0.978	1.117
5	2	2	3	0.405	0.487	0.536	0.622
6	2	3	1	0.56	0.666	1.317	1.557
7	3	1	3	0.848	1.046	1.000	1.204
8	3	2	1	0.521	0.613	0.521	0.616
9	3	3	2	1.010	1.215	1.301	1.588

Fig. 2. R_a surface roughness comparison in wet and dry milling.

Fig. 3. R_q surface roughness comparison in wet and dry milling.

The ANOVA results of the surface quality in wet milling conditions are shown in Figure 4. The results show that the smallest S/N ratios were in level 3 for all variables. Feed rate S had the smallest S/N ratio (0.31), followed by cutting speed (0.99) and depth of cut (2.15). The ANOVA results in dry milling conditions are shown in Figure 5. The results show that feed rate S and cutting speed V had the smallest S/N ratios in level 3 (-3.36, -2.92, respectively). Depth of cut t had its smallest S/N ratio in level 1 (-0.78). Therefore, there is a significant difference in the ANOVA results between the wet and dry milling processes. The FGRA was applied to determine the main factors affecting the surface quality through the following steps:

- Step 1: The surface quality of different machining conditions had the $Y(x)$ and $Z(y)$ reference arrays for wet and dry milling, respectively. The depth of cut, feed rate, and cutting speed were $Y1(x)$, $Y2(x)$, $Y3(x)$, and $Z1(x)$,

$$\begin{bmatrix} Y_1(x) \\ Y_2(x) \\ Y_3(x) \\ Y(x) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 2 & 2 & 2 & 3 & 3 & 3 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 & 2 & 3 & 1 & 3 & 1 & 2 \\ 0.382 & 0.714 & 1.492 & 0.827 & 0.405 & 0.56 & 0.848 & 0.521 & 1.010 \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} Z_1(x) \\ Z_2(x) \\ Z_3(x) \\ Z(x) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 2 & 2 & 2 & 3 & 3 & 3 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 & 2 & 3 & 1 & 3 & 1 & 2 \\ 0.543 & 1.314 & 1.829 & 0.978 & 0.536 & 1.317 & 1.000 & 0.521 & 1.301 \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

Fig. 4. ANOVA results of surface quality in wet milling.

Fig. 5. ANOVA results of surface quality in dry milling.

- Step 2: The angular cosine of the fuzzy membership function was obtained by (4). Figures 6 and 7 depict the fuzzy membership classes of four surface quality parameters in wet and dry environments. The results showed that in the wet machining process, the change of feed rate was the highest (0.7705), followed by the depth of cut (0.7525) and cutting speed (0.5413). The analysis results in dry high-speed milling depicted a clear difference, as the depth of cut was kept at the most considerable value (0.8468), followed by the feed rate (0.6748) and cutting speed (0.487). Hence, in comparison with wet milling, the feed rate dramatically influenced the surface quality. Cutting speed had an almost negligible impact on the surface quality, just as in wet milling. Meanwhile, in dry milling, the depth of cut had the most influence on surface quality.
- Step 3: The grey Euclidean relationship levels were calculated using (5) - (8) and are depicted in Figures 6 and 7. The Euclidean grey equivalent ratios of different elements were not much for the wet milling process. But it was still found that the feed rate most influenced the surface quality in wet milling. In dry milling, the depth of cut had the most effect on surface quality.

$Z2(x)$, $Z3(x)$ for conventional and dry milling, respectively. The reference and the comparison matrixes are shown in (11) and (12).

Fig. 6. Grayscale analysis to surface quality in wet milling.

Fig. 7. Grayscale analysis to surface quality in dry milling

- Step 4: The fuzzy grey relationship scores of the input variants were obtained by (12) and are illustrated in Figures 6 and 7. The results showed a comprehensive way to evaluate the impact of experimental variants on the surface quality in both convenient and dry milling conditions. Therefore, the matt grey related scores for wet and dry milling surface quality of the three factors depth of cut t , feed rate S , and cutting speed v were 0.7527, 0.7869, 0.6302, and 0.8167, 0.7199, 0.6040, respectively.

Hence, the influence of feed rate on the surface quality in the high-speed machining of a difficult-to-cut material in wet milling is the most. By contrast, the depth of cut has the most

significant influence on the surface roughness in dry machining, while the cutting speed has an almost negligible effect on the surface quality in both dry and wet milling methods.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the high-speed cutting parameters optimization of milling processes in dry and coolant fluid conditions to ensure a satisfactory surface quality. FGRA was obtained to analyze the relation among the surface roughness parameters R_a , R_q , and the cutting parameters cutting speed v , spindle speed S , and depth of cut t . ANOVA was used to determine the model's adequacy and factor significance. The main results can be summarized as:

- The surface quality in high-speed milling of mold steel JIS SKD61 in dry conditions is lower than in coolant fluid conditions with the same cutting parameters.
- The effects of different cutting parameters on the surface roughness in dry and coolant fluid environments differ. Cutting speed v had the smallest S/N value at 0.31 and 0.21, respectively. By contrast, the S/N value of the depth of cut t was highest, at 2.51 and -0.78, respectively, followed by the S/N of spindle speed S .
- The FGRA confirmed that the influence of spindle speed was the most in the coolant fluid high-speed milling of hardened steel. By contrast, the effect of depth of cut on the surface roughness in the dry machining was the most significant. At the same time, both dry and wet conditions showed that the influence of cutting speed was insignificant.

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NOMENCLATURE

X	Comparison matrix
Y	Reference matrix
l	Resolution coefficient, $l \in [0, 1]$
Δ_{min}	Minimum absolute difference, $\Delta_{min} = \min Y(k) - X_i(k) $
Δ_{max}	Maximum absolute difference, $\Delta_{max} = \max Y(k) - X_i(k) $
$\Delta(k)$	Absolute difference, $\Delta(k) = Y(k) - X_i(k) $
ξ_i	Relational coefficient
R	Fuzzy grey relational grade
R_1	Fuzzy membership grade
R_2	Euclidean grey relational grade

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AUTHORS' PROFILE

The-Hung Le is a lecturer at Hanoi Vocational College of High Technology. He is a PhD candidate in the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering at Hanoi University of Industry. His research work focuses on the multiple optimizations of high-speed machining process of hard-cutting alloy steel.

Van-Bong Pham is an associated professor in the Manufacturing Department, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Hanoi University of Industry. His research work focuses on the multi-optimization of the cutting processes.

Dung Hoang Tien is an associated professor in the Mechanical Technology Department, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Hanoi University of Industry. His research work focuses on dynamic machining, modeling and optimization, adaptive machining, AM/3D printing technology, and micro-machining.

The Effect of Different Curing Temperatures on the Properties of Geopolymer Reinforced with Micro Steel Fibers

Mohammed Shaker Amouri

Department of Civil Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq

mohammed.amori2001m@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Nada Mahdi Fawzi

Department of Civil Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq

nada.aljalawi@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Abstract-In this study, geopolymer mortar was designed in various experimental combinations employing 1% micro steel fibers and was subjected to different temperatures, according to the prior works of other researchers. The geopolymer mortar was developed using a variety of sustainable material proportions (fly ash and slag) to examine the influence of fibers on its strength. The fly ash weight percentage was 50%, 60%, and 70% by slag weight to study its effect on the geopolymer mortar's properties. The optimal ratio produced the most significant results when mixed at a 50:50 ratio of fly ash and slag with 1% micro steel fibers at curing temperature 240°C for 4 hours through two days. The compressive strength of the geopolymer mortar increased by 11%, 11.5%, and 14% after 3, 7, and 28 days when utilizing fibers. The result shows that fly ash with a ratio of 50% by weight of slag improved the compressive strength of the mixture. It was discovered that a combination with 50% of the weight of fly ash with micro steel fibers, when treated at 240°C for curing age of 3, 7, and 28 days, had a flexural resistance rate of 28%, 30%, 33% higher than a mixture without fibers.

Keywords-sustainable material; geopolymer mortar; fly ash; ground granulated blast furnace; slag

I. INTRODUCTION

The primary binder used in concrete production is Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC). The environmental concerns surrounding the manufacturing of OPC are well-known. Furthermore, the amount of energy needed to manufacture only steel and aluminum is equal to that necessary to build OPC [1]. Cement production varies widely due to differences in the availability of raw materials [2]. Sustainable materials are being developed to limit the emission of CO₂ from the cement industry and help recycle the industrial waste by incorporating environmentally friendly materials into civil engineering project [3]. Many cement composites may be found in addition to regular concrete. Various byproducts may be employed to produce blended cement classified as supplementary cementitious materials, such as GGBFS, Fly Ash (FA), and Silica Fume (SF) [4]. FA and slag waste from thermal power plants pose a severe environmental hazard if not treated and repurposed. Since the FA from thermal power plants is buried,

it does long-term damage to the environment by polluting the groundwater and harming the farmlands [5]. The byproduct of combustion is a fine powder. A significant amount of this garbage is produced every year, creating a substantial environmental threat. Pozzolanic (siliceous and aluminous) materials may be utilized to minimize waste to some degree [6].

In 1978, the term "geopolymer" was developed to designate a group of mineral binders having a similar chemical makeup to zeolites. On the other hand, geopolymers use polycondensation of silica and alumina precursors instead of traditional Portland/pozzolanic cement to form the matrix. Geopolymers are mainly composed of source materials and alkaline liquids. Alumino-silicate-based raw materials with high silicon (Si) and aluminum (Al) content should be used. Byproducts like FA and SF may be added to the mix. As opposed to other alumino-silicate compounds, geopolymers are a unique creation (e.g. alumino-silicate gels, glasses, and zeolites). Geopolymerization produces higher concentration of solids than alumino-silicate gels or zeolite synthesis [7]. Geopolymer concrete, made from FA and slag, is an excellent alternative to conventional concrete because it is more environmentally friendly and has diverse ingredients and qualities [8]. Therefore, in this paper, the effect of different proportions of FA by weight of slag with different curing temperatures is studied.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Fly Ash

The acquired FA is a fine, glassy powder produced by coal combustion throughout the generation of electrical energy at the ISKEN-MENT-Turkey power station. The chemical composition of the FA used in this research is shown in Table I.

B. Slag

The slag utilized in this study complied with ASTM C618 [8] requirements, as shown in Table II.

TABLE I. FLY ASH CHEMICAL COMPOSITION

Oxide	Content %	(ASTM C618) requirements [9]
Fe ₂ O ₃	5.35	Sum of value more than 70%
Al ₂ O ₃	17.59	
SiO ₂	65.63	
SO ₃	0.21	Max. 5%
MgO	0.84	--
CaO	0.98	--
L.O. I	2.76	Max. 6%
K ₂ O	2.33	--
Na ₂ O	1.36	--

TABLE II. GGBFS CHEMICAL COMPOSITION

Oxide	Content %	(ASTM C618) requirements [9]
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.35	Sum of value more than 70%
Al ₂ O ₃	25.53	
SiO ₂	45.88	
SO ₃	4.98	Max. 5%
MgO	4.95	--
CaO	37.21	--
L.O. I	3.89	Max. 6%
K ₂ O	2.10	--
Na ₂ O	0.96	--

TABLE III. PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FINE AGGREGATES

Sieve size, mm	Cumulative percentage pass	IQS (45-1984), zone 2
10	100	100
4.750	91	90-100
2.360	80	75-100
1.180	71	55-90
0.60	53	35-59
0.30	22	8-30
0.150	7	0-10

TABLE IV. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF MICRO STEEL FIBERS ACCORDING TO THE MANUFACTURER

Properties	Micro steel fibers
Tensile strength (MPa)	2600
Diameter (mm)	0.2
Density(kg/m ³)	7800
Length (mm)	13
Aspect ratio	65
Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)	250

C. Sodium Hydroxide

Commercially available NaOH flakes have a 98% purity. NaOH is used to make geopolymer mortar solutions. NaOH is made by melting caustic soda flakes with water. Based on the ratio of the soda flakes added to the water, different molar concentrations may be obtained.

D. Sodium Silicate

The concentration of Na₂SiO₃ is determined by the ratio of Na₂O to SiO₂ and H₂O. The Na₂SiO₃ used in this formulation was produced in the United Arab Emirates.

E. Water

Distilled water was used to dissolve the caustic soda flakes to make the NaOH solution. Tap water was added to the geopolymer mix to improve workability. It conforms to IQS 1703 [10].

F. Fine Aggregates

This research used natural sand from the Al-Ekhadir (Karbala city) area as fine aggregates. It belongs to zone 2 and complies with the physical and chemical characteristics of the Iraqi standard requirements IQS (No.45/1984) [11] as shown in Table III.

G. Micro Steel Fibers

Table IV shows the properties of the micro steel fibers utilized in this research.

H. Superplasticizer

A high range water reducer (superplasticizer) based on modified sulfonated naphthalene formaldehyde condensate was used to improve the geopolymer mortar's workability. It confirmed to ASTM C494 [17].

III. GEOPOLYMER MANUFACTURING

A. Alkaline Solution Preparation

The sodium hydroxide molar concentration was set to 12 molars when making the geopolymer mortar in this experiment. The sodium silicate-to-sodium hydroxide ratio was set at 2:1, and the solution-to-cementitious-material ratio was set at 0.45. Table V shows the sodium hydroxide flakes weight.

TABLE V. AMOUNT OF SOLID NaOH FOR 1kg OF SOLUTION AT SPECIFIED MOLARITY AND WEIGHT CONCENTRATION [1, 12]

Molarity (mole/L)	NaOH concentration (w/w%)	Weight of NaOH flakes (g)	Weight of Water (g)
8	26.2	262	738
10	31.4	314	686
12	36.2	362	638
14	40.4	404	596
16	44	440	560

B. Mixing

The day before it was utilized, the alkaline liquid was produced and then mixed with the superplasticizer before the mixing procedure. The dry components (GGBS, FA, fibers, and sand) were first incorporated by hand for about 2 minutes before the alkaline liquid and superplasticizer were combined at a 75% concentration. After 5 minutes of mixing, the mixture was left for roughly 15 seconds before the remaining 25% of the mixed alkaline liquid was added and then it was re-combined for another 5 minutes. Approximately 10 to 15 minutes of mixing time were required to achieve homogeneity as shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI. MIX DESIGN OF 1m³ GEOPOLYMER MORTAR

Mix	Fine aggregates	Water *	FA/Slag ratio	Slag	FA	Sodium silicate solution	NaOH	Micro steel %
G1	1400	75	0.5:0.5	375	375	225	112.5	-
G2	1400	75	0.5:0.5	375	375	225	112.5	1
G3	1400	75	0.6:0.4	450	300	225	112.5	-
G4	1400	75	0.6:0.4	450	300	225	112.5	1
G5	1400	75	0.7:0.3	525	225	225	112.5	-
G6	1400	75	0.7:0.3	525	225	225	112.5	1

weight in Kg/m³

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mortar testing was carried out in accordance with ASTM: C109-2 [13]. Since compressive strength is an essential feature of concrete mixtures or mortar, regular patterns in standard specifications are highly reliant on compressive strength at 3,7, and 28 days of curing age, with varying curing temperature. The test was performed on 50×50×50 mm cubic test samples as shown in Table VII and Figures1-2.

TABLE VII. COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH TEST RESULTS

Mix	Compressive strength result (MPa)								
	Curing age of testing (days)								
	3			7			28		
	80°C	160°C	240°C	80°C	160°C	240°C	80°C	160°C	240°C
G1	41.73	45.06	49.82	42.60	46.18	51.33	43.53	48.25	54.42
G2	45.36	50.81	55.63	46.88	51.11	57.21	48.44	53.31	62.23
G3	32.06	36.89	38.32	33.66	39.77	41.81	36.63	43.48	45.12
G4	40.04	42.64	44.51	41.88	44.27	46.43	42.86	46.87	48.31
G5	30.50	34.29	36.1	32.85	37.20	38.01	34.69	39.45	41.50
G6	36.29	38.20	41.9	39.92	40.64	43.64	41.72	43.52	44.32

The increase of the proportion of the replacement of FA with GGBFS giving optimal compressive strength was at 50% FA and 50% slag (G1) with an additional 1% of fibers (G2) at 3,7, and 28 days. This conclusion is in accordance with the findings in [14]. The compressive strength of geopolymer mortars increases by increasing curing temperatures from 80°C to 160°C and 240°C. That conclusion is in accordance with the findings in [15]. The results of G1, G3, and G5 show increases in compressive strength with the increasing percentage of GGBFS, compared with G1 at 240°C and 28 days of curing as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 1. Compressive strength of geopolymer mortar at 28 days with curing temperatures.

Fig. 2. Geopolymer mortar cubes.

Fig. 3. Relationship between compressive strength and GGBFS.

Flexural strength testing is a method of determining the way materials respond to basic beam loading. The test was carried out according to ASTM C 293M-16 [16]. Cubic 50×50×50 mm specimens were used in this test with different curing ages (3, 7, 28 days). The result is shown in Table VIII. The optimal proportion mix was G1 (50% FA : 50% Slag) and G2 (50% FA : 50% Slag : 1%Fiber).

TABLE VIII. FLEXURAL STRENGTH RESULTS

Mix	Flexural strength result (MPa)		
	Curing age of testing (days) with 240°C		
	3	7	28
G1	5.12	5.3	5.7
G2	6.57	6.9	7.61

Fig. 4. Flexural strength of geopolymer mortar at 240°C curing temperature.

Table VIII and Figure 4 indicate that increased compressive strength leads to increased flexural strength, which is clearly shown by the experimental results of these two properties. This study found that at 3, 7, and 28 days of curing age, the flexural strength of geopolymer mortar supplemented with micro steel fibers was increased by 28%, 30%, and 33% compared with the mixture without fiber at the same temperature of 240°C, which is the ideal dry heat curing temperature for fly ash-slag blends with a 50:50 weight ratio. However, the introduction of fibers in concrete increased the capacity to regulate fracture propagation, transforming the brittle cementitious material into a ductile composite. These results are in accordance with the findings in [18].

Fig. 5. Geopolymer prisms during curing.

V. CONCLUSION

The main conclusions according to the results of the current study on geopolymer mortar are:

- Geopolymer is an ecologically acceptable substitute for OPC in structural applications.
- FA and slag-based geopolymer mortar are preferable to conventional concrete because of their sustainable ingredients and improved characteristics.
- Best geopolymer mortar qualities may be achieved by adding 1% by volume micro steel fibers to the mixture.
- The additional micro steel fibers in geopolymer mortar increase strength by 10%, improving bond strength.
- The optimum strength of geopolymer mortar was acquired with proportions of 50% of FA: 50% of GGBFS with 1% of micro steel fibers (Mix G2).
- The addition of GGBFS to geopolymer concrete as an alternative to FA improved compressive strength in mixtures G2, G4, and G6 with ratios of 11%, 8.5%, and 5% respectively, with 240°C curing temperature at 28 days.
- Geopolymer mortar can develop high early strength by using high curing temperatures.
- By increasing temperatures of curing age from 80°C to 240°C, the compressive strength increased by about 25% without fibers and 28.5% with micro steel fibers (at 28 days).
- The flexural strength increased by 28%, 30%, and 33% by additional micro steel fiber for 3, 7, 28 days of curing respectively.

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A Novel Feature Extraction Descriptor for Face Recognition

Ahmed B. Salem Salamh
Material Science and Engineering Department
Kastamonu University
Kastamonu, Turkey
nuclear_2010@hotmail.com

Halil Ibrahim Akyüz
Computer and Teaching Technologies Education Dpt.
Kastamonu University
Kastamonu, Turkey
hakyuz@kastamonu.edu.tr

Abstract-This paper presents a new feature extraction technique for face recognition. The new model, called multi-descriptor, is based on the well-known method of local binary patterns. It involves many different neighborhoods of the central pixel. Its unique advantage is that this descriptor allows the use of different neighborhood sizes instead of only one point. This structure ensures reasonable effectiveness and also provides the possibility to obtain a different distribution of features. Based on the new descriptor, a face recognition model using the pairwise feature descriptor based on the proposed descriptor was developed in this work, and local binary patterns were created to investigate the similarity and dissimilarity between the two models. For both models, the training was done using the support vector machine method on different face databases to overcome face recognition problems such as camera distance, expression, large head size, and illumination variations. The proposed technique achieved perfect accuracy on almost all tested databases including the Extended Yale B and Grimace database.

Keywords-multi descriptor model; local binary pattern; face recognition; feature extraction

I. INTRODUCTION

Face recognition has been intensively researched and developed to introduce models that lead to more accurate results [1]. The great importance of face recognition lies in the identification and authentication, especially in security and registration systems. The main idea in any recognition technique is to interpret the physical characteristics of the object to be recognized [2]. Biometric recognition is widely used. Face recognition outperforms fingerprint and iris recognition [3]. Most problems in face recognition usually involve pose, scale, orientation, illumination, and facial expression. Over time, numerous methods have been proposed to solve these problems [4]. Moreover, constrained and unconstrained environments have become complicated due to different lighting conditions, pose, occlusion, and distance from the camera [5]. Different angles and illuminations affect facial features as the physical characteristics of the human face change [6]. There are many methods that have been used for face recognition under different illumination conditions during the last decades [7]. The performance of the recognition techniques has achieved significant results under controlled and uncontrolled environments such as under illumination and pose

variations, which are challenging situations. Variations in the illumination of the face images occur when the light source is at different angles to the direction of the face [8]. Moreover, face recognition accuracy and recognition time are two major factors that affect the quality of face recognition algorithms [9]. Deep learning has been developed with higher accuracy and complex structure, but common deep learning techniques require large databases, much computation time for training, and high power consumption.

Deep learning, local features, and geometric techniques are used in facial feature extraction. The function of facial feature extraction is to identify facial features such as structure, size, and shape of the facial image after face recognition. Features such as nose, mouth and eyes or geometry calculations, represent the face. Feature based descriptor techniques have been successfully used for face recognition due to their robustness, efficiency and simplicity. Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) [10], Local Binary Patterns (LBP), and Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) [11] in combination with Nearest Neighbors, Support Vector Machine (SVM) technique are used for person recognition [12]. The LBP technique, was proposed in [13] for texture description and has the advantage of being robust and simple. LBP continues to be used for face recognition as it gives very good results compared to other techniques, while it has improved its performance many times over [14]. Moreover, with the increasing use of machine learning techniques, researchers have integrated algorithms such as LBP and ensemble ad boosted strategy to achieve accurate results in face recognition. Moreover, the use of more than one strategy, for example LBP and Gabor wavelet filter, for feature extraction has led to better results, and the integration of different techniques is said to give much better performance. LBP describes smaller details of appearance, while Gabor processes the structure of faces over a wider range of scales [15]. LBP is recognized as a powerful feature extraction method for face recognition and texture classification [16]. LBPH uses a histogram by dividing the cropped face image blocks and counting the histogram for each block by integrating the histogram blocks to introduce the final feature vector. The LBPH process is applied to each face image to represent vectors for each image and finally compare the tested face vector with the total trained vectors to compare two face images [17]. In the field of face recognition, there are

many face databases with different features, and selecting the databases that are suitable for evaluating the new technique is challenging. In this work, most face recognition problems were considered. To ensure the diversity, 6 databases were selected for the evaluation of the algorithms. The derivation is based on the mathematical theory derived from the equation for local binary patterns to achieve perfect accuracy in face recognition. For this purpose, different descriptors were used to extract features, to calculate the histogram for each descriptor, and to generate a pair of feature vectors considering the proposed face recognition model.

II. METHODOLOGY

In this part, the combination of multi-descriptor and SVM is presented in detail. In this work, known databases have been used to evaluate the performance of descriptors while ensuring the diversity of data. Each database contains a different number of subjects. Each subject is called a class and is denoted by C . The number of subjects in each database is different. For each class, there is a different number of samples, denoted by S . The face databases contain a variety of features. The databases used in the study were cropped and reformatted into images of 128×128 pixels.

III. THE PROPOSED METHOD

Appearance based feature extraction works on representing facial details. It stands out for its efficiency, accuracy, and robustness. The initial LBP method simply works by threading central pixels of 3×3 neighborhoods to binary encode the value of the central pixel. The value of the central pixel is denoted by g_p and its 8 neighbors by g_c [18]. Subtracting ($g_p - g_c$) gives a negative or a positive value. The resulting value is encoded to 0 if it is negative and to 1 otherwise. Finally, the binary code is converted to decimal value to represent the feature. The main functionality of the proposed feature extraction based on appearance considers the mean value as a threshold value and compares it with the 8 neighboring values to generate a new value, which represents the new value as a feature. The advantage of multi-descriptor models MD1 and MD2 is that they generate distinguishing features by determining the value that describes the facial image. The proposed technique starts by introducing a new mathematical equation to describe the facial structure in different distributions as shown in Figure 1, by comparing 8 neighbors with the mean value in a gray scale image representing the value from 0 to 255 pixel intensity. The variety of x values is to ensure the distribution of the data, that is, the values of x_8 and x_0 are variable depending on the application. The application of the multi-descriptor equations (1)-(3) to the original images of the Extended Yale B database is shown in Figure 2. The results are shown in Figures 3-4.

$$MDN = (x_8 f(g_p - g_c) + (\sum_{i=7}^{n=0} \frac{x(i+1)}{k} f(g_p - g_c))) * 2.55 \quad (1)$$

$$F(x) = \begin{cases} \text{New value} & \text{if } X \geq 0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$F(x) = \begin{cases} \text{New value} & \text{if } X \leq 0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1. Multi structures of descriptor.

Fig. 2. Some samples per person with illumination variation from the Extended Yale B database.

Fig. 3. Samples from the Extended Yale B produced by the MD1 model.

Fig. 4. Samples from the Extended Yale B produced by the MD2 model.

IV. SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE

Machine learning has become a desirable technique in most areas of recognition. One of these techniques is SVM. SVM is a supervised learning algorithm for handling regression and classification problems, which performs classification by finding a hyperplane that can separate two classes. In this paper, SVM [19] is used to databases which are divided into two categories, training and testing, to perform classification. SVM uses Error-Correcting Output Codes (ECOC), binary classification, and an ensemble method for multi-class classification problems. Two methods used in ECOC are one against one and one against all, which was used in this work.

V. FACE RECOGNITION WITH MULTI-DESCRIPTOR

Figure 5 shows the overall architecture using a multi-descriptor model for classification consisting of two main parts, namely a training set and a test set. The same model was used

for face feature extraction to represent the face structure. Multi-Descriptor one (MD1) has different parameters than Multi-Descriptor two (MD2). Based on the flexibility of the derived equation, it was explained how to generate facial features. The MD1 uses a value of x8 equal to 50 and x0 equal to 0 and the MD2 uses a value of x8 equal to 60 and x0 equal to 0. Together, they brought different representations of facial images. The evidence of the differences between MDN and the pair-LBP model is doubted. For this reason, a new LBP architecture for face recognition was introduced, as shown in Figure 6. The classification of both models was conducted with the use of SVM.

VI. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

To compute and evaluate the performance of face recognition models using machine learning techniques, the most commonly used metrics [20] are defined in this work as follows:

For all matrices, consider P as the number of positive samples, N as the number of negative samples, T as True, and F as False.

Accuracy (ACC) is an indicator used frequently to measure classification performance.

$$ACC = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (4)$$

Sensitivity or True Positive Rate (TPR) reflects the samples positively classified in the total number of positive samples, also known as actual positive samples.

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (5)$$

Positive Predictive Value (PPV) or precision indicates the proportion of positive samples classified correctly in the total number of positive predicted samples.

$$PPV = \frac{TP}{FP+TP} \quad (6)$$

F-measure or F1 score reflects the harmonic mean of precision and recall. The value of F1 is ranged from 0 to 1. High values of the F-measure indicate high classification performance.

$$F1 = \frac{2TP}{2TP+FP+FN} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 5. Face recognition architecture using the multi descriptor model.

Fig. 6. Face recognition architecture using the local binary pattern model.

VII. FACIAL RECOGNITION DATA

The Yale face database consists of 15 subjects with 11 images taken under different conditions for each class, giving a total of 165 grayscale images [21]. Extended Yale B has 28 classes, with each class containing 9 poses and 64 illumination conditions for a total of 16128 face images [22]. The University of Essex has introduced 4 folders of data (Faces94, Faces95, Faces96, and Grimace) [23]. The total face database contains 395 faces of people of both sexes with 20 images for each subject. It contains photos of people from different ethnic backgrounds, mainly first-year university students. Most of the subjects are between 18 and 20 years old, while there are also some older subjects. Some persons wear glasses or have beards.

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF FACIAL RECOGNITION DATASETS

Dataset	Number of subjects	Number of images
Yale	15	165
Extended Yale B	28	16128
Faces94	152	3060
Faces95	72	1440
Faces96	72	3013
Grimace	18	360

VIII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 7 presents the performance of the two models. Both show good performance in terms of sensitivity, precision, and F1 score and excellent results on the challenges encountered in each database, especially when the subject moves during the acquisition of the image.

Fig. 7. Multi-descriptor and LBP performance comparison using sensitivity, precision, and F1 score.

Figure 8 shows the accuracy of the MD and the LBP models. Both models showed excellent performance, with the proposed MD either coming close or outperforming the LBP.

Fig. 8. Performance comparison of the MD and the LBP models for face recognition.

The results show that the new descriptor, which uses a new feature extraction equation, is more efficient on different poses, illuminations, facial expressions, and glasses, than the LBP model. This means that the new model is suitable to face the challenges of face recognition and other tasks when feature extraction is required for description, verification, and identification. The descriptor was tested and verified on several face images in the first part, which clearly shows how well it can describe face details. This is very important and shows the ability to represent all the features of a face. The new descriptor may contribute to the recognition of other tasks, such as covid19, retinal vessels, and texture classification, which we plan to study in the future.

IX. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a new feature extraction model called multi-descriptor (MD) model. A key finding was the use of the derived equations to describe facial features with pair technique and different distribution. The technique was developed for face feature extraction, but is certainly suitable for most other types of texture description with more descriptors. The classification for face recognition was performed using SVM. The proposed descriptor outperformed the LBP model in Extended Yale B, Face94 and Grimace databases, having accuracy of 99.437%, 98.814%, and 100% respectively. This shows that the proposed descriptor is completely different from the conventional LBP and improves the recognition accuracy of faces and handles perfectly the challenge of poses, illuminations, expressions, face position, and camera distance. Combinations of MDN and LBP models with different structures and distributions of data could be used in future work.

AUTHORS'NOTE

The authors announce that they have complete access to all the data. There are no financial disclosures from the authors.

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A Review on the Use of Machine Learning Against the Covid-19 Pandemic

Sardar Asad Ali Biabani
Science and Technology Unit
Umm Al-Qura University
Makkah Al-Mukarramah, Saudi Arabia
sabiabani@uqu.edu.sa

Nahla A. Tayyib
Faculty of Nursing, Deanship of Scientific Research
Umm Al-Qura University
Makkah Al-Mukarramah, Saudi Arabia
natayyib@uqu.edu.sa

Abstract-Coronavirus-2019 disease (Covid-19) is a contagious respiratory disease that emerged in late 2019 and has been recognized by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a global pandemic in early 2020. Since then, researchers have been exploring various strategies and techniques to fight against this outbreak. The point when the pandemic appeared was also a period in which Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) algorithms were competing with traditional technologies, leading to significant findings in diverse domains. Consequently, many researchers employed ML/DL to speed up Covid-19 detection, prevention, and treatment. This paper reviews the state-of-the-art ML/DL tools used, thoroughly evaluating these techniques and their impact on the battle against Covid-19. This article aims to provide valuable insight to the researchers to assess the use of ML against the Covid-19 pandemic.

Keywords-Covid-19; machine learning; deep learning; coronavirus; evaluation; detection; prevention; treatment

I. INTRODUCTION

Deep Learning techniques can be employed in many technical predicaments instead than conventional ones in order to save time and resources. This paper investigates and evaluates the use of Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) techniques on the fight against the Covid-19 pandemic. We will mainly focus on four states: At first, DL and ML models require a lot of data in their training process to provide accurate predictions. Therefore, we begin this study by reporting some Covid-19-related datasets used to train ML/DL tools. Then, we will investigate the way these tools are employed to prevent the disease, either by tracking the spread of the virus or by helping in the productions of a new vaccine. Thirdly, the paper will study the utilization of ML techniques in the discovery phase, presenting the models and algorithms adapted to diagnose and detect the virus. Finally, we will examine the same approaches, but this time applied to the drug discovery and treatment of the disease. This paper aims to present a review about the use of ML against Covid-19, to evaluate these techniques, and to analyze their effectiveness to counter the pandemic. However, before talking about implementing ML or DL techniques in any given field, essentially, when the models we are dealing with are on supervised learning methods, the fundamental problem to deal

with is data. Various types of Covid-19 datasets available for practitioners and researchers are examined below.

A broad range of data was collected and made open during this pandemic. It ranges from classic Computerized Tomography (CT) scans to X-Ray Chest (XRC) radiograph images, but one can also find datasets based on text data, video, or sound. Authors in [1] collected a dataset of 123 computerized CT scans. This dataset contains not only Covid-19 but also MERS, SARS, and ARDS (other coronaviruses) images. The authors in [2] provide a more extensive dataset of 275 CT scans of Covid-19 patients. A familiar and productive technique used to augment data in ML is segmentation. This technique was used in several studies [3] to develop more samples. In addition to segmentation, other studies collected negative Covid-19 CT images to combine them with positive cases for binary classification diagnosis models [4-6]. XRC images belong to a different type of data. One of the first efforts to collect an XRC Covid-19 dataset was [7]. The authors used a collection of more than 13000 images to train a neural network classification model that achieved 93.11% accuracy. Moreover, added preliminaries in the XRC datasets were developed in [1]. This resource framed the basis of many extensions [8-11], whether by appending more images of Covid patients, using data augmentation techniques such as segmentation or by adding non-Covid-19 images. In addition, an Italian hospital provided more than 4700 X-ray images of Covid-19 patients [12]. Another popular dataset type deals with tracking and visualizing Covid-19's new cases and deaths in real-time. The most known dataset of this kind is [13], while [14] was used to predict the pandemic's spread.

Besides these platforms that offer universal statistics, many country-focused datasets accumulate information about specific countries [15-17]. Although these datasets represent limited regions, they generally present richer resources since they consider demographic aspects, travel restrictions, and sometimes even personal data. In [18], the authors presented a collection of Covid-19, pneumonia, and healthy videos. A related dataset [19] consolidated data from some hospitals and web resources to present a collection of images and videos of lung ultrasounds. Additionally, the Coswara ongoing project [20], consists of collecting breathing, cough, and speech sounds from Covid-19 patients to build a diagnostic tool. Likewise,

another sound-based South African dataset was erected [21] on cough audio.

Table I summarizes the cited datasets, the nature of the data they contain, and, more importantly, the number of samples in each one. Notably, the big problem in using these datasets to train DL models is that they do not have enough data to predict real-world situations accurately.

TABLE I. REVIEWED COVID-19 DATASETS

Ref.	Nature of the data	Number of samples
[1]	Frontal view X-rays	123
[2]	CT scans	275
[3]	CT scans	20 cases
[4]	CT scans	5900 images of 1200 patients
[5]	CT scans	888 CT scans of 888 subjects
[6]	CT scans	366,558 CT scan images
[7]	XRC	13000 images
[12]	X-ray images	4700
[19]	Videos	247

The following sections will provide an extensive literature review of the papers that used ML techniques to help the spreading prevention, detection, and treatment of Covid-19.

II. ML METHODS FOR COVID-19 PREVENTION

This section will examine the operation of ML techniques in the prevention of the spreading of Covid-19. To accomplish this, we will present two effective solutions that have been used in response to the outbreak: Vaccines (to reduce the spread of the infection) and spread estimation (to embrace the appropriate restrictions at the right time and place).

A. Vaccine Discovery

The invention of a vaccine is arguably the most prolific Covid-19 area of research. In fact, given its significance in putting an end to the limitations placed on people (lockdown, festivities, gatherings), the vaccine is the ultimate solution to the Covid-19 crisis. Unfortunately, the firms that use ML techniques in their vaccine development pipeline publish minimal data, if any [22]. A pioneering effort to use ML in the process of developing an effective Covid-19 vaccine was conducted in [23]. The authors trained an XGBoost model (a decision-tree-based ensemble ML algorithm) to predict the best candidate protein for the vaccine. Their work resulted in 6 potential candidates. The authors adopted an optimized ML-based technique to pick some suitable amino acid fibers to improve the composition of already discovered vaccines [24]. Separate studies [25-27] relied on Support Vector Machine (SVM) and other ML techniques in the same direction. SVM is a supervised learning ML algorithm generally used to classify data by figuring out the best hyper-plane that could separate them with the lowest error rate.

The most documented DL-based approach to explore the world of proteins is the AlphaFold project powered by Google DeepMind [28, 29]. It focuses on predicting the 3D structure of proteins based on their genetic sequence. During the first months of the pandemic, DeepMind published a prediction for many proteins related to SARS-CoV-2, the virus responsible for Covid-19. This work aimed to contribute to the understanding of the functioning of the virus.

B. Spread Estimation

The compartmental models are the most used models to forecast the spread of the pandemic [30]. They rely on stochastic frameworks to predict the right actions, decisions, and strategies to perform under any circumstances. In [31], the authors used this method to evaluate the impact of social distancing on the pandemic spread to predict the expected number of infections after the lockdown. A similar approach was used in [32] to predict the outbreak's growth in Wuhan, the Chinese city where the first Covid-19 cases were detected. The main recommendation of this work was that the lockdown and travel restrictions in China would help the control of the spread of the virus in the rest of the world. Compartmental models were further used in various studies [33-36] to predict the transmission of Covid-19 in Japan, Egypt, and other countries. Researchers used DL [37] and logistic growth [38] models to estimate the spread in China and South Korea. A complex approach was used in [39], where the authors used Markov Chain Monte Carlo and the number of confirmed deaths and cases to predict the reproduction rate. DL models were also used to predict a condition that refers to rapid breathing associated with Covid-19 infections. The authors in [40] relied on a bidirectional Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) model and data coming from smartphones. Impressive results were provided by the authors in [41] by training a Deep Neural Network (DNN) on a sizeable real-time dataset collected from smartphones. A Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model was used in [42] to estimate the pandemic spread in Canada. The authors in [43] developed a technique that joined LSTM and GRU to design and train a model to measure the Covid-19 release and death cases. Table II sums up the primary discussed studies that used ML/DL tools for Covid-19 prevention.

TABLE II. ML STUDIES ON THE PREVENTION AGAINST COVID-19

Role	Ref	Model
Vaccine discovery	[23]	XGBoost
	[24]	Combinational ML system
	[25, 26]	SVM
	[28, 29]	DNN
Spread estimation	[31-36]	Compartmental models
	[38]	Logistic growth models
	[39]	Markov Chain Monte Carlo
	[40]	Bidirectional GRU
	[42]	LSTM
	[43]	GRU + LSTM

III. ML METHODS FOR COVID-19 DETECTION

A prominent area where Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods shined during the Coronavirus pandemic is disease diagnosing and detecting. Several published papers highlight the use of DL models on Covid-19 identification. It is also worth noting that many of the studies we found are on CT chest scans [44]. The authors in [45] used a DL model to perform visual feature extraction from CT chest images. This project aimed to implement a classifier discriminating between Covid-19 and other pneumonia diseases. The researchers in [46] achieved promising results (86.30% accuracy) when developing a classification model to tackle the same problem. Authors in [47] proposed a similar work by implementing a DL

algorithm to detect Covid-19 infections through CT segmentation. A robust system was developed in [48], where the authors created and trained a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) on lung images to detect Covid-19 cases. The authors in [8] proposed another CNN model trained on CT chest scans and aimed to distinguish people affected by Covid-19 from others. Authors in [47] took a different approach than we have seen hitherto. They presented an approach based on Deep Transfer Learning to build and train a model to classify chest CT images. Moreover, the researchers in [49] opted for Transfer Learning (TL) to design a classification model to detect patients infected by Covid-19 based on their CT chest scans. However, instead of applying the DenseNet201 pre-trained model as the basis of their architecture, the authors proposed the ResNet50 model. Also, based on CT chest images, the authors of [50] proposed a model based on ResNet-50 and DPN-92 for classifying infected and non-infected patients. TL was also proposed in [51], where the Inception pre-trained model was used to create a diagnosis model. The authors of [52] intended the same goal. However, their approach was slightly different since they trained their model on X-ray images. Similarly, the authors in [9] proposed a TL model based on pre-trained models such as VGG19, VGG16, ResNet, DenseNet, and InceptionV3. It should be mentioned that these DNN models are well-known for reaching state-of-the-art results for many applications, especially in computer vision classification. Authors in [53] proposed a new classification model based on the Random Forest algorithm and X-ray scans from people affected by Covid-19 and other lung diseases. An aggregated model was developed in [54], where pre-trained models such as ResNet, VGG, and AlexNet were used, along with SVM. The pre-trained models were used for feature extraction, while the SVM model handled the classification. In another direction, some studies were exploring a completely different path to achieve the same goal of detecting Covid-19, namely sound-based and video-based techniques. For example, the authors of [18] used videos of healthy people and patients affected by Covid-19 and pneumonia. These data then fit a pre-trained model (VGG-16) used in the prediction phase. Moreover, authors in [55, 56] shown that respiratory sounds (mainly cough and breathing sounds) could be employed to detect people affected by Covid-19. The authors of [55] built binary classifiers for distinguishing Covid-19 positive patients from other respiratory diseases. Figure-1 illustrates the intersections between Covid-19 and other lung diseases and why it is difficult to distinguish one from the others.

IV. ML METHODS FOR COVID-19 TREATMENT

So far, this article explored the use of ML methods in the detection and prevention against Covid-19. However, the most straightforward and essential action to fight the outbreak is to assist the affected people to recover. It can eventually be solved by finding drugs that have a practical impact in fighting the new virus. This section will discover how ML models contributed to alleviating this problem and how efficient they were. Drug discovery is one of the trickiest and most challenging areas in medicine. Furthermore, it is known for taking many years to give valuable results.

Fig. 1. Covid-19 vs. other lung diseases.

Many researchers have turned their attention towards DL techniques instead of traditional technologies to speed up this process. For instance, the authors in [57, 58] used LSTM, CNN, and other DL models in their quest to find acting antivirals among the existing known drugs. Several other studies focused on Biomedical Knowledge Graphs (BKGs), a technique used to detect similarities and relationships between drugs, viral proteins, and genes. Authors in [59] utilized BKGs to identify a promising treatment for Covid-19. Authors in [60] used the same technique to describe the relations between gene-disease pairs. The ML model showed relations between the viral protein and some previously known drugs, which led to the prediction of many potential drug candidates that could be effective against Covid-19 [61]. Similar work has been done in [62], in which the researchers used a DL model to find candidate drugs. A multitask ML model and more than 2000 human proteins were used in [63] to find relations between Covid-19 and Known Drug Targets (KDTs). The drug representation was extracted in [64] using a deep graph network and known biological interactions.

ML and DL techniques were also applied to narrow the possibilities in the molecular docking process, one of the most computationally expensive, yet frequently used techniques in drug design. The authors used a neural network to narrow 3 million candidates to 1000 [65]. A Random Forest model to identify 187 molecules in the coronavirus S-protein was proposed in [66]. Moreover, the ML framework to predict viral protein activities was developed in [67]. The ensemble model used in this framework studied 19 drugs and ranked them based on their capacity to prevent the coronavirus proteases. The authors also used docking to assess critical aptitude.

AI was also used to find new chemical compounds. The authors in [65] used the protein homology model along with 28 DL models and Reinforcement Learning (RL) techniques to evaluate drugs based on some predefined metrics. Furthermore, the authors in [68] used RL in their quest to discover new SARS drugs. More precisely, they used Deep Q Learning and evaluated the discovered molecules according to 3 predetermined factors.

Figure-2 summarizes the ML-based initiatives in handling the Covid-19 crisis.

Fig. 2. ML solutions towards the Covid-19 pandemic.

V. EVALUATION AND DISCUSSION

Many researchers have used AI as a forefront tool in the fight against Covid-19. Choosing this technology instead of traditional approaches was driven by the impact that DL techniques have gained during the last decade. This section addresses these contributions evaluates their impact, and presents their limitations. ML and DL approaches have contributed to the findings and improvements in the fight against the pandemic. We presented many examples in this paper to back up this claim. However, our study also shows that AI did not play a game-changing role in this fight. We dedicate this section to present our observations and explain why this is the case.

The companies that used ML tools in their research and development process generally publish little relevant information about their findings, particularly in drug discovery and treatment of the disease, although the biggest challenge the development of effective DL solutions faces is the lack of data. DL is known to be more effective when an abundant amount of (useful) data is available. However, as we have seen above, Covid-19 datasets are generally composed of a few samples. For instance, we have seen models built upon data collected from only 28 cases. The number of samples is not the only issue with Covid-19 datasets. The quality of these samples also raises another challenge. Many datasets are being collected from web portals, affecting the quality of images and the information credibility. Another issue regarding Covid-19 data consists of their non-representativeness. There is a substantial disparity in the number of tests between countries, classes, and cities in the same country, affecting the scaling of the trained models and resulting in inaccurate predictions. The challenge of extracting these samples could explain the lack of quality and quantity of data related to Covid-19. Besides, one should not forget that we are dealing with personal data, so privacy constraints come into play. One solution that has been used in lots of studies to handle this problem is data augmentation. Simultaneously with data augmentation, TL could present a great opportunity using the already available models and data developed for similar medical scenarios.

It is essential to note that the dilemma with data issues when using DL models is that we can have a well-trained model that gives high performance in the limited data but fails to scale when new situations arrive. Therefore, it is unlikely to get a solution applied in the real world. Our study shows that most of the contributions are generally about predicting the

spread of the pandemic or detecting the virus. There are relatively few studies in the drug and vaccine discovery area. This is in line with the previous remark about real-world implementations since these areas present a more significant risk and therefore do not allow a margin of error to play with non-scalable and non-precise models. Our study also revealed that the primary source of Covid-19 data is in the form of images. Therefore, CNNs constitute the basis for many propositions. There is also the issue regarding privacy protection and the issue of the interpretability of DL models and how much we could trust their predictions in critical situations.

Table III exhibits the problems of existing DL/ML approaches when applied to the Covid-19 pandemic.

TABLE III. PROBLEMS WITH THE USE OF AI REGARDING COVID-19

Problem	Details	Proposed solutions
Competition	Closed models and datasets	Open-source initiatives
Data	Number of samples	Open-source initiatives
	Quality of samples	Data augmentation
	Non-representativeness	TL
Model	Scalability	Data quantity and quality
	Privacy	Differential privacy
	Interpretability	More research

VI. CONCLUSION

According to the official public service announcement on Coronavirus from the WHO, Covid-19 caused almost 5 million deaths while there are more than 238 million confirmed cases. This enormously heavy toll has generated the commitment of the research and development communities to alleviate this crisis. It turned out that ML and DL tools have been widely used in many applications during the last decade, including healthcare applications [69, 70]. To render valuable guidance to researchers in evaluating the use of ML/DL models against Covid-19, this paper studied the available Covid-19 datasets, the indispensable fuel for any DL-based approach. Then, the article reviewed how ML/DL tools were used in preventing, diagnosing and treating/curing the Covid-19 virus. We presented the models that advanced to detect the virus and then find drugs to treat the disease.

Finally, the last section of the paper is devoted to the thorough evaluation of these techniques, along with a discussion about their effectiveness in fighting Covid-19. The results that came from this study reveal that ML/DL techniques are not mature enough to be used in critical situations when people's lives are at stake, mainly due to the scarcity of the required medical data that are needed to train the models. The quality of the available data samples often raises some concerns. We proposed several potential solutions to remedy these circumstances, such as encouraging open-source initiatives, data augmentation, TL, and differential privacy.

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Hierarchical Control of a Low Voltage DC Microgrid with Coordinated Power Management Strategies

Shrishell Muchande

Department of Electrical Engineering
Fr. Conceicao Rodrigues Institute of Technology
Navi Mumbai, India
skmuchande@git-india.edu.in

Sushil Thale

Department of Electrical Engineering
Fr. Conceicao Rodrigues Institute of Technology
Navi Mumbai, India
sushil.thale@frit.ac.in

Abstract-A microgrid consists of a cluster of renewable energy sources, energy storage elements, and loads. One of the main objectives of a microgrid is to provide reliable and high-quality power to the loads. Under normal operating conditions, this is achieved through suitable Power Management Strategy (PMS). However, under emergency conditions, such as the failure of any source, overloads, or faults, the PMS may not be able to retain the microgrid in operating conditions. Any emergency condition may demand a significant change in control and coordination between various subsystems of the microgrid to survive and continue the operation. This feature makes a microgrid "a fault resilient" system as visualized in its objectives. This paper proposes a novel Coordinated Power Management (CPM) strategy based on three-layer hierarchical control for an autonomous Low Voltage DC (LVDC) microgrid. The proposed CPM strategy ensures the continuation of the microgrid operation under normal and emergency conditions. An emergency control layer is established to extend the microgrid operation during an emergency condition. The performance of the proposed control scheme is validated through simulation and experimental results.

Keywords-coordinated power management; DC microgrid; hierarchical control; fault resilient system

I. INTRODUCTION

Some of the challenges the conventional power generation faces are the environmental pollution, the reduction in the fossil fuels reservoirs, and the continuous increase in the power demand, which lead to increased penetration of the RES based Distributed Generation (DG). The resultant large penetration of RESs like Solar Photovoltaic (SPV) panels and wind turbines in existing grid is subsequently challenging its stability due to their intermittent nature. Small capacity sources with diverse nature integrated with Energy Storage Systems (ESSs) feeding aggregated loads are controlled and coordinated as a single entity, referred to as a Microgrid (MG). It facilitates the integration of free and locally available micro energy sources with suitable energy storage elements to meet the local load demand. In MGs, micro-sources are controlled through suitable power electronic converters. Based on voltage type, an MG can be classified as an AC MG, a DC MG or DCMG, and a Hybrid MG [1]. A DCMG possesses more advantages such as higher efficiency and natural interface with RES, ESS, and the loads.

Figure 1 shows a typical schematic of an LVDC MG configuration.

Fig. 1. A typical LVDC MG configuration.

The intermittent behavior of RES along with the unpredictable load fluctuations generally results in imbalance between the power generation and the load demand which significantly affects the overall operation of the system. Various power sharing control strategies have been presented in the past and are classified as decentralized, centralized and multilevel (hierarchical) control. In decentralized control, generally power management with droop control is adopted based on the capacity of individual sources. This method is simple and easy to implement with locally measured variables, but possesses some operational challenges like optimal Load Sharing (LS), voltage regulation, power regulation, real time source optimization etc. These challenges mainly persist due to the lack of information about source parameters. To address these issues, some improved droop control strategies have been proposed to enhance the load sharing accuracy, source optimization and voltage regulation achieved with low bandwidth communication [2, 3].

In centralized control, the sources are controlled by a remotely located centralized controller with high-speed communication links. The communication network with sufficiently large bandwidth plays an important role to exchange the information among the micro sources. However, the reliability of this centralized scheme suffers by the high probability of single point failures like the failures of the

central controller or of the communication networks. The hierarchical control is a better approach which neither suffers a single point failure nor demands the use of a high-speed communication network. However, a low to medium bandwidth communication link is needed, which plays an important role in the overall optimization of the system operation. Most of the difficulties associated with decentralized and centralized control are overcome in this approach. The hierarchical control provides continuous operation at suboptimal level during a failure of the controller or communication network.

In the existing literature, various control schemes for DC MGs have been reported. Authors in [2] presented the drawbacks of conventional droop control and showed the effect of different droop gains on the current sharing accuracy and voltage regulation. The current sharing accuracy changes with the higher value of line impedance while reduction in voltage. Authors in [3] proposed and analyzed 3 nonlinear droop control techniques to obtain the optimal operation for load sharing accuracy and bus voltage restoration. A power distributed control method for proportional load power sharing and bus voltage restoration is reported in [4]. The proportional output power sharing with load voltage restoration is achieved by adjusting only the output source voltage instead of introducing the virtual impedance. However, poor load sharing at light load and voltage deviation in heavy load conditions persist in the system. Frequency droop control method is proposed in [5]. Fuzzy logic is used to define the frequency droop coefficient. Authors in [6] proposed and evaluated a fault detection method which is independent of the MG topology. Authors in [7] proposed a decentralized controller with low bandwidth communication to enhance high reliability, low voltage regulation, and equal load sharing. Eigenvalue analysis and mathematical modal were derived. The conventional droop curve equation is shifted along with x-axis by adding additional voltage. A similar approach has been presented in [8], but the compensating average voltage of the identified critical busses is determined by the proposed modal analysis.

The hierarchical architecture was proposed for DC microgrid with reliable and optimum utilization of resources in [9, 10]. Primary level control is embedded in Local Controllers (LCs) directly acting on power converters according to the references generated by the secondary level controller with faster dynamics. The secondary level control facilitates functions like bus voltage regulation, power management, and overall system optimization. Authors in [11] proposed a power management control strategy to DC MGs under different operating conditions. The developed control algorithm ensures optimal utilization of the available resources and maintains a healthy State of Charge (SoC) of the ESS. A two-level hierarchical control algorithm is proposed in [12] that can operate the main source at constant power and reduce the fluctuations on the voltage-controlled source in system while maintaining the SoC of the storage unit. Authors in [13] addressed the Adaptive Dynamic Power Management Strategy (ADPMS) for a self-reliant DC MG. Authors in [14] presented the design and implementation of a low voltage autonomous

MG integrating different RES combination with suitable energy storage units to meet the electrical energy needs in remote locations. It consists of a single voltage source converter and a Bidirectional DC Converter (BDDC) to manage the power flow in self-sustain low voltage MGs.

Emergency power and energy management system are essential in ensuring the optimal restoration process and continue the healthy operational amongst available RESs, energy storage system. Authors in [15] proposed a multi-level novel reconfigurable hierarchical architecture for an AC MG to transfer its functionalities from a source-level control to system level control to supports long-term optimization of MG operation under normal conditions and front-line switching roles in emergency conditions. Authors in [16] proposed the design and control of integrated RESs for energy management. The peak load demand problem was resolved with a combination of demand side energy management and ESSs. Authors in [17] proposed a methodology of making a schedule of list of actions such that the distribution system operator is able to provide continuous electricity supply for classified customers. This is achieved by considering some power management options such as intentional load shedding, dispatch of expensive fossil fuel sources, system reconfiguration, and so on. Authors in [18] presented a mathematical formulation based on mixed integer linear programming under normal and emergency operating conditions for an AC MG to improve the system resilience.

As discussed above, the focus of the research in DC MGs is more on power management under steady-state operation. Not much research is reported in operational management under emergency operating conditions. Therefore, it is essential to make more investigations in emergency cases to extend the MG operation in such emergency. This paper describes the novel Coordinated Power Management Strategy (CPMS) implemented on a typical LVDC MG architecture shown in Figure 2. The proposed CPMS facilitates LVDC MG operation under both steady-state and emergency conditions. The proposed strategy incorporates 3 levels of hierarchical control. The details of the proposed strategy are provided along with the simulation and the experimental results. The proposed strategy makes a LVDC MG a fault-resilient system able survive and perform under all operating conditions.

II. THE COORDINATED POWER MANAGEMENT STRATEGY FOR THE LVDC MICROGRID

An MG's main objective is to provide reliable power under all operating scenarios and this demands the use of a failsafe power management strategy. It is also essential to use the locally available resources optimally. The main focus is to maximize the power extraction from RES and to relieve the ESS from its major share in supplying power to the loads. With the abovementioned objectives, a 3 layered hierarchical control strategy is proposed for an autonomous LVDC MG. The power topology of the proposed LVDC MG considered for this study integrates 2 solar PV power plants and a fuel cell-based source as RES components while the ESS consists of battery-based and ultra-capacitor based sources.

Fig. 2. MG power architecture of the proposed control strategy.

The battery-based source is meant for long term power backup and the ultracapacitor-based source is designed to meet the transient load requirements. Figure 2 shows the schematic of the complete LVDC MG. The boost converters with SPV are designed to operate in two modes: Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) mode and Constant Current Mode (CCM). Similarly, a Bidirectional Converter (BDC) with battery and ultracapacitor is configured to operate in Voltage Control Mode (VCM) as well as in CCM when absorbing the excess power. The FC-based source with the boost converter is configured to work in both VCM and CCM.

A. The Proposed Three Layer Hierarchical Control

The hierarchical control is divided into 3 levels: local control, emergency control, and supervisory control as shown in Figure 3. The local control acts as the primary control directly on the DC-DC converters interfaced with each source. This includes source optimization and local power/energy management of each source. The top layer consists of supervisor control which optimizes the overall system performance while ensuring system stability. The emergency layer monitors the source and system parameters to ensure that their values are within the limits. In case of any parameter crossing the set limits, the emergency control layer intervenes with the local or supervisory control to initiate the necessary actions. In case of emergencies like a severe MG bus fault, the emergency control initiates the actions directly to ensure no damage occurs to the system components.

Fig. 3. The proposed three layer hierarchical control structure.

The converter of each source is designed with self-sustainable local control to work independently and feed the power to its own local loads. The supervisory control is responsible to control various primary controller parameters as and when required. The low band-width communication link between the supervisory and the local controller ensures the information exchange needed for the control and the coordination of power generation balancing and load demand. It also ensures the source and system level data for identifying the transient/emergency conditions for changing the mode of operations, as well as the calculation of the reference signals to source level primary controller parameters. The overall MG is designed to provide 3kW of DC load at 48V bus voltage. The specifications of the various power converter components and their ratings used in the hardware implementation are given in Table I.

TABLE I. POWER CONVERTER DETAILS OF THE STUDIED DC MG

Converter	V _s	P _{OUT} (kW)	L (mH)	ESR _L (mΩ)	C (μF)/V	ESR _C (Ω)	Conv. Switch
Battery BDC	24V	1	0.56 50A	10	470 / 200V	0.05	SKM100 GB063D
SPV-boost conv. 1&2	31V	1	0.26 50A	6	1000 / 200V	0.1	SKM 100 GB 063D
Fuel cell	24V	1.2	0.56 50A	10	1000/ 200V	0.1	SKM 100 GB 063D
Ultra-capacitor 165F/48V	24V	--	0.26 50A	6	470 / 200V	0.05	SKM 100 GB 063D

The switching frequency for all the converters is selected to be 20kHz. The supervisory control is realized on a Texas Instrument's TMS320F28379D dual core controller board whereas the local control for each source is realized on TMS320F28069 controller boards. Based on hierarchical control strategy, the supervisory controller selects the mode of operation for each local converter through serial communication executed on the DSP. Figure 4 shows the power and control scheme implemented for various converters. The details of design of both VCM and CCM are given in [10]. The emulated fuel cell source is designed to be similar to a battery based source except the unidirectional boost converter instead of the BDC. Figure 5 shows a photograph of the

developed LVDC MG in hardware with the specifications listed in Table I. The functionalities of the proposed control strategy were verified with simulations carried out in the PSIM platform. The simulations were carried out to investigate some technical operational challenges and the way they were addressed suitably. Various operating scenarios under normal and emergency conditions were created as cases listed below. Also, hardware implementation of power topology along with the proposed control scheme was carried out to validate the results.

power generation and loading scenarios for the proposed DC microgrid for urban applications, a few Normal Operational Scenarios (NOS) are describing as below.

Fig. 4. (a) Solar PV 1 and 2 boost converter with CCM and MPPT control mode. (b) Battery and ultra-capacitor boost converters with VCM and CCM control mode. (c) Mode select control logic with communication received from the supervisory controller.

B. CPMS Simulation Results in Normal Operating Conditions

The hierarchical control based algorithm ensures the continuity of supply and efficient source utilization under all operating conditions. The supervisory control mentors the local variable parameters from the local controllers to perform the system level operating modes and passes the charging/discharging information. Considering the different

Fig. 5. Photograph of the developed LVDC MG setup.

NOS-1: During the light load conditions, the MG bus load is fed from the SPV and battery sources. As seen in Figure 6, the SPV source 1 is operating in MPPT mode to supply the primarily load current. The battery source maintains the MG bus voltage by absorbing the excess power or delivering the deficit power. The load is reduced at $t = 2s$, the excess power from the SPV 1 is absorbed by the battery. Before $t = 2s$, the load demand is met by SPV 1 and the battery.

Fig. 6. NOS 1: Light load condition supported with SPV and battery.

NOS-2: Under light load conditions, load is fed by the SPV and battery sources, but if the SPV power is more than the connected MG bus load, then battery charging is carried out. Figure 7 shows, the solar PV power generation changes as per solar insolation level. The SPV source supplies the available power to the load in the MPPT mode.

Fig. 7. NOS 2: Light load condition supported with SPV and battery with opportunity charging scenario.

The battery source maintains the MG bus voltage by absorbing the excess power or delivering the deficit power. The battery can be availed with opportunity charging in case the PV power is more than the instantaneous load demand. At $t = 2.5s$ the solar insulation level is changed and excess power from solar PV 1 and 2 is utilized to battery charging.

NOS-3: The MG bus load increased from 0.5kW to 2.8kW. The SPV sources 1 and 2 are both operating in MPPT mode primarily delivering the available power to the load. Fuel cell-based source working in current controlled mode supplements the SPV sources feeding the load. The battery source maintains the MG bus voltage by absorbing the excess power or delivering the deficit power. The simulation results for full load condition with the fuel cell operating in CC mode supplemented by both SPV sources is shown in Figure 8. Under full load conditions, all the sources participate to feed the MFG bus load while both the SPV sources deliver the available maximum power.

Fig. 8. NOS 3:-Full load condition supported with SPV (MPPT mode), fuel cell (CC mode), and battery sources (CV mode).

NOS-4: The MG bus load increased from 0.5kW to 2.8kW. SPV sources 1 and 2 are both operating in CC mode. The fuel cell source is configured to deliver the available power to the load while maintaining the MG bus voltage. The battery source delivers no load power but is engaged in charging through the FC as can be seen in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. NOS 4: Full load condition supported with SPV (CC mode), fuel cell (CV mode), and battery sources (charging mode).

NOS-5: The SPV sources 1 and 2 are both operating in CC mode. The battery source is configured to primary deliver the available power to the load while maintaining the MG bus

voltage. At 1.5s, the capacitive load imposed on the MG bus results in large transient current requirement. The ultracapacitor source pumps the demanded transient current, thus relieves the battery from supplying the transient load. The transient phase mitigation by the ultracapacitor source is shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. NOS 5: Transient loading condition.

C. CPMS Simulation Results in Emergency Operating Conditions

Emergency conditions such as MG short bus faults, failure of controllers/sources, loss of generation, and heavy overloads can occur in a DC MG. However, in the extreme case of a fault, the PMS may not be capable of retaining the MG in normal operating condition. When it comes to improving the resiliency and the reliability of the DC MG, power management and coordination strategy play a vital role. It is assumed that the fault was occurred, detected, and isolated by the emergency control layer and then control and coordination actions have to react quickly ensuring stability. Considering the different power generation and loading scenarios for the proposed DC MG, a few emergency operating scenarios (EOSs) are described below.

EOS-1: The SPV sources 1 and 2 are both operating in MPPT mode. The battery source is configured to primarily deliver the available power to the load while maintaining the MG bus voltage. At 2.5s, due to passing clouds, the power available from the SPV sources to zero. The battery source pumps additional load current to maintain the MG bus voltage. Figure 11 shows the simulation results of a sudden loss of the non-dispatchable SPV source.

Fig. 11. EOS 1: Sudden loss of the non-dispatchable SPV source.

EOS-2: The SPV sources 1 and 2 are both operating in MPPT mode. The battery is assumed to be charging with the excess power from the SPV sources. At 1.5s, the SPV Source 2 suffers from loss of generation. At 2s, due to the increase in load demands, the fuel cell source kicks in to supply the additional load current to maintain the MG bus voltage. The simulation results are shown in Figure 12.

Fig. 12. EOS 2: Sudden loss of the dispatchable battery source.

III. HARDWARE RESULTS

A laboratory scaled prototype (Figure 5) was designed and implemented for validation of the proposed MG with hierarchical control to supply 3kW DC load at 48V. Some selected hardware results are presented in Figures 13-16 indicating the various parametric measurements and their dynamic responses under different operating conditions (only few illustrative results are shown in this paper). Figure 13 shows the SPV source and battery source managing the overall load requirement of the MG under light load conditions. Figure 13(a) shows the available SPV power changes as per the variation in the solar insolation and the deficit power that is then delivered by the battery source ensuring the MG bus voltage is maintained within the specified allowable limit. Figure 13(b) shows the SPV source emulation with the MPPT mode primarily delivering the available power to the load while maintaining MG bus at 48V throughout the operation.

Figure 14 shows the emulated fuel cell and battery sources managing the overall load requirements of the MG. The SPV source is operating in MPPT mode primarily delivering the available power to the load. This situation may arise when the SPV source is not available, e.g. under rainy conditions or during the night. The fuel cell-based source working in current controlled mode supplements the battery source feeding the load. The battery source maintains the MG bus voltage by delivering the deficit power. In normal operating conditions, it is ensured that the SPV and the battery handle the load requirement. Under heavy load conditions, the fuel cell source along with the SPV and battery sources are utilized to supply the net MG bus load, whereas in light load conditions, the SPV source operating in MPPT mode delivers the excess power to the battery. Figure 15 shows the opportunity charging of the battery source when the SPV source power at the MPPT is more than the one demanded by the MG bus load. The battery source gets charged through the excess SPV source power while maintaining the MG bus voltage.

Fig. 13. (a) The SPV source is in the MPPT mode primarily to supply the load current and the battery source maintains the MG bus voltage by absorbing the excess power or delivering the deficit power due to solar insolation changes. (b) SPV emulation with MPPT tracking.

Under transient loads, like switching of capacitive loads, or short term fault conditions, the current drained from the battery source can be very high which may lead to the faster deterioration of the battery cells thus reducing the life of the battery. As shown in Figure 16, under such conditions the UC source gets engaged due to the faster current loop design and hence the faster dynamic response.

Under any transient current demand conditions, the UC source supplies the current, thus reducing the current requirement demanded from the battery source. The hardware setup of the LVDC MG with the proposed coordinated power management strategy implemented was tested under various other conditions as explained in the simulation results.

Fig. 14. (a) FC (CC mode) and battery (CV mode) under a particular loading condition. (b) The FC source feeds designated power to the load based on the command received from the CPM, and the battery source supply the deficit power.

Fig. 15. SPV source with MPPT mode delivering available power to load and excess power under light load condition is supplied to the battery source with opportunity charging.

Fig. 16. (a) Capacitive load switching: The UC source contributes the transient current relieving the battery source. (b) Expanded view of (a).

The performance of the MG proved to satisfy the requirement of reliable MG bus supply under all the operating conditions. Because a DC MG involves the integration of different types of renewable energy sources with dynamical changing characteristics and continuous changing in loads, MG control needs to be designed to ensure that the bus voltage stability is maintained all the time. The power sharing between the MG sources which ensures flat MG bus voltage profile under any operational conditions while reliably fulfilling the load requirements is a challenging task. Most of the researchers focused on power sharing under normal operating conditions while at emergency conditions the focus was on the protection of the system. While some researchers have already addressed the suitable power management strategy like adaptive dynamic power management strategy, different combinations of RESs with suitable energy storage units, demand side energy management and ESSs, intentional load shedding, dispatch of expensive fossil fuel sources, system reconfiguration by considering one by one the issues to be taken into the account under normal operating conditions. Very few papers have reported a power sharing strategy under emergency operating conditions in DC MGs. Under emergency conditions the demand in control and coordination between various subsystems of the MG to survive and extend the MG operation may significant change. This paper presented a highly effective hierarchical control with coordinated power management strategy for MG sources and ESSs to handle both normal and abnormal situations. The proposed control strategy was validated with simulation and experimental results in an implemented LVDC MG to showcase its reliable behavior under normal and emergency conditions.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presented the implementation of a hierarchically controlled LVDC MG with SPV, fuel cell source as RES components, and ESS comprised of battery based and ultra-capacitor based sources. The proposed LVDC MG system can facilitate the integration of such RESs to supply continuous power to the load. The proposed coordinated power management strategy based on hierarchical control for an autonomous LVDC MG ensures the reliable operation of the system with renewable energy sources, storage, and loads. The proposed strategy ensures the proper power sharing and the continuation of the MG operation under normal and emergency conditions. The hierarchically controlled DC MG operating in autonomous mode under normal and emergency conditions has been tested and some of the hardware results were reported.

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AUTHORS PROFILE

Shrishell Muchande completed his B.E. and M.E. degrees in Electrical Engineering at the University of Mumbai, Mumbai, India, in 2008 and 2013, respectively. Since 2016, he is a research scholar in the Department of Electrical Engineering, Fr. Conceicao Rodrigues Institute of Technology, Navi Mumbai, Mumbai, India. He has over 4 years of experience in industry. His interest areas include power electronics, renewable energy systems, microgrids, and control in microgrids. From 1996 to 2012, he was worked at the Lokmanya Tilak Collage of Engineering, Koparkhairane, Navi Mumbai. Since 2013, he has been a member of the Faculty of the Department of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering, Gharda Institute of Technology, Lavel, Ratnagiri, Maharashtra, India.

Sushil Thale obtained his B.E. degree in Electrical Engineering in 1992 and M.E. in Electrical Engineering in 1996 from the University of Mumbai, India. He completed his Ph.D. at the Indian Institute of Technology-Bombay with specialization in Power Electronics and Power Systems in 2015. He is currently working as a Professor (Electrical) and Dean (R&D) at Fr. Conceicao Rodrigues Institute of Technology, Navi Mumbai, India. His areas of research include renewable energy Systems, electric vehicle control, and microgrids.

A Super High Gain L-Slotted Microstrip Patch Antenna For 5G Mobile Systems Operating at 26 and 28 GHz

Mouaaz Nahas

Department of Electrical Engineering
College of Engineering and Islamic Architecture
Umm Al-Qura University
Makkah, Saudi Arabia
mmnahas@uqu.edu.sa

Abstract-Microstrip patch antennas have been widely investigated and used in modern mobile communication technologies including 5G. Previous works in the area demonstrated that such antennas can be designed to operate in the low, mid, and high bands of 5G networks. This paper focuses on high-band millimeter-wave 5G mobile applications. In particular, the proposed microstrip patch antenna was designed to operate at 26 and 28GHz, which are the first introduced and widely used frequency bands of the 5G. This study aims to enhance the gain and other radiation characteristics of the antenna by adding a combination of different slot shapes to a single rectangular patch that is commonly used in other 5G antennas. The results show that an extremely high gain is achieved by inserting two symmetric L-slots and a middle-placed square slot. The dimensions of the slots were simulated and optimized using the CST Studio Suite simulator. A comparative study was also conducted showing that the proposed antenna features higher gain and directivity and provides very good VSWR and efficiency along with a reasonably large enough bandwidth at the two resonance frequencies considered.

Keywords-5G mobile communications; antennas; gain; microstrip; patch; slot

I. INTRODUCTION

Low profile, low cost, small size, easy fabrication, and the conformity of microstrip patch antennas have led to their wide adoption in mobile communication systems including mobile phones, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), Global Positioning System (GPS), and many more applications [1-2]. Such antennas also have been recently found very effective in 5G wireless communication devices [3-4]. The millimeter-wave (mmWave) band represents a major part of 5G networks. The new mmWave bands allocated for 5G connectivity lie between 24.25–27.5, 27.5–29.5, 37–40, and 64–71GHz [5]. In particular, the first introduced 26 and 28GHz frequency bands are the two most important operating bands for mmWaves used in 5G, as defined by the Federal Communication Commission (FCC) [6-7]. For example, South Korea, US, and Japan considered the 28GHz band for their first 5G deployments, while Europe and China considered the 26GHz band [8]. The

availability of mmWave spectrum, especially at 26 and 28GHz, has attracted the interest of various radio technologies, including mobile communication. Therefore, these particular frequencies have attracted considerable attention from many researchers working in 5G [7-11]. On the other hand, many researchers focused on improving the radiation characteristics of microstrip patch antennas for 5G applications. A major issue in microstrip antennas is their narrow bandwidth, which can be improved using various methods such as slotted patch, thick substrates, low effective permittivity substrates, incorporating multiple resonances, and optimizing impedance matching [12-13]. Moreover, the main disadvantages of using mmWaves can be the high path loss, the susceptibility to atmospheric and rain absorption, shadowing by materials or human body, etc., which can all be mitigated by using antennas with high gain and large bandwidth [14]. Nevertheless, the narrow bandwidth is not a major issue in 5G as in wireless applications operating at lower frequency bands, instead the achievement of high gain stands as the main challenge, provided that the bandwidth is not severely compromised. The primary goal of this study is to improve the microstrip patch antenna gain for 5G applications working at 26 and 28GHz bands (Ka-band). A summary of the key related works in this area follows.

In [15], a compact planar inset-fed microstrip antenna was designed at 28GHz and provided 6.83dBi gain. In [4], a triple-band antenna, using low relative permittivity and low thickness substrate, was designed to operate at 24.4, 28, and 38GHz. The gains achieved at these frequencies were 6.65, 7.02, and 5.05dBi respectively. In [16], a dual-band Coplanar Waveguide (CPW) slot directive antenna was designed to operate at 28 and 38GHz for 5G. The maximum gains achieved for the two bands were 6.6 and 5.6dBi respectively. In [17], a broadband elliptical-shaped slot antenna was designed to cover the 5G band from 20 up to 40GHz, having a maximum gain of 5dBi. In [18], a dual-band Planar Inverted-F Antenna (PIFA) with a CPW feeding line was designed. This antenna achieved a bandwidth of 3.34 and 1.395GHz and a gain of 3.75 and 5.06dBi in the 28 and 38GHz bands respectively. In [19], a combined structure was developed, using a microstrip patch

Corresponding author: Mouaaz Nahas

radiator and a waveguide aperture, to provide a wide beam and high gain in a particular tilt direction. The maximum achieved gain was 7.41dBi at 28GHz. In [20] a slotted microstrip patch antenna was designed to operate at 28GHz for 5G applications. The design was based on the use of two slots of different shapes placed in the middle of the patch and connected through a narrow short strip. This compact antenna design provided a 6.37dBi gain. In [21], a dual-band (28 and 45GHz) elliptical-slotted circular patch antenna was designed for 5G communications and provided the maximum gain of 7.6dBi at 28GHz. In [22], Defected Ground Structure (DGS) and stub slot configuration were used to design a dual-band (28 and 45GHz) microstrip patch antenna with wide bandwidth and high gain (8.31dBi). Further studies that attempted to optimize microstrip patch antennas to operate at 28GHz for 5G communications were presented in [23-24], while the gains they obtained were 7.43 and 9.82dBi respectively. Furthermore, many studies focused on the use of microstrip patch arrays to enhance beamforming and directivity, and hence gain, of microstrip patch antennas for 5G applications. In [10], a novel antenna array design, based on using a square patch, an edge-plated air-filled cavity, and an hourglass-shaped aperture-coupled feed, was developed for the global 26 and 28GHz 5G bands. The presented 1×4 antenna array provided a peak gain of 10.1±0.7dBi. Many studies considered the design of array-based microstrip patch antennas for the 26GHz [25-29] and 28GHz [14, 30-36] 5G bands. Among these studies, the maximum gains achieved were 16.4dBi [25] and 19dBi [12] for the 26 and 28GHz bands respectively, which are considered very high. However, in terms of simplicity, such designs might not be the right choice in many cases, since the integration of patch arrays substantially increases the design complexity and the overall size of the antenna.

This study aims to design a dual-band single patch microstrip antenna operating at both the 26 and 28GHz mmWave bands of 5G. The slotted patch method is used in an attempt to improve the antenna gain significantly, as well as return loss (reflection coefficient), Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR), directivity, and efficiency while maintaining a sufficiently large bandwidth in the two 5G bands considered.

II. ANTENNA DESIGN

Considering that patch antennas are widely used in other shapes [37], the proposed antenna was based on a rectangular patch that has two symmetric back-to-back L-shaped slots and a single square slot placed between them. The antenna was built on a rectangular Rogers RT5880 substrate of 20mm length, 16.5mm width, and 0.508mm thickness. The relative dielectric permittivity ϵ_r was 2.2, and the loss tangent $\tan \delta$ was 0.0009. Further details on the RT Duroid 5880 substrate can be found in [38]. Among the various feeding techniques available for microstrip patch antennas, the inset feed was selected to achieve a good impedance matching between the feed line and the patch. The dimensions of the patch were 9.9×9.7mm², fed by a 50Ω microstrip line of 0.7mm width and 4.75mm length. Table I provides the optimized dimensions of the proposed antenna depicted in Figure 1. The values from L_{L1} up to W_S in the table represent the optimized dimensions obtained from a

parametric study performed using the sweep option available in the CST Studio Suite simulator.

TABLE I. OPTIMIZED DIMENSIONS OF THE SLOTTED PATCH OF THE PROPOSED ANTENNA

Dimension	L_P	W_P	L_{L1}	L_{L2}	W_{L1}	W_{L2}	L_S	W_S
Value (mm)	9.7	9.9	5.3	1	1.5	0.5	3.95	4.25

Fig. 1. Geometrical representation of the slotted patch element of the proposed microstrip antenna.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section provides the simulation results of the designed antenna, using the CST simulation software. Table II shows the detailed results of the radiation parameters chosen in this study to analyze the performance of the developed microstrip patch antenna. These parameters are center frequency (how close it is to the selected band), reflection coefficient (S11), bandwidth, gain, directivity, VSWR, and efficiency. The parameters listed in the table are introduced below. The reflection coefficient is most commonly referred to as "return loss" and is calculated in dB as:

$$\text{Return Loss} = -20 \log |\Gamma| \quad (1)$$

where Γ is the voltage reflection coefficient. As in all other microstrip antenna design studies, the bandwidth was measured at -10dB return loss.

The gain was measured in dBi (decibels-isotropic) as a reference to an ideal hypothetical isotropic antenna radiating (or receiving) energy equally in all directions. While the gain is the ratio of the radiation intensity in a given direction to the average of total input power, the antenna directivity, in contrast, is the ratio of the peak radiation intensity in a certain direction to the total radiated power [39]. The gain G is related to the directivity D by:

$$G = \eta D \quad (2)$$

where η is the efficiency factor lying between 0 and 1. For an ideal lossless antenna, η equals to 1 (i.e. 100%). The antenna efficiency is calculated as the ratio of the power radiated from the antenna to the power delivered to it. The higher the efficiency the more reliable and useful the antenna would be, particularly for 5G communications which require high speeds and reliable communication processes. The VSWR is a ratio between the maximum and the minimum voltage expressed by:

$$\text{VSWR} = \frac{V_{\max}}{V_{\min}} \quad (3)$$

VSWR measures the impedance mismatch between the feeding system and the antenna [38]. Its value must lie between 1 and 2, and the greater match is achieved as this value decreases towards 1. VSWR is calculated by [40]:

$$VSWR = \frac{1+|\Gamma|}{1-|\Gamma|} \quad (4)$$

TABLE II. SIMULATION RESULTS OF THE PROPOSED ANTENNA AT 26 AND 28 GHz

Frequency (GHz)	S11 (dB)	BW (GHz)	Relative BW (GHz)	Gain (dBi)	Directivity (dB)	VSWR	Efficiency
25.98	-24.14	0.55	2.12%	8.63	9	1.13	95.89%
28.2	-25.45	1.1	3.93%	11.26	11.8	1.11	95.42%

TABLE III. COMPARISONS OF ALL ANTENNAS AT THE 28 GHz BAND

Design	Gain (dBi)	Center frequency (GHz)	Minimum S11 (dB)	BW (GHz)	Relative BW (GHz)	Directivity (dB)	VSWR	Efficiency %	Other 5G bands (GHz)
Proposed	11.26	28.2	-25.45	1.1	3.93%	11.8	1.11	95.42%	25.98
[23]	9.82	28.1	-42	1.29	4.61%	-	1	99.99%	-
[21]	8.31	28	-54	5.13	18.32%	8.35	1	98%	38.5
[20]	7.6	28	-40	1.3	4.64%	7.68	1.01	85.6%	45
[18]	7.41	28	-35	1.5	5.35%	-	-	-	-
[3]	7.02	28.1	-19.3	0.9	3.21%	7.69	1.244	85.5%	24.4, 38
[14]	6.83	28.06	-18.25	1.1	3.93%	-	1.278	-	-
[19]	6.37	28	-40	2.48	8.86%	6.99	1.022	86.73%	-

The results show that the designed antenna provides high performance against all parameters considered in the study. For example, the reflection coefficients at the 26 and 28GHz frequency bands were equal to -24.14 and -25.45dB respectively. Such extremely low return loss values have a considerable impact on gain and directivity, which both scored very high values. On the other hand, the VSWR values in the two frequency bands are very close to 1, indicating a great match between the feeding system and the antenna. Moreover, the antenna efficiency exceeded 95% at both considered bands. Furthermore, the bandwidth of the proposed antenna in the two frequency bands is acceptable for 5G applications. Such moderate bandwidth values are outweighed by the super high gain achieved, which was the main objective of this study. As mentioned above, gain is of a higher priority than bandwidth in developing 5G antennas, given that the bandwidth is kept wide enough to cover 5G services. The high gain values achieved here by a single patch structure might be obtained by using array antenna structures, which in turn compromises the design simplicity and cost-effectiveness. The relative bandwidth in the table was calculated as the ratio of the bandwidth to the center frequency of the band in which the antenna operates (i.e. 26 or 28GHz in this case). A detailed comparison between the proposed antenna results and those achieved in other studies is provided in the next section. Figure 2 shows the S11 parameter in dB with respect to the operating frequency. The obtained center frequency and bandwidth are annotated on the graph for both considered operating bands. Figures 3 and 4 show the radiation pattern and the E-H plane of the proposed antenna at both resonance frequencies.

where Γ is calculated as a function of the load (Z_L) and source impedance (Z_S) by [40]:

$$\Gamma = \frac{Z_L - Z_S}{Z_L + Z_S} \quad (5)$$

be noted that all studies on the 26GHz band found in the literature were either based on antenna arrays or not designed for 5G applications (Ka-band), hence no comparison for 26GHz antenna designs is provided. The results are arranged in descending order according to the gain value. The best output value of each parameter is highlighted to facilitate the comparison between the various antenna designs.

Fig. 2. S11 parameter as a function of frequency for the proposed antenna design.

Fig. 3. The radiation pattern and E-H plane for the proposed antenna at 26GHz.

IV. COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED ANTENNA WITH OTHER DESIGNS

Table III provides a detailed comparison between the proposed antenna and a set of other designs that used a single patch structure and a resonance frequency of 28GHz. It should

It can be observed that the proposed antenna provided the highest gain and directivity without compromising other parameters, except the bandwidth which was compensated by

the very high gain and directivity. This indicates that the proposed microstrip patch antenna can be a strong candidate for 5G mobile communication devices, especially when simplicity, low cost, and small size are the key design requirements.

Fig. 4. The radiation pattern and E-H plane for the proposed antenna at 28GHz.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In response to the rising need for fast and reliable mobile communication devices, a rectangular slotted microstrip patch antenna was developed for high-band 5G applications. The main goal was to enhance the antenna gain along with other radiation characteristics. The proposed antenna was intentionally designed with a single patch for simplicity and aimed to resonate the antenna at the 26 and 28GHz 5G frequency bands simultaneously. The antenna consisting of double symmetric L-slots and a single square slot placed in the middle provided very good radiation characteristics, especially the peak gain. The antenna gains for the two resonance frequencies were 8.63 and 11.26dBi respectively, which were significantly higher than those achieved in the reviewed literature. The corresponding directivity values for the two considered bands were 9 and 11.8dB, and the minimum reflection coefficients obtained were equal to -24.14 and -25.45dB respectively. The latter values are far below the -10dB return loss at which the bandwidth is usually measured. The bandwidths of the two bands at -10dB return loss were equal to 0.55GHz (2.12% fractional bandwidth) and 1.1GHz (3.93% fractional bandwidth) respectively, with a total bandwidth of 1.65GHz covering the 5G spectrum lying between 25 and 29GHz. Furthermore, for the 26GHz band, the VSWR and efficiency were 1.13 and 95.89% respectively, while for the 28GHz band, the VSWR and efficiency were 1.11 and 95.42% respectively. These results proved to be satisfactory when compared to other designs. Based on these results and the small dimensions, light weight, and relatively simple design, the proposed microstrip patch antenna can be a suitable choice for the development of 5G mobile communication devices. In the future, we can investigate various combinations of other slot shapes or antenna array structures to further improve the radiation characteristics, particularly bandwidth.

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AUTHORS PROFILE

Mouaaz Nahas was born in 1977 in the UK. He received a B.Sc. degree in Electrical Engineering from Jordan University of Science and Technology, Jordan, in 2001, an M.Sc. degree in Communications Engineering from Loughborough University, UK, in 2002, and a Ph.D. degree in Embedded Systems from the University of Leicester, UK, in 2009. He is currently an Associate Professor in the Department of Electrical Engineering at Umm Al-Qura University, Makkah, Saudi Arabia. His main research interest is antenna design for modern wireless communication applications.

A Non-Parametric Empirical Method for Nonlinear and Non-Stationary Signal Analysis

Yaakoub Berrouche

LIS laboratory, Department of Electronics
Faculty of Technology
Ferhat Abbas Sétif 1 University
Sétif, Algeria
berrouche@gmail.com

Abstract—A Non-parametric Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition (NCEEMD) method is a novel technique for nonlinear and non-stationary signal analysis to detect a gearbox fault. The NCEEMD method was based on the CEEMD, but the Gaussian white noise was replaced by the fractional Gaussian noise. The NCEEMD method does not need to choose the appropriate SNR and the number of ensemble trials before signal processing, which makes it a non-parametric method. This new approach was evaluated using a simulated malfunction signal representing two typical faults in gearbox systems: modulation and rub-impact. Its performance was evaluated in terms of MSE and computation time. A comparative study between the EMD, EEMD, CEEMD, and NCEEMD methods showed that the latter performed better by improving the computation time and accuracy of CEEMD. The proposed method is a non-parametric method that provides a powerful tool in extracting the modulation and the rub-impact features from a vibration signal. The NCEEMD method helps to track down the gearbox faults and resolve this crucial problem in mechanical machines.

Keywords—complementary ensemble empirical mode decomposition; fractional Gaussian noise; gearbox fault detection; nonlinear signal analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Gears are common and vital components in rotating machines, having a typical nonlinear and non-stationary signal. Monitoring the condition of a gear can help in the early detection of potential failures and avoidance of damages [1]. The predictions are based on the analysis of vibration signals generated by mechanical equipment. Many conventional methods of signal processing, such as statistical methods and Fourier analysis, have been applied to the analysis of vibration signals to diagnose gearbox faults. However, these methods are based on the assumption that the signals are stationary and linear, while gear defects have the nature of non-stationary processes [1].

Several methods have been proposed to deal with non-stationary signals. Among these techniques, the wavelet transform has good localization properties in the time and frequency domains, and it has been applied to the detection of damage in gear systems [2, 3]. However, the main drawback of the wavelet transform is the definitive choice of the wavelet

base function before it is used [1, 4], making it non-adaptive. The Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) was developed as a powerful tool to analyze nonlinear and non-stationary signals [5], and it has been applied in machine fault diagnosis [1, 6-10]. EMD decomposes a signal into a finite number of Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMFs) by taking advantage of the signal's local properties. However, the main drawback of EMD is the mode mixing problem, where oscillations of different time scales can appear in one IMF, or oscillations with the same time scale can appear in different IMFs. To overcome the mode mixing problem, the Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition (EEMD) was proposed as an improved method of EMD [11]. EEMD is a noise-assisted data analysis method where the true IMFs are defined as the mean of an ensemble of trials, each consisting of the original signal plus a finite white noise. EEMD has been applied to the diagnosis of rotating machinery faults [12-14]. However, the resulting IMFs can be corrupted by additive white noise. The residue noise can be decreased by using a large number of ensemble trials (N_e), resulting in high computation times. The Complementary EEMD method (CEEMD) was proposed to reduce computational times [15]. For this purpose, the white noise is added and subtracted separately from the original signal to generate two sets of IMFs. The average of IMFs of the same order could effectively reduce the final white noise residue.

This study proposes a new method named NCEEMD to enhance the performance of CEEMD by reducing the number of ensemble trials and therefore the amount of calculation and computation time. The NCEEMD method is based on the principles of the CEEMD, but the Gaussian white noise is replaced by fractional Gaussian noise [16, 17]. The proposed method was evaluated using a simulated malfunction signal caused by modulation and rub-impact that represent two typical faults in gearbox systems. Its performance was evaluated in terms of fault diagnosis and computation time, and it was compared with the performance of EMD, EEMD, and CEEMD methods.

II. MATHEMATICAL THEORY

A. EMD Algorithm

The EMD method decomposes any non-linear and non-stationary signal into a finite number of IMF components by

Corresponding author: Yaakoub Berrouche

taking advantage of the local properties of the signal. This process is applied without requiring an a priori basis as the wavelet method by using a sifting algorithm. So, the original signal can be obtained by superposing the obtained $M-1$ IMFs and one residual $r(t)$ as [5]:

$$s(t) = \sum_{j=1}^{M-1} IMF_j(t) + r(t) \quad (1)$$

A more detailed description is provided in [5]. However, the main disadvantage of EMD is the problem of mode mixing, which affects the decomposition accuracy and the interpretation of the results.

B. EEMD Algorithm

The EEMD was proposed in [11] to overcome the mode mixing problem of EMD. The EEMD method defines the true IMF as the mean of an ensemble of trials, each consisting of the investigated signal corrupted by an additive white noise [11]. For a given number of ensemble trials N_e , a finite white noise is added to the signal in each trial, and then this noisy signal is decomposed into IMFs by using the EMD method [11]. Eventually, the true IMFs are obtained by averaging the IMFs of the same order. A complete description can be found in [11]. The EEMD method removes the problem of mode mixing. However, the resulting IMFs will be contaminated by the added noise. The added noise in the decomposed results can be reduced by using a large number of ensemble trials, increasing computation time.

C. CEEMD Algorithm

The CEEMD method was proposed to reduce the computational time of EEMD and the white noise residue. In this approach, white noise is added and subtracted separately from the original signal to generate two sets of IMFs with positive and negative noises [15]. The average of IMFs of the same order could eliminate the noise residue in the final IMFs. A drawback of CEEMD is the selection of the right level of added white noise and the number of adequate trials before each signal processing.

D. NCEEMD Algorithm

This study proposes the NCEEMD method to further reduce the number of ensemble trials. This method is based on the CEEMD method, but the Gaussian white noise was replaced by the Fractional Gaussian Noise (FGN). The FGN is a stationary process obtained by periodically sampling the fractional Brownian motion process $B_H(t)$ and by computing the first difference, defined by [17]:

$$x(n) = B_H(n) - B_H(n-1) \quad (2)$$

The autocorrelation of FGN is given by:

$$R_x(k) = \frac{\sigma^2}{2} (|k-1|^{2H} - 2|k|^{2H} + |k+1|^{2H}) \quad (3)$$

The FGN is characterized by the Hurst exponent H , where $0 < H < 1$, and its variance σ^2 . For $H = 1/2$ the FGN process is a white noise process, while other values produce nonzero correlations. For $0 < H < 1/2$ the correlation is negative, the autocorrelation decays very rapidly, and the frequency response looks like a high-pass filter. For $1/2 < H < 1$ the correlation is

positive and the autocorrelation decays very slowly. The frequency response is similar to a low-pass filter.

E. Hurst Exponent Selection

The FGN is characterized by a Hurst exponent H which is defined in two intervals. Two criteria were used in a systematic approach to select an appropriate H and ensure a successful NCEEMD decomposition. The first criterion was to determine the values of H that provide decomposition without mode mixing and no redundant IMF components. Figure 1(a) represents the different results of NCEEMD decomposition for the simulated malfunction signal described in Section III, according to the Hurst exponent where a value of 0 represents no redundant IMF component and the value of -1 represents the mode mixing [18]. Therefore, H within the range of $[0, 1/2]$ is a good value for a successful NCEEMD decomposition. Furthermore, it has been shown that the bandwidth of each IMF in the EMD method was much narrower for H lower than $1/2$, and it increased with H greater than $1/2$ [16]. Then, to ensure that the NCEEMD method behaves like an effective filter without mode mixing, the range $0 < H < 1/2$ must be chosen.

The second criterion was used to determine the exact value of H in the selected range. To reach this aim, the accuracy of the decomposition using RMSE between the IMF1 and the rub-impact component of the simulated malfunction signal was evaluated according to the Hurst exponent, as shown in Figure 1(b). As it can be noted, the method has fewer errors in the range of $0.16 < H < 0.20$, while RMSE has a minimum at $H=0.185$. Therefore, the appropriate value of the Hurst exponent is $H=0.185$.

Fig. 1. Hurst exponent selection: (a) Relationship between the Hurst exponent and decomposition results obtained from NCEEMD, (b) Relationship between the Hurst exponent and RMSE (NCEEMD method).

III. SIMULATION EXPERIMENTS

Simulation experiments were conducted on a gearbox signal model, as an example of a non-linear and non-stationary

signal, to analyze the performance of the proposed method and compare it with the conventional empirical method.

A. Gearbox Signal Model

The vibration signal, acquired from a normal gearbox, composed of a pair of gears and meshing under a constant load and speed, is represented by [19]:

$$x(t) = \sum_{m=0}^M X_m \cos(2\pi m N f_s t + \varphi_m) \quad (4)$$

where M is the number of tooth-meshing harmonics, X_m and φ_m are the amplitude and the phase modulation function of the m^{th} meshing harmonic, respectively, N is the teeth number of the gear, f_s is the rotating frequency, and Nf_s is the meshing frequency. When gears with faults are meshing, the amplitude and the phase of the vibration signal would be modulated. The gear fault vibration signal can be expressed by [19]:

$$y(t) = \sum_{m=0}^M X_m (1 + a_m(t)) \cos(2\pi m N f_s t + \varphi_m + b_m(t)) \quad (5)$$

where $a_m(t)$ and $b_m(t)$ are periodic functions whose frequencies are the rotating frequency and its multiples that include the fault information of the gear vibration signal.

In this study, the normal gear vibration signal was used with one periodic function of the m^{th} meshing harmonic of the amplitude and phase. When gears with a fault are meshing, both the amplitude and phase of this signal are modulated by the same periodic functions ($(a_m(t)=b_m(t))$). In addition to the modulation, the gear fault vibration signal can also include a rub-impact fault. Therefore, all the decomposition methods mentioned in Section II were tested and compared on a simulation signal that included modulation and rub-impact components.

B. Application of NCEEMD on the Gearbox Signal

The NCEEMD and two conventional methods were tested on a simulated gearbox signal as an example of a nonlinear and non-stationary signal. Two typical faults exist in a fault diagnosis of a gearbox: modulation and rub-impact. When the local rub-impact occurs in the gear, it produces an impact signal characterized by pulses of very short duration whose amplitude decreases exponentially. In addition, the normal gear vibration signal, with one periodic function of the m^{th} meshing harmonic, was modulated by amplitude and phase modulation. The rub-impact signal, the amplitude, the phase-modulating signal, and the simulated malfunction signal that combines them are shown in Figure 2.

The simulated malfunction signal was decomposed by NCEEMD and the conventional methods EMD and EEMD to extract the rub-impact component and detect a fault, as shown in Figures 3-5. By comparing the decomposed components, NCEEMD successfully extracted the various components embedded in the simulated malfunction signal without mode mixing. This best performance in terms of RMSE was obtained with one trial and a low level of added FGN (SNR=25dB). On the other hand, EMD failed to extract the rub-impact component due to mode mixing between different IMFs. Likewise, EEMD extracted the rub-impact component but with a high computation time (number of ensembles $N_e=200$) and high error rate. These results suggest that NCEEMD is a sufficient method to diagnose a gearbox signal.

Fig. 2. Gearbox signal: (a) The rub-impact signal, (b) The simulated malfunction signal.

Fig. 3. The decomposed two components obtained by NCEEMD. (a) IMF1, (b) IMF2.

In conventional empirical methods, the level of noise added and the number of ensemble trials are the two primordial parameters needed to ensure a successful decomposition. Therefore, to measure the performance of NCEEMD and show that it can solve the problem of choosing the level of white noise added and determine the number of ensemble trials before processing, the appropriate number of ensemble trials is calculated by evaluating the correlation between the IMF1 and the high-frequency component in the simulated malfunction signal.

Fig. 4. The decomposed two components obtained by EMD. (a) IMF1, (b) IMF2.

Fig. 5. The decomposed two components obtained by EEMD. (a) IMF1, (b) IMF2.

The relationship between the number of ensemble trials and the decomposition results obtained by EEMD (SNR=20dB), CEEMD (SNR=10dB), and NCEEMD are shown in Figure 6. These results show that NCEEMD requires a high SNR and one trial to reach a 95% of correlation. This means that the proposed method needs a low level of noise added with one trial to ensure successful decomposition. On the other hand, conventional methods need low SNR and a large number of ensemble trials before signal processing. Furthermore, the proposed method is non-parametric and decomposes any

nonlinear and non-stationary signal in low computation time and high accuracy, compared to the classical methods.

Fig. 6. Relationship between the correlation coefficient and the number of ensemble trials: (a) EEMD, (b) CEEMD, (c) NCEEMD.

IV. CONCLUSION

Gearbox fault detection is a crucial task in mechanical machines. This paper proposed an efficient fault detection technique by introducing a new method named NCEEMD. Three techniques were compared, namely EEMD, CEEMD, and NCEEMD. Simulation experiments showed that EEMD, CEEMD, and NCEEMD managed to extract the gear meshing and the rub-impact fault components from a gearbox signal. However, the EEMD and CEEMD methods used a large number of ensemble trials and a high level of added noise that caused large computational time and more contamination with noise. However, the proposed NCEEMD method achieved better performance in terms of accuracy and computational time, without choosing any parameters before signal processing. Therefore, the proposed method is non-parametric and more adequate to deal with a nonlinear and non-stationary signal.

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The Possibility of Minimizing Rutting Distress in Asphalt Concrete Wearing Course

Hanady M. Abd Al Kareem
Department of Civil Engineering
College of Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
EnHanodaa@gmail.com

Amjad Hamad Khalil Albayati
Department of Civil Engineering
College of Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
a.khalil@uobaghdad.edu.iq

Abstract—The excessive permanent deformation (rutting) in asphalt-concrete pavements resulting from frequent repetitions of heavy axle loads is studied in this paper. Rutting gradually develops with additional load applications and appears as longitudinal depressions in the wheel path. There are many causes of the rutting of asphalt roads, such as poor asphalt mixing and poor continuous aggregate gradation. All factors affecting the mixture resistance to permanent deformation must be discussed, and all must be properly considered to reduce the rutting propensity of asphalt-aggregate mixtures. In this study, several mixtures were produced with the most common techniques in rutting resistance (using the most effective additives for each mixture), and their performance was compared with the (conventional) mixture currently used in Iraq. The tests focused on the asphalt-concrete mixture for wearing courses. Different mixtures types were tried, namely, dense hot asphalt mixture (HMA) with two different asphalt contents (4.7% and 5.3%), Open-Grade Friction Course (OGFC) mixture, Stone Mastic Asphalt (SMA) mixture, and Beton Bitumineux a Module Eleve (BBME). The modifiers included natural Sisal Fibers (SFs), Carbon Fibers (CFs), and mineral filler (hydrated lime, HL). Marshall test was carried out to find stability and flow values. Rutting was evaluated by the repeated load test for cylindrical specimens under two temperatures (40°C and 60°C) to obtain the permanent deformation parameters. The parameters were used as input to the VESYS 5W software to evaluate the rut depth during different times of design life under 7×10^6 Equivalent Single Axle Loads (ESALs). The results of the selected mixtures were compared with the mixture designed in the laboratory dense gradation mix Job-Mix Formula (JMF) within the limits of the Iraqi specification (SCR2003). Manipulation of the aggregate gradation that is customary in the implementation of the local mixture showed that the best performance regarding rutting resistance was exhibited by JMF, which decreased the rut depth at 40°C and 60°C by 21.63mm and 44.304mm respectively, in comparison with the conventional mixture. Changing the aggregate gradation of the local mixture gives better performance in rutting resistance without additives or changing the percentage of asphalt, at the same cost.

Keywords—rutting; HMA; SMA; OGFC; sisal fibers; carbon fibers; hydrated lime; Job Mix Formula; repeated load test; BBME; VESYS

I. INTRODUCTION

The term "permanent deformation" has been used to describe any distortion of a pavement surface, including shoving and pushing due to mix instability [1]. Today, this form of distress refers to the longitudinal depression or "ruts" that form in the wheel paths due to the consolidation and/or lateral movement in one or more of the component pavement layers due to repeated, transient load applications [1]. Because rutting appears only as a change in the transverse surface profile, it is often erroneously blamed on surface instability [2]. The rutting of asphalt roads has many causes, e.g. poor asphalt mix and poor aggregate gradations. All the factors affecting mixture resistance to permanent deformation must be properly considered in order to reduce the rutting propensity of asphalt-aggregate mixtures. At the same time, it must be emphasized that the states of stress and strain caused by traffic loading also significantly influence pavement rutting [2]. In this study, different approaches are used to minimize the rutting distress in local asphalt concrete pavement structures, all of which concentrate on asphalt concrete mixtures for wearing courses. Different types of dense hot asphalt mixtures are used, which are considered the workhorse of HMA since they may be used effectively in all pavement layers for all traffic conditions [1, 2]. Dense-graded mixes are designed to resist all types of distresses developed from the applied stresses. These distresses include fatigue cracking, rutting, moisture damage, and thermal cracking. They are expected to minimize the service life and increase the maintenance costs [3].

Rutting is considered to be a major distress that frequently occurs in flexible pavements due to the nonlinear, viscous, and plastic behaviors of asphalt mixes [4]. Rutting on high volume roadways can be prevented if angular coarse and fine aggregates are used and if the air voids in the mixture do not fall below approximately 3.0% [5]. A Stone-Mastic Asphalt (SMA) mixture is a gap-graded HMA that maximizes rutting resistance and durability with a stable stone-on-stone skeleton held together by a rich mixture of Asphalt Cement (AC), filler, and stabilizing agents, such as fibers and/or asphalt modifiers. The primary purpose of SMA mixes improves rut resistance and durability. Therefore, these mixes are almost exclusively used for surface courses on high volume interstates, and U.S.

highways. Special cases such as heavy, slow-moving vehicles may warrant the use of SMA for intermediate and base layers [6]. The gradation of the aggregates is the largest element that affects the overall performance of the pavements when studying the rutting behavior of asphalt pavements [6, 7]. Open Graded Friction Course (OGFC) mixtures are designed to be permeable to water, which differentiates them from dense-graded and SMA mixtures that are relatively impermeable. These mixtures use only crushed stone or, in some cases, crushed gravel with a small percentage of manufactured sand. OGFC mixtures reduce splash/spray from tires in wet weather and typically result in a smoother surface than dense-graded HMA [6]. Authors in [7] found that the result of permanent deformation of OGFC with Carbon Fibers (CFs) under repeated pressure levels of 0.068, 0.138, and 0.206MPa at 25°C decreased by 16.9, 17.8, and 10.1% when using CFs by 0.3% and a length of 2cm at pressure levels of 0.068, 0.138, 0.206MPa, respectively. With modified asphalt pavement, some ACs require modification to meet specifications. Modified AC usually has a higher initial cost than the unmodified AC, but it provides a longer service life with less maintenance [8, 9]. The present research focuses on additives with effective performance on rutting resistance that are suitable for the selected mixtures. Fibers are currently being used extensively in porous asphalt friction courses more than polymers and other additives, with the primary purpose of increasing asphalt content without any drain down problems [10]. The fiber reinforces the binder system, thus causing an increase in its viscosity. The resulting mix has greater stability and possibly higher resistance to rutting and other distress than similar mixes without the addition of fibers. Mineral and natural fibers were used and their rutting behaviors were compared. Hydrated Lime (HL) is also used to improve HMA as mineral filler. It is an additive that increases pavement life and performance through multiple mechanisms [11].

Two types of fibers are used, man-made CF and Sisal (Agave Sisalana) Fibers (SFs). CF is a very strong lightweight synthetic fiber typically made by carbonizing acrylic fibers at high temperatures. CFs can be used as an additive to asphalt to make electrically conductive AC [12]. SFs are obtained by the removal of fiber bundles from dried sisal plant leaves growing in tropical environments. SFs have high strength and rigidity because of their high cellulose rate (~%78-88). In addition, SFs have good elasticity due to their high moisture absorption capability because of their hollow structure and the large amount of hydroxyl groups in their chemical bonds. This eco-friendly fiber is also cheaper than synthetic fibers, which are used for technical textiles while it is a useable material for reinforcing dense graded pavement [13]. Additionally, mineral filler HL can be considered an alternative modifier to improve the properties of asphalt binders and mixtures. HL can significantly improve both moisture damage and rutting resistance. The application of Hin asphalt binders is an effective and economical method to improve the performance of asphalt mixtures to resist moisture damage and rutting. Several studies have shown the beneficial application of HL in asphalt mixtures to improve moisture susceptibility either by adding dry HL to wet aggregates or by adding lime slurry to dry aggregates [14, 15].

The road construction industry faces the challenge of designing and constructing high-performance asphalt materials to meet the ever-growing demand of increasing traffic volumes and axle loadings. EME (Enrobés à Module Elevé) or simply high-modulus asphalt was developed in France in the mid-seventies. EME is a high-performance material for use in heavy-duty pavements. EME for base courses and Beton Bitumineux à Module Eleve (BBME) for binders and wearing courses are called High-Modulus Asphalts (HiMAs). Two classes of EME and 3 classes of BBME are defined. EME class 2 and BBME class 3 are specified for the most heavily trafficked roads. They require higher binder contents according to aggregate gradation [16]. The Job Mix Formula (JMF) or dense gradation mix submittal is the mechanism to confirm that the produced mix is in accordance with the project specifications. The end result of a successful mix design is a recommended mixture of aggregates and asphalt binder. This recommended mixture also includes aggregate gradation and asphalt binder type asphalt binder content are specified based on the JMF along with the allowable specification bands for inherent material and production variability. These target values and specifications are based on the JMF and not any general HMA gradation requirements. Thus, the mix designer is free to choose a particular gradation for the JMF, and then the manufacturer is expected to adhere quite closely to this JMF gradation during production. The Iraqi standard specifications for roads and bridges, SCRB R/9, 2003, allowed the prepared JMF for asphalt mixtures to accommodate some tolerances with regard to the following properties: coarse aggregate gradation, fine aggregate gradation, filler content, AC content, and mixing temperature [17].

II. MATERIALS

Locally available materials were utilized in this study. AC 40-50 and AC 20-30 (for the BBME mixture only), aggregates (coarse, fine), and filler were used. SF, CF and HL were used as additives, and 6 AC mixtures were prepared for wearing a course layer with 3 different asphalt contents, i.e. 4.7%, 5.3%, and 6% depending on the type of mix, by the weight of the total mixture as shown in Tables I and II.

TABLE I. SELECTED AC OF THE MIXTURES

Types of Mixture	Selected AC%	Ref.
Conventional HMA without additives		-
High-stiffness asphalt (EME)	4.7	[37]
JMF		[38]
SMA		[42]
Hot mix asphalt (HMA)	5.3	[39]
OGFC	6.0	[40]

TABLE II. SELECTED MODIFIER CONTENT (%)

Modifier Types	Modifier content (%)	Modifier's length (cm)	Ref.
Carbon fiber (CF)	0.3%	1.5	[38]
Sisal fiber (SF)	0.3%	0.5	[20]
Hydrated lime (HL)	1.5%	-	[41]

A. Asphalt Cement

In this research project, the experimental work was carried out by using AC 40–50 and AC 20–30 penetration grade

bitumen from the Daurah refinery. Table III shows the AC physical properties.

TABLE III. PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF AC

Test	Test condition	Units	Asphalt binder (20-30)	Asphalt binder (20-30)	EME* specification
Penetration	100g, 25°C, 5s, 0.1mm	1/10mm	24	24	20-30
Ductility	25°C, 5cm/min	cm	18	18	-
Flash point	-	°C	300	300	240 Min.
Softening point	(4±1)°C/min	°C	61.5	61.5	55-63
Specific gravity	-	g/cm ³	1.03	1.053	-
Penetration index	--	-	-0.27	-0.27	+0.7 Max. -1.5 Min.
Retained penetration.		%	75	75	55 Min.
Change of mass		%	-0.074	-0.074	0.5 Max.
Retained ductility	25°C, 5cm/min	cm	13	13	-
Softening point	(4±1)°C/min	°C	68.4	68.4	-
Increased softening point	-	°C	6.9	6.9	8 Max.

TABLE IV. PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF THE AGGREGATES

Laboratory test	ASTM designation	Test results	SCRB specification
Course aggregates			
Apparent specific gravity	C-127	2.687	-
Bulk specific gravity	C-127	2.61	-
Water absorption, %	C-127	0.21	-
Fractured pieces (angularity), %	D-5821	96	90 Min
Percent wear (Los Angeles, abrasion), %	C-131	17.8	30 Max
Fine aggregates			
Apparent specific gravity	C-128	2.683	-
Bulk specific gravity	C-128	2.62	-
Water absorption, %	C-128	0.4	-

B. Aggregates

Coarse crushed aggregates were obtained from the Al-Nibaie quarry. The coarse aggregate size ranged between 12.5mm and the No. 4 sieve (4.75mm). Fine aggregates were bought from a local source. Laboratory evaluation described the basic properties of the aggregates. The results are presented in Table IV according to the specification limit (SCRB, 2003) [17]. For HMA and JMF, aggregate gradation was selected according to [17], with a nominal maximum size of 12.5mm, (wearing course type IIIA). OGFC gradation was selected according to the ASTM7064 specification [18]. The nominal maximum size of the aggregates is 12.5mm. The SMA gradation selected in this study follows the AASHTO [19]. Table V and Figures 1-3 show the selected aggregate gradation. EME samples shall be designated as EME 0/10, EME 0/14, and EME 0/20, and BBME samples shall be designated as BBME

0/10 or BBME 0/14 according to their aggregate size [16]. The target grading should fall within the appropriate limits explained in Table IX [20]. For the purposes of this work, the appropriate grading for the wearing course based on [17] is BBME 0/14. The selected gradations with the specification limits of BBME 0/14 are tabulated in Table VI and Figure 4.

TABLE V. SELECTED AGGREGATE GRADATION

Sieve size	Passing by weight (%)				Specification range		
	Selected gradation				SCRB	OGFC	SMA
	HMA	JMF	OGFC	SMA			
3/4"	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
1/2"	95	96	92.5	90.5	90-100	85-100	90-100
3/8"	83	*90	47.5	64	76-90	35-60	50-80
No. 4	59	*63	17.5	28	44-74	10-25	20-35
No. 8	43	*38	7.3	17.5	28-58	5-10	16-24
No. 50	13	13	-	-	5-21	-	-
No. 200	7	5	3	10.5	4-10	2-4	8-11

TABLE VI. SELECTED AGGREGATE GRADATION AND LIMITING VALUE FOR EME

Test sieve opening (mm)	EME 0/14	BBME 0/14		SCRB (R/9, 2003)		
		Sieve size (mm)	Specification range (%)	Standard sieve (mm)	Specification range	Selected gradation
31.5	-	-	-	-	-	-
20	100	20	100	19	100	100
14	90-99	14	90-99	12.5	90-100	95
10	-	10	-	9.5	76-90	83
6.3	42-65	6.3	-	4.75	44-74	50
4	-	4	-	2.36	28-58	40
2	19-42	2	19-42	0.3	5-21	13
0.25	8-18	0.25	8-18	0.075	4-10	7
0.063	5-9	0.063	5-9	-	-	-

Fig. 1. Specification limits and selected gradation for HMA and JMF.

Fig. 2. Specification limits and selected gradation for OGFC.

C. Mineral Filler

Limestone dust from the lime factory in Karbala Governorate was used as the mineral filler.

Fig. 3. Specification limits and selected gradation for SMA.

Fig. 4. Specification limits and selected gradation for EME.

D. Additives

CFs were used in this work. They were added at 0.3% by weight of mix and had 1.5cm length. These fibers were obtained by using a paper shredder machine, as shown in Table VII [18].

TABLE VII. PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CARBON FIBERS

Test properties	Typical lalue
Nominal thickness (mm)	0.167
Fiber length (mm)	Can be produced at any length
Color	Black
Density (gm/cm ³)	1.82
Tensile strength (N/mm ²)	40000
Elongation-at-break (%)	1.7
Tensile modulus of elasticity (kN/mm ²)	225
Base	Polyacrylonitrile
Temperature of carbonization	1400 °C

TABLE VIII. PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SISAL FIBERS

Test properties	Typical value
Diameter (mm)	5
Fiber length (cm)	90-110
Color	Natural white cream
Density (gm/cm ³)	1.58
Tensile strength (N/mm ²)	385 to 728
Elongation-at-break (%)	2.75
Young's modulus (GPa)	9-22
Moisture	6.55
Fire resistance	Good

TABLE IX. HYDRATED LIME PROPERTIES

Property	Result
Specific gravity	2.43
Passing sieve No. 200 (0.075mm) (%)	99
Specific surface area (m ² /kg)	395

The second additive, SF is a performance leader among the most comprehensively used common fibers. Approximately 3.8 million tons of SFs are developed each year worldwide. They were added at 0.3% by weight of mix and had 0.5cm length [21]. These fibers were obtained by using a paper shredder

machine, as shown in Table VIII. Finally, HL is a promising material to be used in pavements due to its unique physical, chemical, and mechanical characteristics. It was used as an additive for asphalt mixtures (dry mix with aggregate) at a percentage of 1.5% by weight of aggregates [17]. The chemical and physical properties of HL (Figure 7) are listed in Table IX.

Fig. 5. Images of CF and SF after shredding and HL.

III. SPECIMEN PREPARATION AND TESTING PROCEDURE

The procedure covers preparation, compaction and testing of 101.6mm (4in.) diameter and nominal 63.5mm (2.5in.) height cylindrical specimens using the Marshall Apparatus in accordance with ASTM D 6926-04 [21]. Following this phase, the selected weight of asphalt binder was heated to the temperature that produces a kinematic viscosity of 170 ± 20 centistokes (i.e. 150°C) and was mixed thoroughly with preheated aggregates for two minutes. To complete the molding process, the compaction procedure was conducted at temperature that produces an asphalt binder kinematic viscosity of 280 ± 30 centistokes (i.e. 140°C). For each specimen, Marshall stability and flow tests were performed. The cylindrical specimens were placed in a water bath at 60°C for 30 minutes and then they were compressed on the lateral surface at a constant rate of 50.8mm/min (2in/min) until failure. The maximum load resistance and the corresponding flow value were recorded, and the average results were reported. Figure 6 shows the preparation of the specimens.

Fig. 6. Marshall specimens.

Repeated Load - Permanent Deformation testing was applied to the Marshall specimens and the resilient vertical strain was computed under load repetitions via a Pneumatic Repeated Load System (PRLS). Diametric loading was conducted to a steady loading rate of 60 cycles per minute, and the loading system for every cycle consisted of a 0.1s load duration and 0.9s rest period to simulate the testing conditions clarified in [23]. The mix and testing variables were:

- Test temperature: Two levels of temperature, 40 and 60°C, are used.
- Stress: 137.9kPa (20 psi) stress was selected as target.

- Asphalt Grade: AC type 40-50 and type 20-30 were used.
The procedure of the test can be summarized as follows:
- Place the specimens in the room of testing for two hours at 40°C and 60°C to achieve the test temperature and permit uniform temperature spreading in the specimens.
- Position the LVDT on the specimen and connect it to a PC, as shown in Figure 10.
- The pressure actuator is set. The control of both the rest and loading ports is also set to the preferred load and the duration of rest after the end of the sample "setup".
- Start the repeated load test until 10,000 cycles are reached or the specimen fails.

The results of rutting tests in terms of permanent strain (ϵ_p) are plotted against the number of repetitions by (1) for each specimen to find plastic parameters, the intercept (a) and the slope (b). These parameters can be estimated from (1) [5]:

$$\epsilon_p = aN^b \quad (1)$$

The intercept (a) represents the permanent strain at a number of load repetitions (N) equal to one, while slope (b) represents the rate of change in the permanent strain as a function of the change in loading cycles (N) on the log-log scale. Once the regression coefficients have been calculated, the permanent deformation coefficients alpha (α) and mu (μ) are computed using the relationship given in (2) and (3) [5]:

$$\alpha = 1-b \quad (2)$$

$$\mu = (a-b)/\epsilon_r \quad (3)$$

where ϵ_r is the resilient microstrain, ϵ_p the plastic microstrain, μ (μ) is the permanent deformation parameter representing the constant proportionally between permanent strain and resilient strain (i.e. plastic strain at $N=1$), and alpha (α) is a permanent deformation parameter indicating the rate of decrease in incremental permanent deformation as the number of load applications increases.

Fig. 7. Repeated load system.

For each mixture, 6 samples were used (3 samples for each temperature) to evaluate the permanent deformation. The analysis of the results is based on the temperature and mixture type under constant stress and constant time of loading (0.1s loading, 0.9s unloading) as showing in Figure 7.

IV. PAVEMENT PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

To reduce the risk of unsatisfactory pavement performance to an acceptable level, engineers must be able to reliably

predict pavement behavior over time. In this study, VESYS 5W software is used to predict the pavement performance. VESYS 5W has been successfully used to analyze the asphalt pavement performance under field traffic and under accelerated pavement testing loads. A period of 15 years is considered in the analysis. VESYS 5W needs to be provided with parameters in form of input data to run the analysis. These input parameters include the material properties of the layers, thickness, traffic data, and environmental conditions. The VESYS analysis procedure uses advanced mechanistic concepts to predict the behavior and performance of flexible pavements. Strain and deflection responses are computed and then used in conjunction with the failure criteria to predict pavement distress in terms of cracking, rutting, and roughness. Distress is used to define pavement performance in terms of the life history of the Present Serviceability Index (PSI). All the components of the design procedure have been formulated to take into account the inherent variability in traffic estimates, material properties, environmental conditions, and in the many construction practices used (VESYS 5W user Manual 2003) [24].

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Marshall Stability and Flow

The results show that in the case of HMA, a greater increase in stability is observed by adding filler than by adding fibers (of both types) for the same asphalt content. An increase in stability of up to 12.5% is observed when using natural fibers (SF) compared to using CF, but the increase reaches 25% in the case of using HL compared to SF with an increase in asphalt content. The mineral filler effect on the asphalt indicates that lime substantially increases the viscosity (stiffness) of AC binders. The increase in viscosity of the asphalt binder also increases the resistance to water as shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. HMA stability by changing the asphalt content for each type of additive.

In the case of SMA, as shown in Figure 9, the opposite is observed: the stability increases by adding fibers (of both types) more than by adding fillers (HL). An increase in stability of up to 16% occurred when using CFs compared to using HL, which reaches 24.2% when using SFs compared to CF. Because the strength of SMA relies mostly on the stone-on-stone aggregate skeleton, the fibers must be designed to mix and be placed with a strong coarse aggregate skeleton that provides the desired strength and stability to the mix more than fillers.

Fig. 9. Increasing stability of SMA by changing the type of additives.

After choosing HMA (5.3% asphalt content with HL) and SMA (with SF), as the best choices from the previous mixtures, the remaining mixtures are discussed and compared with the control mixture (Figure 10). It is noted that the EME mixture has a high stability value (increased by 56.8%) compared to the conventional (control) mixture and others because it increases binder stiffness and consequently the value of Marshall stability. Regardless of the above, the JMF achieves high stability without increasing the optimum asphalt content or additives (by 90.7% compared to the control mixture), because the aggregate gradation with low maximum aggregate size achieves higher stability values against that of the common high maximum size gradations and enhances the performance of asphalt mixtures, crack resistance in particular. In addition, the increasing stability values may be due to the increase in workability and the easiness of compaction and the best interlock in particular.

Fig. 10. Comparison of changes in the stability of the mixtures.

TABLE X. MARSHALL STABILITY AND FLOW RESULTS.

Mix type	Asphalt Content (%)	Modifier type	Stability (kN)	Flow (mm)
Control mix	4.7	Without additives	8.29	3.2
EME			13	3.3
HMA	4.7	CF	8.06	3.8
		SF	8.2	3.2
		HL	9.12	2.3
	5.3	CF	9.82	2.5
		SF	10.05	3.4
SMA	5.3	HL	12.53	2.7
		CF	10.33	2.6
		SF	12.83	2.9
JMF	4.7	Without additives	15.81	3.3

The Marshall stability test results are listed in Table X. The results indicate that the increase and decrease in the Marshall flow is related to the type and content of the additive, as well as to the type of mixture. When flow values are examined, it is observed that high flow values are usually related to plastic mixtures subject to permanent deformations. However, flow values are measured between the required specification ranges of 2 to 4mm.

B. Suggested Performance Tests for OGFC

In the case of an OGFC mixture, two tests instead of the Marshall test are suggested to evaluate its performance. As shown in Figures 11 and 12, for both tests, the highest value of air voids (%AV) appears for the mixture containing the filler HL (30%) and the worst result in the draindown test compared to the mixture with CF, while the mixture containing SF gives the desired result in the draindown test and acceptable air voids (10%) compared to the mixture with CF because the natural fiber gives the best stability and the most homogeneous distribution inside the OGFC mixture.

Fig. 11. Comparison of air void test result.

Fig. 12. Comparison of draindown test result.

VI. PAVEMENT PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

All the components of the design procedure were formulated to take into account the inherent variability in traffic estimates, material properties, environmental conditions and the many forms of construction practices used.

- Pavement structure: The geometry of the pavement structure is shown in Figure 13. The structure is a conventional flexible pavement section with 5 layers: wearing course, binder (leveling) course, base course, subbase course, and subgrade.

Fig. 13. Geometry of the pavement structure.

Fig. 14. Eighteen-kip ESAL configuration.

- Temperature: The assumed Mean Air Pavement Temperature (MAPT) is 40°C. Such a temperature is expected to occur in the middle of the AC pavement layer during the hot summer seasons in Iraq.
- Material Properties: When the pavement structure is treated as a multilayer elastic system, it is necessary to quantify the material stiffness properties. These properties are needed for the calculation of the stresses, strains and deflection response in the pavement system under the application of traffic loading. The parameters (α and μ) shown in Tables XI-XIII are calculated from the repeated load test that was performed on the asphalt mixtures, and are used as input into the VESYS 5W to estimate the rut depth of a selected pavement structure using the properties of different asphalt mixtures. Alpha (α) and mu (μ) parameters for binder, base and subbase courses are taken as default values, while the corresponding value for the wearing course varies according to the laboratory test results.

TABLE XI. PLASTIC PARAMETERS FOR MIXTURES WITH 4.7% AC

Selected asphalt content (4.7%) @ 40°C						
Mix type	Control mix	Control mix CF	Control mix SF	Control mix HL	EME	JMF
α	0.378	0.409	0.485	0.502	0.706	0.810
μ	0.189	0.205	0.243	0.252	0.353	0.403
Selected asphalt content (4.7%) @ 60°C						
α	0.302	0.244	0.253	0.345	0.506	0.746
μ	0.151	0.122	0.127	0.173	0.253	0.373

- Traffic loading: Low traffic loading is used in this study. The low-volume road category is defined by AASHTO as roads that carry significant levels of truck traffic, and the maximum number of 18kips (80kN) is shown in Figure 14. The Equivalent Single Axle Load (ESAL) applications

considered for flexible and rigid pavement design are 7000,000 over 15 years. In this study, 1 million ESAL applications are used for the design life. The annual growth rate is assumed to be 5%.

TABLE XII. PLASTIC PARAMETERS FOR MIXTURES WITH 5.3% AC

Selected asphalt content (5.3%) @ 40 °C						
Mix type	HMA CF	HMA SF	HMA HL	SMA CF	SMA SF	SMA HL
α	0.402	0.474	0.642	0.442	0.632	0.234
μ	0.201	0.237	0.321	0.221	0.316	0.117
Selected asphalt content (5.3%) @ 60 °C						
α	0.325	0.362	0.503	0.344	0.404	0.126
μ	0.163	0.181	0.252	0.172	0.202	0.063

TABLE XIII. PLASTIC PARAMETERS FOR MIXTURES WITH 6% AC

Selected asphalt content (6%) @ 40 °C			
Mix type	OGFC CF	OGFC SF	OGFC HL
α	0.376	0.405	0.286
μ	0.188	0.203	0.143
Selected asphalt content (6%) @ 60°C			
α	0.251	0.290	0.102
μ	0.126	0.145	0.051

VII. RESULTS OF THE VESYS 5W RUN

By using VESYS 5W, the permanent deformation result was estimated as a rut depth in mm plus the PSI. Rut depth less than 12.5 mm is the desired criteria that be maintained over a service life of 15 years, as suggested in [27].

A. HMA (4.7%)

As shown in Figures 15 and 16, additives may improve the performance of the mixture, but only if they are suitable for grading the mixture and containing the appropriate asphalt content, e.g. the mixture with the HL reduces rut depth more than the mixture with SF and CF. At 7 million ESALs and 40°C, the rut depth for mixtures with HL, SF, and CF is 7.8, 9.56, and 18.64mm respectively, which shows that the addition of HL improves the mechanical behavior by increasing the stability of the mixture at relatively high temperatures (40°C and 60°C). The HL content displays an effective influence, particularly at 40°C. The HL filler actually stiffens the asphalt film and reinforces it. Furthermore, lime makes HMA less sensitive to moisture by improving the aggregate-asphalt bond. This synergistically improves rut resistance [28].

Fig. 15. Rut depth of HMA (4.7%) at 40°C

Fig. 16. Rut depth of HMA (4.7%) at 60°C

Fig. 19. Rut depth of SMA (5.3%) at 60°C.

B. HMA (5.3%)

Figures 17 and 18 show that increasing the asphalt content leads to a reduction in the rut depth under the same ESALs at two test temperatures, for every mixture and every type of modifier. The rut depth for the HL, SF, and CF mixtures are 3.18, 8.72 and 17.45mm respectively at 7 million ESALs and 40°C. This improvement is probably due to the well-distributed additives, in different directions of the bituminous matrix, which are highly resistant to shear displacement and strongly prevent any movement of the aggregate particles, therefore increasing the rutting resistance of the mixture [29, 43]. From the above, the best option for the HMA-type mixture with the additive for both asphalt contents is HMA (5.3%) with HL.

Fig. 20. Rut depth of SMA (5.3%) at 60°C.

Fig. 17. Rut depth of HMA (5.3%) at 40°C.

It is noted that the mixture of SMA with fibers gives a better result compared with HL filler. On the other hand, the natural SF performs better inside the SMA mixture than the CF. For example, at 7000000 ESALs and 40°C, it is noted that the rut depth in mixtures with SF, CF, and HL is 3.33, 12.72, and 17.45mm respectively.

D. OGFC

Similar to the previous mixture, the mixture containing fibers (SF and CF) gives a better result compared to the mixture with filler (HL). However, this mixture has less resistance than SMA under high temperatures and heavy ESAL. For example, it is noted that the mixture with SF exceeds the permissible limit of rutting as for 3.7 million ESALs under the temperature of 40°C it was 12.63mm and with CF 16.39mm, as shown in Figures 21 and 2. It is noted that both stone matrix asphalt (SMA) and OGFC with fibers are used as stabilizers. Fibers decrease the drainage of the mix and increase the resistance more than hydrated lime.

C. SMA

Figures 19 and 20 show the effect of different mixture types (changing gradation) on the rut depth. Such mixtures need to be modified for draindown.

Fig. 18. Rut depth of HMA (5.3%) at 60°C.

Fig. 21. Rut depth of OGFC 40°C.

Fig. 22. Rut depth of OGFC 40°C.

E. Conventional (Control) Mixture

As seen from Figures 23-26, maximum rut depth occurs in conventional mixtures when higher temperatures and higher stresses are applied. The asphalt mixture becomes softer with increasing temperature, which leads to more permanent deformation at the same stress. Increasing stress has a negative effect on the pavement structure and increases the movement of pavement particles, leading to large rutting at the same temperature [30]. After selecting the mixtures with the highest rutting resistance from the above, they are compared with the control mixture (Figures 23-26). At 7000000 ESALs and 40°C, it is noted that the rut depth decreases by 20.48mm when using HMA 5.3% (HL) and by 20.33mm when using SMA (SF).

Fig. 23. Rutting depth for HMA 5.3% (HL) and conventional mix at 40°C.

Fig. 24. Rutting depth for HMA 5.3% (HL) and conventional mix at 60°C.

F. BBME

Figures 27 and 28 illustrate the effect of high modulus and conventional mixture on the rutting depth of the pavement

geometry. It can be seen that at the 15th year after 7,0000,0000 ESALs at 40°C and 60°C, the BBME mixture exhibits lower rut depths of 21.14 and 25.33mm respectively, than the conventional mixture. Therefore, the stiff binder improves the pavement performance susceptibility to permanent deformation failures during hot summers and repeated loads [31, 36].

Fig. 25. Rut depth for SMA with SF and conventional mix at 40°C.

Fig. 26. Rut depth for SMA with SF and conventional mix at 60°C.

Fig. 27. Rutting depth for BBME and conventional mix at 40°C.

G. Dense Gradation Mix (JMF)

Finally, the JMF gives the best rutting resistance results. It can be seen that after 15 years and 7,0000,0000 ESALs at 40°C and 60°C, the JMF mixture exhibits lower rut depths by 21.63 and 30.4mm than the control mixture, as shown in Figures 29 and 30, because the addition of fine aggregates strongly increases the friction within the mixture. In addition, angular aggregates are known to have more resistance to rutting than other configurations [32]. Additionally, the aggregates form the

internal structure of the asphalt mixture and are responsible for its strength and durability in carrying loads and mixing the internal bonds that help resist deformations [33].

Fig. 28. Rutting depth for BBME and conventional mix at 60°C.

Fig. 29. Rutting depth for JMF and conventional mixture at 40°C.

Fig. 30. Rutting depth for JMF and conventional mixture at 60°C.

Based on the previous results, it is concluded that the strongest and most resistant to rusting under high load and high temperatures are the JMF and the BBME mixtures. However, attention should be given to an important point regarding the BBME mixture, as it may not be used in practice as a surface layer except in rare cases, due to the fact that it may be prone to thermal cracking and fatigue cracking and it may not provide a surface texture with sufficient skid resistance.

When multiple layers of EME are constructed, it is crucially important that good bonding between the two courses is achieved [33, 35]. Therefore, the choice of type depends on the conditions and specifications determined by the

requirements, its efficiency in solving the desired problem, and its effectiveness over the years, which altogether achieve the lowest cost and good performance. In this study, the change in aggregate gradations within the permissible limits of the local mixture used currently in Iraq without additives or changing the content of asphalt is the most efficient in resisting the high temperatures prevailing in Iraq and the least expensive with a high rutting resistance (which is the common deformation mode in the country) and other deformation performance, as shown by the results.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the test results, the optimal mixture for this study is JMF with 4.7% binder content. When flow values were examined, it was observed that high flow values are usually related to plastic mixtures subject to permanent deformations. The performance of the HMA mixture can be improved by using additives, and it was found that the use of HL as a filler gives better results than the use of fibers, and by increasing the asphalt content from 4.7% to 5.3% for the same mixture gradation, stability and rutting resistance increase. The main outcomes of this study are:

- The addition of HL improves the mechanical behavior by increasing the stability of the mixture at relatively high temperatures.
- Marshall stability increased by 10% in HMA (4.7%) with HL and by 51% in HMA (5.3%) with HL in comparison with the control mixture, but regarding rutting resistance, the HMA (5.3%) mixture with HL was more resistant than the HMA (4.7%) mixture with HL under high temperatures and heavy load.
- It was concluded that the best additive is usually the fibers, especially the natural SFs. Fibers have been used in a global scale for many decades to reinforce paving materials. A very common use of fibers is to add them into open graded mixtures or porous asphalt to avoid draining down bitumen from aggregates. However, the use of fibers in dense graded mixtures to increase stability or improve cracking resistance is less common.
- SF has good elasticity due to its high moisture absorption capability and because it acts as a reinforcement inside both mixtures. The stability was 12.83kN and the flow was 2.9mm in the case of SMA (SF), while the draindown was 0.25% and the percentage of air voids was 20.8% in the case of OGFC (SF). Regarding rutting resistance, the SMA mixture was more resistant than the OGFC mixture under high temperatures and heavy load.
- It was noted that BBME gave good Marshall stability and flow values that were greater than those of the conventional mixture by 58.6% and 3.1% respectively. It also exhibited and high resistance to permanent deformation. It was noted that the BBME gave good resistance to deformation values because a stiffer asphalt binder plays a role in rutting resistance at high temperatures.
- Finally, the JMF gave the best and highest results in Marshall stability and flow, which were increased by 90.7%

and 3.1%, respectively, and also high rutting resistance by decreasing the rut depth by 21.63mm in comparison with the conventional mix under 7000000 ESALs and 40°C after 15 years of operation because the addition of fine aggregates increases the friction within the mixture. The permanent deformation parameters alpha and mu are more sensitive to temperature and stress level than the other parameters considered in this research. The test results show the difference in shape between conventional (40-50) and stiff (20-30) binders at 40°C and 60°C. This means that the BBME mixture has excellent resistance to permanent deformation (rutting) and a high effect on alpha and mu.

- The effect of the gradient on the plastic parameters (alpha and mu) is very high and clear by comparing the mixtures, where the aggregates are the main element in the strength of the mixture and the appropriate gradation in the extent of its durability and resistance to deformation. The JMF mixture gave the highest values of alpha and mu.

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Investigating the Causes of Poor Cost Control in Iraqi Construction Projects

Nagham Nawar Abbas
Department of Civil Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
nagham.nawwar@gmail.com

Abbas M. Burhan
Department of Civil Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
abbasm.burhan@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Abstract-Controlling cost in construction projects is an essential issue. This study investigates the most critical problems that cause weakness in cost control in Iraqi construction projects. The quantitative technique was used by conducting a survey directed to professionals who work on construction projects. One hundred and sixty-four questionnaire forms were distributed to private sector companies, government companies, and government institutions, and the responses were subjected to the required statistical analysis. The results indicate that the most influential factors are the weakness in keeping up with the use of modern concepts, methods, and technologies, the delay in receiving the amounts due for work done from the owner, fluctuations in market prices, the lack of knowledge and the inefficient use of currently available tools and technology, and the security situation in the country. The results indicate that the Iraqi construction projects suffer from weakness in cost control, which causes them to stop or delay their delivery, and this needs serious and quick solutions. One of the most important solutions is the adoption of modern technologies and their inclusion in the construction sector and the development of special systems for managing costs that are appropriate to the Iraqi construction environment.

Keywords-cost control; construction project; statistical analysis; causes; investigation

I. INTRODUCTION

A construction project will be successful if its technical goals are aligned with its budget and the budget is not exceeded. It is difficult to envisage a construction project being completed without cost variances and schedule delays, which may occur at any time during the procedure due to various factors such as poor management, supervision, and control [1]. Most construction projects require the completion of a specific set of operations to deliver a specific product. Construction projects include new buildings and structures, additions, changes, conversions, expansions, reconstruction, renovations, large replacements, and mechanical and electrical installations. Cost and time control is essential in the construction industry [2].

In general, a construction project's success is determined by its ability to fulfill the client's cost, time, safety, resource allocation, and quality objectives. A successful project meets

technical goals, stays on schedule, and stays within cost limitations [3]. The construction industry as a whole has been deemed to be underperforming, resulting in an inability to attain effective cost performance. As a result, most building projects have a wide range of costs [4]. One of the most important concerns confronting the construction sector is cost overrun [5]. Time and cost overrun are common issues for the majority of construction projects [6, 7].

Cost overrun is a common theme in Iraq's construction industry. Despite the development of many cost control approaches and technologies, the Iraqi construction industry has yet to implement them [8]. This research contributes to the identification of the current reality of the Iraqi construction sector.

II. DESIGN OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE

Initially, previous studies were reviewed to collect, organize, and analyze relevant information in a manner appropriate to the intended purpose. After that, this information was subjected to a series of discussions, analyses, and modifications that helped develop a questionnaire. The first page of the questionnaire is a cover containing information related to the research topic. The questionnaire included two parts. The first part includes general information about the concerned entity (such as its type and name) and information about the people who fill out the questionnaire from the target community in the study (specialization, educational qualification, workgroup, and the amount of experience). The second part includes a list of factors that are probable to have a negative impact on the control of the cost of a construction project. This part includes 22 closed questions designed with a five-point Likert scale (1: Always, 2: Frequently, 3: Sometimes, 4: Scarcely, 5: Never). Each respondent was asked to assign a degree of measure to each factor based on his/her perceptions about the Iraqi construction sector's environment.

The most prominent and important problems the process of construction project cost control faces, according to the review of the previous literature and interviews with experts specialized in the field of construction projects, are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. A REVIEW OF THE ISSUES THE CONSTRUCTION PROJECT COST CONTROL

S	Issue	References
1	Weakness in keeping up with the use of modern concepts, methods, and technologies	[9-12]
2	Lack of knowledge and inefficient use of currently available tools and technology	[13, 14]
3	Failure in the decision-making process due to various reasons	[12]
4	Poor communication and transfer of information and data between the concerned parties	[15]
5	Lack of progress in measuring work properly	[16]
6	Poor planning and scheduling and not dividing work items in a way that helps tracking costs easily	[14, 17]
7	Unclear contract documents (contracting details, technical specifications, general and special requirements)	[17]
8	Failure to prepare an appropriate purchase plan	[14, 18]
9	Fluctuations in market prices	[14, 18]
10	Involving inexperienced executive staff in terms of cost and low labor productivity	[17, 18]
11	Low labor productivity	[16]
12	Changes made by the owner	[14, 18, 19]
13	Changes resulting from design errors	[19]
14	Poor management of site data and not accurate documentation	[14, 18, 19]
15	Delay in receiving the amounts due for work done from the owner	[18]
16	Excessive waste of materials on the site	[19]
17	Inaccurate estimation of quantities	[14, 20]
18	Insufficient information needed to achieve cost control	[20]
19	Lack of a fixed and specific method in the process of making measurements for real work	Added during the open survey
20	Not clearly specifying the type of data and information required	Added during the open survey
21	Inadequate analysis of cost data to ensure a better benefit in the control process	Added during the open survey
22	Security situation in the country	Added during the open survey

III. FACE VALIDITY

Face validity, or content validity is a sort of validity in which diverse aspects, skills, and behaviors are measured appropriately and successfully. The research tools and data may be reviewed by professionals in the field of study to this goal. Vague and cryptic questions can be updated, and the difficult items can be reworded based on the reviewers' remarks [21]. Since the construction of the scale of measurement items was primarily based on an exhaustive analysis of the literature and detailed reviews by numerous industry experts, professionals, and academics, the content validity of the proposed questionnaire was satisfied in this study. Five specialists with more than 10 years of experience in construction projects and with an academic background in questionnaire evaluation were consulted to analyze the questionnaire and make revisions that best match the Iraq conditions.

IV. PILOT STUDY

A pilot study is a small experimental attempt or study that applies to a part of the study population whose characteristics are usually similar to those of the study population [22, 23]. According to [24] the pilot research is a test run for the questionnaire, which includes detecting any vague questions, testing the phrasing of questions, testing the data collection technique, etc. The most important challenge that the study faced is the difficulty of communicating with experts directly due to the covid-19 related quarantine, so finishing this stage took a long time. The sample size for the pilot study is preferably between 30 and 50 [25]. In this research, 35 respondents were selected, the questionnaire was distributed to them, and the answers were collected, organized, and prepared for conducting the required statistical tests. The pilot study was applied to respondents with characteristics similar to the total sample, and after ensuring the validity of the research tool, the

questionnaire was distributed to the total sample without including the pilot sample.

V. PILOT STUDY TESTS (VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY)

Using a good research tool is one of the most critical factors to reach acceptable and valuable results. According to [26], one of the researcher's key goals is to develop his research tool which should be characterized by three traits, i.e. it should be meaningful, accurate, and efficient. The data collected from the pilot study were subjected to the required tests using the statistical analysis software Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 26 to verify the extent of validity and reliability.

A. Statistical Validity

The validity of an instrument refers to how well it measures what it is supposed to measure [27]. This test is used to find the correlation coefficients between each item in a specific portion and the part as a whole [28]. Each of the 22 items of the questionnaire was assigned a different symbol from F1 to F22. Table II shows the results of the internal validity test for the second part of the questionnaire titled Possible Reasons for Poor Cost Control in Construction Projects.

B. Statistical Reliability (Cronbach's Alpha)

The value of the Cronbach's alpha constant, which ranges from 0 to 1, is an essential technique of calculating reliability. The closer it is to 1, the higher the degree of reliability [29]. Table III shows the classification of reliability according to the value of the Cronbach's alpha coefficient.

After implementing the Cronbach's alpha test, the results were compared with the standard values mentioned in Table II and they were found to be within excellent limits with a value of 0.902 which confirms the reliability of the used questionnaire.

TABLE II. ITEM CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS

Item	Correlation coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)
F1	0.479**	0.000
F2	0.427**	0.000
F3	0.484**	0.000
F4	0.629**	0.000
F5	0.620**	0.000
F6	0.506**	0.000
F7	0.577**	0.000
F8	0.604**	0.000
F9	0.252**	0.002
F10	0.577**	0.000
F11	0.512**	0.000
F12	0.365**	0.000
F13	0.519**	0.000
F14	0.696**	0.000
F15	0.379**	0.000
F16	0.586**	0.000
F17	0.707**	0.000
F18	0.736**	0.000
F19	0.665**	0.000
F20	0.660**	0.000
F21	0.684**	0.000
F22	0.193*	0.017

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)
 **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

TABLE III. RELIABILITY CUT-OFF VALUES [30]

Cronbach's alpha	Degree of reliability
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$	Good
$0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$	Acceptable
$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$	Questionable
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$	Poor
$0.5 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

VI. QUESTIONNAIRE DISTRIBUTION

Convenience sampling was adopted. Convenience sampling is a sort of nonprobability sampling in which respondents are chosen because they are "convenient" data sources for researchers [31]. The questionnaire form was distributed to the intended sample, consisting of 180 individuals, and 164 forms were answered (response rate 91%). After checking, 14 forms were found to be incomplete, resulting in a total of (150) forms which were processed. Professionals in Iraqi construction projects (architects, civil engineers, mechanical engineers, electrical engineers, and other professionals with associated specialty) were included in the research population. The questionnaire was distributed manually in paper form through group interviews with specialists from different workplaces and through an electronic link. Questionnaire completion took about 7 to 9 minutes. Table IV shows the statistical analysis of the characteristics of the target sample.

VII. QUESTIONNAIRE DATA ANALYSIS

The quantitative method was used. Quantitative data analysis methods can be beneficial to a researcher attempting to extract meaningful conclusions from a vast body of qualitative data. The key advantage is that a quantitative analytical technique allows the separation of many confounding elements that can obfuscate the core qualitative conclusions [32].

TABLE IV. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE TARGET SAMPLE

Question	Categories	Percentage
Concerned party percentage of respondents	Contracting companies	51%
	Owner	42%
	Consulting offices	7%
Respondents' educational level	Diploma	1%
	Bachelor's degree	56%
	Master's degree	38%
	Ph.D.	3%
	Other	2%
Respondents specialization	Architects	1%
	Civil engineers	85%
	Electrical engineers	5%
	Mechanical engineers	3%
	Others	6%
Current field of respondents	Designers	5%
	Consultants	8%
	Project managers	19%
	Contractors	4%
	Site engineers	53%
	others	11%
Respondents' experience	Less than 5 years	27%
	5-10 years	33%
	11-15 years	23%
	16-20 years	8%
	More than 20 years	9%

Statistical approaches play an essential part in most studies that rely on quantitative data analysis by converting ordinal to numeric data using a rating scale (i.e. the 5-point Likert scale). IBM SPSS was used to analyze the data. The Relative Importance Index (RII) method was employed to determine the respondents' rankings of items/variables. RII can be calculated by:

$$RII = \frac{\sum W}{(A * N)} \quad (1)$$

$$RII = \frac{5(n_5)+4(n_4)+3(n_3)+2(n_2)+n_1}{5(n_5+n_4+n_3+n_2+n_1)} \quad (2)$$

where W is the weight given to each component by the respondents (ranging from 1 to 5), A represents the most significant weight (which equals to 5), and N is the total number of people who took part in the survey. The RII value ranges from 0 to 1 (0 not inclusive). The higher the RII value, the more significant the attribute's impact. RII, on the other hand, does not take into account the relationships between the various elements. Table V shows the details of the statistical analysis of the second part of the questionnaire. The results indicated that "Weakness in keeping up with the use of modern concepts, methods, and technologies" is the highest cause of weakness to control costs in construction projects according to specialists' point of view with RII=80.00, mean=2.00, SD=0.82. The follow-up and use of the world's continuous development in administrative and technical tools related to project cost management has a significant role in solving most of the problems facing this process and shortening the time for the relevant parties. This study is in agreement with the findings in [9,11]. "Delay in receiving the amounts due for work done from the owner" came second with RII=78.81, mean=2.06, SD=0.96. This reason falls outside the control of the implementing party and hinders the good management of project costs, but sometimes this delay may be based on problems or weaknesses in the data provided by the contractor. This result is in agreement with [18].

TABLE V. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE SECOND PART OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE

Item	Mean	Std. deviation	RII	Rank
Weakness in keeping up with the use of modern concepts, methods, and technologies	2	0.82	80	1
Delay in receiving the amounts due for work done from the owner	2.06	0.96	78.81	2
Fluctuations in market prices	2.11	0.9	77.88	3
Lack of knowledge and inefficient use of currently available tools and technology	2.23	0.85	75.5	4
Security situation in the country	2.24	0.91	75.23	5
Poor planning and scheduling and not dividing work items in a way that helps tracking costs easily	2.4	1.09	72.05	6
Failure in the decision-making process due to various reasons	2.46	0.85	70.86	7
Involving inexperienced executive staff in terms of cost and low labor productivity	2.46	0.91	70.73	8
Changes made by the owner	2.5	0.91	69.93	9
Poor management of site data and not accurate documentation	2.56	1.08	68.74	10
Inadequate analysis of cost data to ensure a better benefit in the control process	2.62	0.98	67.68	11
Lack of progress in measuring work properly	2.62	1.03	67.68	12
Failure to prepare an appropriate purchase plan	2.62	1.06	67.68	13
Insufficient information needed to achieve cost control	2.65	0.95	67.02	14
Low labor productivity	2.68	0.96	66.49	15
Poor communication and transfer of information and data between the concerned parties	2.7	0.99	66.09	16
Inaccurate estimation of quantities	2.72	1.04	65.56	17
Changes resulting from design errors	2.81	0.93	63.71	18
Not clearly specifying the type of data and information required	2.85	0.98	63.05	19
Excessive waste of materials on the site	2.89	1.06	62.12	20
Unclear contract documents (contracting details, technical specifications, general and special requirements)	3.01	1.1	59.74	21
Lack of a fixed and specific method in the process of making measurements for real work	3.05	1.08	59.07	22

The ranked third reason for the poor cost control is "Fluctuations in market prices" with RII=77.88, mean=2.11, SD=0.90. It is a problem that frequently occurs in the construction sector in Iraq due to the country's fluctuating economic conditions and negatively affects the performance of construction projects. Also, this result is in agreement with what was stated in [14, 18]. The fourth reason is "Lack of knowledge and inefficient use of currently available tools and technology" (RII=75.50, mean=2.23, SD=0.85). This result is somewhat consistent with the first result, which indicated the weakness of keeping pace with modern technologies, as the current technologies are insufficient and need to be developed. This result is in agreement with [13, 14]. The fifth reason for poor cost control is the "Security situation in the country" with RII=75.23, mean=2.24, SD=0.91. This is actually and negatively reflected on the performance of construction projects in general and not only on the cost performance. The top 5 reasons for the poor cost control appear to be reasonable and commensurate with the problems that Iraqi building projects face. The two lowest-ranking reasons are "Unclear contract documents (contracting details, technical specifications, general and special requirements)" and "Lack of a fixed and specific method in the process of making measurements for real work".

VIII. CONCLUSION

According to the opinions of specialists in the field of the Iraqi construction sector, construction projects mainly need to develop in the field of knowledge by adopting the most modern, at a global level, techniques in this field to solve multiple problems, including cost overruns. Also, there is a need for real solutions related to financing. Specifically concerned with addressing the problem of late payments allocated to projects, which impede the progress of projects. On the other hand, there is an urgent need to address the issue of market prices and reduce price fluctuations that occur at various times in the Iraqi market and negatively affect the cost

of construction projects. Cadres of the public and private sectors need continuous education and updating in order to keep pace with the most prominent developments in the field of construction. Finally, the general security situation of any country is directly reflected in the performance of its construction projects. The data indicate that cost overruns can be minimized. It is evident from the fact that most of the factors mentioned in each of the problems is caused by human incompetence and therefore can be removed to a large extent. Good management strategies may influence this situation more favourably than any other treatment and can have both short and long term effects. Also, most indicators require the presence of specialized systems and trained cadres to use them for the purpose of reducing the problem of cost overruns. Therefore, striving towards automating cost control operations will be very beneficial.

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Evaluating the Efficiency of Finance Methods in Residential Complex Projects in Iraq

Alaa S. Khameesa
Department of Civil Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
dr.alaa@bauc14.edu.iq

Meervat R. Altaay
Department of Civil Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq

Abstract-Financial funding of a construction firm plays an important role in all aspects of the process development. It has been noted that financial crises have a direct impact on the construction industry. The Iraqi government, whether locally or globally, has faced a severe shortage of financing which has resulted in incomplete projects. Due to the financial crisis that Iraq went through which led to the suspension of many residential complex projects and the difficulty of the use of public financing methods, we researched the private financing (public-private partnership) methods instead of public financing methods in residential complex projects implementation. This study verified the financial problems and the factors that relate to the possibility of their occurrence with the use of a questionnaire that was designed and distributed to professionals in the field. Arbitration of the questionnaire, pilot study, questionnaire distribution, and statistical tests were conducted. The T-test (paired samples T-test) was used to find out if there are differences between the public and private financing methods. The results showed that the private financing (public-private partnership) methods, under the current conditions in Iraq, are better than the public financing methods.

Keywords-finance methods; residential complex projects; paired samples t-test; Iraq

I. INTRODUCTION

Many previous studies have criticized the public financing methods. Their issues include the completion of the project on time, the completion within budget, delay in payment of contractor entitlements, clear roles and responsibilities for project participants, errors and inconsistencies in the contract document, etc. The concept of Public-Private Partnership (PPP) is relatively new to residential complex projects for the Iraqi government since the construction of residential complexes is the responsibility of the Iraqi government which uses public financing methods. Due to the high cost of residential complex projects in recent years, PPP schemes have become popular in the global construction market. By implementing them, governments are able to put projects on the right track without worrying themselves too much about raising funds [1]. PPP can be defined as the contractual agreements between a private party and a part (or all) of the government. Under this contract, the private party agrees to perform certain functions or activities which are considered a public responsibility.[2].

A PPP project includes many important contractual arrangements between the participants. It is a complex network of relationships that includes multiple parties and their formal relationships are defined by contracts. The basic rationale for establishing partnerships is that both public and private sectors have unique characteristics that provide them with advantages in specific aspects of the service or project delivery. The most successful partnership arrangements are built on the strengths of both sectors to establish complementary relationships [3]. The concept of PPP has been around for centuries in Europe and the United States while it has been a recent development in other parts of the world. PPP as a concept originated in the UK and its early development was primarily driven by the need for new investments and financing possibilities to provide and deliver public sector assets and services [4]. Common reasons for the discontinuation of projects are insufficient project preparation, inadequate funding, lack of administrative/legal procedures, inflation, variance in project scope, political factors, client's death, conflicts, and incompetence of the project manager. In addition, the lack of strong government control and monitoring management is a key factor contributing to the causes of discontinuation projects [5]. Table I represents a set of success and failure factors in the use of financing methods collected from previous studies.

II. QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN

All necessary information was collected, reviewed, and formalized based on literature review, personal observations, and interviews with experts in the topic.

A. Part I (General Information)

This part contains general information about the participant (name, age, gender, ministry name, and sector of work), as well as classifications of educational qualifications, specializations, employment positions, and work experience.

B. Part II (Evaluating the Efficiency of Public Financing)

This section contains a list of 32 factors that can occur when using public funding related to project completion in time, cost, quality, quality of communication between project parties, experience and skill needs, government guarantee, and quality of service. Regulatory and legal framework, capital strength, project financing, ability of the contractor to deal with

a large number of projects at the same time, etc. It was constructed using the 5-point Likert scale (very high, high, medium, week, very week) design [18]. The respondents answered based on their experience.

TABLE I. PROJECT SUCCESS AND FAILURE FACTORS

Most Important factors	Ref.
Competition and innovation Improved operation and maintenance quality The government is able to focus on core public sector responsibilities	[7]
Financial and capital strength Technical ability Personnel reserve Project management capacity Ability of communication	[10]
Favorable legal and political support Financial allocations are available Favorable social support Economic viability Reliable contractual arrangement Government guarantee and experience	[8]
Avoid claims and consequent disputes Avoid cost and time overruns Consider concurrent delays Project progress can be efficiently tracked throughout the project lifecycle	[6]
Appropriate concessionaire contracts and agreements Clear definition of project scope and documentation The roles and responsibilities are clear Accelerated permitting and approvals Appropriate risk distribution	[12]
Appropriate risk distribution and risk sharing Competition and innovation Commitment of public and private sector Thorough and realistic cost and benefit assessment Feasibility of technical project Good governance Favorable legal framework	[13]
On time financing Public organizations' cooperation Commitment Quality of team intercommunication	[15]
Public awareness and support Public safety A multidisciplinary and multinational team Quality control and supervision Financial market availability Appropriate project identification	[17]
Adequate funding throughout the project Multidisciplinary/competent project team Contractor's good combination of expertise of design and techniques of building Strong design of contractor and construction management capability Comprehensive contract documentation Contract form and contract period	[14]
Quality improvement Shorter project durations Reduction of long term projects	[16]
Shortest construction and concession period Most cost-effective and innovative solution Safest for construction Strongest financial commitment	[11]
Legal and economic framework can be developed. Political stability-opposed/support Right project can be selected Feasibility study Financial capability Compatibility/complimentary skills	[3]

C. Part III (Evaluating the Efficiency of Private Financing - PPP)

This part contains a list of 32 factors that can occur when using PPP related to completion of projects in cost, time, quality. Appropriate risk distribution and risk sharing, quality of communication between parties of project, skill needs and experience. A comprehensive cost-benefit assessment with good project cost, experienced management, skilled and multidisciplinary staff, speed in permits and approvals, project financing, ability of the contractor to deal with a large number of projects at the same time, etc. It also was created with the use of the pentatonic scale design [18].

III. QUESTIONNAIRE ARBITRATION

Questionnaire arbitration is a good approach for professionals to see if the questionnaire is measuring what they want to measure [19]. According to the arbitration, the questionnaire was submitted to a group of contracting experts in funding of residential complexes projects. The previously developed questionnaire was presented to them, their comments and recommendations were taken into account, and the amendments they mentioned were approved.

IV. PILOT STUDY

Before collecting the final data from the entire sampled population, a pilot study was conducted. The pilot study is a trail run for the questionnaire, which includes checking the wordings of questions, clarifying ambiguous questions, and evaluating the techniques that were utilized to collect the data [20]. The study's main purpose is to identify obstacles and concerns that are more ambiguous than others, allowing remedial actions to be taken and the testing process to be improved. The sample size of the pilot study should range from 30 to 50 respondents. The sample size of the current study was 40.

V. STATISTICAL VALIDITY OF THE PILOT STUDY

According to [21], validity refers to how well an instrument measures what it is designed to measure. Validity has many different aspects and methods of evaluation. There are two statistical tests that should be performed, namely internal validity and external validity (Figure 1). They are used to ensure the questionnaire's validity. The tests of statistical validity were conducted with the data obtained from the pilot study. The tests included in the statistical validity of the pilot study were conducted with IBM SPSS V.26.

Fig. 1. Statistical validity tests of the pilot study.

A. Internal Validity

The questionnaire's internal validity is the first statistical test used to determine its validity. It is done by computing the correlation coefficients between each item in one field and the entire field [22]. Table II shows the results.

TABLE II. SPEARMAN'S RHO CORRELATION FOR EVALUATING THE EFFICIENCY OF PUBLIC FINANCE IN PILOT DATA

Spearman's Rho	Item	Correlation coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)	Item	Correlation coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Pf 1	0.619**	0.000	Pf17	0.685**	0.000
	Pf 2	0.605**	0.000	Pf 18	0.705**	0.000
	Pf 3	0.624**	0.000	Pf 19	0.403**	0.000
	Pf 4	-0.159*	0.044	Pf 20	0.161*	0.042
	Pf 5	-0.175*	0.027	Pf 21	0.650**	0.000
	Pf 6	0.183*	0.021	Pf 22	0.649**	0.000
	Pf 7	0.301**	0.000	Pf 23	0.554**	0.000
	Pf 8	0.380**	0.000	Pf 24	0.665**	0.000
	Pf 9	0.411**	0.000	Pf 25	-0.469**	0.000
	Pf 10	0.567**	0.000	Pf 26	0.676**	0.000
	Pf 11	0.563**	0.000	Pf 27	-0.240**	0.002
	Pf 12	0.568**	0.000	Pf 28	0.613**	0.000
	Pf 13	0.643**	0.000	Pf 29	0.648**	0.000
	Pf 14	0.703**	0.000	Pf 30	0.544**	0.000
	Pf 15	0.508**	0.000	Pf 31	0.561**	0.000
	Pf 16	0.609**	0.000	Pf 32	0.634**	0.000

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)
 **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The correlation coefficients ranged from 0.159 to 0.705, and the P-values were all less than 0.05, indicating that all items are consistent and have the validity to measure what they were put up to measure. Table III shows the values of the Spearman correlation coefficient for the evaluation of the efficiency of private financing (PPP).

TABLE III. SPEARMAN'S RHO CORRELATION FOR EVALUATING THE EFFICIENCY OF PPP IN PILOT DATA

Spearman's Rho	Item	Correlation coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)	Item	Correlation coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)
	PPf 1	0.744**	0.000	PPf 17	0.778**	0.000
	PPf 2	0.695**	0.000	PPf 18	0.729**	0.000
	PPf 3	0.741**	0.000	PPf 19	0.441**	0.000
	PPf 4	-0.289**	0.000	PPf 20	-0.198*	0.012
	PPf 5	-0.248**	0.002	PPf 21	0.698**	0.000
	PPf 6	0.292**	0.000	PPf 22	0.725**	0.000
	PPf 7	-0.165*	0.037	PPf 23	0.673**	0.000
	PPf 8	0.544**	0.000	PPf 24	0.765**	0.000
	PPf 9	0.565**	0.000	PPf 25	-0.441**	0.000
	PPf 10	0.748**	0.000	PPf 26	0.779**	0.000
	PPf 11	0.722**	0.000	PPf 27	-0.405**	0.000
	PPf 12	0.792**	0.000	PPf 28	0.705**	0.000
	PPf 13	0.763**	0.000	PPf 29	0.733**	0.000
	PPf 14	0.752**	0.000	PPf 30	0.570**	0.000
	PPf 15	0.669**	0.000	PPf 31	0.719**	0.000
	PPf 16	0.731**	0.000	PPf 32	0.675**	0.000

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)
 **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The correlation coefficients ranged from 0.165 to 0.792, and the P-values were all less than 0.05, indicating that all items are consistent and have the required validity

B. Structural Validity

The structural validity was calculated by computing the correlation between a particular part of the questionnaire and the questionnaire as a whole [22]. Table IV shows the correlation coefficient between each field and the other fields of the questionnaire.

TABLE IV. SPEARMAN'S RHO CORRELATION COEFFICIENT BETWEEN THE QUESTIONNAIRE'S PARTS

Spearman's Rho	Part	Correlation coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Evaluating the efficiency of public finance	0.782**	0.000
	Evaluate the efficiency of PPP	0.881**	0.000

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)
 **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The correlation coefficients ranged from 0.782 to 0.881, and the P-values were all less than 0.05, indicating that all items are consistent and have the required validity.

VI. STATISTICAL RELIABILITY OF THE PILOT STUDY

A. Cronbach's Alpha Model

One of the most widely used indicators of reliability analysis is Cronbach's alpha. The questionnaire's reliability was calculated using Cronbach's alpha coefficient for each field and for the whole questionnaire. Cronbach's alpha coefficient value lies between 0.0 and +1.0. A greater value indicates a higher degree of internal consistency [23]. Table V shows the classification for the degree of reliability according to the value of the Cronbach's alpha coefficient.

TABLE V. RELIABILITY CUTOFF VALUES [21, 23]

Cronbach's alpha	Degree of reliability
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$	Good
$0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$	Acceptable
$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$	Questionable
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$	Poor
$0.5 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

The findings were found to be within acceptable limits. This result verifies the questionnaire's dependability. The Cronbach's alpha values are shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI. VALUES OF CRONBACH'S ALPHA

Part	Value of α	Reliability
Evaluating the efficiency of public finance	0.885	Good
Evaluate the efficiency of PPP	0.908	Excellent

VII. QUESTIONNAIRE DATA ANALYSIS

The questionnaire data were analyzed using a series of quantitative statistical techniques to obtain a thorough view of the opinions received from the Iraqi experience regarding to the subject of financing residential complexes. These statistical techniques will be explained below. Descriptive statistics is a statistical tool for summarizing, organizing, and simplifying data. The following descriptive statistics were used.

A. Central Tendency Measurement

A measure of central tendency (also known as a central location measure) is a summary measure that aims to describe a whole set of data with a single value that denotes the middle or center of its distribution.

B. T-Test (Paired Samples T-test)

Once the subjects being tested are the same, a paired samples t-test is performed because the two mean scores cannot be independent of each other [24-26]. In testing these samples, we analyzed the data by using the SPSS 26.0's paired samples T-test.

The hypotheses can be expressed in two forms that are mathematically comparable and express the same idea.

(H₀: μ₁ = μ₂) means that the paired populations are equal.

(H₁: μ₁ ≠ μ₂) means that the paired population are not equal.

Or:

(H₀: μ₁ - μ₂ = 0) means that the difference between the paired population is equal to zero.

(H₁: μ₁ - μ₂ ≠ 0) means that the difference between the paired populations is not zero.

where μ₁ is the mean of the population of variable 1, and μ₂ is the mean of the population of variable 2.

The data were processed with the SPSS 26.0. The result of the paired samples T-test can be seen in Table VII.

TABLE VII. RESULT FROM THE PAIRED SAMPLES T-TEST

Paired sample statistics					
		Mean	N	Std. deviation	Std. error mean
Pair 1	Private financing	101.03	160	15.773	1.247
	Public financing	95.01	160	13.539	1.070

Paired Samples Test									
		Mean	Std. deviation	Std. error mean	Lower	Upper	t	df	Sig. 2-tailed
Pair 1	Private financing - public financing	6.025	14.201	1.123	3.808	8.242	5.367	159	0.000

The hypothesis states that the effectiveness of the first method is equal to that of the second. Since the average effectiveness of the second method is higher than the first method's, the second method is considered better.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this study, the factors that evaluate the efficiency of public and private financing were collected from previous

studies and an open questionnaire survey. The study population was relevant to the subject and the questionnaire was designed and arbitrated by experts. Statistical methods were used in data analysis such as descriptive statistics and T-test. Since the average effectiveness of the second method is higher compared to the first method, the second method is considered better. We can conclude that PPP methods are more efficient than public financing methods regarding the construction of residential complex projects in Iraq.

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Understanding the Seepage Behavior of Nai Gaj Dam through Numerical Analysis

Afsheen Bashir

US-Pakistan Center for Advanced Studies in Water
Mehran University of Engineering and Technology
Jamshoro, Sindh, Pakistan
afsheenbasheer@yahoo.com

Rabia Chaudhry

PhD Researcher/Expert in Geotechnical Engineering
Water & Power Development Authority
Punjab, Pakistan
rabiach100@gmail.com

Abdul Latif Qureshi

US-Pakistan Center for Advanced Studies in Water
Mehran University of Engineering and Technology
Jamshoro, Sindh, Pakistan
alqureshi.uspcasw@faculty.muet.edu.pk

Uroosa Memon

US-Pakistan Center for Advanced Studies in Water
Mehran University of Engineering and Technology
Jamshoro, Sindh, Pakistan
uroosamemon11@gmail.com

Naraindas Bheel

Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering
Universiti Teknologi PETRONAS
Perak, Malaysia
naraindas04@gmail.com

Abstract—This study presents the seepage patterns of earth-fill dams, using critical situations by employing the finite element approach. The Nai Gaj dam is 65km northwest of Dadu city in Sindh Province, Pakistan. In this study, the seepage through the main dam body and foundation is computed and simulated for different scenarios, i.e. maximum, normal, and minimum reservoir level. Seepage analysis was conducted by using the SEEP/W sub-program of GEO-SLOPE software. Dam design parameters and dam geometry data were used as input data to compute the unknown seepage. The seepage behavior of the Nai Gaj dam is shown in terms of net flow which consists of equipotential lines, streamlines, velocity vectors, and phreatic lines. The results show the seepage flux, maximum seepage, and exit gradient at different reservoir levels. The results show that the average flow rate at normal, maximum, and minimum reservoir levels are 1.49×10^{-7} cumec/m, 3.38×10^{-7} cumec/m, and 2.108×10^{-8} cumec/m respectively. In addition, the overall stability of the side slope of the dam is discussed.

Keywords—seepage; earth fill dam; phreatic line; SEEP/W; finite element modelling

I. INTRODUCTION

Pakistan is basically an agricultural country. The agriculture in Pakistan depends mainly on water irrigation. In this regard, many dams have been constructed in the past and some others are planned to be constructed in the future. Embankment dams are important and costly civil engineering structures that provide an essential infrastructure for the management of water [1, 2]. One of the critical aspects of dam design is the analysis

of stability and safety of the earth structure under various operating conditions. Dams are built for specific functions, i.e. storage of water for domestic use and irrigation, flood control, entertainment, fishing, and hydroelectric power generation. Design and construction of dams have to meet safety criteria and satisfy specific requirements. Stability of the dam against slope failure is an essential component for the design, operation level under all flood and drought circumstances [3, 4]. The estimated number of the earth fill dams around the world is 11192 [5, 6]. A review of historical dam failures indicates that nearly half of all failures of embankment dams have occurred due to seepage induced internal erosion. Detailed studies of seepage analysis through and beneath the dam body need to be parts of design, construction, and maintenance of any dam component. Most geotechnical studies related to dams involved seepage and stability analysis considering the pore pressure variations in unsaturated soil conditions. Seepage failures occur by rainfall or water infiltration that changes the distribution of pore water pressure. This effect leads to changes in the stress and affects the seepage process of the soil. An analyst must have a good understanding of seepage, its solutions, and the preventive measures for its monitoring. Finite element analysis is extensively used in the geotechnical studies for seepage and stability analysis considering the pore pressure variations. In case of dam seepage, failures occur by rainfall or water infiltration that changes the distribution of pore water pressure. This effect leads to changes in the stress and affects the seepage process of the existing soil. To make the dam safe, it is important to take great care on stability and seepage control

Corresponding author: Naraindas Bheel

while designing embankment dams. Embankment dams are generally constructed with various zones of materials such as two permeable shells and impermeable core in the middle [7].

The main reasons behind embankment dams' failures are seepage, hydraulic failures, piping through the dam body, and structural damage due to earthquakes [8]. Permeable materials such as gravel or coarse sand when used in dam foundation lead to heavy seepage [5, 9-11]. In the past, embankment dams mostly faced seepage problems. As water in the reservoir seeks the paths of least resistance through the dam body and its foundation, it may pose some hazards on the dam safety. Excessive seepage may lead to dam failure if it is not treated and controlled properly. If seepage flow can continue unhindered in appreciable quantities, then the seepage force may erode fine soil particles and wash them out causing piping failure of the dam or create uplift problems. Seepage, therefore, may be considered as one of the most common safety hazards for embankment dams. The basic problem the designers and operators face are to discern how seepage is affecting a particular dam and what measures, if any, must be taken to ensure that the seepage does not unfavourably affect the safety of the dam. This paper presents a case study of the Nai Gaj Dam and highlights the probability of pre and post seepage issues. The SEEP/W GEO-SLOPE software was utilized. It can work quite well on seepage analysis in homogenous and non-homogenous embankment dams [12]. Slope stability analysis confirms the safety of the embankment dam. Different loading conditions can be studied, for example end of construction, steady state, rapid draw down, and the earthquake loading scenario.

The aim of this study is to analyze the steady state seepage behavior of the dam foundation of the Nai Gaj Dam for various scenarios, namely normal, maximum, and minimum reservoir level conditions. In addition, the stability of the dam was analyzed.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

Nia Gaj Dam is located on the Gaj river in the Kirther mountain range. It is located 65km north-west of the Dadu city, Sindh province. The purpose of the Dam Project is to provide irrigation to agriculture lands downstream of the dam. The foundation rocks of this dam project are generally weak and

fragile. Sandstone and silty sandstone beds encountered at the core trench are weak and friable with jointings and open bedding planes [13, 14]. These rock characteristics may indicate poor rock conditions, low shear strength, and probability of increased seepage through the foundation [15].

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Initially, the cross section of the dam was drawn in CAD format and imported in SEEP/W as shown in Figure 1. The material zones in the dam are sandy gravel, random fill, central impervious clay core, sand filter, coarse filter, and drainage blanket. The foundation of the dam mainly consists of sandy siltstone. The dam is 59m high, 1137m long, having a maximum design water level of 56.6m with 10m crest width. The core has an upstream side slope of 1H:3V, and a downstream slope of 1H:4V. The upstream and downstream shoulders have slopes 1V:2.5H. Drainage features, including a chimney drain and horizontal drainage blanket below the downstream shell, have been incorporated in the design to relieve the pore water pressure within the dam body and to dispose the seepage water in a safe manner to prevent erosion and boiling. Numerical analysis was carried out on a typical section of the dam. A non-homogenous section is selected for the analysis of the response of complex materials by varying the water levels in order to understand and analyze the seepage phenomenon. The physical, mechanical and index characteristics of the materials were taken from the references mentioned in Table I. These material properties were assigned to the finite element model of the dam.

The generated FEM mesh is shown in Figure 2. Dirichlet and Neumann boundary nodes were assigned at the inlet and outlet boundary conditions [16, 17]. It was accepted that the discharge is gravity driven flow while the capacity changes due to water compressibility, soil structure compressibility, and changes in matric suction (i.e. drainage), in spite of the fact that soil structure compressibility is related to pore water pressure changes. Subsequently, all the stresses inside the domain are accepted as constant. No loading and unloading of soil mass is included. Once the required data were imported to the SEEP/W, it verified the mesh development (7047 nodes and 6913 elements). Therefore, now the model can be used for simulations and analysis of the results.

ZONES	MATERIAL	LEGEND
1	CLAY CORE	[Orange]
2	SANDY GRAVEL	[Dark Grey]
3	RANDOM FILL	[Red]
4a	WASHED GRAVEL	[Light Grey]
4b	D/S SLOPE PROTECTION	[Red with dots]
5R1-R2	RIP RAP R-1 (ZONE -5)	[Blue with dots]
6	SAND FILTER	[Green]
7	DRAINAGE BLANKET	[Purple]

Fig. 1. X-section of the Nai Gaj dam.

Fig. 2. Mesh formation for the selected non-homogeneous section.

Results are generated for the following scenarios: (i) normal reservoir level (150m), (ii) maximum reservoir level (177.5m), and (iii) minimum reservoir level (130m). The boundary conditions which are used in the analysis are:

- Dirichlet and Neumann boundary nodes are assigned at the inlet and outlet boundary conditions [17].
- Zero flux (Neuman) condition is considered as the boundary node at the bottom of foundation for the all the given conditions.

The results are analyzed in terms of development of net flows for different scenarios, along with velocity vectors, quantity of seepage value through the core and foundation of the dam for different scenarios, and exit gradient. In addition, the stability of the dam was determined based on slope stability analysis.

A. Fundamental Equations

In this study, finite element method is used for the modelling of the groundwater flow in porous media by utilizing the following differential equations to analyze the seepage through the body of the dam at its foundation. Equations are derived on the principle of mass conservation law [17, 18]. The partial differential equation (1) is used in SEEP/W:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} (K_x \frac{\partial H}{\partial x}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (K_y \frac{\partial H}{\partial y}) + Q = \frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

where H is the hydraulic head, K_x and K_y are the horizontal and vertical hydraulic conductivity respectively, Q is the discharge, t is the time θ -domain and volumetric water content.

The above equation is a two-dimensional and nonlinear 2nd order PDE and is used for transient flow. It is derived from Darcy's Law:

$$v = -K \nabla H \quad (2)$$

where:

$$\nabla H = \left[\begin{matrix} \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial H}{\partial y} \end{matrix} \right] \quad (3)$$

where v is the Darcian velocity, K is the hydraulic conductivity of the soil material, and ∇H is the hydraulic gradient.

Equation (1) is dependent on time, and tells that the flow that enters an elemental volume minus the flow leaving the

elemental volume at a point is equal to the volumetric water content at that point. If the volume of water that enters is equal to the volume of water that leaves at steady state situations, then the right side of (1) becomes equal to zero.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} (K_x \frac{\partial H}{\partial x}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (K_y \frac{\partial H}{\partial y}) + Q = 0 \quad (4)$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The material properties which are used in the selected dam sections were taken from past studies and from a feasibility report on the Nai Gaj dam [19]. The inherent material parameters used in the dam are presented in Table I. The mesh was generated by SEEP/W and got a no error report for further computations. Also, the given up- and down-stream boundary conditions were assigned. The physical and mechanical parameters of the materials during the time of construction were adopted. SLOPE/W then verified the development model and found no error in the generation of the numerical model.

TABLE I. INHERENT MATERIAL PARAMETERS OF THE NAI GAJ DAM [1, 19-23]

Dam component	Material	Unit weight (kN/m ³)	Cohesion (kPa)	Friction angle (deg)	Hydraulic conductivity (m/day)
			C	ϕ	
Foundation	Sandy siltstone	20.4*	12	29*	0.00063*
Upstream	Sandy gravel	21.5**	0	37*	86.4***
Downstream	Random fill	18.85*	0	34*	0.0263*
Downstream shell	Riprap	19.5*	0	34*	8640***
Core	Clay	18.85*	9.57	30*	0.000263*
Filter blanket	Sand filter	18.85*	0	36*	26.33*

The seepage analysis of the Nai Gaj dam and its foundation at different reservoir levels was conducted with the use of the SEEP/W. It is assumed that the downstream drain will drain out the seepage and no seepage will develop downstream. For this purpose, flow net has been drawn as shown in Figures 3-5 for the selected dam sections. It was found that if the reservoir is kept at 150m and 130m there is no pronounced seepage observed.

Fig. 3. Flow net of the selected section at maximum reservoir level (177.5m).

Fig. 4. Flow net of the selected section at normal reservoir level (150m).

Fig. 5. Flow net of the selected section at minimum reservoir level (130m).

TABLE II. CALCULATED SEEPAGE FLUX AND EXIT GRADIENT

	Upstream reservoir level (m)	Water head (m)	Seepage flux (cumec/m)
Foundation	177.5 (max)	177.5	1.29×10^{-7}
	150 (normal)	150	4.53×10^{-8}
	130 (min)	130	6.92×10^{-9}
Core	177.5 (max)	177.5	3.38×10^{-7}
	150 (normal)	150	1.49×10^{-7}
	130 (min)	130	2.106×10^{-8}

The exit gradient was calculated at the downstream toe of the dam for 3 reservoir levels, i.e. 177.5, 150, and 130 m (Table III). The factor of safety against piping is described as follows:

$$FS = \text{critical hydraulic gradient} / \text{exit gradient} \quad (5)$$

The value of the critical hydraulic gradient is taken as 1. A dam is considered as safe against piping, if the value of the

factor of safety is between 4 and 5. The results indicate that the values of factor of safety for normal, average, and maximum water level are 7, 6, and 5 respectively. This shows that the dam is safe against piping failure even at the maximum reservoir level of 177.5m. Table III shows that the exit gradient of the selected section was mostly found less than 1 for all the water levels which conforms the safety criteria of the dam. It further support the current design of the dam. From Tables II and III, it can be observed that both the exit gradient and seepage flux are functions of water level.

Generally, the stability of a slope at the downstream embankment is critical at steady state seepage condition. It is assumed that the steady seepage condition may develop when the reservoir is full at maximum retention level, i.e. at EL 177.5m. The phreatic surface is estimated using the flow net development by the SEEP/W program. Furthermore, to support the outcomes, deterministic slope stability analysis was

performed for different loading conditions, such as the end of construction and steady state seepage. The material properties used are mentioned in Table I and the results were discussed in terms of their factor of safety as shown in Table III. The computed FOSs at different loading conditions were further compared with the USACE standards [24]. It was noted that in slope stability analysis, the computed FOSs for different loading conditions are greater than the standard values which indicates safety of the side slopes of the dam as given in Table III.

TABLE III. EXIT GRADIENT AND FACTOR OF SAFETY AGAINST PIPING

Upstream pond level (m)	Exit gradient (m)	Factor of safety against piping
177.5 (max)	0.19	5
150 (average)	0.16	6
130 (normal)	0.14	7

TABLE IV. FACTOR OF SAFETY

Load	Slope	Static equilibrium condition	
		Required*	Computed
End of construction	Downstream	1.30	1.7
Steady state condition	Downstream	1.50	1.8

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, seepage analysis of Nai Gaj dam was carried out with the sub program SEEP/W of the GEO-SLOPE software. The flow rates of the seepage computed at the core of the dam at maximum (177.5m), normal (150m), and minimum (130m) reservoir level were found to be 1.49×10^{-7} cumec/m, 3.38×10^{-7} cumec/m, and 2.108×10^{-8} cumec/m respectively. It was observed that as the reservoir level increased, the seepage quantity also increased. For the three tested scenarios of the reservoir level, the value of the exit gradient was found to be less than 1 which confirms that the dam is safe against piping due to seepage. In addition, slope stability analysis shows that the dam is stable at the end of construction and at steady state seepage condition.

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Load Shedding in Microgrids with Dual Neural Network and AHP Algorithm

Le Thi Hong Nhung

Electrical and Electronics Department
HCMC University of Technology and Education
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
nhunglth@hcmute.edu.vn

Hoang Minh Vu Nguyen

Urban Engineering Department
HCMC University of Architecture
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
vu.nguyenhoangminh@uah.edu.vn

Thai An Nguyen

Electrical and Electronics Department
Cao Thang Technical College
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
nguyenthaian@caothang.edu.vn

Trieu Tan Phung

Electrical and Electronics Department
Cao Thang Technical College
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
phungtrieutan@caothang.edu.vn

Trong Nghia Le

Electrical and Electronics Department
HCMC University of Technology and Education
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
trongnghia@hcmute.edu.vn

Vo Tan Danh

Electrical and Electronics Department
HCMC University of Technology and Education
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
2080602@student.hcmute.edu.vn

Abstract—This paper proposes a new load shedding method based on the application of a Dual Neural Network (NN). The combination of a Back-Propagation Neural Network (BPNN) and of Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) aims to quickly predict and propose a load shedding strategy when a fault occurs in the microgrid (MG) system. The PSO algorithm has the ability to search and compare multiple points, so the proposed NN training method helps determine the link weights faster and stronger. As a result, the proposed method saves training time and achieves higher accuracy. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) algorithm is applied to rank the loads based on their importance factor. The results of the ratings of the loads serve as a basis for constructing the load shedding strategies of a NN combined with the PSO algorithm (ANN-PSO). The proposed load shedding method is tested on an IEEE 25-bus 8-generator MG power system. The simulation results show that the frequency recovery of the power system is positive. The proposed neural network adapts well to the simulated data of the system and achieves high performance in fault prediction.

Keywords—load shedding; ANN-PSO; BPNN; Dual Neural Network; AHP

I. INTRODUCTION

The increase in load consumption over time poses problems of power system stability. To ensure balance in terms of power, the power system must constantly change in size and structure [1]. However, in some unexpected cases such as serious problems in the power system leading to an imbalance of active power, it is necessary to have temporary solutions to restore the

equilibrium of the system. There are many solutions to this problem, as shown in [2], the self-healing ability of the power system depends on the load adjustment based on the voltage, frequency and governor characteristics of the generating sets. In [3-4], traditional load shedding methods are presented using under frequency load shedding relay to set the threshold of the shedding frequency. Currently, many new load shedding methods apply intelligent algorithms. In [5], the decision-making technique in load shedding is presented using the AHP algorithm. In [6], the application of the Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) algorithm is presented in optimizing the amount of load shedding power. In [7-8], the PSO algorithm is applied to optimize the inertia weights and train coefficients to get the optimal settings for the system and improve the voltage quality. In [9], a new adaptive load shedding method based on ANNs and proposed shedding power detection is presented. The ANN is used to estimate the total amount of active power that causes unbalance over the attenuation frequency period, equivalent from the rated value to the threshold value. In [10], the Genetic Algorithm (GA) is also applied to optimal shedding against voltage collapse. However, the GA algorithm has the disadvantage of a very long training time compared to PSO algorithm.

The above studies often use intelligent methods and algorithms individually. Therefore, the results obtained are usually satisfactory but not the best because of the limitations of each method and algorithm. The proposed idea is to combine methods together, thereby using the advantages of one method

Corresponding author: Trong Nghia Le

to overcome the disadvantages of the other method. In this paper, a new load shedding method is proposed based on the application of a dual NN system structured from a Bayesian NN (BNN) and a NN combined with PSO (ANN-PSO), thereby quickly predicting incidents and recommending load shedding strategies. In the structure of the proposed neural network, the BNN is responsible for classifying the fault types in the system to make a decision whether or not to shed the load. The NN combines the PSO with the task of determining the load shedding strategies based on the fault type and fault location in the system, so the proposed NN training method can determine the link weights faster and stronger. The training time is saved and the accuracy is high. The AHP algorithm is applied in this paper to rank the loads based on a hierarchical model of comparing their importance to each other. The ranking results of the loads are the basis for constructing the load shedding strategies of the ANN-PSO. The proposed method in the article helps solve the integration problem in the load shedding issue, quickly determining whether or not to shed the load and propose a strategy for shedding the load quickly.

The effectiveness of the proposed method is simulated and tested on the IEEE 25-bus 8-generator MG system. The simulation results show the efficiency of the power system in frequency recovery. The frequency value quickly returns to the allowable range when a fault occurs after the intervention of load shedding according to the proposed method. The proposed NN adapts well to the simulation data of the IEEE 25-bus 8-generator MG system and achieves high performance in fault prediction.

II. THE LOAD SHEDDING CONTROL STRATEGY CONSTRUCTION BASED ON THE AHP ALGORITHM

AHP algorithm is a method of weight calculating applied to multi-criteria decision problems with the idea of using knowledge and importance priority to rank objects in a system [11-13]. Here, the AHP algorithm is applied to determine the importance factor and rank load unit in the IEEE 25 bus power system. A hierarchical model of the importance comparison of load centers and loads to each other proposed by a system expert or operator is shown in Figure 1. The steps to implement the AHP algorithm are detailed in [5].

Fig. 1. The AHP hierarchical model includes load centers and load units.

The construction of a judgment matrix of the importance factor of the load centers and of the loads in each load center is presented in Tables I and II. The AHP algorithm is applied to calculate the importance factor of the load centers and the load nodes in each load center. The result and load's rank are presented in Table III.

TABLE I. JUDGMENT MATRIX OF LOAD CENTERS

	Load center 1	Load center 2	Load center 3	Load center 4
Load center 1	1	1	1/3	1/5
Load center 2	1	1	1/2	1/3
Load center 3	3	2	1	1/3
Load center 4	5	3	3	1

TABLE II. JUDGMENT MATRIX OF LOAD UNITS IN THE LOAD CENTERS

LC ₁	Load 1	Load 2	Load 4	Load 5
Load 1	1	1	1/3	1/2
Load 2	1	1	1/3	1/2
Load 4	3	3	1	2
Load 5	2	2	1/2	1
LC ₂	Load 6	Load 7	Load 8	
Load 6	1	1/3	1/3	
Load 7	3	1	1/2	
Load 8	3	2	1	
LC ₃	Load 9	Load 10	Load 11	Load 12
Load 9	1	2	2	1/2
Load 10	1/2	1	2	1/3
Load 11	1/2	1/2	1	1/2
Load 12	2	3	2	1
LC ₄	Load 14	Load 15	Load 16	Load 17
Load 14	1	2	2	3
Load 15	1/2	1	2	3
Load 16	1/2	1/2	1	2
Load 17	1/3	1/3	1/2	1

TABLE III. RANKING OF LOAD SHEDDING ACCORDING TO THE AHP

Rank	Load	Load center	W _{ij}	WL _{ci}	Weights of the importance factor W _{ij}
1	Load 1	LC ₁	0.14114490	0.10314687	0.014558655
2	Load 2	LC ₁	0.14114490	0.10314687	0.014558655
3	Load 6	LC ₂	0.13964794	0.12970033	0.018112384
4	Load 5	LC ₁	0.26270020	0.10314687	0.027096703
5	Load 11	LC ₃	0.13498819	0.24139951	0.032586083
6	Load 10	LC ₃	0.17249955	0.24139951	0.041641307
7	Load 7	LC ₂	0.33251593	0.12970033	0.043127426
8	Load 4	LC ₁	0.45501010	0.10314687	0.046932868
9	Load 17	LC ₄	0.10779910	0.52575330	0.056675733
10	Load 9	LC ₃	0.26997638	0.24139951	0.065172166
11	Load 8	LC ₂	0.52783613	0.12970033	0.068460520
12	Load 16	LC ₄	0.18671352	0.52575330	0.098165249
13	Load 12	LC ₃	0.42253588	0.24139951	0.101999954
14	Load 15	LC ₄	0.29222244	0.52575330	0.153636912
15	Load 14	LC ₄	0.41326494	0.52575330	0.217275406

Based on the results of loads' rank, the load that has a lower importance factor will be prioritized for shedding and vice versa. In detail, based on the results in Table I, the Load 1 will be prioritized for shedding first and Load 14 which has the highest importance factor will be shedding last. The implementation of load shedding is performed when the grid frequency attenuation is less than the allowable value and corresponds to the cases in which the MG operates in the island

grid separation mode or a generator failure requires implement load shedding. The process of implementing this load shedding strategy is carried out until the frequency recovers to the allowable range from 49.8Hz to 50.2Hz.

III. BACKPROPAGATION NEURAL NETWORK

The structure of the ANN network consists of 3 main parts, the input layer, the hidden layer, and the output layer. The signal will be the input of the network and will be processed to give the answer. The number of nodes of the layers and the network structure is chosen to suit each problem and training data. BPNN is a feedforward multilayer network using the back propagation error training algorithm proposed in 1986. It is used in many fields. Thanks to its ability to self-learn from errors, the network structure is very suitable for nonlinear problems. The flowchart of the training process of a BPNN can be seen in [14]. However, it also has some disadvantages such as low convergence speed and instability [15]. In order to solve the limitation BPNN the author in [16] proposed to combine it with the Genetic Algorithm (GA) to improve its structure. However, in GA, chromosomes exchange information with each other through crossover, which is a two-way information sharing mechanism with long loop times. PSO algorithm uses multi-point comparison search, so the proposed training method can determine the link weights faster, saving training time and achieving high accuracy [17].

IV. PARTICLE SWARM OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM

The PSO algorithm was proposed in [18]. In the field of power systems, algorithms are often applied in optimization problems [17]. With PSO, each element in the swarm is represented as a vector. In the NN structure optimization problem, each weight vector represents the ANN structure consisting of the weight values of all the nodes in the neural network. Each particle (element) remembers its individual best historical location, called P_{best} . For each iteration, the best global position G_{best} is found. Once the best global position is found, each element will move closer to its individual best position and best global position. After many iterations, this process finds a good network structure for the objective function, since the elements converge to a quasi-optimal solution. The speed and position of each individual are calculated as:

$$v_i^{k+1} = w \cdot v_i^k + c_1 \cdot \text{rand}_1() \cdot (p_{best_i} - x_i^k) + c_2 \cdot \text{rand}_2() \cdot (g_{best} - x_i^k) \quad (10)$$

After each cycle, the position of each individual will be updated as follows:

$$x_i^{k+1} = x_i^t + v_i^{k+1} \quad (11)$$

where w is the inertial weight, c_1 , c_2 are the acceleration coefficients, and rand_1 , rand_2 are random number between 0 and 1.

V. CONSTRUCTING DUAL NN COMBINED WITH PSO

Although NNs have strong non-linear learning and representation capabilities, a traditional NN does not take into account the uncertainties of the weights in the network and only obtain point estimates of the weights [19]. There are many

methods to reduce network complexity and increase efficiency in classification and forecasting. From [19], this paper utilizes a new cyclic NN called Dual NN, in order to classify system failure and release shedding strategy. In detail, the ANN network uses the Back Propagation (BP) algorithm to forecast power system whether load shedding or not. Another ANN uses the PSO algorithm to determine the load quantity needed to load shedding. We combine these 2 NNs to establish forecast value and load shedding in the power system.

VI. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

The proposed method is tested on the Microgrid IEEE-25 bus diagram. This test system consists of 8 synchronous machines with excitation types AC5A and AC8B [20], 25 buses, 25 transmission lines, 9 transformers, and 11 constant impedance loads. The total load demand is 393kW [21]. The diagram of the MG system is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Microgrid diagram of the IEEE 25 bus system.

The construction of the dataset to train the dual ANN is done with loads ranging between 50% and 100% of the load. For each load level, the power grid provides sample data with Island operation cases and generator failure cases. The process of training the dual ANN is shown in Figure 3. About load shedding cases, each different load level has a load combination and the sequence of shedding these loads which is ranked follows the priority based on the AHP algorithm. The load shedding process is conducted based on the results of load rank and is implemented until the frequency is restored to the allowable range. The summary results of load shedding strategies for different load levels are presented in Table IV.

Consider a case study at 95% load, assuming that when there is a DG5 generator problem, the load shedding combination is LS1: Load1, Load2, Load6, Load5, Load11, Load10. For a DG8 generator problem, the load shedding combination is LS3: Load1, Load2, Load6, Load5, Load11, Load10, Load7, Load4. Load shedding is conducted similarly for different generator problem cases. Recovery frequency value and frequency recovery time are within the allowable range.

Fig. 3. Supplemental flowchart for sampling and clustering load shedding using DNN.

The results of the implementation of load shedding strategies are presented in Table V. The comparison of recover frequency for the case with and without load shedding is shown in Figure 4. As the comparison result, when load shedding is not conducted, frequency will decrease deeply and out of the allowable range. Meanwhile, if the load shedding is performed according to the proposed method, the frequency is recovered to the allowable value ranges within 21s to 30s.

TABLE IV. STRATEGIES FOR LOAD SHEDDING ACCORDING TO THE AHP

Load shedding control strategy	Load
LS ₁	Load1, Load2, Load6, Load5, Load11, Load10
LS ₂	Load1, Load2, Load6, Load5, Load11, Load10, Load7
LS ₃	Load1, Load2, Load6, Load5, Load11, Load10, Load7, Load4
LS ₄	Load1, Load2, Load6, Load5, Load11, Load10, Load7, Load4, Load17

TABLE V. FAULT STATISTICS AND LOAD SHEDDING IMPLEMENTATION

Case study	LS	Recovery frequency (Hz)	Amount of load shedding power (kW)	Frequency recovery time (s)
Island operation	LS2	50.004	141.25	23.97
Island operation and loss DG1	LS3	50.034	197.84	22.08
Island operation and loss DG2	LS4	50.020	215.83	20.09
Island operation and loss DG3	LS3	50.026	197.84	28.08
Island operation and loss DG4	LS3	50.007	197.84	25.08
Island operation and loss DG5	LS3	50.066	197.84	30.08
Island operation and loss DG6	LS3	50.064	197.84	25.08
Island operation and loss DG7	LS3	50.065	197.84	23.08
Island operation and loss DG8	LS3	50.090	197.84	21.08

All the data collected through the simulation process were used for the training of the NN. The data consist of 459 training

samples and 123 input variables including 5 system parameters, i.e. line capacity, generator, load, frequency, and each bus voltage. The output of each training sample has 15 variables consisting of: yes/no recognition status (value 1 or 0), load shedding, and 4 load shedding strategies. All the data are processed and 2 separated datasets are established. The first dataset includes 459 samples, with 123 input variables and 1 output variable. The first dataset used BPNN with many different improved algorithms to forecast whether load shedding should be performed or not. The second dataset includes the cases of load shedding. This dataset consists of 167 samples, with 123 input variables and 14 output variables corresponding to the state of load shedding or not. The PSO-ANN is utilized to predict load shedding strategies. The result of the 2 networks will be combined to show the forecast of whether load shedding or not and the suitable strategy.

Fig. 4. Frequency characteristics at Bus 3 (a) without load shedding and (b) with load shedding based on the proposed method.

The training results in Figure 5. We can see that the result of the NN-PSO algorithm in Figure 5(a) has many advantages and is more suitable than the GA-NN with 95.59% testing and 99.74% training accuracy considering 40 input variables. The result (b) network of the improved algorithm gives good results. The Bayesian algorithm performs better with accuracy 100% in training and 96% in testing with 20 input variables. So, the BPNN will use the Bayesian algorithm to improve the network structure.

VII. DISCUSSION

The application of DNN combining PSO and AHP algorithms has supported the decision to load shedding quickly. That makes the power system able to keep the frequency in a steady state. The frequency of the system recovers to the allowable value. The AHP algorithm is applied to build load shedding strategies by ranking loads based on their relative importance.

Fig. 5. Comparison chart of the training results of the proposed method with (a) Comparison of ANN-PSO and ANN-GA, (b) Comparison of the improved algorithms in BPNN network.

The proposed load shedding method used two NNs. The first (ANN1), is responsible for determining whether or not to shed the load. The second (ANN2) is responsible for determining the load shedding strategies. The training results show that using a DNN to separate the information to process, achieves training results which exhibit good performance and increase the processing speed. Meanwhile, other methods [21] perform only one task, the one of shedding the load. This shows that the proposed method is more general. However, the problem is that when the load changes continuously over time, the construction of an adaptive NN, or a NN that learns and self-adjusts the network structure, will be the solutions to the above problem.

VIII. CONCLUSION

A new load shedding method based on the use of dual neural networks is proposed in this paper. A BPNN network is used to determine the severity of the failure. The result makes a yes/no decision to shed the load. The ANN-PSO network supports the proposal load shedding strategy. PSO algorithm is applied to optimize the link weights of the network, which makes accelerates the training and the accuracy of the network. The effectiveness of proposed load shedding was tested on the IEEE 25-bus 8-generator. It was shown that the proposed load shedding maintained the frequency stability in the power system.

In the future, the proposed load shedding method will be improved and along with solving the optimizing load shedding power problem, it will also reduce economic losses.

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Critical Factors Influencing the Bid / No-Bid Decision in the Palestinian Construction Industry

Ibrahim Mahamid

Civil Engineering Department
Arab American University
Jenin, Palestine
imahamid@ymail.com

Abstract—The purpose of this study is to identify and rank the factors influencing the bid/no-bid decision according to their relative importance from the perspective of the contractors in the West Bank in Palestine. To achieve the study objectives, a questionnaire survey was conducted. The survey covered a randomly selected sample of 64 contractors involved in the construction industry in the West Bank. The questionnaire's structure is based on the related literature, the pilot study, and the feedback from local experts in the construction industry. A total of 32 factors that might influence the bid/no-bid decision were identified and considered. Then, the targeted population was asked to rank these factors according to their relative importance. The results indicate that the top five factors affecting a contractor's decision to bid or not include the financial stability of the client, the identity and reputation of the client in the industry, the promptness of the client in the payment process, the expected profitability, and the project's source of funding. On the other hand, the least affecting factors are the type of the project, client's requirements, taxes, laws and government regulations, and weather conditions. The paper provides a comprehensive understanding of the factors affecting the bidding decision. Construction parties and researchers could benefit from the results of this study.

Keywords—bids; bid/no-bid; construction; contractors

I. INTRODUCTION

The construction industry is a major business sector that provides necessary ingredients for the development of an economy [1, 2]. For instance, as an industry sector, construction contributes about 10% of global GDP and absorbs more than 7% of labor [3]. However, it is becoming more and more complex due to the huge number of parties involved in the construction process and of the sophistication of the process itself. According to [4], the construction industry is the business sector that faces most failures in comparison to other industries. This happens because it is too risky and full with uncertainties [5]. In Palestine, the construction industry plays a critical role in providing homes, infrastructure, and public facilities. It also plays a major role in absorbing the national workforce and in improving the Palestinian national economy as a whole. According to [6], the construction activities in Palestine absorb about 17.9% of national workforce. In 2011 and 2012, the construction industry accounted for 11.2% and 10.3% of the value added to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) [6]. However, many local construction projects report

poor performance due to reasons such as 21-4538_s_ETASR_V12_N1_pp8096-8100 shortage in skilled labor or materials, bad relations between the construction parties, shortcomings in bidding strategy, and lack of managerial skills [7].

Construction projects, public and private, are usually awarded to contractors via tenders. The bidding process involves the bid/no-bid decision which is crucial and associated with risks and uncertainties due to various factors that influence it [8]. The influencing factors might relate to the contractor himself, to the client, or to the project conditions and the general environment. Bidding decision problems are highly unstructured. Typically, contractors make their decisions based on their common sense or the rule of thumb which may lead to suboptimal decisions. This is why many researchers have been involved in the development of bidding strategy models. The objective of this study is to identify and rank the factors that might influence the bid/no-bid decision according to their relative importance from the perspective of the contractors in West Bank, Palestine. The next sections provide a summary of the previous studies conducted to identify the related factors, the research methods and the study results.

II. PREVIOUS STUDIES

The literature abounds with studies that have investigated the topic of bidding decisions and the relative strategy. Many of these studies focused on identifying the main factors influencing the bid/no-bid decision in construction projects. Authors in [9] concluded that the critical factors affecting the bidding decision in Saudi Arabia to be client financial capacity, prompt payments, project payment system, clarity of the work and specifications, and project cash flow. Authors in [10] conducted a study to identify the factors affecting the bidding decision in construction projects in Qatar, and found 10 critical factors. Authors in [11] revealed that bidding policy has a high impact on variation orders during the construction phase. Authors in [8] identified and ranked the factors that affect the bid/no-bid decision from the contractors' perspective. The factors are classified into 4 groups: (a) external environmental factors, (b) factors related to the contractor, (c) factors related to the clients, (d) factors related to contract and project characteristics. They found that the top affecting factors include the stability of the construction industry, the contractor's financial capability, the reputation of the client, and

Corresponding author: Ibrahim Mahamid

the financial value of the project. The author in [12] considered the bid/no-bid decision factors in Auckland with the utilization of face-to-face structured interviews incorporating a questionnaire. He concluded that bid/ no-bid decision making is very dependent on the location. He also indicated that the macro environment has a great influence on bidding decision. Authors in [13] reported a significant negative relationship between risk perception and bidding decision and a significant positive relationship between risk propensity and bidding decision.

Authors in [14] conducted a study to investigate and rank the critical factors influencing the bid/no-bid decision criteria and their importance in the Australian construction industry. They identified the 26 most common decision-making criteria and they accordingly grouped them into 5 categories, namely project, market, contractor, client, and contract. Using a questionnaire survey, they revealed that the most highly ranked factors are: client financial capability, project risk, project future benefits, profitability, and number of competitors. Authors in [15] stated that one of the critical decisions taken by contractors is whether or not to bid for a project, due to the complexity and uncertainty surrounding this decision, which is influenced by many factors. They conducted a study in Saudi Arabia to find out the key factors affecting the contractors' bidding decisions in construction projects. They concluded that the top 6 (out of 31) critical factors were: project size, project type, company strength, design quality, expected profit, and cash flow. Authors in [16] conducted a study to identify the main factors influencing contractors' bidding decisions in construction projects in Nigeria. They concluded that the most significant factors affecting the bid/no-bid decision are: financial capability of clients, availability of capital, and availability of material. Author in [17] conducted a study to identify the factors affecting the bidding and markup decisions of contractors, considering a total of 55 factors. The top 3 factors were the need for work, the number of competitors, and the amount of experience on such projects.

Authors in [18] indicated that the decision to bid is a complex activity that requires the consideration of several factors. These factors can be related to capability, time requirement, and cost implication. They performed a study to evaluate the factors related to time and cost performance to test their effect on the bidding decision. Structured questionnaires were used to gather data from construction professionals in both consulting and contracting firms. The study reported the reputation of the client as the most critical factor related to time performance that influences bidding decisions, while location and condition of the site were identified as the key factors related to cost performance. Thus, the reputation of the client, the location, and the condition of the site should be given the most priority by a contractor at the time of bidding. Authors in [19] investigated the factors affecting bid/no-bid decisions of international projects in Chinese construction projects. A total of 41 factors were identified through a literature review as having an impact on the bid decision. Ultimately, 9 main factors were identified as influencing the bidding decision, with contractor's capability and country risk of the host country, being the most important.

Authors in [20] investigated and ranked the critical factors influencing the bid or no-bid decision and their importance for the indigenous small building contractors within the Tanzanian construction industry. The 7 most highly ranked factors (among the 30 considered) are: availability of capital, financial condition of the client, project size, expected profit, project type, need of work, and current workload. Authors in [21] examined the effects of different factors on the success or failure of bids for infrastructure projects in Australia. They found that the most significant factors that increase the success chances of bid are: having a competitive advantage and a local partner and also not competing against a local company. They also concluded that the essential factors to be able to compete include: relevant expertise, resource availability, previous relationship with the client, and previous relationship with consortium members. Authors in [22] and [23] linked the delays in construction projects and bid award policy.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

Thirty two (32) factors that might affect the bid/no-bid decision were identified from the literature review and the feedback from local construction experts. The factors were tabulated in a questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed to evaluate the importance of the identified factors from the target population (contractors). The information was collected from the Palestinian Contractors Union (PCU). The survey was used as a tool to collect the data, and then the data were analyzed with the Relative Importance Index (RII).

A. Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire is divided into two parts. Part 1 includes general questions related to the respondent and company such as the respondent's role in the company, experience in the line of work, decision makers in the company, etc. Part 2 included the list of factors affecting the bid/no-bid decision in construction projects. These factors were categorized into 4 groups according to their sources, namely: (1) factors related to client characteristics, (2) factors related to contractor characteristics, (3) factors related to contract and project characteristics, (4) factors related to the general environment. The respondents were asked to identify the impact level of each factor on the bidding decision. Impact level is classified on a 4-point scale as follows: very important, important, somewhat important, and not important (a 4 to 1 point scale).

B. Study Population

The target population in this study is the total number of contractors with valid registration in the Palestinian Contractors Union (PCU) with grade 1, grade 2 and grade 3 (120 registered contractors). Equation (1) was used to calculate the representative sample size [24]:

$$n = n' / (1 + n' / N) \quad (1)$$

where n is the sample size of the population, n' is the sample size, which can be calculated from: $[n' = S^2/V^2]$, N is the total population (120 contractors), V is the standard error of sample population, equal to 0.05 for 95% confidence level, $t = 1.96$, S^2 is the standard error variance of population elements, $S^2 = P(1-P)$, maximum at $P = 0.5$.

The sample size for the contractors' population can be calculated from (1) as follows:

$$n' = S^2 / V^2 = (0.5)^2 / (0.05)^2 = 100$$

$$n \text{ contractors} = 100 / (1 + 100/120) = 54$$

which means that the minimum sample size needed for this study is 54 respondents.

The questionnaire was distributed to 80 contractors. The contractors were selected randomly from an available list obtained from the PCU. Sixty-four questionnaires were received (response rate = 80%). The respondents indicate that the bidding decision is mostly taken by the general manager of the company (92% of the cases) and sometimes by the project manager (8% of cases). Figure 1 shows the respondents' positions in their organizations. The distribution of the respondents' years of experience in the line of work indicates that 13.2% had less than 5 years of experience, 18.8% had between 5 and 10 years of experience, 45.9% had between 10 and 20 years of experience, and 32.1% had more than 20 years of experience. The distribution of project types that the respondents are involved in shows that 52% are involved in building construction projects, 18% are involved in infrastructure projects, and 30% are involved in both building and infrastructure projects.

Fig. 1. Respondents' position.

C. Data Analysis

The statistical tools of Microsoft Excel were used to analyze the collected data. The considered factors were ranked by the measurement of RII, which is calculated based on the importance level identified by the respondents. RII can be calculated according to (2):

$$RII\% = \frac{4 \times N_4 + 3 \times N_3 + 2 \times N_2 + 1 \times N_1}{4 \times N} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

where N4, N3, N2, N1 represent the number of respondents for very important, important, little important, not important and N it the total number of respondents. For example, the RII% of the "financial stability of client", which got these values: N4 = 33, N3 = 30, N2 = 1, N1 = 0 from the survey, is:

$$RII\% = \frac{4 \times 33 + 3 \times 30 + 1 \times 2 + 0 \times 1}{4 \times 64} \times 100\% = 87.50\%$$

The group index is calculated by using the average of factors under each group as shown in (3):

$$\text{Group importance index (\%)} = \sum_i^n X_i / n \quad (3)$$

where X_i is the relative importance index of factor i under the group and n is the number of factors under the group.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The factors under each group are ranked by the measurement of RII according to (2).

A. General Environment Factors

Table I shows the RII and the ranking of each factor under the general environment group from contractors' view. Seven factors are considered under this group. The results show that the top 3 factors are: economic environment (RII = 80.64%), political situation (RII = 77.27%) and probable number and identity of competitors (RII = 76.59%).

TABLE I. RANKING OF GENERAL ENVIRONMENT FACTORS

Factors related to the general environment group	RII%	Rank
Economic environment	80.64	1
Political situation	77.27	2
Probable number and identity of competitors	76.59	3
Inflation rate	69.21	4
Taxes	62.50	5
Laws and government regulations	58.47	6
Weather conditions	54.45	7

B. Factors Related to the Contract and Project Characteristics

Nine factors are identified under this group. Table II shows the RII and ranking of each factor under the contract and project characteristics group from the contractors' point of view. The results show that the top 3 factors are: size or project (RII = 82.19%), location of project and accessibility (RII = 80.88%) and adequacy of tender information (RII = 78.25%).

TABLE I. RANKING OF CONTRACT AND PROJECT CHARACTERISTICS FACTORS

Factors related to the contract and project characteristics	RII %	Rank
Size of project	82.19	1
Location of project and accessibility	80.88	2
Adequacy of tender information	78.25	3
Identity of consultant & designer	75.62	4
Contract duration	71.01	5
Complexity of the project	69.69	6
Time available for tendering preparation	69.69	6
Contract conditions	67.72	8
Type of roject	67.06	9

C. Factors Related to the Client Characteristics

Table III shows the RII and ranking of each of the 7 considered factors under the client group. The results indicate that the top 3 factors under this group are: financial stability of the client (RII = 87.21%), identity and reputation of client in the industry (RII = 86.15%), and promptness of the client in payment process (RII = 84.91%).

D. Factors Related to Contractor Characteristics

Table IV shows the RII and ranking of each of the 9 factors under the contractor group. The results indicate that the top 3 factors under this group are: expected profitability (RII = 83.80%), current workload (RII = 82.46%), and need for work (RII = 81.79%).

TABLE II. RANKING OF CLIENT CHARACTERISTICS FACTORS

Factors related to client characteristics	RII%	Rank
Financial stability of the client	87.21	1
Identity and reputation of the client in the industry	86.15	2
Promptness of client in payments process	84.91	3
Project source of funding	83.24	4
Previous experience of contractor with the employer	73.05	5
Type of client	72.4	6
Client's requirements	66.48	7

TABLE III. RANKING OF CONTRACTOR CHARACTERISTICS FACTORS

Factors related to contractor characteristics	RII%	Rank
Expected profitability	83.80	1
Current workload	82.46	2
Need for work	81.79	3
Classification criteria for the contractors	81.12	4
Strategy of the company	78.43	5
Availability of required cash	76.13	6
Availability of required resources (raw materials, labors, equipment)	74.41	7
Previous experience in similar projects	71.72	8
Pre-qualification requirement	71.05	9

E. Overall Ranking

The RII and ranking of the investigated 32 factors affecting the bidding decision in construction projects in the West Bank from the contractors' view are listed in Table V. The results show that the top 5 factors are: financial stability of the client, identity and reputation of client in the industry, promptness of the client in payment process, expected profitability, and project source of funding, whereas the least affecting factors are: type of project, client's requirements, taxes, laws and government regulations, and weather conditions. It can be noted that among the top 5 factors, 4 factors are related to the client characteristics group, while the 5th factor is related to contractor characteristics group.

1) Financial Stability of the Client

In general, financial stability of the client indicates his ability to meet debts as they fall due. Financial stability in construction leads to good cash flow for contractors during the project which implies that the contractor will be able to pay for labor, materials, equipment, and other expenditures. In contrast, instability of the clients' economic condition leads to payment delay which affects the contractor's financial abilities and might lead to poor project performance. This result is in line with the findings in [1, 8-10].

2) Identity and Reputation of the Client

A contractor seeks smooth performance for his project. His performance will affect his reputation in the industry. Therefore, clients with good reputation will encourage the contractors to take the bidding decision more comfortably. On the other hand, bad reputation of the client will make the bidding decision to be more difficult, since bad expectations, such as financial problems and delays, will come to mind along with the fact that this may affect the reputation of the contractor himself. This result is in line with the findings in [10].

3) Promptness of Client in Payment Process

Contractors take into considerations in their deals, the client's payment process during the project. It is very important for the contractor to have good cash flow conditions in order to continue the work smoothly. Therefore, promptness in payment of the client is considered as a very important factor that the contractors care about during their bidding decision. Clients that make payments on time will encourage contractors to deal with them and will facilitate their decision to bid. Conversely, delays in payments might lead to conflicts between construction parties which might affect the process of bidding decision making. This result agrees with [9].

4) Project Source of Funding

The source of funding of the project is one of the main factors that the contractors have to know before making their decision to bid. The source of funding may be a person, private institutions, governmental institutions, or donors. Each source has its advantages and disadvantages. Fund sources may differ in their financial stability, payment methods, and promptness. Moreover, contractors may prefer a specific source of funding over the others as they may have previous experience with it and this will significantly affect their bidding decision.

5) Expected Profitability

Expected profitability is a significant factor that affects the bidding decision. If the contractor feels that he will not achieve the expected profit, he probably will not enter the tender. The profit made in projects that the contractor experienced in the past could possibly forecast the possible profit that can be made from the proposed project. Usually, contracting companies submit for bids and opportunities that are expected to exceed the Minimum Acceptable Rate of Return (MARR). Normally, there is no need for contractors to submit bids when the expected profit is less than the targeted one. However, in some cases the contractors are forced to bid for projects that do not exceed the MARR due to reasons such as the need for work and to cover overhead costs. This result is in line with [14, 15].

TABLE IV. TOP FIVE FACTORS AFFECTING BID/NO BID DECISION

Factor	RII%	Overall rank
Financial stability of the client	87.5	1
Identity and reputation of the client in the industry	86.15	2
Promptness of client in payments process	84.91	3
Expected profitability	83.80	4
Project source of funding	83.24	5

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a total of 32 factors affecting the bidding decision in construction projects were identified and categorized in 4 groups. The identified factors were ranked according to the RII of the contractors' point of view in the West Bank in Palestine. Overall, the results indicate that the top 5 factors affecting a contractor's decision to bid or not are the financial stability of the client, the identity and reputation of the client in the industry, the promptness of client in payment process, the expected profitability, and the project's source of funding.

Economic environment, political situation, and the probable number and identity of competitors are ranked in the top 3

positions under the environment group. Laws and government regulations in construction and weather conditions are ranked in the bottom 2 positions as factors having a weak influence on the bidder's decision. Size, location, and accessibility of the project along with the adequacy of tender information are considered key factors affecting a contractor's decision to participate in tenders. Therefore, full and clear tender information should be provided by the owner and consultants to help contractors in taking the bidding decision. Contract conditions and type of project are ranked in the lowest 2 positions and have a weak influence on a bidder's behavior. The current workload and the need of work are identified as the top factors affecting contractor's strategy in bidding. Current and projected workload should be known to the contractor in order to be able to know whether to bid or not. The contractor doesn't want to exceed his capabilities because this might affect his performance and lead to negative effects in terms of delay and disputations with the owners. On the other hand, contractors with low current workload will bid for projects even though these projects may not achieve the expected profits or the MARR in order to cover the job overhead costs and the operating costs.

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AUTHORS PROFILE

Ibrahim Mahamid received his BSc in Civil Engineering from Birzeit University of Palestine in 2001, and his PhD in Construction Engineering and Project Management from Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Norway in 2011. He is currently the head and an associate professor at the Civil Engineering Department, Arab American University, Palestine. His research interests include construction engineering and surveying.

The Dynamics of the Radiated Field Near a Mobile Phone Connected to a 4G or 5G Network

Delia-Bianca Deaconescu

Doctoral School of Electrical Engineering
Technical University of Cluj-Napoca
Cluj-Napoca, Romania
deliadeaconescu@yahoo.com

David Vatamanu

Nicolae Balcescu Land Forces Academy
Lucian Blaga University
Sibiu, Romania
davidvatamanu@yahoo.com

Andreea Maria Buda

Nicolae Balcescu Land Forces Academy
Politehnica University of Bucharest
Bucharest, Romania
budaandreea98@yahoo.com

Simona Miclaus

Dept. Communications, IT & Cyb. Def.
Nicolae Balcescu Land Forces Academy
Sibiu, Romania
simo.miclaus@gmail.com

Abstract-Characterizing the time variations of signals emitted by mobile terminals provides complementary information to health authorities, especially with the increase of frequency and energy of radiation towards millimeter waves. This experimental work aimed to quantify and classify the time variability of the electric field level measured at 10cm from a mobile phone connected sequentially to a 4th and 5th generation mobile network. Statistic analysis was performed on data from real-time spectrum analyzers, while self-similarity was computed by first recurrence plots of the radiated emissions, corresponding to five different types of mobile applications. Moreover, specificities to the communication standard and the type of application were identified.

Keywords-human exposure; 5G NR; LTE; mobile phone; field variability

I. INTRODUCTION

Massive mobile phone use has led to a tremendous data traffic increase in wireless networks. The fifth-generation (5G) of mobile communication technology, called New Radio (NR), has been proposed and developed to provide sufficient data speeds [1-2], as the 4th generation (4G) reached its limits. The core features of 5G technology are low communication latency, higher download speeds, higher cell density, ultrareliability, etc. [3]. Compared to the 4G mobile communication standard, called Long Term Evolution (LTE), that uses frequencies lower than 6GHz [4], the 5G NR standard uses two sets of frequency ranges: Frequency Range F1 (FR1) [5] has a maximum of 6GHz and an extension up to 7.125GHz, and Frequency Range F2 (FR2) from 24.25 to 52.60GHz [6]. The spread of such technologies has raised continuous public worries about the associated health risks. This study aims to examine and compare the time-variability of the radiated emissions on these networks.

4G LTE involves the use of Orthogonal Frequency-

Division Multiplexing (OFDM) and Single Carrier-Frequency Division Multiple Access (SC-FDMA) for downlink (DL) and uplink (UL) transmissions respectively [7]. Two frame types are delivered [8]: type 1 uses Frequency Division Duplex (FDD), while type 2 uses Time Division Duplex (TDD). In FDD mode, the 4G frame has a duration of 10ms and contains 10 subframes or 20 slots. In TDD mode, the frame has the same duration but is divided into 2 halves of frames with a length of 5ms. The minimum resource that can be used in UL and DL is called Resource Block (RB), which lasts 0.5ms, occupies 180kHz, and contains 12 subcarriers with a spacing of 15kHz [9]. The number of subcarriers and symbols differ for each RB, depending on the length of the cyclic prefix and the spacing of the subcarriers. The slots consist of 6 OFDM symbols in an extended cyclic prefix and 7 symbols in a normal cyclic prefix. 5G NR adopts, similar to 4G, the FDD and TDD techniques, while the signals are OFDM modulated. 5G uses a grid structure consisting of subcarriers in the frequency domain and OFDM symbols in the time domain [10]. For services requiring low latency and high frequencies, 5G supports subcarrier spacings of 30, 60, 120, and 240KHz, based on the subcarrier of 15kHz, whereas the subcarrier spacing in 4G is 15KHz [11]. In the time domain, OFDM symbols are used to construct slots, subframes, and frames. A frame is 10ms long and consists of 10 subframes. In the extended cyclic prefix, a slot consists of 12 OFDM symbols, while in the case of a normal cyclic prefix a slot consists of 14 symbols [12]. In the frequency domain, RB consists of 12 consecutive subcarriers. The access in 5G is based on a procedure that involves the detection of the Synchronization Signal (SS). Similarly to 4G, the SS in 5G consists of two signals: the Primary Synchronization Signal (PSS) and the Secondary Synchronization Signal (SSS). One of the biggest differences between 4G and 5G is that in 5G the SS blocks are transmitted as a directional signal with a high periodicity, while in 4G the Cell-specific Reference Signal (CRS) is distributed in frames

Corresponding author: Delia-Bianca Deaconescu

and is transmitted throughout the cellular network. An SS/PBCH block consists of a Physical Broadcast Channel (PBCH) and De-Modulation Reference Signals [13].

Like in 4G, random access in 5G is performed in 4 steps. At first, the User Equipment (UE) identifies the SSB within the SS Burst Set by using part of the time index carried by the PBCH and transmits a Physical Random Access Channel (PRACH). The 5G standard defines 13 PRACH formats, some with fixed and others with variable subcarrier spacings, that can fit into an NR slot. When a base station uses beamforming and different beams are applied to multiple SS/PBCH block transmissions, PRACH resources are associated with SS/PBCH blocks. In this way, UE transmits a PRACH [14] to randomly initiate the access. Therefore, the base station figures out which SS/PBCH block was received by the UE based on the received PRACH resources. In the next random access procedure, the base station can use transmission/reception beamforming directed to the UE.

A major improvement in 5G networks is the use of active antennas that can synthesize many beams pointing to different directions in continuous dynamic [15-16]. Beamforming is achieved by combining elements in an antenna array. Massive Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (Ma-MIMO) exploits the resources in the space dimension and enables users connected to the same base station to use the same time and frequency resources. This ability is defined by a 3GPP antenna port and is associated with a specific set of signals that allow the reuse of time-space resources of the channel. MIMO transmission is based on two different physical phenomena, polarization multiplexing and spatial multiplexing [17].

With the advent of 5G, one of the concerns of mobile technology users is related to the impact of radiation on human health. As the 5G NR standard is characterized by the use of different technical features (advanced TDD, beam-forming, beam steering, and Ma-MIMO), the classical method of measuring the emitted power density of a mobile device, as applied in 4G, cannot be used as such. In [18], a measurement method was proposed based on the evaluation of extrapolation factors associated with beam sweeping and TDD access mode, which can be used to estimate the instant maximum and the total power transmitted during a 5G radio frame. As 5G systems have unprecedented beam management flexibility, Maximum Permissible Exposure (MPE)-specific measurements are applied in unknown beam states. A solution to solve this problem was proposed in [19] using a beam-forming technique of UEs, concluding that using a UE capable to interact actively with the base station forces the system into a suitable mode for measurement. An Electromagnetic Field (EMF) level estimation technique was proposed in [20], derived from a base station tested in Single-User MIMO (SU-MIMO) coding. The efficiency of using the extrapolation technique for 5G technology was demonstrated. The number of multiplexed subchannels increased by using Multi-User MIMO (MU-MIMO) systems, and the spatial variation of the field could be exploited. This approach expands beam-forming and spatial filtering and allows the reuse of time and frequency resources with a low level of user interference. Optimization of the antenna array to obtain maximum performance in Line-of-Sight

(LoS) propagation condition was explored in [21], introducing a predictor factor for beam-forming losses and a way to use it in MU-MIMO systems. Moreover, grating lobes did not have a negative impact in MU-MIMO systems, while using larger inter-element spacings can be advantageous.

In [22], the first experimental measurement session made in a 5G site was presented. A five-step procedure was applied to assess in-situ the exposure of people due to emissions of 5G base stations. Additional factors such as the temporal duty cycle, the spatial duty cycle, and a TDD factor, were added to the description of the theoretical maximum exposure level following IEC Standard 62232: 2017 [23]. Furthermore, the levels of the E-field per resource element were measured and extrapolated to a theoretical maximum strength, while all reported values were below the ICNIRP reference level [24]. In 5G systems, beamforming may represent a health risk due to the momentary intense increase of the radiated power and the dynamics of these variations. So far, no scientific evidence has been reported to sustain this aspect. Some recent studies reported the possibility of reducing exposure by adopting the beamforming technique [25]. In [26], a scenario was considered to evaluate the impact of pencil beamforming, as a strong reduction in human exposure was observed when the tuning of traffic beams integrated localization information. When the localization uncertainty was lower, the synthesized beams were narrower, and the EMF exposure decreased. As stated above, EMF human exposure from cellular network devices originates from two sources: DL (base stations) and UL (own or a nearby person's handset/terminal). The actual power output of UE is set by the network at the lowest level, while the power transmitted by a base station varies with the area it serves. Over time, small cells increased the network capacities and lowered the power. It is reported that more than 70 million small cells will be installed worldwide by 2025, with one-third belonging to 5G systems [27]. Very few papers quantified the radiation emitted by a mobile terminal in 5G networks [28].

This study aims to highlight the time-variation peculiarities of the radiated field near a UE operating in either a 4G or 5G network. The objective was the comparison of the dynamics of the emitted field strength during the use of several mobile applications types, to expand the knowledge on the variation of the user exposure in time. The dynamics of RF exposure may be important in triggering biological responses at the cell membrane level [29]. Since a new approach is proposed for the increasing frequencies towards millimeter-wave range [30], paving the way to the experimental findings on the time-variability of the emitted radiation may represent a valuable complementary instrument in expo-dosimetry of new mobile technologies.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A Motorola smartphone model g 5G plus (XT 2075-3), connected sequentially to 4G and 5G in FR1, was used as the source of EMF exposure. In both connections, the location of the base station was the same related to the UE, at 75m distance, in non-LOS propagation as UE was located inside a building. The main characteristics of the UL signals (both networks used TDD) were: a) in 4G, the central frequency was $f_1=2.59\text{GHz}$ and the channel bandwidth was $BW_1=20\text{MHz}$, b)

in 5G, the connection used band n77 with central frequency $f_2=3.7\text{GHz}$ and channel bandwidth $BW_2=40\text{MHz}$. UE could deliver a maximum transmitted power of 23dBm for 4G and 5G. A line parallel to the UE upper edge was chosen to capture the radiated electric E-field level in far-field conditions of propagation near the phone, at a 10cm distance, where three E-field probes were located at the same distance between them. The following measuring instruments were used (Figure 1): three identical portable real-time spectrum analyzers type Spectran 5 Aaronia (HF 80120 V5 X model), three small PSB E1 E-field probes connected to the analyzers, and laptops.

Fig. 1. Measurement ensemble with electric field probes, real-time spectrum analyzers, laptops, and the Motorola One 5G phone.

The time-series data of emitted power were synchronously recorded and retrieved using Aaronia RTSA Suite Pro and Aaronia MCS Spectrum Analysis. Five mobile applications were used as sources of the EMF emissions on both networks: video call, voice call, file upload, file download, and streaming. Three measurements (R1, R2, R3) were performed on each mobile application and probe (P1, P2, P3). Each power level stream was recorded continuously for 25s and the sampling periodicity was 100ms. The spectral analyzer was set to a Real-Time Bandwidth Span (RTBW) of 88MHz, for 4G and 44MHz for 5G. After collecting the evolution of the signal spectrum in time, the channel power was calculated every 100ms, by:

$$P_{ch} = \frac{\sum_{f=F\text{ start}}^{F\text{ stop}} 10^{\frac{FFT\ Bin(f)}{10}}}{Wb} \quad (1)$$

where $F\text{ start}$ and $F\text{ stop}$ are the limits of the spectrum in the channel, $FFT\ Bin(f)$ is the power level of each of the spectral components (440 frequency bins were used), and window bandwidth Wb is the resolution bandwidth (195kHz for the 4G and 98kHz for the 5G). Once the power levels were determined, the E-field strengths in air, at 10cm from the UE and their time-evolution was calculated, using the field probe calibration files.

Based on these time series of E-field strength values, the descriptive statistics of field levels per each emission type were calculated and represented in Poincare plots for all 90 situations (5 mobile applications \times 2 communication standards \times 3 field probes \times 3 repetitions). The idea of capturing the self-similarity of the emission dynamics was implemented over the

time series in the form of a two-dimensional recurrence map called Poincare plots, which was applied for the first time in [31] for wireless local area network emissions. Standard descriptors were used to quantify the Poincare ellipse geometry: the ellipse axes, namely SD1 (short-term variability) and SD2 (long-term variability). SD1 represents the standard deviation of the distances of points from axis 1, and SD2 represents the dispersion of points along the axis. The areas of ellipses were calculated to emphasize the differences between the standards, which indicate the total variability and the SD1/SD2 ratios showing the randomness of the time series of the radiated E-field strengths. All the calculations were made to observe the differences in the electromagnetic time-print of the emissions between 4G and 5G.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mean, median and interquartile ranges (IQR) of the E-field strengths, measured in the air at the three points where the probes P1...P3 were situated can be seen in Figure 2. The outliers are represented in the emissions of the 5 mobile applications and can be observed as prominent during streaming and voice calls. Three repetitions are shown for each probe, each of the same color. Figure 2 contains 5 graphs corresponding to each mobile application marked on the abscissa. The first nine boxplots of each graph correspond to 4G, while the second nine correspond to 5G emissions. Upload in 4G presented the largest IQR in which E-field strengths spread. IQR is a measure of the variability around the median, indicating the range of the middle half (50%) of the data. All 4G transmissions during upload, download, and video call showed visible IQR intervals with few outliers. The 5G transmissions on these applications had multiple outliers, indicating that the E-field levels were too far from the central values. Another difference was observed between the 4G and 5G field-level spread for video calls. Voice call and streaming had outliers in both 4G and 5G, indicating that field variability is the highest during such activities. On the other hand, upload and video call in 4G caused more exposure than in 5G. Download and voice call cause lower exposure in 4G, while streaming showed similar exposure levels in both communication standards. However, in these measurements made 10cm from the phone, the field levels were far beyond the ICNIRP safety limits guidelines [24].

Figure 3 shows four characteristic Poincare maps of the time distribution of E-field strength values, measured during video call and file download in 4G and 5G. It can be observed that short-term variability is lower than long-term during an application running in 4G, while the variabilities are vice versa in 5G.

In each network, the radiated field level tends to have a certain scatter pattern for all applications, so the self-similarity in the time variation of the signals depends on the communication standard. Moreover, specificities could be observed between the type of mobile applications. In this sense, Figure 4 shows the ratios between the ellipse axes, the SD1/SD2 ratios, and the average of the results for all probes.

Fig. 2. Boxplots with outliers of E-field strength distributions for all mobile applications, all probes, and repetitions in 4G and 5G networks.

Fig. 3. Poincare maps of E-field strength near the phone in 4G (left) and 5G standard (right) during two applications.

The results of the ellipse axis ratio for R2 and R3, are presented for the 5 applications on both networks. The lowest ratio between short- and long-time variabilities was found in upload on 4G. The highest ratio between short- and long-time variabilities was found in the 5G download. For all 5G applications, the randomness of the emitted field was higher in the short- than the long-term, as compared to the respective 4G. The Poincare ellipse areas, shown in Figure 5, indicate that the largest variability of the radiated field corresponds to file upload and video call in 4G. Figure 5 indicates the average areas for two repetitions of the measurements. The total variabilities of the emitted fields were higher in 5G than in 4G for file download, streaming, and voice call. However, upload and video call in 4G had at least one order of magnitude larger variability than the other applications in both standards. As this specific feature confirms that file upload and video call led to the highest exposure levels in 4G, as deduced from Figure 2, it

can be concluded that these applications could be the most interesting for further biological dosimetry research. In 5G, the largest variabilities of the radiated field were observed for voice calls and file download. These high variabilities may be due to the higher field levels in 5G for these two mobile applications. Therefore, at least voice calls deserve special attention in future dosimetric studies devoted to the biological effects of 5G signals.

Fig. 4. Average ratios SD1/SD2 of E-field strength ellipses for all mobile applications in 4G and 5G in two repetitions: R1 (up), R2 (down).

Fig. 5. Areas of the Poincare maps of E field strength for all applications in 4G and 5G in two repetitions: R1 (up), R2 (down).

Previous findings, extracted by applying a different methodology but still based on real-time spectrum analyzers and small and sensitive field probes, emphasized specific features of the time variability of signals emitted by a 4G phone [28]. In line with those findings, this study allowed a step further in extracting the main peculiarities of the time dynamics of the emitted radiation, by comparing the 4G and 5G sub-6 GHz band networks using the same phone model. The novelty of this research was the approach of a complementary characterization of human exposure by the energy fluence rate adapted to the GHz frequency range. Based on this quantity, it was shown that a prediction is possible based on differentiating chaotic behavior from true randomness of 4G and 5G emitted signals evoked by recurrence quantification.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed to identify the differences in the time variability of signals emitted by a mobile phone when sequentially connected to a 4G-LTE or 5G-NR network. The main reason behind this study was the need of describing not only the dose of radiation absorbed by a human body while using a phone but also the average or the momentary dose rate. While the present safety exposure standards do not yet expressly require such knowledge, increasing the frequency towards tens of GHz in 5G networks means an increase in the energy of the radiation so it might need a time-dependent description similar to the ionizing radiation. Moreover, the averaging time used to describe the biological impact of the field is also very important to accurately describe the safety of people exposed to very short and quasi-stochastic pulses [31].

By experimentally determining the E-field strength variation during the 25s usage of 5 different mobile communication activities in either 4G or 5G networks, which allowed TDD technique and respectively had 20 and 40MHz bandwidths for the transmission, streams of 250 field values were gathered and treated as time-series. The boxplot representations of these data allowed obtaining descriptive statistic distributions, while the Poincare plots showed self-similarity by first recurrence means. The results showed that: a) more intensive dynamics are encountered generally in 5G UL signal than in 4G, b) the time variability is dependent not only on the communication standard but also on the type of mobile application used, c) short-term variability is lower than long-term when using a 4G application, as compared to 5G where the short-term variability of field level is higher than the long-term, d) the lowest ratio between short- and long-time variabilities was encountered for file upload in 4G, while the highest ratio was encountered for file download in 5G, and e) the largest total variabilities in 4G were associated to upload and video call, while in 5G they were noted during voice call and file download. These results provide important knowledge that completes the picture of amplitude-time variation of human exposure to near-the-body used mobile devices.

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An Inclusive Study on the Effect of Strain Rate on the Stress-Strain Behavior and the Undrained Shear Strength of Clay Soils in Kombolcha, Ethiopia

Salman Mohammed

Faculty of Civil Engineering
Arba Minch Institute of Technology
Arba Minch, Ethiopia
salmanmohammed872@gmail.com

Democracy D. Dirate

Faculty of Civil Engineering
Arba Minch Institute of Technology
Arba Minch, Ethiopia
democracy.dilla@amu.edu.et

Defaru K. Dasho

Faculty of Civil Engineering
Arba Minch Institute of Technology
Arba Minch, Ethiopia
defaru.katise@amu.edu.et

Ramesh K. Verma

Faculty of Civil Engineering
Arba Minch Institute of Technology
Arba Minch, Ethiopia
vermark42@gmail.com

Vasudeva R. Pampana

Faculty of Civil Engineering
Arba Minch Institute of Technology
Arba Minch, Ethiopia
vasudevarao_9@yahoo.com

Ruth B. Sangalang

Faculty of Civil Engineering
Arba Minch Institute of Technology
Arba Minch, Ethiopia
ruthie_sang@yahoo.com

Abera E. Koshuma

Faculty of Hydraulics and Water Resource Engineering
Arba Minch Water Technology Institute
Arba Minch, Ethiopia
abera.ermias@amu.edu.et

Abebe T. Ayalew

Faculty of Hydraulics and Water Resource Engineering
Arba Minch Water Technology Institute
Arba Minch, Ethiopia
abebe.temesgen@amu.edu.et

Abstract-This research aims to study the effect of strain rate on the stress-strain association and shear strength of clay soils in Kombolcha, Ethiopia. Field and laboratory experimentations were conducted on 3 soil samples collected at 4.5m depth, considering the physical and engineering properties of the soil. Unconsolidated, undrained triaxial compression tests were performed under confining pressure on the specimens that were axially loaded at a rate of strain varying from 0.38mm/min to 1.14mm/min by taking 2 points above and below 1% of the specimen height. Stress-strain relations were developed under the stated different rates of strains to describe their effect. It was revealed that the strain rate effect was observed. By increasing the strain rate shifts the stress-strain curve upward, and the corresponding shear strength of the soil also increased under effective stress. Accordingly, the strain rate increased the shear parameters. The average angle of friction increased by 13.43%, 15.08%, 13.18%, and 14.33% when the rate of strain changed from 0.38 to 0.57mm/min, 0.57 to 0.76mm/min, 0.76 to 0.95mm/min, and 0.95 to 1.14mm/min respectively, while the average cohesion increased by 17.67%, 19.52%, 14.87%, and 16.48%. The failure at strain rate 1%/min of sample height (0.76mm/min) was uniformly distributed and there was uniform pore pressure distribution throughout the sample height. The effect is slightly more when the shear strength increased at the left side than at the right side. Average shear strength parameters such as cohesion and angle friction were recorded for strain rates from 0.57mm/min to 1.25mm/min specifically for the clay soils found in Kombolcha town, Ethiopia.

Keywords-inclusive study; rate; strain; shear; soil

I. INTRODUCTION

Investigation on the properties of soil is significant in designing and building structures with foundations secured by materials such as soils and/or rocks. Soils have a maximum shearing resistance that they can sustain to the applied shear stress, which is a function of the effective normal stress that can determine its magnitude [1]. Shearing resistance is developed by friction, interparticle forces, cementation, or bonding at particle contacts, therefore, if the effective normal stress is zero, then the shearing resistance must be zero (unless there is cementation between the particles). If at a point on any plane within a soil mass the shear stress becomes equal to the shear strength of the soil then failure will occur. One of the factors that affect the shear strength of the soil is the strain rate [2]. The strength of saturated clay, as observed in undrained shear tests increases with the increasing strain rate [3-5]. The peak shear resistance increases from slow to fast strain rate.

Small strains occur from increased strength in terms of effective stress, and large strains from decreased excess pore pressure [6, 7]. Increasing the strain rate applied to a saturated soil means larger effective stresses and consequently greater shear resistance [8]. At large strains, the relationship between void ratio and effective stress is strain-rate dependent. As the strain-rate is increased, larger effective stress is required to

Corresponding author: Defaru K. Dasho

hold the soil at any given void ratio [9]. At faster strain rates, adjacent soil particles find it more difficult to move relatively, and, unless restrained by increased effective stress, will tend to ride up over one another. The measured pore water pressure is smaller at fast than at slow strain rate. The behavior of the pore pressure following a sudden increase in the strain rate proves that there is fundamentally an inverse relationship between the strain rate and the excess pore pressure [10-12]. The effect of strain rate on the stress-strain relationship and shear strength of clay by conducting a series of triaxial compression tests on remolded soil samples prepared with 38mm diameter and height of twice the diameter was studied in [13-15]. The type of triaxial test employed was Consolidated Undrained (CU) test with pore pressure measurement and by using different effective consolidation pressures. The specimens were axially loaded at a rate of strain varying from 0.001mm/min to 2mm/min. The results show that the strain rate affects both the stress-strain relationship and the strength of the soil. As the strain rate increases, the strength of the soil also increases, but the strain rate has a more pronounced effect on the cohesion and little effect on the angle of internal friction of the soil [16].

In this research, Unconsolidated Undrained (UU) triaxial test was used to measure the undrained shear strength of clay soil from Kombolcha. The soil in the town is dominantly fine-grained, belonging in the clay group. The aim of this research is to set quick and convenient UU shear tests for the clay soils found in the study area and to determine the best strain rate for the elastic and shear strength behaviors of soils [17]. Kombolcha is an industrial and grooming town that has seen increase in its infrastructures. The town is found in the Eastern part of the Amhara region, Ethiopia, and is located about 375km north of the state capital, Addis Ababa, along the road to Mekelle and 23km southeast of Dessie city. It is situated on the western margin of the Main Ethiopian Rift valley and covers an area of about 120km². Soils found in this town belong mostly to the fine-grained clay class [18].

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To achieve the study goals, 8 soil samples were collected from Kombolcha at a depth of 4.50m from the ground surface. From the samples, 3 were nominated to represent the other 5 samples according to their physical properties. The remolded clay specimens were prepared and used in the laboratory [19]. The selected samples' locations are presented in Table I.

Moisture content and field densities of the 3 pits were determined in the field and the samples were transported to the laboratory while they were kept in a plastic bag to prevent moisture loss. The measured amount of the wet soil was put in a conventional oven of 105°C and kept for 24 hours and was examined to determine its weight loss in order to determine moisture and density of the collected soils [20].

TABLE I. TEST PIT LOCATION AND COORDINATES OF THE STUDY AREA

Pit No.	Location	Latitude (DMS)	Longitude (DMS)
Pt-1	Kurangoye	11° 5' 27.59"	39° 43' 11.64"
Pt-2	Elkbeye	11° 4' 48.36"	39° 42' 50.76"
Pt-3	Sheshaber	11° 5' 27.59"	39° 42' 35.64"

A. Soil Grain and Consistency Limit Test

Sieve analysis was performed to determine the distribution of the coarse, larger-sized particles, and hydrometer test was conducted for 24 hours to determine the distribution of finer particles (less than 0.075mm). Two jars with 1000ml capacity were used. A control jar with distilled water and 5g of sodium hexametaphosphate was used as a dispersing agent and the other was a soil sample with distilled water and 5g of dispersing agent. A mechanical stirrer was also used for mixing the soil samples with distilled water and the dispersing agent. Soils passing through a 0.425 mm sieve were used to determine the plastic and liquid limits of fine-grained soil. The specimens were soaked for 30 minutes and mixed for 5 minutes [21-23].

B. Specific Gravity and Free Swell Determination Tests

The specific gravity of the samples was determined with the help of a pycnometer using a soil sample that passed through the 2mm sieve. The sample was connected to the hydrometer and was oven-dried at 105°C. A minimum soil sample of 20g was used [24]. Free swell index is the increase in the volume of soil, without any external constraints, on submergence in water. Representative oven-dried soil samples having mass of 10g passing through 0.425 mm sieve were put in 100ml of water in a jar for 24hours. Swelling was examined as a percentage of the volume change to the original volume [25 ,26].

C. Compaction Test

Laboratory compaction procedures were used to determine the relationship between water content and the dry unit weight of soils. The soil samples were compacted in 3 layers with a 24.4N rammer dropped from a height of 305mm producing a compactive effort of 600 kN-m/m³. 8% of 3000g of the test sample were added in mm as the initial water content and 4% water content increments were used to obtain a well-defined maximum dry unit weight. After obtaining the density and moisture of each compacted soil sample, Maximum Dry Density (MDD) and Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) were determined from the compaction curve [27,28].

D. Consolidation and Permeability Test

This test was performed to determine the magnitude and rate of volume decrease a laterally confined soil specimen undergoes when subjected to different vertical pressures. From the measured data, the consolidation curve (pressure-void ratio relationship) can be plotted. These data are useful in determining the compression index and the recompression index of the soil. Besides, the obtained data can also be used to determine the coefficient of consolidation and the coefficient of secondary compression of the soil. Tests were carried on the undisturbed samples by pushing the consolidation ring into the ground at a depth of 4.50m during the sample collection. The samples were transported to the laboratory while they were kept in a plastic bag. Soil samples with diameter of 63mm and height of 20mm were loaded with pressures from 7kPa to 1600kPa. For each loading the compression was recorded from the dial gauge at intervals of 0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 8, 15, 30, 60, 120, 240, 480, and 1440 minutes for 24 hours. Unloading to examine unloading behavior was also done in steps. A total of 3 consolidation tests were run on undisturbed samples and different results were obtained. From the test results of the

consolidation curve (pressure-void ratio relationship), compression index (Cc) and expansion index (Ce) were determined [29]. The purpose of the permeability test is to determine the permeability (hydraulic conductivity) of the soil by the falling head test method. A representative soil sample that passed through the 4.75mm sieve was collected and compacted at optimum moisture content to achieve maximum dry density in a mold having 10cm diameter and 12.73cm length. After the soil sample was saturated, its permeability was examined by allowing the water to come through it falling from the initial head. The head change and the time taken to the water to come through the sample were recorded until the water began to flow out of the water bath [30].

E. Unconsolidated Undrained Triaxial Compression Test

In this paper, remolded cylindrical specimens passed through the 2.36mm sieve and having a diameter of 38mm and a length twice the diameter (76mm) were used. All the test samples were compacted within 6 layers in a manner that can represent the site condition of the soil. Axial load was applied to produce axial strain at a rate of approximately 1%/min of the specimen height, which is used as a reference rate in this study. The confining pressure was calculated from the unit weight of the soil, the depth where the samples were collected, and by assuming a coefficient of earth pressure at rest to represent the site that was conveniently used as per Kombolcha town soils behavior. Hence, 5 different strain rates were used, the conventional strain rate of 0.76mm/min and 2 strain rates below and 2 above it. Trials were done during the triaxial test for each selected pit sample. The trials were conducted with increasing strain rate of 0.5% (0.38mm/min), 0.75% (0.57mm/min), 1% (0.76mm/min), 1.25% (0.95mm/min) and 1.5% (1.14mm/min) of specimen height with confining pressure of 50kPa, 100kPa, and 150kPa in order to assess the better strain rate for Kombolcha clay soils. A failure envelope was used to determine the shear strength parameters of the test samples [31-33].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Soil Index and Density Results

As described in Table II, the average moisture content was 31.60%, which lies between stiff and soft clays.

TABLE II. MOISTURE CONTENT, BLUK AND DRY DENSITY, SPECIFIC GRAVITY, AND ATTERBERG'S LIMIT RESULTS

Pit No.	Location	Moisture content, %	Bulk Density, g/cc	Dry density, g/cc	Liquid limit, (%)	Plasticity Index (PI %)	Soil class	Specific gravity, at 20°C
Pt-1	Kurangoye	30.12	1.75	1.34	63.68	33.11	CH	2.75
Pt-2	Elkbeye	29.71	1.85	1.43	56.47	31.50	CH	2.72
Pt-3	Sheshaber	34.84	1.77	1.31	78.32	44.04	CH	2.76

The ranges for bulk density and dry density are 1.75 to 1.85 and 1.31 to 1.43g/cc respectively, which are within the range of silt or clay. The soil grain size analysis ranges results of the obtained samples are 5.82 to 10.14% sand particles, 25.44 to 32.14% silt, and 57.43 to 67.25% the clay fraction. These results show that clay soil is dominantly found, which was also indicated by the results of Atterberg limit results. The liquid limit for these clay soils was found above 50% and a plasticity

index of more than 30% was obtained. Hence, soils are classified as highly plastic clay (CH) as presented in Table II with an average specific gravity of 2.75.

B. Compaction and Free Swell Results

Optimum Moisture Content (OMC, %) and Maximum Dry Density (MDD, g/cc) of the test pits are listed in Table II. They vary from 22.50% to 29.80% and from 1.39g/cc to 1.55g/cc respectively. Maximum dry density of the soil for all pits is greater than the in-place dry density of the soil, which shows that it needs densification to attain maximum density and optimum moisture.

Fig. 1. Standard proctor compaction test results for pit one.

C. Soil Free Swell, Consolidation, and Permeability Results

The results of the free swelling of the study area lie within the range from 49.21 to 60.25%, which describes the medium swelling potential (Table III). The magnitude of the compression index varies between 0.25 and 0.29 whereas the swelling index of the clay soils ranges between 0.0169 and 0.0280. The soils fall within the permeability range of 6.78×10^{-5} to 8.09×10^{-6} cm/s at 20°C, which indicates that the area is accumulated by fine soils with low permeability.

TABLE III. COMPACTION PROPERTIES, COEFFICIENT OF COMPRESSION AND SWELLING INDECES, AND PERMEABILITY RESULTS

Pit No.	Free swell, %	OMC, %	MDD (g/cc)	Compression index, Cc	Swelling index, Ce	Coefficient of permeability at 20°C, K(cm/s)
Pt-1	51.53	27.50	1.46	0.27	0.0178	8.09E-06
Pt-2	49.21	22.50	1.55	0.25	0.0169	6.78E-06
Pt-3	60.25	29.80	1.39	0.29	0.0280	7.19E-06

D. Unconsolidated Undrained Triaxial Compression Results

The plots of deviatoric stress to axial strain relationship for the same strain rates under different confining pressure for the 3 test pit samples are shown in Figure 2.

In a similar manner, the stress-strain curves for the not listed strain rates were performed. From these graphs, it was observed that an increase in confining pressure shifts the stress-strain curve upward with different patterns, which illustrate the increase in shear strength up to the failure point. Maximum deviatoric stresses at failure for each strain rate were obtained to determine the shear strength parameters called angle of friction and cohesion.

Fig. 2. Deviatoric stress-strain curves for Pt-1 at (a) 0.38, (b) 0.57, Pt-2 at (c) 0.57 and (d) 0.76, and Pt-3 at (e) 0.95 and (f) 1.14mm/min strain rates under 50, 100, and 150kPa confining pressure.

Fig. 3. Stress strain behavior of the three pits under various strain rates.

Plots of the deviatoric stress versus axial strain with the different strain rate and same confining pressure is shown in Figure 3. Only 4 stress-strain graphs are presented (pit-1 for confining pressure of 50kPa, pit-2 for confining pressure of 100kPa and 150kPa, and pit-3 for confining pressure of 150kPa). By the same fashion, all 3 pit samples' stress-strain graphs were developed for confining pressures of 50kPa, 100kPa, and 150kPa under different strain rates. It was revealed that an increase in the strain rate shifts the stress-strain curve upward, which describes the faster strain rate induced increase in deviatoric stress and failure point of the soil under induced pressure. Figure 5 presents the shear strength parameters with the different strain rates for 3 test pit samples. The results were derived from Figures 2 and 3. From Figure 5, it is observed that the cohesion and the angle of internal friction increase when the strain rate increases. Shear parameters angle of friction (ϕ^0) and cohesion (C in kPa) axes are determined for each stress path at failure strain rates. In a similar way the remaining three samples' determination is done and shear strength parameters are presented in Figure 6. The average angle of friction is equal to 6.81^0 and the average cohesion is 13.55kPa under the described strain rates. These results define clay soil behavior. The soils were weak to bear the imposed load from the buildings in Kombolcha.

Fig. 5. Strain rate effect on: (a) angle of friction and (b) cohesion of soil.

Fig. 4. Normal to shear stress chart at failure and different strain rates for (a) pit-1, (b) pit-2, and (c) pit-3.

Fig. 6. Increase in soil shear parameters: (a) angle of friction and (b) cohesion.

Accordingly, at higher strain rates (0.75 to 1.25mm/min) produced in higher undrained shear strength for the clay soil samples, the results show that the failure at the strain rate of 1%/min (0.76mm/min) of sample height is uniformly distributed and there is uniform pore pressure distribution throughout the sample height. It was also shown that the angle of friction and the cohesion of soils are inversely related as indicated in Figure 5. As illustrated in Figure 6, the strain rate increased the clay soil shear parameters. These shear strength parameters actually indicate properties of clay soils with high plasticity. Hence, the average angle of friction increased by 13.43%, 15.08%, 13.18%, and 14.33% at strain rates of 0.38 to 0.57mm/min, 0.57 to 0.76mm/min, 0.76 to 0.95mm/min and 0.95 to 1.14mm/min respectively (Figure 6 a)), whereas, the average cohesion increased by 17.67%, 19.52%, 14.87% and

16.48% respectively (Figure 6(b)). As indicated in the results of the angle of friction, the change in the strain rate is not significantly affected, but cohesion is slightly more increased with the early strain rates for these soils. The minimum average unconsolidated undrained shear test result for clay soils from Kombolcha occurs for the strain rate of 0.76mm/min to 0.95mm/min.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The current study described the soils in Kombolcha town as dominantly clay soils. UU triaxial compression tests were performed on the soil at different strain rates. When the strain rate increased, the stress-strain curve moved up and the shear strength also increased. The failure at strain rate 1%/min of sample height is uniformly distributed and there was uniform pore pressure distribution throughout the sample height. The increase in undrained shear strength can be associated with the less excess pore water pressure during shearing at faster rates. Test were conducted on the clay soil of Kombolcha using strain rates ranging from 0.75% (rate of 0.57mm/min) to 1.25% (rate of 0.95mm/min) of specimen height of the remolded samples and the average stress-strain and shear strength behaviors of these samples were studied.

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Stability Analysis of Boundary Layer Flow and Heat Transfer of Fe_2O_3 and Fe-Water Base Nanofluid over a Stretching/Shrinking Sheet with Radiation Effect

Hazoor Bux Lanjwani

Institute of Mathematics and Computer Science
University of Sindh
Jamshoro, Pakistan
hazoor.bux@scholars.usindh.edu.pk

Muhammad Saleem Chandio

Institute of Mathematics and Computer Science
University of Sindh
Jamshoro, Pakistan
mschandio@hotmail.com

Kamran Malik

Department of Mathematics
Government College University
Hyderabad, Pakistan
Kamranmk99@gmail.com

Muhammad Mujtaba Shaikh

Department of Basic Sciences and Related Studies
Mehran University of Engineering and Technology
Jamshoro, Pakistan
mujtaba.shaikh@faculty.muet.edu.pk

Abstract-In this paper, the radiation and slip effects are investigated on the boundary layer flow and heat transfer of Fe_2O_3 and Fe-water base nanofluids over a porous stretching/shrinking sheet. A similarity transformation is used to convert the system of governing partial differential equations into ordinary differential equations, which are then numerically solved in Maple software with the help of the shooting technique. At different ranges of the applied parameters, dual solutions are found. The effects of the different physical factors such as radiation, nanoparticle volumetric fractions, suction, and slip parameters are determined and discussed. The skin-friction coefficient and local Nusselt number are influenced significantly by the applied parameters. In the boundary layer regime, the increase in nanoparticle volume fractions and radiation parameters enhance the temperature and boundary-layer thicknesses, while increasing Prandtl number, suction, and thermal slip parameters decrease the temperature and reduce thermal boundary-layer thicknesses. The suspension of iron nanoparticles shows more enhancement in skin friction and Nusselt number than the iron oxide nanoparticles in base fluid water.

Keywords-boundary layer; dual solutions; shooting method; radiation; nanofluid

I. INTRODUCTION

Nanofluids are made up of solid nanoparticles and common base fluids such as water, oil, glycol, polymer fluids, and so on [1, 3-5]. The nanoparticles are made from metals, metal oxides, and carbides, and have far greater heat conductivity. Their insertion considerably enhances thermo-physical properties such as thermal conductivity, viscosity, thermal diffusivity, and the convective heat transfer coefficient. Nanofluids may be employed in many industrial and technological applications [2], including microelectronics, coolants, fuel cells, pharmaceutical

operations, household freezers, chillers, and lubricants. Several methods have been developed to improve the thermal conductivity of typical common liquids, including suspending macro/micro particles of solid materials in them.

Two types of nanofluid models have been created and effectively employed as a result of recent developments in nanotechnology. Buongiorno [6] proposed the initial model, which incorporated 7 slip factors as critical components in generating a relative velocity between the nanoparticles and the base fluid. Only thermophoresis and Brownian motion were considered essential among the 7 slip components when creating a model for convective transport in nanofluids. The second nanofluid model was proposed by Tiwari and Das [7] to study the effect of nanoparticle volume fractions on thermal characteristics enhancement. Researchers used and modified these two well-known nanofluid models by using different physical flow parameters [8-11].

Many engineering and practical science applications, such as paper manufacturing, wire drawing, extrusion, metal spinning, and hot rolling, rely on the boundary layer flow through a stretching/shrinking sheet. Crane [12] was the first to work on the stretched sheet. Since then, a broad range of issues related to these topics was examined. Authors in [13] examined the heat and mass transfer on a stretched sheet with suction and blowing. Many researchers were also interested to study the flow over a stretching sheet. The study of viscous flow past on shrinking sheet along the suction action was pioneered in [14]. It is worth mentioning that mass suction is required to keep the flow inside boundary layer flowing. The analytic solution of the magnetohydrodynamic flow of a second grade fluid on a shrinking sheet was investigated in [15]. Authors in [16] explored the MHD rotational flow of a viscous fluid over a

Corresponding author: Muhammad Mujtaba Shaikh

shrinking surface. Authors in [17] were the first to investigate the nanofluid flow through the boundary layer of a stretching sheet. The boundary layer slip flow problem is quite relevant in practice. Wang [18] analyzed the impact of the partial slip on flow of a viscous fluid through a stretching sheet using numerical simulations. Authors in [19] examined the natural convection of magnetohydrodynamics nanofluid flow on a vertically flat plate. Authors in [20] examined the impact of the particle sizes and volume fractions on the Al₂O₃-water base nanofluid. Authors in [21] studied the steady boundary-layer flow through a continuously moving plate with different nanoparticles immersed in water in a 2D (two-dimensional) flow. Author in [22] considered 2D nanofluid flow past a moving plate in a continuous free-stream. Authors in [23] examined 2D laminar stagnant-point fluid flow with heat absorption and generation. Authors in [24] investigated the behavior of slip factors using single and multiphase nanomaterial models. Authors in [25] inspected the inclination of the magnetic field in a convective radiative heat transfer micro-nanofluid using a porous medium.

Various scholars have studied the occurrence of multiple solutions to the boundary value problems. These solutions are caused by the non-linearity of the equations at various ranges of the physical parameters that can be seen in the literature. Several academics assessed the stability of a range of solutions to find which is the stable and physically realizable. Many scholars, including the authors in [26-28] have come up with different solutions and they proved that only one solution was found stable through stability analysis.

The primary aim of this study is to determine how various flow parameters impact water-based nanofluids created by stretching and shrinking sheets. The Tiwari and Das model is used to investigate the heat radiation and slip effects of iron (Fe) and iron oxide (Fe₂O₃) nanoparticles. The similarity transformations are used to convert the partial differential equations into ordinary differential equations. The shooting approach is applied for solution of the resulting system of equations. According to the findings of this study, dual solutions exist for certain ranges of the physical parameters that are illustrated in the graphs. Due to the occurrence of dual solutions, the bvp4c Matlab program is used to perform the stability analysis. The stability tests reveal that the first solution is the stable and the physically realizable, while the second is not stable.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Let's consider a two-dimensional boundary layer flow and heat transfer in a water-based nanofluid containing iron (Fe) and iron oxide (Fe₂O₃) nanoparticles over a stretching/shrinking sheet. The sheet is considered to be parallel to the plane $y = 0$, and the flow is contained at $y > 0$. The sheet is stretched and shrunk with velocity $u_w = cx$, where $c > 0$ is the stretching rate, with two opposed and equal forces applied in the direction of the x-axis. The base fluid (water) and nanoparticles are considered to be in thermal equilibrium. Table I lists the thermo physical properties of water as well as the nanoparticles that are used in the present study.

TABLE I. THERMO PHYSICAL VALUES OF BASE-FLUID AND SOLID NANOPARTICLES [36]

Base fluid and kind of particles	$\rho(kg/m^3)$	$C_p(J/Kgk)$	$k(W/mk)$
Water (H ₂ O)	997.1	4179	0.613
Iron (Fe)	7870	460	80
Iron oxide (Fe ₂ O ₃)	5180	670	80.4

The governing equations of the problem by using the Tiwari and Das model [7] are written as:

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \frac{\mu_{nf}}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \quad (2)$$

$$v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} + u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = \alpha_{nf} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} - \frac{1}{(\rho c_p)_{nf}} \frac{\partial q_r}{\partial y} \quad (3)$$

The Roseland approximation, q_r is defined as:

$$q_r = -\frac{4\sigma^* \partial T^4}{3k^* \partial y} \quad (4)$$

where σ^* is Boltzmann's constant and k^* is the absorption coefficient. It is assumed that the temperature difference is very small. As a result, when the Taylor series is applied to the temperature of the free stream fluid flow which is indicated by T_∞ and ignoring higher order terms, the T^4 can be defined as:

$$T^4 \cong -3T^4 + 4TT_\infty^3 \quad (5)$$

The specified boundary conditions are:

$$v = v_w; u = \lambda u_w + A \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}; T = T_w + B \frac{\partial T}{\partial y}; \text{ at } y = 0$$

$$u \rightarrow 0; T \rightarrow T_\infty; \text{ as } y \rightarrow \infty \quad (6)$$

where v, u are the velocity components in the x and y directions and U_∞ and u_w are the velocities of free stream fluid and sheet respectively, A and B are slip factors, T, μ_{nf}, α_{nf} and ρ_{nf} are the temperature, viscosity, thermal diffusivity and density of the nanofluid respectively, as defined in [32]:

$$\alpha_{nf} = \frac{k_{nf}}{(\rho c_p)_{nf}}, \mu_{nf} = \frac{\mu_f}{(1-\phi)^{2.5}}$$

$$\rho_{nf} = (1 - \phi)\rho_f + \phi\rho_s$$

$$\frac{k_{nf}}{k_f} = \frac{(2k_f+k_s)-(-k_s+k_f)2\phi}{(2k_f+k_s)+(-k_s+k_f)\phi}$$

$$(\rho c_p)_{nf} = (1 - \phi)(\rho c_p)_f + \phi(\rho c_p)_s \quad (7)$$

where ρ_s and ρ_f are the densities of solid nanoparticles volume fractions and fluid (water) respectively, k_f and k_s are the thermal conductivities of the base fluid and solid nanoparticles volume fractions respectively. Furthermore, the μ_{nf} (the viscosity of the nanofluid) was estimated in [33] and the similarity transformation is taken according to [34]:

$$u = cx f'(\eta); v = -\sqrt{cx} f(\eta); \eta = y \sqrt{\frac{c}{\nu_f}}$$

$$\theta(\eta) = \frac{T - T_\infty}{T_w - T_\infty} \quad (8)$$

Transformation (8) instantly fulfills the differentiation in terms of (1), however (2) and (3) are reduced to the following non-linear ordinary differential equations:

$$\frac{1}{(1-\phi)^{2.5}} f''' + \left((-\phi + 1) + \phi \left(\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_f} \right) \right) (ff'' - f'^2) = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{1}{Pr} \frac{1}{\left((1-\phi) + \phi \left(\frac{\rho c_p}{\rho c_p} \right) \right)} \left(\frac{k_{nf}}{k_f} + \frac{4}{3} Rd \right) \theta'' + f\theta' = 0 \quad (10)$$

and the boundary conditions take the form:

$$f(0) = S; f'(0) = \lambda + \delta f''(0); \theta(0) = 1 + \delta_T \theta'(0)$$

$$\text{at } \eta = 0, f'(\eta) \rightarrow 0; \theta(\eta) \rightarrow 0; \text{ as } \eta \rightarrow \infty \quad (11)$$

where prime stands for the derivative with respect to η , $Rd (= 4T_\infty^3 \sigma^* / k_f k_f)$ is the radiative parameter, $Pr (= \mu_f / k_f)$ is the Prandtl number, $\delta = A \sqrt{c/\vartheta_f}$ is the velocity slip, $\delta_T = B \sqrt{c/\vartheta_f}$ is the thermal slip parameter and λ is the stretching/shrinking parameter. When $0 < \lambda < 1$, the fluid and the plate are moved in the similar direction. Likewise, for $\lambda < 0$ and $\lambda > 1$, these are in opposite direction of the motion. When $\lambda < 0$ shows that the flow of the ambient fluid is in the positive x -direction and the movement of sheet is in negative x -direction, $\lambda > 1$ shows that the flow of ambient fluid is in the negative x -direction and the movement of the sheet in the positive x -direction. In the present paper, both cases are considered but main focus was given on $\lambda < 0$.

The local Nusselt number Nu_x and the skin friction coefficient C_f are key physical parameters that are described as:

$$C_f = \frac{\tau_w}{\rho_f u_w^2}, \quad Nu_x = \frac{q_w}{k_f (T_w - T_\infty)} \quad (12)$$

Shear stress τ_w and surface heat diffusion q_w are defined as:

$$\tau_w = \mu_{nf} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0} \text{ and } q_w = - \left(\frac{k_{nf}}{k_f} + \frac{4}{3} Rd \right) \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0} \quad (13)$$

By the use of (8) and (13) in (12), we get:

$$C_f (Re_x)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{1}{(1-\phi)^{2.5}} f''(0) \\ (Re_x)^{-\frac{1}{2}} Nu_x = - \left(\frac{k_{nf}}{k_f} + \frac{4}{3} Rd \right) \theta'(0) \quad (14)$$

where $Re_x = \frac{x u_w}{\nu_f}$ reports the Reynolds number.

III. STABILITY ANALYSIS

As this problem has dual solutions, stability analysis is required to find a stable and physically reliable solution. To evaluate the stability of the solutions, at first the governing system of (2) and (3) will be written into an unsteady form like:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \frac{\mu_{nf}}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} + u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = \frac{k_{nf}}{(\rho c_p)_{nf}} \left(1 + \frac{4Rd}{3} \right) \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \quad (16)$$

where t denotes the time. The transformation (8) will be modified by introducing new dimensionless time dependent variable τ .

$$u = cx f'(\eta, \tau); v = -\sqrt{cx} f(\eta, \tau);$$

$$\eta = y \sqrt{\frac{c}{\vartheta_f}}; \theta(\eta, \tau) = \frac{T - T_\infty}{T_w - T_\infty} \text{ and } \tau = ct \quad (17)$$

By implementing (17) into the (15) and (16) we get:

$$\frac{\partial^3 f(\eta, \tau)}{\partial \eta^3} + (-\phi + 1)^{2.5} \left[\left((-\phi + 1) + \phi \left(\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_f} \right) \right) \left\{ \frac{1}{2} f(\eta, \tau) \frac{\partial^2 f(\eta, \tau)}{\partial \eta^2} - \left(\frac{\partial f(\eta, \tau)}{\partial \eta} \right)^2 - \frac{\partial^2 f(\eta, \tau)}{\partial \eta \partial \tau} \right\} \right] = 0 \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{1}{Pr} \left(\frac{k_{nf}}{k_f} + \frac{4Rd}{3} \right) \frac{\partial^2 \theta(\eta, \tau)}{\partial \eta^2} + \left(1 - \phi + \phi \left(\frac{\rho c_p}{\rho c_p} \right) \right) \left[\frac{\partial \theta(\eta, \tau)}{\partial \eta} f(\eta, \tau) - \frac{\partial \theta(\eta, \tau)}{\partial \tau} \right] = 0 \quad (19)$$

The boundary conditions are:

$$f(0, \tau) = S, \quad \frac{\partial f(0, \tau)}{\partial \eta} = \lambda + \delta \frac{\partial^2 f(0, \tau)}{\partial \eta^2},$$

$$\theta(0, \tau) = 1 + \delta_T \frac{\partial \theta(0, \tau)}{\partial \eta},$$

$$\frac{\partial f(\eta, \tau)}{\partial \eta} \rightarrow 0, \quad \theta(\eta, \tau) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } \eta \rightarrow \infty \quad (20)$$

To obtain stability for the solutions $f(\eta) = f_0(\eta)$ and $\theta(\eta) = \theta_0(\eta)$ that satisfy the specified boundary value problem given in equations (2)-(3), we expressed:

$$f(\eta, \tau) = F(\eta) e^{-\gamma \tau} + f_0(\eta),$$

$$\theta(\eta, \tau) = G(\eta) e^{-\gamma \tau} + \theta_0(\eta) \quad (21)$$

$G(\eta)$ and $F(\eta)$ are the related functions to $\theta_0(\eta)$ and $f_0(\eta)$ respectively, and γ is the unknown minimum eigenvalue. The following linear eigenvalue problem system is generated by using (19) into (18)-(21):

$$\frac{\partial^3 F}{\partial \eta^3} + (-\phi + 1)^{2.5} \left[\left((-\phi + 1) + \phi \left(\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_f} \right) \right) \left\{ \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial \eta^2} f_0 + F \frac{\partial^2 f_0}{\partial \eta^2} - 2 \frac{\partial f}{\partial \eta} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \eta} + \gamma \frac{\partial F}{\partial \eta} \right\} \right] = 0 \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{1}{Pr} \left(\frac{k_{nf}}{k_f} + \frac{4Rd}{3} \right) \frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial \eta^2} +$$

$$\left(1 - \phi + \phi \left(\frac{\rho c_p}{\rho c_p} \right) \right) \left[f_0 \frac{\partial G}{\partial \eta} + \frac{\partial \theta_0}{\partial \eta} F + \gamma G \right] = 0 \quad (23)$$

The set $F(\eta) = F_0(\eta)$ and $G(\eta) = G_0(\eta)$ is used in (22) and (23) to acquire the initial decay or growth of solutions of (21). Therefore, the following system of eigenvalues has been solved:

$$F_0''' + (-\phi + 1)^{2.5} \left\{ \left((-\phi + 1) + \phi \left(\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_f} \right) \right) (F_0'' f_0 + \gamma F_0' - 2f_0' F_0' + f_0'' F_0) \right\} = 0 \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{1}{Pr} \left(\frac{k_{nf}}{k_f} + \frac{4Rd}{3} \right) G_0'' + \left(1 - \phi + \phi \left(\frac{\rho_{cp}_s}{\rho_{cp}_f} \right) \right) \{ G_0' f_0 + \theta_0' F_0 + \gamma G_0 \} = 0 \quad (25)$$

with boundary conditions:

$$F_0(0) = 0, F_0'(0) = \delta F_0''(0), G_0(0) = \delta_T G_0'(0) \\ F_0'(\eta) \rightarrow 0, G_0(\eta) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } \eta \rightarrow \infty \quad (26)$$

To get the smallest eigenvalue, the linearized equations (24) and (25) with boundary conditions (26) are solved in MATLAB using the bvp4c solver techniques. As mentioned in [35], we must relax one boundary condition into the initial condition. In this case, $F_0'(\eta) \rightarrow 0$ as $\eta \rightarrow \infty$ into $F_0''(0) = 1$. The smallest negative eigenvalues indicate the disturbance's initial growth. As a result, the solutions related to the fluid flow are said to be unstable. The fluid flow is said to be stable in case obtained smallest positive eigenvalues.

IV. NUMERICAL METHOD

The boundary value problem given in (9) and (10) is solved using the shooting method in Maple software, using the initial and boundary conditions (11). On the other hand, this method turns the boundary value problem into an initial value problem. Therefore, we get:

$$f' = F_p, f'' = F_{pp}$$

$$\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right) F_{pp}' +$$

$$(1 - \phi)^{2.5} \left\{ \left(1 - \phi + \phi \left(\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_f} \right) \right) (F_{pp} - (F_p)^2) \right\} = 0 \quad (27)$$

$$\theta' = \theta_p, \phi' = \phi_p,$$

$$\frac{1}{Pr} \frac{1}{\left((1-\phi) + \phi \left(\frac{\rho_{cp}_s}{\rho_{cp}_f} \right) \right)} \left(\frac{k_{nf}}{k_f} + \frac{4}{3} Rd \right) \theta_p' + F \theta_p = 0 \quad (28)$$

The boundary conditions take the form:

$$F(0) = S, F_p(0) = \lambda + \delta F_{pp}(0), \theta(0) = 1 + \delta_T \theta_p(0) \\ F_{pp}(0) = \alpha_1, \theta_p(0) = \alpha_2, \quad (29)$$

where α_1, α_2 are taken as the unknown initial conditions. So, the shooting values for the missing initial values of α_1, α_2 are important. The solution must satisfy the boundary conditions $F_p(\eta) \rightarrow 0, \theta(\eta) \rightarrow 0$ as $\eta \rightarrow \infty$ of the specified boundary value problem. The computation is done in Maple by using the shootlib function and the shooting method. In this paper, the thickness of the boundary layer η_∞ is taken between 4 and 7, at which the convergence shown in the graphs is obtained. For fixed values of the used parameters, 2 velocity and temperature profiles are achieved, each totally satisfying the problem's required boundary conditions. As a result, the quantities $f''(0)$ and $-\theta'(0)$, have two distinct values.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The shooting method in Maple is used to obtain the numerical solutions to the system of ordinary differential equations (9) and (10) that are subjects to the boundary conditions of (11). Figures 2–17 show the results of the impact of the non-dimensional physical parameters on the velocity and temperatures profiles as well as the skin friction coefficient and Nusselt numbers. Table I shows the thermo physical properties of the base fluid and nanoparticles used in the present study. Table II shows the comparison result of the 2 numerical methods, the shooting method used in Maple and the bvp4c used in Matlab. The comparison shows much symmetry in the results that encourage us to consider that our obtained results are correct and trustworthy. In addition, in the case of dual solutions, stability analysis has been performed with bvp4c in Matlab to determine which solution is reliable and stable by obtaining the smallest eigenvalue using (24)-(26). The solution which corresponds to a positive least eigenvalue is considered as a reliable and stable solution. The solution which corresponds to a negative least eigenvalue is considered as an unstable solution. Table III shows the numerical values of the stability of solutions for the different values of velocity slip and radiation. The eigenvalues (γ) concerned to the second solutions are negative, while they are positive for the first solutions. The results of Fe₂O₃-water base nanofluid and Fe-water base nanofluid are shown by different colors in plots. The solid lines are related to the study of the stable solution (first solution) and the dashed lines are used to denote the second, unstable solutions. Table IV shows the critical points concerned to Figures 2-5, where two solutions are merged. Furthermore, the impact of the various used parameters of this study are presented and discussed below through graphs.

Fig. 1. Physical illustration of the model.

The variation in skin friction coefficient ($f''(0)$) and local Nusselt number ($-\theta'(0)$) along the change in stretching and shrinking parameter (λ) under the impact of different values of the suction parameter (S) are shown in Figures 2 and 3 respectively. For $\lambda > \lambda_c$, there are dual solutions. Both solutions merge at λ_c , and there is no solution for $\lambda < \lambda_c$ where λ_c denotes the critical point. Figure 2 shows that when the suction rate is increased, the skin friction coefficient reduces for values $\lambda > 0$ and rises for $\lambda < 0$ in the first (stable) solution. Furthermore, the rate of skin friction (drag force) is examined to be larger in Fe₂O₃-water base nanofluid than in

Fe-water base nanofluid for $\lambda > 0$ (for stretching case of the sheet) and vice versa for $\lambda < 0$ (for shrinking case of the sheet) for the same values of the suction parameter (S). The Nusselt number (rate of heat transfer) rises as the suction parameter (S) is increased in both solutions (Figure 3).

In addition, the variations of skin friction coefficient ($f''(0)$) and local Nusselt number ($-\theta'(0)$) along the variation of the suction parameter at various values of nanoparticles volume fraction (ϕ) are shown in Figures 4-5. For $S > S_c$, dual solutions also exist. At the critical point S_c , both solutions merge, while no solution is observed for $S < S_c$. In both Fe₂O₃-water base and Fe-water base nanofluids, the skin friction coefficient rises as the nanoparticle volume fraction increases, while it decreases in the second solution (Figure 4). The rate of skin friction for the Fe-water base nanofluid is observed to be greater than that of the Fe₂O₃-water base nanofluid. It may be noted that the viscous fluid flow in Figures 4 and 5 is shown by black colored lines. Figure 5 shows that the Nusselt number decreases with an increase in the rate of nanoparticles volume fraction in both solutions in both types of nanofluids. Heat transfer rate is observed greater in Fe-water base nanofluid than in Fe₂O₃-water base nanofluid. The comparative results of the variations of the skin friction coefficient and local Nusselt number with the variation of nanoparticles volume fraction regarding to Fe₂O₃-water base nanofluid and Fe-water base nanofluid are presented in Figures 6 and 7. It is seen that the Fe-nanoparticles show the greater resistance in flow, which means greater rate of skin friction coefficient is observed as compared to the Fe₂O₃ in water base nanofluid. Due to the greater resistance of suspending Fe nanoparticles in water, the rate of heat transfer of Fe-water base nanofluid remains greater than that of the Fe₂O₃-water base nanofluid as shown in Figure 7. Furthermore, due to the repeated trend of the result, only graphs of Fe-water base nanofluid are presented here for further study.

Furthermore, Figures 8-17 show the velocity and temperature profiles for various values of the applied parameters. Figures 8 and 9 show the velocity and the temperature profiles of the boundary layer flow of the Fe-water base nanofluid at different values of nanoparticle volume fraction (ϕ). The influence of ϕ shows that with any increment in the concentration of nanoparticles the velocity of the fluid decreases throughout the boundary layer region in the first (stable) solution. Actually, the nanoparticles develop a friction in fluid molecules which retards the flow. The nanoparticles also increase the thermal conductivity of the base fluid, so the heat is transferred from the hot regime to the cold one in faster rate and in result, warms the thermal boundary layer regime. Hence, the concentration of nanoparticles increases the temperature and the thermal boundary layer thickness of the base fluid as shown in Figure 9. The effects of the suction parameter (S) on $f'(\eta)$ and $\theta(\eta)$ profiles are shown in Figures 10 and 11. It can be clearly observed that any increment in S raises the suction rate of the fluid at sheet and in result, momentum boundary layer thickness and fluid velocity decrease in the first solution throughout the nanofluid flow. In the second solution, the opposite result can be observed. Any increment in S decreases the thermal boundary layer thickness and the temperature of the nanofluid throughout the flow in

both solutions. Figures 12 and 13 show the impact of λ (for shrinking case) on $f'(\eta)$ and $\theta(\eta)$ profiles respectively. Both the profiles of velocity $f'(\eta)$ and temperature $\theta(\eta)$ are decreasing for increasing λ (in the first solution) and increasing for increasing λ (in the second solution) for the shrinking case.

The influence of the Prandtl number (Pr) on the temperature profile $\theta(\eta)$ of the Fe-water base nanofluid is shown in Figure 14. When the parameter Pr is raised, the temperature of the nanofluid decreases. Because fluids with a high Pr value have a low thermal diffusivity, the temperature of the moving fluid drops. The temperature and thickness of the boundary layer decrease as Pr increases. The influence of radiation parameter (Rd) on the temperature profile is drawn in Figure 15. The temperature profile increases as the radiation parameter increases. As the value of Rd increases, the divergence of radiating heat flux increases as k^* decreases. As a consequence, the rate of radiating heat transfer to the fluid's boundary layer flow rises which increases the temperature of the fluid. The velocity profile $f'(\eta)$ of the Fe-water base nanofluid in the first solution decreases when the velocity slip parameter (δ) increases, as can be seen in Figure 16. Basically, any increment in δ shows more fluid particles slipping on sheet, so the fluid flow decelerates near the sheet. In the second solution, any change in parameter values causes the nanofluid velocity to rise. The influence of thermal slip parameter (δ_T) on the temperature profile $\theta(\eta)$ is shown in Figure 17. When the thermal slip increases, the thickness of the thermal boundary layer and the temperature profile both decrease in both solutions. The fluid velocity is initially decreased when the thermal slip parameter is raised, resulting in a decrease in net molecular mobility. Consequently, less molecular momentum decreases the thermal boundary layer thickness and the temperature profile.

VI. CONCLUSION

The steady two-dimensional boundary layer flow and heat transfer of Fe₂O₃ and Fe-water base nanofluid over a flat stretching/shrinking sheet with radiation and slip effects were studied numerically in this paper. The nanofluid model in [7] is used with a porous medium. The similarity transformation is used to convert the system of partial differential equations into ordinary differential equations. The shooting method is used to solve these equations numerically. Due to the existence of dual solutions, stability analysis is performed using `bvp4c` in Matlab. The following conclusions are drawn based on the numerical investigations:

- Dual solutions are observed for certain ranges of stretching/shrinking and suction parameters.
- Stability analysis shows that one solution is stable and physically reliable while the other is unstable.
- The skin friction coefficient decreases for $\lambda > 0$ and increases for $\lambda < 0$ as the rate of suction is increased.
- The heat transfer rate and the skin friction coefficient are decreasing in the second solution when the velocity slip parameter δ increases.

- Fe-water nanofluid shows a greater rate of skin friction and Nusselt number as compared to Fe₂O₃-water nanofluid.
- An increase in nanoparticles' volume fraction decreases the skin friction coefficient and increases the Nusselt number.
- Increase in velocity slip, suction, nanoparticles volume fraction, and shrinking parameters decreases the velocity profiles and the associated boundary layers thicknesses.
- The rise in nanoparticle volumetric fraction and radiation increases the temperature profiles and the boundary layer thicknesses.

TABLE II. COMPARISON ALONG THE VARIATION OF $f''(0)$, AND $-\theta'(0)$ WITH λ AT $s = 2, Pr = 6.2, \delta = 0.1, \phi = 0.1, \delta_T = 0.7$ AND $Rd = 1.5$ FOR FE-WATER BASE NANOFUID

Parameter λ	Shooting method		bvp4c method	
	$f''(0)$	$-\theta'(0)$	$f''(0)$	$-\theta'(0)$
-1	1.2976198	0.83568	1.297520	0.83667
-0.6	0.919529	0.59991	0.919595	0.598838
0	0.00000	0.88279	0.00000	0.883671
0.5	-0.92239	0.8969	-0.92356	0.89789
1	-1.69817	0.90856	-1.69773	0.90891

TABLE III. SMALLEST EIGENVALUES AGAINST VARIOUS δ AND Rd VALUES WHEN $\delta_T = 0.7, \phi = 0.1, \lambda = -1, S = 2$ AND $Pr = 6.2$ FOR FE-WATER BASE NANOFUID

Parameters		bvp4c method	
δ	Rd	1 st solution	2 nd solution
0.2	0.5	0.83568	-1.297520
0.2	1	0.59991	-0.919595
0.3	0.3	0.88279	-0.00000
0.4	0.6	0.8969	-0.92356

TABLE IV. CRITICAL POINT VALUES OF THE INVESTIGATED NANOFUIDS

Parameters	Numerical values	Critical point (Fe)	Critical point (Fe ₂ O ₃)
S	2	-1.552	-1.1675
	2.15	-1.811	-1.357
	2.3	-2.092	-1.565
ϕ	0	1.9096	1.9096
	0.1	1.666	1.825
	0.2	1.625	1.859

Fig. 2. Skin-friction $f''(0)$ variation against various λ and S values.

Fig. 3. Nusselt number against various λ and S values.

Fig. 4. Skin-friction against various S and ϕ values.

Fig. 5. Nusselt number against various S and ϕ values.

Fig. 6. Skin-friction against ϕ for the particular nanoparticles in water base nanofluid.

Fig. 7. Nusselt number against ϕ for particular nanoparticles in water base nanofluid.

Fig. 11. Temperature $\theta(\eta)$ against various S values.

Fig. 8. Velocity $f'(\eta)$ against various ϕ values.

Fig. 12. Velocity $f'(\eta)$ against various λ values.

Fig. 9. Temperature $\theta(\eta)$ against various ϕ values.

Fig. 13. Temperature $\theta(\eta)$ against various λ values.

Fig. 10. Velocity $f'(\eta)$ against various S values.

Fig. 14. Temperature $\theta(\eta)$ against various Pr values.

Fig. 15. Temperature $\theta(\eta)$ against various Rd values.

Fig. 16. Velocity $f'(\eta)$ against various δ values.

Fig. 17. Temperature $\theta(\eta)$ against various δ_T values.

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Evaluation of the Effect of Tightening Torque on Single-lap Bolted Joints

Djamal Boualamallah

Laboratory of Materials and Reactive Systems
University of Sidi Bel Abbes
Sidi Bel Abbes, Algeria
djamal.boualamallah@yahoo.com

Abdelkader Ghazi

Laboratory of Materials and Reactive Systems
University of Sidi Bel Abbes and
University of Mascara
Algeria
ghaziaek@yahoo.fr

Abdelkader Miloudi

Laboratory of Materials and Reactive Systems
University of Sidi Bel Abbes
Sidi Bel Abbes, Algeria
miloudidz@yahoo.fr

Mohamed Merzoug

Laboratory of Materials and Reactive Systems
University of Sidi Bel Abbes
Sidi Bel Abbes, Algeria
m_merzoug01@yahoo.fr

Abstract-In this experimental research, a set of tests was conducted on single-lap bolted joints in terms of choosing between two types of bolts and exploiting the optimal solution for connecting samples. Then the effect of the tightening torque on the mechanical behavior of single-lap joints was evaluated. Six simple tensile tests were performed with different values of torque and the results are reported.

Keywords-bolted assembly; mechanical behavior; experimental approach; damage mechanisms

I. INTRODUCTION

The construction of a structure generally involves the assembly of parts. Different assembly technologies can be used: bolting, riveting, gluing, welding, or their combinations. It is natural to assume that increasing the number of the elements that contribute to the connection increases the complexity of the structure as a whole [1]. The advantage of bolted structures is their ease of installation [2-3]. This type of connection concerns both metal sheets (aluminum, steel, etc.) and composite sheets, with aluminum or steel bolt bodies. The use of this type of structure requires the mastery of their mechanical strength. Several previous works have focused on the study of the mechanical characterization of bolted connections. These studies have focused on several aspects, including the following:

- The flexibility of the fixation.
- Load transfer.
- Stress concentrations.
- The effect of torque.
- The effect of the clearance between the bore and the body of the bolt.

- The different modes of rupture, etc.

This type of assembly has the interesting advantage of its ease of realization (drilling of holes in the plates and mounting of the fastener with or without washers). Moreover, the use of bolted assembly implies that the maintenance of a mechanical system is easier because we can repair or change the component that cannot function properly without separating all the parts of the structure. Moreover, this type of assembly makes the transport and delivery of the components easier. The bolted assembly allows minimizing the volume of finished products. Nevertheless, the presence of the bore hole is the weak point of this type of structure due to the concentration of stresses which is often the main cause of crack initiation. The dimensioning of this type of assembly must be based on numerical behavior models that allow choosing and optimizing the design parameters (dimensions), bolt and sheet (plate) properties, tightening torque, number of bolts, spacing between bolts, etc. that are optimal in terms of strength or stiffness. Difficulty also lies in determining the load transfer rate between the bolt and the plates. It is important to note that in the case of complex three-dimensional structures containing a large number of fasteners, the importance of nonlinearities (behavior, contact) would quickly lead to excessive memory and calculation time requirements [1].

Several research studies on bolted connections have addressed the influence of torque on their overall mechanical behavior under static and dynamic stresses [2]. Authors in [4] have experimentally studied the mechanical strength of a bolted composite plate connection subjected to tensile-shear stress by analyzing the effects of the diameter of the washers and the value of the tightening torque. Figure 1 shows that the increase in the tightening is accompanied by the breaking stress, but the configuration in terms of geometry of the sample is different in our research. Authors in [5] carried out a numerical simulation

of a bolted connection of aluminum plates of thickness $e=2\text{mm}$, with three values of the tightening torque $C_s= 1, 1.5, \text{ and } 2\text{kN}$. It was shown that the elastic load increases with the value of the tightening torque. Authors in [6] studied the caulking around the fastener. The loss of preload and its influence on stress distribution was studied in [7]. Authors in [8] studied the multi-line structure of fasteners under mechanical and thermal loading, taking into account several parameters such as clearance, friction between plates and transferred load. The analytical solution of this study is based on the principle of virtual powers. Recently, authors in [9] studied the bolted joint in uni-axial tension, using two models, the first one based on Latham and Crookoft energy, and the second one based on Gurson continuous damage. It was shown that the behavior of the structure is composed of 8 phases: linear elasticity of the material, sliding of the sheets corresponding to the bore/bolt clearance, matting phase, linear elasticity phase of the structure, plasticization phase around the substrate bores, stable and then unstable cracking phase which ends in rupture. It was found that if the tightening torque is low, the slippage appears earlier.

In the work presented in this paper, we have studied the influence of the tightening torque and the bolt material (hardened and galvanized steel) on the strength of single-lap bolted connections through experimental tests. Predicting failure mode in steel connection is a complicated task, requiring knowledge of stress distribution in the connection and understanding of different failure modes with different loading configurations. It is very difficult to model the complicated failure mechanism by analytical methods [10].

II. MATERIAL

The material used is galvanized steel grade H300LAD+Z. Figure 1 shows the elasto-plastic stress-strain curve behavior of the steel. Such materials are characterized by increased mechanical strength and the ability to resist static and shock [11].

Fig. 1. Typical load-displacement curve of a specimen.

The mechanical characteristics (Table I) of the base metal such as yield strength σ_e , ultimate tensile strength σ_u , deformation ϵ , and Young's modulus E were obtained from the curve in Figure 1.

TABLE I. MECHANICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Tensile test result	Characteristics			
	σ_e [MPa]	σ_u [MPa]	E [MPa]	ϵ [%]
Value	410.12	580.22	210317.9	0.195

III. BOLTS USED

The type of bolts used is hexagonal head steel (Figure 2). For the bolts, the quality class is symbolized by two numbers. The first is one hundredth of the minimum tensile strength or [MPa] of the material and the other is 10 times the ratio between the minimum yield strength (σ_e) and the breaking strength R_r . The first series of bolts used are made of 4.8 galvanized steel with yield strength, $\sigma_e = 320\text{MPa}$ and breaking strength $\sigma_r = 400\text{MPa}$. During the tightening operation with the minimum tightening torque ($C=19\text{Nm}$) the wear of the bolt threads is obtained (Figure 3). The second series of bolts used are made of hardened and tempered steel at 400°C of class 8.8 M5-20-10 (Figure 2), whose dimensions are: Nominal diameter 5.8mm, pitch: 0.8mm, $\sigma_r \approx 800\text{MPa}$, and $\sigma_e \approx 640\text{MPa}$. The hexagonal nut M5 - 10, is characterized by: Minimum tensile stress $\approx 800\text{MPa}$, yield strength $\sigma_e \approx 640\text{MPa}$, pitch = 0.8mm, and thickness = 4.6mm. The flat washer is made of ordinary steel and has the following dimensions: Minimum diameter = 6.5mm, maximum diameter = 12mm, and thickness = 1.6mm.

Fig. 2. Bolt symbolization.

Fig. 3. Wear of the zinc-plated steel bolt (4.8).

Fig. 4. Oil-hardened steel bolt.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A. Test Specimens and Machine

When installing an assembly (bolt + washer + nut), it is essential to apply an appropriate tightening torque. This tightening torque is used to tension the bolt in order to keep the elements in contact. A torque wrench of ECO BUDGET brand - 19-110 NM -1/2in was used (Figure 5). The thickness of the sheet metal is 2mm. The types of specimens were tested as a single lap joint (Figure 5). Six values of tightening torque were used: 19, 25, 30, 33, 36, and 39N.m. In order to avoid the effects of friction with the nut of the bolt, a support washer was placed. The most frequently used single-bolt specimen is the Tension-Shear (TSS) specimen (Figure 6). The geometry of tensile-shear specimens is defined by [12, 13].

Fig. 5. Torque wrench ECO BUDGET.

Fig. 6. The studied configurations.

In this case, the bolt is stressed mainly with shear, but this stress is not pure. A bending moment is induced that tends to cause the plates to bend and deflect (Figure 7). It has been observed that the point of higher concentration of stress was in the first threads of the screw, near the screw head, whatever load was applied [14].

Fig. 7. Single lap joint loaded in tension-shear (sheet deformation - spacing).

B. Influence of Torque

At the beginning of the tensile test of the assembly and the movement of the pieces on each other, the two influential parameters are the coefficient of friction and the torque. The first one is influenced by the surface condition and lubrication of the parts. The greater the clamping force, the greater the tensile force will be to obtain a relative displacement of the two substrates. In order to find the influence of the tightening torque, we performed tensile tests using 6 tightening torque values: 19, 25, 30, 33, 36, and 39Nm, on a specimen with a bolt fastening. The substrates have a bore diameter of 6mm corresponding to a clearance of 0.2mm. The test results are presented by the load-displacement curves in Figure 8. For the high torque $M=40\text{Nm}$, the thread was damaged by rotation and the high torque power which produced heat and damaged the structure (Figure 9). Figure 10 shows the maximum load that the connection can support for different torque values. We notice that the optimal results are for the tightening torques of 25 and 30Nm. This is because the tightening torque mainly influences the elastic phase before sliding and the maximum level of load [2-17]. The tightening torque has been correctly introduced by applying local compression to the substrate and by pulling the bolt, thus allowing the prestressing forces to be introduced into the substrates [17].

Fig. 8. Tensile curve load – displacement for 6 values of torque.

Fig. 9. Thread breakage.

Fig. 10. Variation of maximum load vs of torque.

C. History of the Damage Mechanism of a Bolted Assembly

The mechanical strength of bolted connections has been the subject of several studies. Studies related to the mechanical strength in tension-shear, dynamics, fatigue, etc. can be found in the literature [2-9]. This work has been undertaken with the objective of identifying the chronology of fastener damage. Figure 11 shows the evolution of the applied load as a function of the total displacement of the structure.

Fig. 11. Load vs displacement of a bolted assembly.

Figure 11 highlights different phases of accommodation of the connection: (1) friction and sliding of the sheets, (2) elastic transfer, (3) plastic transfer phase of secondary bending, (4)

pull-out of the element and breakage of the connection. From the knowledge of the different zones it is possible to deduce the stiffness of the bolted connection K , the elastic limit of the joint, and the breaking load.

D. Breaking Mode and Edge Effect

In these tensile experiments that produced a shear stress, the process was performed according to the standard and all recommended conditions for this type of test, so the results (Figure 12) were in agreement with the literature used in the field of assemblies (shear stress and peel). Figure 13 shows the failure modes for tightening torques of 19 and 39Nm. We note that the failure occurred at the bolt, by shearing with a small displacement at the level of the structure of 5.6mm for $M=39Nm$ and 6.3mm for $M=19Nm$. The maximum torque creates torsion in the bolt diameter, which means that the bolt is damaged before the tensile test. The low value of the torque $M=19Nm$ does not create the necessary adhesion for the structure [18].

Fig. 12. Mixed tensile-shear failure mode.

Fig. 13. Mode of rupture for $M=19Nm$ and $M=39Nm$.

Fig. 14. Mode of rupture for $M=33Nm$ and $M=36Nm$.

For torques $M=33Nm$ and $M=36Nm$, it can be seen from Figure 14 that the strength is comparable with respect to the torque $M=19Nm$, but the displacement is significant with

respect to the latter; because the large value of the torque gives a clear adhesion between the substrates [15-19], so we have a mixed traction-shear failure mode.

For torques $M=25\text{Nm}$ and $M=30\text{Nm}$ it can be seen from Figure 15 that the resistance is high compared to the other torques. In this case, the mode of failure is acceptable [15-17], which means the deformation occurs at the bolt hole, and the bolt was not broken by the tensile operation.

Fig. 15. Mode of rupture for $M=25\text{Nm}$ and $M=30\text{Nm}$.

It can be seen that the mode of failure is ductile because of the presence of the cups in the majority of the fracture surface. Figure 16 shows the failure faces of the bolts. It is noted that the failure mode is ductile because of the presence of cups in the majority of the failure surface. The fracture face (which may also be located under the head of the bolt) has a grainy appearance which may be distributed at several levels of the threaded part. There is a generally localized break on the threaded part of the bolt. This rupture follows a plastic deformation of the material.

Fig. 16. Faces of bolt failure.

V. CONCLUSION

The indispensability of knowing the properties and mechanical characteristics of the components before any

construction or assembly obliges us to always develop our instruments and means of calculation, testing and even control when it comes to the use of standardized components such as bolts. At the end of the work carried out within the framework of this article, which deals with the study of the rupture and damage of a bolted assembly made of thin sheets of thickness $e=2\text{mm}$ in galvanized steel, we conclude to the following:

- The nature of the material of the bolt has an overall influence on the behavior of the structure (type of steel).
- The correct torque for the connection extends its service life, so the value of the torque applied to the bolt must be carefully selected, because it has an obvious impact on the modification of the behavior of the structure and thus exceeds the danger from the point of view of fracture mechanics.

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A Distributed Control Approach for Demand Response in Smart Grids

Atef El Gharbi

Faculty of Computing and Information Technology
Northern Border University

Rafha, Saudi Arabia

Institut National des Sciences Appliquées et de Technologie (INSAT), LISI

Carthage University

Tunisia

atef.gharbi@nbu.edu.sa

Abstract—The smart grid is a new concept that has been developed during recent years to improve the intelligence and efficiency of electric power system management. Traditional electricity systems are combined and integrated with information technology, communication technology, and intelligent control technology in the smart grid. Demand Response (DR) refers to the changes in consumers' electricity consumption behavior in response to dynamic pricing or financial incentives. Based on the control manner, DR methods are classified as centralized or distributed. In distributed techniques, customers communicate with the other consumers and provide data to the power utility about the overall use. In this paper, we focus on the distributed approach of DR using the shifting method for a short-term horizon. To be more specific, three well-known solutions were studied: the Resource Allocation with Legitimate Claims, the Constrained Fair-Splitting Dispatch, and Real-Time Pricing. Finally, we compare the different techniques of DR distributed approaches based on the control mechanism.

Keywords—demand response; distributed approach; resource allocation with legitimate claims; constrained fair-splitting dispatch problem; real-time pricing

I. INTRODUCTION

Demand Response (DR) is a technique describing the way the demand side responds to the supply-side price techniques or incentive measures [1-3]. DR leads to modifications in end-use customer consumption patterns as a result of the changes in electricity pricing over time or incentive payments designed at encouraging lesser energy use during periods when the market prices are higher or when system reliability is affected. DR is a cost-effective way to minimize power usage, and the cost of putting it in place is less than the cost of adding more generation capacity to get the same result [4]. The fundamental advantage of DR is that it improves power system use by establishing a closer relation between customers' consumption and the electricity price [5]. DR is becoming increasingly crucial in the interaction between supply and demand, which is the most critical aspect of the smart grid compared to traditional power systems. When consumers participate in DR programs, they are more likely to decrease their electricity use

during critical peak periods or shift some peak demand to off-peak periods [6]. As a result, the economy and security of the electricity systems are improved. Customers can react to high prices in one of the following methods [7]:

- Foregoing is a method for limiting electricity consumption during times of high prices, but not consuming it thereafter.
- Shifting is a technique to reschedule power usage from high-priced periods to other times.
- Onsite generation is a method where some users have backup emergency generators that can be used to respond partially or totally to their use demands.

In this paper, we are interested in the shifting method as it is the most used in DR.

DR methods are classified as centralized and distributed, based on their control mechanism. In the centralized approach, customers interact directly with the power utility, without communicating with each other. In the distributed approach, consumers communicate with the others and inform the power utility about its use [8]. The main contributions of this paper are: (1) the introduction and exhibitions of results of the most famous distributed solutions for DR using the short-term horizon shifting method, (2) addressing a comparison between the distributed solutions.

II. BACKGROUND

DR methods are classified as centralized or distributed, based on the control mechanism. In centralized DR, the response decisions for energy assignment or load scheduling are solely handled by the power utility, based on groups formed by sets of customers. In this method, each consumer participates without having to be aware of the other customers in the group's involvement [9]. Furthermore, fixing the problems centrally necessitates transferring all the consumers' personal data to the aggregator, resulting in significant communication overhead and privacy problems. This central strategy, on the other hand, always entails a large computational load along with the privacy issue. In the

distributed approach, the power utility's key role is the delivery of pricing information, depended on the total system consumption. Customers can manage directly with one another to accomplish aggregated load reduction. Unlike a central authority which collects data to make decisions, the decentralized control ensures scalability and protection of consumer privacy [10]. In the literature review, there were found two primary families on distributed DR approaches. The first group includes techniques that treat energy uses as continuous [11] which makes the underlying DR issue convex and hence computationally feasible. The second group includes techniques representing energy uses as a combination of discrete and continuous uses [12].

The interaction between consumers and providers can be divided into 3 approaches based on the time scale: long-term horizon, medium-term horizon, and short-term horizon. Price-based demand response is concerning customers' energy consumption changes in reaction to changes in their purchase prices [13]. This category includes Real-Time Pricing (RTP), Time-Of-Use (TOU), and Critical-Peak Pricing (CPP). For RTP, electricity prices are set for a short-term horizon of time, usually one hour [14], to match fluctuations in wholesale electricity prices. Customers are frequently given price information a day or hour ahead of time. TOU defines different costs for medium-term horizon of time, which are commonly established in 24-hour increments [15]. CPP is a combination of TOU and RTP, and it is more difficult to implement [16]. The base program is TOU, and under certain circumstances, substantially higher peak pricing is used (e.g. whenever the system reliability is affected or when power costs are very elevated). Incentive-Based Programs (IBPs) control consumption without using power costs. Instead, customers agree to reduce their load during crucial circumstances and to be paid for that [17]. The load can be controlled in two ways. It might be the utility that guides the load and takes appropriate actions, or it could be the consumers the ones who take appropriate actions in the event of an emergency. Classic programs and market-based programs [18-20] are the two types of incentive-based programs.

To the best of our knowledge, no research has been published about the evaluation of the different DR techniques in a distributed way using the shifting method for a short-term horizon. In this paper, the assessment of three different distributed DR techniques is conducted. The scope is to provide a very contribution in the awareness of the best approach based on specific criteria.

III. DISTRIBUTED DR CONTROL ALGORITHMS

In a centralized solution, the DR procedure is controlled by only one unit, which gathers the demand information from the customers and then makes decisions for demand scheduling. In distributed DR, demand information is not centrally gathered and customers have direct access to grid state meters. With this information, consumers are able to react based on the system's state, if it is critical. In this section, we present the most important techniques related to DR of smart grid as distributed approach.

A. Resource Allocation with Legitimate Claims (RALC)

In RALC, the provider agent must determine how much energy $\pi_{i,t}^{in}$ each customer agent should be assigned, taking into account certain limits. As a result, the energy demand allocation problem is to consider how much energy should be allocated to each customer agent $\pi_{i,t}^{in}$. The proposed allocation method is based on distributive fairness and is self-organized [21]. Customer agents agree on the criteria for conducting the allocation. Any of the provider agents then computes this allocation. The allocation is done pursuant to a set of canons in distributive justice. To this purpose, we propose the following mechanism for agreeing on load allocation at a certain time t (hour):

1. Information about the load $L(t)$ is available at the provider agent (t).
2. Every customer agent i sends a request to the provider agent asking the desired power $\pi_{i,t}^{in}$ as well as the constraints $\pi_{i,t}^{min}$ and $\pi_{i,t}^{max}$.
3. The provider agent calculates the total amount of power requested $\pi_t, \pi_t^{min}, \pi_t^{max}$. There could be a variety of scenarios:
 - $L_t = \pi_t^{min}$: If the equality holds, all customer agents are given the smallest amount of authority, $\pi_{i,t}^{in} = \pi_{i,t}^{min}$.
 - $\pi_t^{min} \leq L_t \leq \pi_t^{max}$: Customer agents are assigned power within their needed range. Each customer agent's power is assigned by the provider agent based on a rank attributed according to a set of weights. Weights are assigned to all customer agents after they reached an agreement a set of canons. In this case, every customer receives power $\pi_{i,t}^{in}$ such that:

$$\pi_{i,t}^{in} \leftarrow \pi_{i,t}^{min} + \min(L_t - \pi_{i,t}^{min}, \pi_{i,t} - \pi_{i,t}^{min})$$
 - $L_t \geq \pi_t^{max}$: The customer agent obtains the exact amount of power required, $\pi_{i,t}^{in} = \pi_{i,t}^{max}$.
4. The provider agent provides each customer agent with the computed allocation $\pi_{i,t}^{in}$.
5. Each customer agent must pay $\lambda_t \times \pi_{i,t}^{in}$ in accordance to the provided energy $\pi_{i,t}^{in}$.

The second protocol in step 3 is crucial, as it requires the customer agents to agree on the way the load will be divided. To do so, the Rescher's canons are used as voting functions f_* for the allocation, and the relevance of each function is decided by its associated weight w_* . The process of determining the way the load is divided is essentially an allocation procedure that is frequently applied. The weights' initial value is set at $w_* = \frac{1}{m}$ (where m represents the functions number), and the procedure proceeds as follows:

A consensus on a particular ranked list of customer agents should be reached in order to proceed with the allocation. The

Borda count protocol is used as a consensus-based voting approach. In the Borda count process, each function f^* is considered as a voter. Each vote in Borda count voting sorts the candidates based on a specific criterion. Each candidate in the list is given Borda points: for example, if we have n customer agents, then the rank k receives $n - k + 1$ Borda points. The Borda points obtained from each vote are added together to give a total Borda score for every agent. The candidate having the highest Borda score gains the Borda count procedure, however it is possible to find several "winners," therefore we construct a Borda point queue in decreasing order and assign electricity to the head of the queue until there are no more to allocate. Under a set of functions F , the Borda score B of candidate i is calculated by:

$$B(i, F) = \sum_{f^* \in F} w_{f^*} \times bpts(f^*(i)) \quad (1)$$

where $f^*(i)$ determines each f^* 's rank order for candidate i , $bpts()$ computes the Borda points for that rank, and w_{f^*} is the weight associated with the function f^* .

The Borda count function returns the Borda_ptq list after computing the Borda score B for each agent i . Algorithm 1 presents the main idea explained above, where A is a set of N Consumer agents, and F is a set of m voting functions f^* , each with its own weight w_{f^*} .

Algorithm 1. Resource Allocation with Legitimate Claims.

```

1: For each time slot  $t \in T$  do
2:    $\pi_t \leftarrow 0, \pi_t^{\min} \leftarrow 0$ 
3:   for each customer agent  $i \in N$  do
4:      $\pi_{i,t} \leftarrow \pi_t + \pi_{i,t}$ 
5:      $\pi_{i,t}^{\min} \leftarrow \pi_{i,t}^{\min} + \pi_{i,t}$ 
6:   end for
7:    $L_t \leftarrow \text{update}(L_t)$ 
8:   If  $L_t > \pi_t$  then
9:     for each customer agent  $i \in N$  do
10:       $\pi_{i,t}^{\text{in}} \leftarrow \pi_{i,t}$ 
11:    End for
12:   Else if  $L_t > \pi_t^{\min} \ // \ L_t < \pi_t$ 
13:      $\text{rank orders} \leftarrow []$ 
14:     for every voting function  $f^* \in F$  do
15:        $\text{rank orders} \leftarrow \text{rank orders} \cup f^*(A)$ 
16:     end for
17:      $\text{Borda\_ptq} \leftarrow \text{Borda count}(\text{rank orders}, F)$ 
18:     repeat
19:        $i \leftarrow \text{head}(\text{Borda\_ptq}) \ // \ \text{customer } i$ 
20:        $\text{Borda\_ptq} \leftarrow \text{tail}(\text{Borda\_ptq})$ 
21:        $\pi_{i,t}^{\text{in}} \leftarrow \pi_{i,t}^{\min} + \min(L_t - \pi_{i,t}^{\min}, \pi_{i,t} - \pi_{i,t}^{\min})$ 
22:        $L_t \leftarrow L_t - \pi_{i,t}^{\text{in}}$ 
23:     until  $(\text{Borda\_ptq} = \text{Null})$ 
24:   else  $// \ L_t = \pi_t^{\min}$  then
25:     for each customer agent  $i \in N$  do

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26:        $\pi_{i,t}^{\text{in}} \leftarrow \pi_{i,t}^{\min}$ 
27:     End for
28:   End if
29: End for
30: End

```

As a running example, Figure 1 depicts the agents ranked by a group of voters, each of whom creates its own rank list. Borda points are assigned to each rank in a list and then are combined together in a weighted sum to produce a single final rank list and final Borda score for each agent.

Fig. 1 The Borda count voting mechanism in a simple form.

B. Constrained Fair-Splitting Dispatch (CFSD)

SFSD is the most famous DR method. At first, we consider a direct graph $G = \{V, E\}$ where each customer i can possibly transmit information to other customers called its neighbors N_i . The customers sending data (respectively receiving data) to the customer i are called the in-neighbors (respectively out-neighbors) of i and are represented by the set N_i^- (respectively $N_i^+ = \{j \in V: (i, j) \in E\}$). The number of in-neighbors (respectively out-neighbors) of agent i is called the in-degree (respectively out-degree) and is denoted by D_i^- (respectively D_i^+). Π denotes the total amount of power that the system should collectively deliver, i.e.: $\Pi = \sum_{i=1}^n \pi_i$. The ratio consensus technique is explained below. Consider the exchange of data between customers in a direct graph where each customer i in the graph keeps two values, y_i and z_i , called internal states, which are independent and updated as a linear combination of customer i 's prior internal states and the past internal states of its in-neighbors respectively. For each $k \geq 0$, each customer i updates y_i and z_i , in the following way [22]:

$$y_i(k+1) = \sum_{j \in N_i^-} \frac{1}{D_j^+} y_j(k) \quad (2)$$

$$z_i(k+1) = \sum_{j \in N_i^+} \frac{1}{D_j^-} z_j(k) \quad (3)$$

$\forall k$, customer i computes:

$$\gamma_i(k) = \frac{y_i(k)}{z_i(k)} \quad (4)$$

Lemma 1: For every customer i , it is demonstrated in [22] the convergence of $\gamma_i(k)$ to some constant γ .

Then, each customer i asymptotically obtains:

$$\gamma = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \gamma_i(k) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n y_j(0)}{\sum_{j=1}^n z_j(0)} \quad (5)$$

Without loss of generality, we assume that the total resource amount Π is known to a power entity V , who is able to exchange data with specific customers V^+ (having a number m). Besides, the initial conditions in (2) are set to $y_i(0) = \Pi / m - \pi_i^{\min}$ if $i \in V^+$, and $y_i(0) = -\pi_i^{\min}$ otherwise. Moreover, the initial conditions in (3) are set to $z_i(0) = \pi_i^{\max} - \pi_i^{\min}$, $\forall i$. Then, as long as $\sum_{i=1}^n \pi_i^{\min} \leq \Pi \leq \sum_{i=1}^n \pi_i^{\max}$, we conclude from Lemma 1 that the i -th node can asymptotically determine its contribution π_i as:

$$\pi_i = \pi_i^{\min} + \gamma(\pi_i^{\max} - \pi_i^{\min}) \quad (6)$$

where:

$$\gamma = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \gamma_i(k) = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{y_i(k)}{z_i(0)} = \frac{\Pi - \sum_{j=1}^n \pi_j^{\min}}{\sum_{j=1}^n (\pi_j^{\max} - \pi_j^{\min})} \quad (7)$$

Note that (6) satisfies $\pi_i^{\min} < \pi_i < \pi_i^{\max}$, $\forall i$, and also $\sum_{i=1}^n \pi_i = \Pi$. Additionally, every customer i can independently declare infeasibility if $\gamma > 1$ or $\gamma < 0$. The solution in (6) is not considered as the optimal solution, but it ensures a "fair" splitting of the total amount of resource Π proportional to the "excess" capacity of each node.

As a running example, Figure 2 depicts the convergence of $\gamma_i(k)$ for $j = 1, \dots, 4$ over 30 iterations. We can conclude from the graph that after about 13 iterations, all customers obtain a common value $\gamma = 0.9$. As a result, the customers decide the solution is possible and update their output in accordance with (6), obtaining $x = [0.279, 0.129, 0.364, 0.228]^T$.

Fig. 2 Convergence of constrained fair-splitting dispatch algorithm.

C. Real-Time Pricing (RTP) Algorithm

The provider agent modifies its energy supply tactics in every iteration, based on the consumer agents' energy

consumption strategies, whereas the consumer agent i adjusts its energy consumption based on real-time costs (see Figure 3). We present here the Optimal RTP algorithm based on the utility maximization for smart grid [23] in which:

$\pi_{i,j}^{t*}$ is the optimal requested power by the consumer agent i to the provider agent j , λ_j^t is the updated price by the provider agent j , $L_i^*(\lambda_j^t)$ is the capacity update, and μ_j^t the coordination parameter. The requested power is:

$$\pi_{i,j}^{t*}(\lambda_j^t) = \arg \max_{\pi_{i,j}^{\min} \leq \pi_{i,j}^* \leq \pi_{i,j}^{\max}} U(\pi_{i,j}^*, \omega_{i,t}) - \lambda_j^t \pi_{i,j}^* \quad (8)$$

and the price update is provided by:

$$\lambda_j^{t+1} = \left[\lambda_j^t + \gamma \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \pi_{i,j}^{t*}(\lambda_j^t) - L_i^*(\lambda_j^t) \right) \right]^+ \quad (9)$$

where $[x]^+ = \max\{x, 0\}$.

The capacity update is given by:

$$L_j^*(\lambda_j^t) = \arg \max_{L_j^{\min} \leq L_j^* \leq L_j^{\max}} \lambda_j^t L_j^* - C_i(L_j^*) \quad (10)$$

and the coordination parameter by:

$$\mu_i^{t+1} = \left[\mu_i^t - \gamma \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \pi_{i,j}^{t*}(\lambda_j^t) - b_i \right) \right]^+ \quad (11)$$

1) Real-Time Pricing Formulation

Algorithm 2: Executed at consumer agent i .

- 1: for every $t \in T$
- 2: Receive the new price λ_j^t from the provider agent j .
- 3: Compute the consumption value $\pi_{i,j}^{t*}$ using (8).
- 4: Send the updated $\pi_{i,j}^{t*}$ to the provider agent j .
- 5: Calculate the coordination parameter μ_i^t by (11).
- 6: end for

Algorithm 3: Performed by the provider agent j .

- 1: repeat
- 2: if time $t \in T$
- 4: Calculate the new electricity price λ_j^t by solving (9).
- 5: Send the new price λ_j^t to each consumer i .
- 6: else
- 7: Update the capacity value $L_i(\lambda_j^t)$ using (10).
- 8: Receive $\pi_{i,t}^*$ from all the consumer agents $i \in N$.
- 9: Update the total load $\sum_{i \in N} \pi_{i,j}^{t*}$ accordingly.
- 10: end if
- 11: until the end of planned period.

The pricing mechanism proposed in this study aims to align social benefit with individual welfare, i.e. to find a suitable pricing so that the locally optimal solution is the same as the

globally optimal solution. From the Algorithm 2, the consumer agents are regarded independent agents who are responsible for their own well-being. To improve their benefits and contentment, each consumer agent requires a specific quantity of power. The mission of a smart grid is to manage the coordination of the customer agents to cover the requested power, so that there is a balance between energy production and consumption. Form the Algorithm 3, it is clear that the provider agent is trying to fulfill the consumer agents' requests or facilitate the coordination between customer agents so that they can guarantee the total requested power and maintain a balance between energy production and consumption (in accordance with the consumer agents' needs and constraints). The following characteristics are included in the proposed algorithms.

- Algorithms 2 and 3 are considered distributed algorithms in which each utility company and user solves the subproblems locally to allocate energy. There is no requirement for a central controller or a third party.
- Each user helps energy allocation by coordinating the demand from several power entities to satisfy his need.
- The distributed Algorithms 2 and 3 protect power entities' and customers' privacy. However, this leads to a more complicated solution.

Figure 3 depicts the communication between the utility company and the user in a multiseller–multibuyer system. The electricity pricing and energy demand are the two pieces of information that must be exchanged between the utility provider and the customer. Algorithms 2 and 3 summarize the distributed algorithms at each utility business and each user respectively. Each utility business adjusts its supply in response to the electricity price. Each utility company determines the price of power depending on its supply and demand from all customers. The price is then made public to all users. The electricity price and the user's coordination parameter are used to update each user's demand.

Fig. 3 Information exchange between the provider and the consumer agents.

2) Running Example

Figure 4 depicts the relationship between the provider's hourly fee and the consumed electricity. Customers actually lower their use during peak hours (as shown in the Figure at hours 18 and 19) because the price is doubled. Furthermore, clients determine the optimal consumption at the lowest price (in the Figure at hours 11 and 12): this is illustrating the most significant benefit of the RTP algorithm.

Fig. 4 Total power consumed with RTP algorithm.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Through this section, we study the features of each technique: DR with RALC, CFSD, and the RTP algorithm. Some numerical results illustrating the results of each are provided and compared. For the purposes of simulation throughout our research, we will use a network with $C = 7$ companies and $U = 150$ clients.

Figures 5 and 6 show the customers' average utility and energy usage as functions of the timeslots required for all comparative frameworks to converge to the steady customers' association with power companies. The results show that the RTP algorithm produces the highest consumer utility (Figure 5) and the lowest customer electricity consumption (Figure 6). This trend is the result of the use of (8)-(10), including both monetary and electricity-related aspects, as described above. Furthermore, the RALC, which is self-organized and based on distributive fairness, delivers acceptable outcomes in terms of consumers' utility and electricity consumptions. CFSD, on the other hand, does not optimize the electricity consumption and achieves the lowest customers' utility and high electricity consumption. When compared to the other two algorithms, the RTP algorithm outperforms both, demonstrating the huge benefit of using optimization in the overall process. The results reveal that: (a) The CFSD applies no optimization. Users choose time periods at random to place their schedulable loads. (b) The RALC is a greedy algorithm, in which everyone strives to reduce its total electricity cost by lowering the base price. This one simulates a scenario in which there is no cost fluctuation fee and users do not collaborate while making judgments. (c) The RTP algorithm provides optimal results.

Fig. 5 Customers' average utility.

Fig. 6 Customers' total energy consumption.

V. CONCLUSION

DR is an important subject in smart grid implementations, allowing better system operation and extension, and increased market efficiency. It can be used to lower the overall load in response to peak power constraints as well as for auxiliary services like frequency regulation, which has a faster scale reaction time. In this paper, we studied the most widely known techniques in distributed DR, namely RALC, CFS, RTP. We compared these techniques based on two criteria: customers' average utility and energy usage. The results show that the RTP technique is the best as it ensures the highest consumer utility as well as the lowest customer electricity consumption. For future work, it is possible to extend the distributed algorithms to make them robust to faulty consumers.

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An Intelligent Detoxification Function of Liver Algorithm-Partial Transmit Sequence (IDFLA-PTS) for the Reduction of Peak to Average Power Ratio in Underwater Acoustic OFDM Communication

Amir Ali

College of Underwater Acoustic Engineering and Key Laboratory of Marine Information Acquisition and Security, Ministry of Industry and Information Technology, and Acoustic Science and Technology Laboratory, Harbin Engineering University, Harbin, China
amir@hrbeu.edu.cn

Baowei Chen

College of Underwater Acoustic Engineering and Key Laboratory of Marine Information Acquisition and Security, Ministry of Industry and Information Technology, and Acoustic Science and Technology Laboratory, Harbin Engineering University, Harbin, China
cbwwin@163.com

Waleed Raza

College of Underwater Acoustic Engineering and Key Laboratory of Marine Information Acquisition and Security, Ministry of Industry and Information Technology, and Acoustic Science and Technology Laboratory, Harbin Engineering University, Harbin, China
waleed@hrbeu.edu.cn

Asif Ali

College of Nuclear Science and Technology
Harbin Engineering University
Harbin, China
aliasif@hrbeu.edu.cn

Haisen Li

College of Underwater Acoustic Engineering and Key Laboratory of Marine Information Acquisition and Security, Ministry of Industry and Information Technology, and Acoustic Science and Technology Laboratory, Harbin Engineering University, Harbin, China
hsenli@126.com

Abstract-Intelligent algorithms in artificial intelligence have brought several benefits to digital signal processing. The boom in machine learning and intelligent systems provides new perspectives and methods to solve many research problems in Underwater Acoustic (UWA) Orthogonal Frequency Divisional Multiplexing (OFDM) communication. Partial transmit sequence is a tremendous technique for the mitigation of high Peak-to-Average Power Ratio (PAPR) in OFDM communication systems, but finding the optimum phase factors has still a few problems. In this paper, a Partial Transmit Sequence (PTS) based on an Intelligent Detoxification Function of Liver Algorithm-Partial Transmit Sequence (IDFLA-PTS) is proposed for the mitigation of PAPR in the UWA OFDM communication systems. This algorithm reduces the PAPR and the complexity of the proposed UWA OFDM model. The IDFLA-PTS is also compared with the Genetic Algorithm-Partial Transmit Sequence (GA-PTS). Besides this, the Bit Error Rate (BER) performance of the IDFLA-PTS is shown when a High Power Amplifier (HPA) is used for the BELLHOP channel model. The experimental results of the proposed IDFLA-PTS method achieved nearly optimum results

with fair complexity as compared to GA-PTS and boosted the BER performance.

Keywords-underwater acoustic communication; OFDM; PAPR; Intelligent Detoxification Function of Liver Algorithm-Partial Transmit Sequence (IDFLA-PTS)

I. INTRODUCTION

The research on OFDM has been explored due to its distinct advantages over other techniques for wireless communication systems [1, 2]. Due to its optimum results, now many kinds of research have taken steps in underwater communication and exploration [3]. For any communication network, a system should be noiseless, with less multipath delay, and with less Doppler shift [4]. Underwater Acoustic Sensing Networks (UWASNs) are formed by deploying different underwater acoustic transmitters and receivers which monitor the ocean. The battery deployed modems are installed, which consumes more power depending on its applications. For short-range communications this is not an issue, but for long-

range UWA applications, it is necessary to save battery power. The OFDM system is utilized for high-speed communication, but due to its major drawback of PAPR, researchers have contributed a lot to mitigate it up to the maximum level. PAPR has bit error degradation and leads to nonlinear distortion and affects the power efficiency of power amplifiers in the underwater communication systems [5]. Therefore, the mitigation of PAPR has become a competitive and worth thinking research to have soft, reliable, and long-range communication in UWA communication. Linearly operating powerful amplifiers are needed for high peaks, but designing and manufacturing those powerful amplifiers is comparatively costly [6, 7].

A power amplifier is in the saturation region during high PAPR creating inter-symbol interference among subcarriers, manipulates thus the original signal resulting in lower BER performance. To avoid this scenario, the average power of the transmitting signal is reduced. But reducing the average power will lead to a reduction of BER performance as well as the Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR). However, to reduce the peak power of the signal, much research has been done previously [8-11]. Therefore, many researchers prefer to solve the problem of high PAPR by reducing the peak power of the transmitting signal. After experiments and simulations, many researchers have developed PAPR reduction methods like clipping, selective mapping, tone injection and reserved carriers, active constellation, coding, and partial transmit sequence [12-14]. Although clipping is the simplest technique, it clips the signals with unwanted peaks and distorts the communicating signal and increases BER. On the other hand, few techniques cause inefficient energy increment of the signal, such as tone injection, tone reservation, and active constellation. Selective mapping (SLM) is also an efficient technique having better performance than others, as it has no energy increment and it does not distort the communication signal, but it still is rather complex [15-17]. The PTS is the only efficient technique due to its distortionless feature with the least complexity. In this paper, we propose a PTS technique based on the Intelligent Detoxification Function of Liver algorithm (IDFLA) to minimize PAPR and acquire better performance than the GA-PTS system. The IDFLA is a self-efficacy algorithm that is extracted from medical science. It removes the toxic substances from the bloodstream and balances the hormonal level. Besides this, it breaks down fats and makes them more easily digestible.

II. RELATED WORK

A lot of work has been proposed to mitigate PAPR, but few researches have been found to use intelligent computing techniques. Therefore, the research on using various machine learning and deep learning algorithms still seeks attention for future generation networks. A few major articles are discussed below for both UWA OFDM communication networks and terrestrial networks. Authors in [18] proposed a novel method to reduce PAPR and nonlinear distortion at the receiver side using a machine learning algorithm. This method is named Frequentative Decision Feedback (FFB). This work was proposed for underwater acoustic OFDM communication. An energy-efficient underwater acoustic OFDM communication system was introduced in [19] without using any intelligent

algorithm for the reduction of PAPR. The authors used PTS as a PAPR mitigation tool. An artificial bee colony-based SLM technique was proposed in [16]. The authors used selective mapping as a PAPR reduction technique. However, the computational complexity was too high. The Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) method was used to mitigate the PAPR of the OFDM signal in [20]. This technique was based on adaptive PSO. This method also lacked in reducing the complexity of the overall system while searching the optimal combination of phase factors. Genetic Algorithm (GA) was proposed in [21-24] for PAPR mitigation. An efficient method using SLM Wavelet-OFDM (WOFDM) was used, which is based on a genetic machine learning algorithm. The optimum phase factors were searched using GA. In [25] the authors introduced a novel research, also based on GA. This technique performs well in reducing the peak signals in an OFDM system. The Tone Reservation (TR) method was used, which is based on the selection of the Peak Reduction Tone (PRT). However, finding an optimal PRT set of data is problematic, because the complexity of the system is increased exponentially while searching the PRT data set. This method also uses TR-based clipping which creates distortion and degrades the BER performance.

The current paper proposes a novel IDLFA approach with a lesser computational complexity. The proposed IDLFA-PTS based algorithm easily searches the optimum phase factors in PTS method and gives improved performance.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

The transmitted OFDM signal with N subcarriers in terms of the continuous-time domain can be expressed as:

$$x(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} X_n e^{j2\pi f_n t}, \quad 0 \leq t < NT \quad (1)$$

where $x(t)$ denotes the OFDM signal, f is the spacing of subcarriers, and NT indicates the data block interval, which carries useful information. The above equation can be written in terms of the discrete-time domain as:

$$x(n) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} X_k e^{j2\pi f_k n}, \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, N-1 \quad (2)$$

Here, the PTS technique is utilized, which focuses on the discrete-time domain hence taking into consideration (2). The main drawback of the OFDM communication system is the varying high peaks. The varying power of such high peaks is much greater than the average power when the subcarriers are added after the modulation block. The PAPR is the resultant of the ratio of maximum transferred signal power (power of varying high peaks) to the average transferred power.

$$\text{PAPR} = \frac{\max |x_n|^2}{E[|x_n|^2]} \quad (3)$$

The mathematically expected value of the OFDM signal can be defined by the $E[\cdot]$ operator. A function used to observe the overall performance of PAPR reduction is known as a Complementary Cumulative Distribution Function (CCDF), which is the most prominent way in the reduction of PAPR. Specifying $\text{PAPR}(1)$ is higher than $\text{PAPR}(0)$ (threshold level) and can be given as:

$$\text{CCDF} = P(\text{PAPR}(1) > \text{PAPR}(0)) \quad (4)$$

$$CCDF = 1 - (1 - e^{-PAPR(0)})^N \quad (5)$$

In Figure 1, the bit-stream of digitally inserted inputs is mapped with the constellation. After QPSK modulation symbols are further divided into subcarriers of length N. These subcarriers are added in a serial to parallel converter block to convert them into parallel for fast computation. The Inverse Fast Fourier Transform (IFFT) is applied to reduce the computational complexity instead of the more complex Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform (IDFT). The signal is then passed through a parallel to serial conversion to transmit the generated signal serially. After adding a Cyclic Prefix (CP), the signal is transmitted through an underwater acoustic channel. The process at the receiver end is the reverse. After removing the cyclic prefix, the serial bit stream is modified into parallel form. The parallel moving data are then demodulated by Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). Hence, the resulted data are converted from the frequency domain to the time domain. Thus, the serial signal at the receiving end has been improved, which is then compared with the transmitted source generated signal.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the system model.

IV. PTS TECHNIQUE FOR PAPR REDUCTION

A block of input stream data N (Symbols) is sub-divided into M disjoint sub-blocks using the partitioning method denoted as:

$$X = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} X^m \quad (6)$$

Generally, PTS has adopted 3 primary partitioning methods for the better reduction performance of PAPR, which are the interleaving scheme, the adjacent scheme, and the pseudo-random scheme. To choose less complex and best PAPR reduction performance, a pseudo-random scheme has been implemented in our proposed model. Sub-blocks are further oversampled by a factor of (L - 1)N zero paddings to estimate the value of PAPR in the continuous-time domain. IFFT is applied on the oversampled sub-blocks of size LN and transferred sub-blocks as:

$$X^m = [x_1^m, x_2^m, \dots, x_{LN-1}^m] \text{ where } 0 \leq m \leq M-1 \quad (7)$$

The n-th symbols of x(n) signal can be generated by the product of the m-th sub-blocks (X^m) with phase factors (bm) and summed up after applying IFFT. The OFDM signal after the PTS technique of phase rotated sub-blocks with the lowest PAPR is:

$$x(n) = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} b_m X^m \quad (8)$$

where b_m is the phase factor that can be defined as:

$$b_m = [b_1, b_2, b_3, \dots, b_{m-1}] = \arg \min(\max|\sum_{m=1}^M b_m X^m|) \quad (9)$$

The partial transmit sequence is the IFFT of sub-blocks (X^m). The selection of phase factors is the real aim of the PTS scheme. But comprehensively finding the optimal phase factors suffer from exponential complexity, so the choice is very much limited to specific elements to reduce the phase factor (b_m) complexity.

V. IDFLA FOR PTS

The IDFLA simulates the refining of blood and the maintenance of hormonal levels. The hepatic vein (a particular vein of the liver) carries alcohol and drugs to the liver for detoxification. Here nutrients are equivalent to phase factors. b_i = [b_{i1}, b_{i2}, ..., b_{im-1}], where i is taken up to the maximum number of substances denoted by max Am, which represents the maximum substances carried out by the vein towards the liver. To obtain optimal nutrients (vitamins, i.e. B12), the hepatic vein carries out alcohol and drug substances, from which the liver utilizes vitamins and eliminates the toxic (waste) materials from the body. In IDFLA-PTS, the source of the nutrients in terms of phase factor can be expressed as:

$$X_{new} = \theta(X_{old} - X_{threshold}) \quad (10)$$

where X_{threshold} is the threshold value up to which the liver controls the nutrients, X_{old} is the old value of substances for detoxification, and θ is the user-generated random variable within the specified limit of range taken as θ = [+1, ..., -1]. The proposed IDFLA-PTS model is depicted in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the proposed IDFLA-PTS.

The optimal value defines the Beneficial Nutrients (BN) required for a healthy body and will be considered as the best solution. The BN in terms of mathematical form can be given as:

$$BN = \frac{1}{1+f}, \dots, X_{new} \geq 0 \quad (11)$$

and it does not operate if {Halt, ..., X_{new} < 0} where X_{new} is the representation of the minimal expected value of PAPR in underwater acoustic communication. The liver collects all the substances to differentiate them with intelligent principles into beneficial nutrients and toxic substances, and then accepting the suitable nutrients according to their required level. The probability (Pr) of accepting nutrients is:

$$Pr = \frac{\text{acceptable nutrients}}{\text{summation of all acceptable nutrients}} \quad (12)$$

After accepting the nutrients, the liver looks for new alcoholic contaminated food and allows the food with nutrients. The liver repeats the whole detoxification process after some time in order to accept the remaining nutrients. An intelligent liver considers other substances as toxic and sends them to the waste part, and continues its function in order to maintain the health of the body.

$$\text{Possible BN} = (Pr \times X_{old}) - T_{limit-5} \quad (13)$$

if value is \geq threshold, then limit = -5
 if value is $<$ threshold, then put limit = 0

The steps defined are repeated in a continuous-time cycle to generate the possible beneficial nutrients. In the IDFLA-PTS algorithm, continuous-time cycle and possible beneficial nutrients are made to find the desired phase factors.

The steps of the proposed IDFLA-PTS algorithm are:

1. Set up the threshold value.
2. Take a random number θ within the specified range to generate a new phase factor.
3. Determine the best-fit phase factor by solving (11).
4. This value continues up to the given limit.
5. Go back to step 2 until the halt condition is not achieved. This process continues to generate the possible solutions.
6. New generated phase factor is calculated by (10) and the best fit is solved using (11).
7. Then the probability of beneficial nutrients can be achieved by (12).
8. Considering the remaining substance as toxic after multiple iterations, it starts the detoxification of new random contaminated food using (13).
9. The whole process is repeated until the beneficial nutrients for maintaining the health of the body are acquired.
10. Set and memorize the best fit values.

VI. SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In order to achieve optimum results of our proposed model, experiments were carried out in an underwater tank, while simulations were performed in MATLAB 2017b using the BELLHOP channel. The experiments in the water tank proved to have better results.

A. Simulations

In this section, simulation results and numerical analysis of the proposed IDFLA-PTS are given. The MATLAB version 2017b was used, the number of subcarriers during simulations in an underwater OFDM system is $N=512$, and QPSK modulation was employed. The Bellhop ray tracing communication channel was utilized. In the PTS technique, the partitioning is random. The number of sub-blocks was $M = 128, 256, 512$, along with $W=4$ selected phase factors. The phase factors became $bm \in \pm 1$. The PAPR in IDFLA-PTS and GA-PTS were compared and their comparison with different numbers of sub-blocks was conducted in terms of complexity. The best fit phase factor was chosen and then the sequence was generated as $bm = [b1, b2, bm-1]$. In GA-PTS, the selection of

b is random. The parameters that are implemented in the simulation are given in Table I. Figure 3 illustrates the performance of PAPR in the original OFDM signal and IDFLA-PTS. In IDFLA-PTS, by considering the sub-block number $M = [128, 256, 512]$. The PAPR of the conventional OFDM signal can be observed in the Figure, which is 11.22dB when the CCDF of PAPR is 10^{-3} . The ideal exact IDFLA measurement is 7.4dB, while the observed PAPR of the proposed IDFLA-PTS with different sub-blocks, i.e. 128, 256, and 512 is 8.2dB, 7.7dB, and 7.59dB respectively. It is observed that taking a greater number of M (sub-blocks) decreases PAPR. The improved performance and PAPR comparison of IDFLA-PTS and GA-PTS with $M = [128, 256, 512]$ sub-blocks are shown in Figure 4.

TABLE I. SIMULATION SYSTEM PARAMETERS

Serial number	Parameters	Data
1	Length of FFT points	8192
2	Number of subcarriers	512
3	Cyclic prefix time	21.56ms
4	Sound speed	1500m/s
5	Sampling frequency	96kHz
6	Signal modulation type	QPSK
7	OFDM symbol number	24
8	Modulation order	4
9	Up sampling rate	2
10	Maximum multipath delay	12ms
11	Bandwidth	6KHz

Fig. 3. PAPR comparison of IDFLA-PTS, exact IDFLA-PTS, and original OFDM signal.

The simulation of GA-PTS at $M=2048$ was an additional task in order to check the improved performance. After taking the mentioned sub-blocks, the PAPR values of GA-PTS were 8.62dB, 8.02dB, 7.65dB, and 7.5dB respectively. So, the difference in the PAPR of both methods for the same number of sub-blocks was 0.42dB, 0.32dB, and 0.06dB respectively. Concluding after the comparison, one can see that the performance of the proposed IDFLA-PTS method is better, faster, and more cost-effective, as it converges to 7.65dB at $M=512$, which has similar PAPR at $M=2048$ in the GA-PTS, i.e. 7.5dB, so the cost is decreased 4 times in the IDFLA-PTS method. In Table II, the PAPR of IDFLA-PTS and GA-PTS is illustrated with a different number of sub-blocks. The original

signal has a PAPR of 11.2dB, while the optimum exact PAPR is 7.4dB.

Fig. 4. PAPR comparison of IDFLA-PTS, GA-PTS, and exact IDFLA-PTS.

TABLE II. REDUCTION OF PAPR WITH IDFLA-PTS AND GA-PTS

PAPR reduction method	Number of sub-blocks	PAPR (dB)
IDFLA-PTS	128	8.2
IDFLA-PTS	256	7.7
IDFLA-PTS	512	7.55
GA-PTS	128	8.6
GA-PTS	256	8.02
GA-PTS	512	7.65
GA-PTS	2048	7.5

TABLE III. UWA BELLHOP CHANNEL SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameters	Processing Data
Surface height	100 m
Transmitter side depth, transducer (TX)	25 m
Receiver side depth hydrophone (RX)	40 m
Distance between TX and RX	3 km
Frequency range	8-12kHz

Fig. 5. Comparison of proposed IDFLA-PTS, GA-PTS, and conventional-PTS in terms of BER.

The parameters used in the Bellhop channel configuration are mentioned in Table III. In the simulation, the Bellhop channel is executed in MATLAB window containing all the features of shallow water. We supposed surface height (depth) of 100m, the transducer is dipped in water up to the depth of 25m, and the depth of hydrophone was kept at 40m while the distance of the hydrophone (RX) and transducer (TX) was 3km. For a better understanding of the proposed method, the BER vs. SNR of IDFLA-PTS with GA-PTS and conventional PTS are compared. The best-fit algorithm in UWA communication must produce less BER and higher SNR thus creating a better environment for communication. Figure 5 shows the BER performance over the range of SNR. It is observed that IDFLA-PTS has better performance than the traditional methods. The parameters mentioned in Table I are taken into consideration. The yellow line determines the BER curved line of the IDFLA-PTS method that has better performance than GA-PTS. The red curved line determines the BER of the GA-PTS. It is noticed that using the GA gave a slightly more BER. The blue curve shows the BER of the conventional-PTS. From Figure 5, it is clear that the proposed method IDFLA-PTS performs better with lower BER and higher SNR, which determines the best performance for an underwater and acoustic system..

B. Experiment

To observe the simulated idea of the proposed IDFLA model, we did experiments at Harbin Engineering University on the June, 1, 2020. The transducer (transmitter) and receiver (hydrophone) were placed at different depths (25m and 40m respectively) in a water tank. The distance between the hydrophone and transducer was 3km, which is similar to the simulation parameters. The experimental layout is shown in Figure 6, which portrays the experimental setup and the underwater acoustic tank channel.

Fig. 6. Experimental setup in underwater acoustic tank channel.

The transmitter was connected with the computer via a power amplifier. The parameters given in Table I were employed in the experiments. The signal was generated from the signal generator and was transmitted through an underwater acoustic channel. After hitting the surrounding boundaries of the water tank, the acoustic signal creates various paths at the

receiver side (multipath). When acoustic signals with different frequencies are transmitted, then peaks are overlapped, and high peaks are also observed which affects the performance of the signal's BER. For PAPR reduction, we introduced the IDFLA-PTS algorithm, which selects the optimum phase factors, and provides better BER performance. The transmission of the signal is efficient in the proposed method. During the signal transmission, multiple high peaks occurred in the underwater acoustic channel. The high peaks passed through the proposed algorithm block, where they were further calculated and informative peaks were reduced by the iterative process. In Figure 7, the impulse response of the underwater tank channel is illustrated. It is mainly relying on the sound speed, ranging from 1490m/s to 1500m/s. Hence, one can observe several time delays with normalized amplitude due to the nature of the UWA channel. The signal suffers from multipath when reaching the receiver side. Figure 8 shows the simulated and experimental BER curves of the proposed IDFLA-PTS algorithm. It is noted that the curves are close to each other with only a slight difference between them. This proves our method to be very feasible for practical applications.

Fig. 7. Channel impulse response of the underwater tank with the IDFLA-PTS algorithm.

Fig. 8. BER comparison of the proposed IDFLA-PTS, simulation and experiment.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, the IDFLA-PTS is proposed for the UWA OFDM communication system. It is verified that the proposed method has better performance than other intelligent PAPR reduction techniques. The IDFLA algorithm is independent of other complex parameters that can affect in-band and out-band distortion. The proposed IDFLA-PTS method was compared with GA-PTS with varying number of sub-blocks and achieved optimum PAPR. It is concluded that the IDFLA-PTS method proved to be efficient, less complex, while it reduces PAPR with enhanced BER performance. The IDFLA-PTS algorithm can be implemented in the future for the reduction of PAPR with other methods in order to create a less complex and efficient UWA OFDM communication system.

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AUTHORS PROFILE

Amir Ali received the BE in Electronic Engineering from Mehran University of Engineering and Technology, Jamshoro, Pakistan in 2016. He was a Junior Expert Engineer in National Engineering Services Pakistan from 2016 to 2018. Currently he is pursuing his MS. in the College of Underwater Acoustic Engineering, Harbin Engineering University, China. His research interests are wireless communications, machine learning, underwater image processing, 5G, IoT, and blockchain technology.

Baowei Chen received his PhD from the Harbin Engineering University in 2012. Currently, he is an associate professor of the College of Underwater Acoustic Engineering, Harbin Engineering University. He has worked as a visiting scholar at the University of Guelph, Canada. His research interests include the design of underwater acoustic electronic systems and the research and implementation of underwater acoustic signal processing algorithms, the design of sonar electronic systems, and the acquisition technology of ocean environment information.

Waleed Raza received his BE in Electronic Engineering from the Department of Electronic Engineering, Dawood University of Engineering and Technology, Karachi, Pakistan in 2017. He is currently pursuing an MS in Hydroacoustic Engineering in the College of Underwater Acoustic Engineering, Harbin Engineering University, China. His research areas of interests include underwater acoustic OFDM communication, machine learning, and digital signal processing.

Asif Ali received his BS degree in Physics from Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur, Pakistan in 2017. Currently, he is pursuing an MS degree in Nuclear Engineering at the Harbin Engineering University, China. His current research interests include system engineering, nuclear physics, and nuclear power plant safety.

Haisen Li received his PhD degree from Harbin Engineering University in 1999. From 2002 to 2003, he was a Senior Visiting Scholar at the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI), USA. He is currently a Professor at the College of Underwater Acoustic Engineering, Harbin Engineering University and the Chief of the TI-HEU DSP joint laboratory. His research interests include multi-beam echo sounder technology and underwater acoustic target detection and location. He is a fellow of the Acoustical Society of China, the Standing Director of the Heilongjiang Acoustics Society, and the Visiting Research Fellow of WHOI. He is also a reviewer or a member of the editorial board for many prestigious international journals, such as *Technical Acoustic*, *Hydrographic Surveying and Charting*, and the *Journal of Harbin Engineering University*. He is currently a reviewer of the National Natural Science Foundation of China.

Using Google My Maps as a Geospatial Ticket Management System for Scheduling and Monitoring Power Distribution Network Works

Case Study of Patras Area's Distribution Network Engineering & Construction Section

D. Pylarinos

Patras Area's Distribution Network Engineering & Construction Section

Department of Peloponnese-Epirus Region

Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator S. A.

Greece

d.pylarinos@deddie.gr

Abstract-The need to ensure the long-term ability of power distribution systems to meet demands means that upgrades and alterations/expansions, as well as inspection and maintenance works, are constantly necessary. This paper presents an approach to use custom Google Maps as a ticket management system for scheduling and monitoring such works. A geospatial representation is rather useful in networks that are great in length and follow irregular routes (which is typically the case for power distribution networks). However, acquiring a representation of such networks, especially for the Low Voltage side, is an enormous task. This paper presents a cost-free and easy-to-implement approach that can be used in the absence of a full geospatial representation of the network. This approach utilizes an assign-to-the-feeding-transformer (for all Low Voltage issues) and assign-one-indicating-point (for each Middle Voltage issue) scheme, thus, requiring a minimum amount of data easily retrieved from the network. This approach provides a georeferenced ticket management system that can be employed for improved monitoring and scheduling through a user-friendly and free-to-use web-based application which use requires no additional costs or training. The presented approach has been applied in the area of Patras, Greece and initial results, showing a significant improvement in productivity, ranging from 10% to 42%, are further presented and discussed in this paper along with background information.

Keywords-power distribution network; google maps; custom; ticket management system; geospatial; georeference.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electrical networks and installations are generally divided in three main categories: production, transmission and distribution [1]. The distribution system (network) includes all Medium Voltage (MV) and Low Voltage (LV) equipment used to carry electricity to the final consumer whereas the transmission system includes all HV equipment used to carry HV between HV substations [1]. A Distribution System Operator (DSO) is an entity responsible for operating, maintaining and developing the power distribution system in a given area [2]. The number of DSOs within a specific country

as well as their exact nature, their inner structure, the level of involvement of outside contractors and their general mode of operation varies from country to country [3-6]. In Greece, HEDNO [7] is currently the sole DSO for the whole distribution network throughout the country with over 7.5 million customers and a network length that exceeds 240.000 km (with the low voltage network holding a marginal majority of this sum) and over 163.000 installed medium/low voltage transformers [8]. To measure the reliability and quality of services provided by DSOs, two values are widely used: SAIFI and SAIDI. The System Average Interruption Frequency Index (SAIFI) is the average number of interruptions that a customer would experience within one year whereas the System Average Interruption Duration Index (SAIDI) is the average interruption duration within one year for each customer served [6]. In SAIFI and SAIDI terms, HEDNO scores rather low in comparison with other European DSOs [4] but well better than the median world value [9]. Although there is always room for improvement, it should be noted that comparing such values between different areas and countries may be misleading as local conditions vary (e.g. the weather, the landscape, the age of the network etc.).

Network expansions and upgrades as long as the initial network design have a significant impact on the performance of a network (and thus of its operator) [10-11]. The followed inspection and maintenance strategies are also key factors [12-15]. This paper presents and discusses an approach to improve ticket managing, and thus scheduling and monitoring of works, using geospatial data. The use of geospatial data has proven a rather useful tool in a variety of cases [16] including various applications in the power network industry [17-22]. However, the ticket-management aspect is often neglected. At the moment, HEDNO is running a major project aiming to incorporate GIS technology in the core of its functions, expected to be completed in late 2022 [23]. This paper presents an intermediate step undertaken meanwhile from the HEDNO's Network Engineering & Construction Section (NECS) of Patras Area, Greece in an effort to increase the section's

productivity and to familiarize its personnel with the use of digitized and geospatial data. A major initial goal was that no additional cost (in terms of software, equipment, personnel or training) should be required at any time. The proposed approach does not require a detailed geospatial representation of the network either. Thus, it can easily be followed by other organizations under similar conditions.

II. CASE STUDY AND BACKGROUND

A. Traditional Naming Scheme for Network Components

Traditionally, in the absence of GIS systems and of geospatial data, simple naming rules had to be employed in order for the personnel to be able to navigate and work on the network. For example, in this particular case, MV lines were named after the High Voltage Substation they are connected to, along with an arithmetic value. If a line splits, then each subsection was named adding a dash and another arithmetic value. MV poles are also numbered and thus a third dash and arithmetic value was added to the naming scheme. These data were maintained in numerous hard copy maps and sheets depicting the network in various zoom scales. Of course, the network changes over time (e.g. MV poles may be added or removed at any time), which creates similar issues with the ones mentioned in [20]. However, unlike what happens with transmission towers [20], pole numbering is not indicated on the actual poles in the field. Only key network components (e.g. MV/LV transformers) are equipped with indicating signs. MV/LV substations are traditionally named using local toponyms (city areas, village names or general location names), although not always accurately, followed by an arithmetic value. Substations were then used as starting points to pin-point other LV network components such as LV poles or spans, that do not bear a specific name tag. However, the traditional naming scheme for key network components such as MV/LV transformers is soon to be abandoned since jurisdiction areas are gradually merging and this means that components with the same name would ultimately be found in the same jurisdiction (as there are numerous places and villages with identical toponyms throughout Greece).

B. Area and Network Data

The case study area covers over 1,500 km² and includes more than 200,000 customers connected to over 3,000 MV/LV transformers. The area is depicted in Figure 1 (in red) and, in more detail, in Figure 2 with the MV lines shown in solid green color. It should be noted that MV lines are mostly overhead, with small parts (mostly within major cities) being underground. In comparison, larger parts of the LV network are underground, but again these are to be found mostly within major cities (mostly in the city of Patras). This means that the larger part of the network is subjected to open-air environmental stress and thus its inspection and maintenance is essential for the system's reliability.

C. Inspection and Ticketing

Standard procedure within HEDNO is for the area's Network Operation & Maintenance Section (NOMS) to perform yearly inspections of the network and note down all potential issues, including potential upgrade works, as judged

by them on site. Issues that fall under the NECS's jurisdiction are forwarded in the form of hard-copy notes (tickets) for further consideration. These tickets are given a unique number for all future reference. Each ticket describes the issue and its location by using the traditional naming schemes previously described. The NECS is then expected to prioritize the received tickets and schedule on-site visits and consequent studies. Finally, the studies are handed to an outside contractor and the NECS is then responsible for inspecting and monitoring the contractor's works. It should be noted however that all HEDNO personnel is allowed (and expected) to report any potential issues they spot at any time (e.g. when working on other projects or even when not on duty). HEDNO also receive reports from citizens about potential issues. Needless to say that these reports do not use the internal naming scheme described earlier to provide location information.

Fig. 1. A view of Greece with the case studied area (screenshot from Google Earth. Map data: Data SIO, NOAA, U.S. Navy, NGA, GEBCO. Image Landsat/Copernicus).

Fig. 2. A closer view of the studied area with the MV distribution lines in green solid color (screenshot from Google Earth. Map data: Data SIO, NOAA, U.S. Navy, NGA, GEBCO. Image Landsat/Copernicus, Data LDEO-Columbia, NSF, NOAA).

D. Network Expansions and Alterations

The NECS has to study and perform network expansions and alterations that are requested by network customers and land owners. This is because according to Greek legislation (e.g. laws 1468/50, 1672/51, 2941/2001, 4001/2011), the DSO is allowed to install MV and LV installations in private and public properties. However, contrary to the legislation in effect for transmission installations [24], no expropriation or easement is applied on the properties. Thus, any land owner can receive a building permit without informing or consulting the DSO, regardless of the existence of MV and LV on the property. After acquiring the permit, the land owner notifies the DSO who is then required to alter the network in a fashion that would allow the safe construction (and continuing existence) of the building. Land owners can also quote a variety of reasons (e.g. works that do not require specific permits) to request network alterations. Connecting new customers to the grid may also demand extended works as there are no limitations regarding the distance/position etc. Finally, NECS receives guidelines from within the DSO regarding standard desired upgrades, strategic expansions etc. The result of the above is that there is a constant flow of requests to the NECS for network alterations and expansions.

E. Weaknesses and Effects on Scheduling

1) Trying to Cope with Hard Copy Tickets

As explained earlier, after receiving the tickets/notes, the NECS has to schedule on-site visits and network studies, if needed, as a follow up. During scheduling, one has to consider the distance and routes between different locations, the nature and importance of each issue, general guidelines, deadlines etc. In an attempt to achieve this, hard copy tickets and notes were kept in different stacks related to their priority status and their general location. The personnel would then have to go through the stacks in an attempt to formalize a schedule. As new requests were received almost daily, this meant that the time consuming, and prone to errors process of going through the hard-copy stacks also had to be repeated almost daily.

2) Multiple Tickets and Narrow Data View

A significant weakness in the scheme described above, is the inability to identify multiple tickets and/or requests on the same issue. HEDNO is currently equipped with different software to monitor the progress of studies and the finances/logistics of construction works but none of them can be used effectively for managing the prior stage (ticket-monitoring and assigning), i.e. they are not designed to keep track of tickets/requests that do not ultimately result to a study or construction work. The available software is also unfitting to provide a wider view of the data. Instead, they are more oriented towards a case by case approach, i.e. they are rather useful when the user searches for a specific information but tend to be rather time consuming and not user friendly when the user tries to acquire a wider view of the data. Simple queries can be submitted but the return time is significant and their functions are not easily (or at all) customized. A user often has to use multiple software, perform multiple queries, go through several entries and move between multiple screens to actually get the needed information.

3) Naming Scheme Issues

The naming approach for MV/LV transformers described in previous sections, suffers from the fact that toponyms may provide a rough idea of the approximate location of a given group and its proximity to other groups but not of the proximity of specific group members to others. This means that e.g. two transformers belonging in the same group may actually have a greater distance between them compared to the distance each of them has with neighboring substations belonging to different groups. The issue worsens if one considers that the overall shape of a group following a toponym is bound to be irregular. This means that even though e.g. group A may be closer to group B in general, and this can be understood by the respected toponyms, a specific transformer belonging to group A may actually be closer to a transformer from another group instead. A simple example is depicted in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. A simple example of the traditional naming convention scheme. The image shows six different groups (A-F) of MV/LV transformers, with each group using the same toponym for all transformers in the group. Group A is adjacent to groups B, C, E and F. However, the far right transformer of Group A is closer to a transformer of Group D than to any of the transformers in Groups B, F and E. Further, certain transformers within all groups are closer to transformers of adjacent groups than to transformers in their own group. (screenshot from Google Earth, map data: Google Earth)

4) Other Issues

Other obvious issues caused by the lack of geospatial representation is not considering the actual routes between different points (a minor issue for distribution networks however compared to transmission systems [20]), having a lengthier learning curve for new personnel and being unable to easily correlate outside reports (e.g. when they use street addresses) with specific network works and components.

III. UTILIZING THE AVAILABLE GEOSPATIAL DATA

During a process similar to the one described in [20], geospatial data (i.e. coordinates) for all MV/LV transformers as well as the route of MV lines had been acquired previously. These data could then be utilized to provide a geospatial representation of all tickets, studies and works that should

improve overall scheduling and, thus, productivity. However, a key goal that was set was that no additional cost (in terms of software, equipment, personnel and even additional training) should be required at any time. An approach similar to [20] was judged unsuitable due to the nature of the application and of the available data. Free to use software such as Google Earth, Maps.me and MantisBT previously used by the author in transmission applications [20, 25] were also found unsuitable. A ticketing system without a geospatial representation, such as MantisBT, could solve the multiple-ticketing issue but would do little to improve scheduling whereas geospatial representation software that had to function locally, such as Google Earth, was also found to be unsuitable as several different employees needed to have access to the information. Thus, it was decided to use custom Google Maps (Google My Maps) [26] instead and try to work within its restrictions.

A. Restrictions and Solutions

Google My Maps enforces certain limitations to custom maps created by users. These are related to the number of layers, the number of Points-Of-Interest (POIs) per layer and per map, the size of imported files etc. Also, unlike Google Earth, Google My Maps does not provide a pop-up function when two POIs superimpose one on top of the other. Regarding the discussed case study, the routes of MV lines had to be redrawn and different line sections or parts had to be united (e.g. at the bus of the High Voltage substation or before and after a MV component) in order to follow the restrictions (Figure 4). It should be noted however that the actual route of MV lines is not necessary for the system’s function and it is only added as a visual aid. The spreadsheet with all MV/LV transformers and their coordinates also had to be split into smaller spreadsheets to comply with Google My Maps restrictions.

Fig. 4. A printscreen from the custom map showing the MV lines layer (screenshot from Google My Maps, Map Data © 2021 by Google Maps).

B. POIs, Custom Icons and Representation

For the MV network, it was decided that one POI would be created for each ticket, even if the ticket referred to a line section (in such a case, the POI would be inserted in the approximate middle of the section). For the LV network, each ticket is assigned to the POI depicting the MV/LV transformer that feeds the corresponding circuit (one POI for all tickets fed by the same transformer). It was decided to import POIs for all transformers in the map, even for the ones with no active tickets. This way, map editing would be easily conducted within Google Maps, the maps would present a better view of the network and they could also be used for navigation purposes. Custom made icons were developed for the POIs with different icons representing different types of issues and with different colors representing a different status and/or prioritization. Examples of custom made icons and of map parts are depicted in Table I and Figure 5 respectively.

TABLE I. EXAMPLES OF CUSTOM MADE POI ICONS

•	LV POI (LV/MV transformer) without active tickets
XT	LV POI with active ticket(s) (low priority)
XT	LV POI with active ticket(s) (at least one of high priority)
XT	LV POI with active ticket(s) (assigned)
MT	MV POI with active ticket(s) (low priority)
MT	MV POI with active ticket(s) (high priority)
MT	MV POI with active ticket(s) (assigned)
MT	MV POI with all tasks completed

Fig. 5. A simple example of how POIs appear in th the custom maps (at a remote location). The image has been slightly edited to erase placenames (screenshot from Google My Maps, Map Data © 2021 by Google Maps).

C. Additional POIs

In general, additional icons can be created and used to depict different types of tickets, depending on the application. For example, in this case, tickets related to street addresses (and not feeding transformers) such as tickets related to the urban underground network and tickets reported by people outside the DSO are depicted with different icons. To avoid overpopulating the map, such POIs can be deleted when

completed or they can be merged with existing POIs. For example, tickets regarding customer requests can be imported in different layers and when concluded, can be merged as a text comment in existing LV POIs.

IV. WORKING WITH CUSTOM MAPS

A. Split into Two Maps

It was decided to construct two custom made maps: one for onsite visits/studies (the so-called “studies map”) and one for construction (the so-called “constructions map”). This was done to comply with the internal structure of the NECS and the overall organization scheme but also in order to avoid internal confusion and to avoid showing redundant data to employees (as different employees work in the respected subsections).

B. Create New POIs, Edit Existing POIs, Monitor Past Tickets

In order for POIs to have the desired number of metadata categories, they were created by importing spreadsheets to the custom maps. New POIs however can then be created from within Google My Maps and inherit the structure of a given group. Each POI in a certain group was equipped with several metadata fields (description, comments, alphanumeric codes, styling etc). Using the styling option, a user can link the appearance of a POI with a certain metadata field and just edit this field to alter the way the POI appears (Figure 6). By editing a POI’s metadata, the user can also move a ticket’s description/number from an active field to an inactive one. It should be noted that the built-in search function considers all text within all fields. Thus, the maps retain a list of past works/tickets, with all data being easily searchable and retrievable. This feature is then used to identify redundant or overlapping tickets.

C. Removing Duplicates

The first group of tickets to be inserted into the studies map was consisted of 489 tickets. 327 tickets out of the 489 were part of the 2021 yearly inspection whereas the remaining 162 were low-priority tickets left over from previous years (17 tickets from 2018, 79 tickets from 2019 and 67 tickets 2020). A total of 33 tickets were removed as duplicates. 14 of these, were tickets that were identical with other tickets from the same yearly inspection whereas 19 were identical with tickets from previous years. An additional 13 were tickets referring to issues that had been solved since (studied or declined) without reaching the construction stage. An additional 4 tickets were found to be identical with works in the construction stage (and map). Thus, through the process of entering the data in the two maps, the number of tickets was reduced from 489 to 439.

D. Scheduling

For scheduling, one has to consider the priority status, the location, the available routes, the proximity with other tickets and customer requests, the weather in each area etc. The user can see the geospatial representation of issues and click on POIs (Figure 6) to acquire more information in order to construct an optimal working schedule. Figure 7 shows a part of the map in an urban location (an area with a significantly larger network and issue density compared to Figure 5). An important additional function is that the search function can be

employed to identify all the POIs that fall under the same MV line (or subsection) as shown in Figure 8. This way the user can also consider electrical connections when scheduling works (e.g. a construction work at a certain section of a MV line can be combined with works at the LV circuits of MV/LV transformers that are fed by this MV line section). This also means that depicting the actual lines is of no particular importance for this system’s functionality (provided that the correct and full data for each POI are used).

Fig. 6. An example of the metadata of a LV POI as shown in the custom maps. The user can simply edit the metadata by clicking the pencil icon in the bottom of the pop up window. The number (and name) of categories in the metadata correspond to the number (and names) of columns of the initial spreadsheet. (screenshot from Google My Maps, Map Data © 2021 by Google Maps).

Fig. 7. An example of an urban location as shown in the custom maps. The map has been manually edited to erase placenames. (screenshot from Google My Maps, Map Data © 2021 by Google Maps).

Fig. 8. Using the search function to see all the POIs belonging to a certain MV line (a narrower search using a line subsection would return the POIs in this specific subsection). The map has been manually edited to erase placenames. (screenshot from Google My Maps, Map Data © 2021 by Google Maps).

V. RESULTS

Assessing (and documenting) the effect in productivity is not an easy task as there are a number of outside factors that may have an impact on the final results. The main question regarding this case study, is if the proposed scheme will help the NECS cope with yearly inspection tickets faster (before the next yearly inspection and ideally within 6 months) while not causing any delays to any of its other works. So, one has to consider not only the trend regarding the inspection tickets but also the overall numbers. These should be considered not only in terms of their absolute value but also in terms of their total cost (as some tickets may require far more work than others) in order to acquire a correct view of the effect of the proposed approach.

A. Inspection Tickets

The first results regarding inspection tickets show a rather significant improvement as depicted in Figure 9. A week after the application, a new group of 58 tickets (corresponding to a certain MV line section that had just been inspected) were submitted to the NECS increasing the total number of initial tickets to 497. Considering the studies map, the actual initial number of active POIs was 473 (24 of the 497 tickets were assigned to the same MV/LV transformers). This number fell to 371 after a month (a reduction of 102 active POIs per month). This means that, with this rate, the number of active POIs (and thus inspection tickets), should be expected to fall to zero within 5 months since the application of the custom maps (and within 3 months for each following year, as this group of tickets included 163 tickets from previous years).

Fig. 9. A summary of the results regarding inspection tickets and POIs.

B. Number of Studies and Respective Costs

The number of studies and their total cost also increased significantly in the first month of the application of the proposed scheme. The average number of cases studied per month for the previous 36 months were 82 with an average total predicted cost per month of 376 thousand euros. The first month after the application of the proposed scheme, these numbers increased to 108 cases studied with a total cost of 414 thousand euros, an increase of 31.71% and 10.11% respectively. In terms of construction, the average number of constructed studies for the past 36 months was 74 and the average total final cost per month was 133 thousand euros. These numbers also increased the first month of the application of the proposed scheme to a total of 96 constructed studies with a total cost of 190 thousand euros, an increase of 29.73% and 42.86% respectively. It should be stated that the constructed studies of each month are not necessarily the same studies studied within this month or even the month before. Apart from this, the gap between the predicted costs and the actual final costs should be largely attributed to the bidding procedure followed in Greece (the cost of public works is generally calculated using standard prices whereas outside contractors bid by proposing discount rates on the standard prices and the works are assigned to the bidder offering the largest discount). A summary of the results is shown in Table II.

TABLE II. NUMBER OF STUDIES AND COSTS (BEFORE AND AFTER)

	Monthly average (past 36 months)	After 1 month with custom maps	+/- (%)
Cases studied	82	108	+26 (+31.71%)
Predicted cost of studies (rounded)	376,000 €	414,000 €	+38,000 € (+10.11%)
Constructed studies	74	96	+22 (+29.73%)
Actual cost of constructed studies (rounded)	133,000 €	190,000 €	+57,000 € (+42.86%)

VI. DISCUSSION

The initial results presented in the previous section show a significant improvement in all fronts. However, there are several limitations regarding this approach that should be stated. First of all, there is no easy way to extract the POIs and edit their structure (e.g. to a spreadsheet), as only kmz and kml exportation is supported. This means that to add an extra category in the metadata of POIs or to change the name of a metadata category, one has to actually work with the exported kml/kmz files, which requires specialized software and/or knowledge. Performing any type of statistical or meta-analysis is also an issue. Backing up is also not user-friendly as the user can either extract the data in kml/kmz files or save a copy of the entire map. Neither option is suitable to monitor the progress of works in the long term. Saving copies of the maps does not allow easy comparisons between them. Reimporting a previously exported kml/kmz file as a new layer to an existing map could solve this but the limit to the number of layers per map and the limit to the size of kml/kmz files to be imported, means that the user would eventually have to extract and

reimport one kml/kmz file per layer, which is rather time consuming and would result to a vast number of locally kept files. Another significant disadvantage is that Google My Maps is a rather unforgiving application with limited “undo” capabilities, which means that a human error is not easily spotted or fixed. Finally, it should be noted that although the custom maps are easily viewed by multiple users, a refresh of the web page is needed to acquire the latest edition of the map. So, a no-simultaneous editing policy is required to avoid overlapping between different users.

On the other hand, if the map developer maintains a strategy that considers all limitations (both of the software and of a specific case study), it is possible to produce a scheme with significantly more pros than cons. Google My Maps is currently a free application that is designed for the ordinary user, which means that no extra software, staff or specialized training of any kind is required to develop or maintain the maps. Also, following the proposed approach, map editing is rather fast and requires minimum effort and time in terms of everyday work. It should be noted that although geospatial representations have been incorporated in various applications, the proposed approach differs in that it provides a geospatial ticket-managing approach which is cost-free, easy to implement/maintain, and does not require a detailed geospatial representation of the network. Thus, it can be implemented in a variety of cases with similar characteristics, especially in the absence of a more sophisticated GIS system or in case the installed GIS system does not offer a ticket-management capability (which is often the case with specialized GIS software).

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the approach followed by the Patras Area’s Distribution Network Engineering & Construction Section in an attempt to acquire a free and user-friendly geospatial representation of works related to the power distribution network of the area. The presented scheme uses Google My Maps effectively as a geospatial ticket management system to monitor and schedule works. Given the rather user-friendly nature of Google Maps, this scheme requires no additional training to develop or maintain. Gathering the data also requires a minimum effort, as LV issues are assigned to the transformer that feeds the corresponding circuits and a single indication point is used for each MV issue. The bulk of points (i.e. the LV/MV transformers) are imported from available spreadsheets that are customized to suit the needs of the users. Custom icons are used to depict POIs of different categories and different colors to depict their condition or priority. Adding new points and editing existing ones is easily conducted within Google My Maps. The main initial goal for this approach was to improve the speed with which the Section coped with issues recorded during network inspections. Initial results showed a significant improvement to this but at the same time also showed a significant increase in overall productivity, ranging from 10% to 42% depending on the aspect considered each time. This approach can easily be implemented by other utilities in the absence of a GIS system and of detailed geospatial data of the network, as it is rather easy to implement and maintain, requires no additional cost at

any level and offers a significant improvement to traditional hard copy based approaches or to ticket management systems that do not incorporate a geospatial representation.

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DFT Investigation of the Structural and Optoelectronic Properties of Alkali Metal Hydrides MH (M=Li, Na)

Taieb Iliass

Materials Science and Informatics Laboratory
Faculty of Science, University of Djelfa
Djelfa, Algeria
iliassstaieb@yahoo.com

Hamza Ziani

Materials Science and Informatics Laboratory
Faculty of Science, University of Djelfa
Djelfa, Algeria
hamza_ziani@yahoo.com

Ahmed Gueddim

Materials Science and Informatics Laboratory
Faculty of Science, University of Djelfa
Djelfa, Algeria
ahmed_gueddim@yahoo.fr

A. Djamel Guibadj

Laboratory of Physical Chemistry of Materials
Faculty of Science, University of Laghouat
Laghouat, Algeria
d.guibadj@gmail.com

Abstract-This paper presents *ab initio* calculations within the Density Functional Theory (DFT) for the structural and optoelectronic properties of the alkali metal hydrides LiH and NaH in rocksalt structure (B1). This study used the Generalized Gradient Approximation (GGA) of Wu-Cohen to consider the electronic exchange and correlation interactions. In addition, the Tran-Blaha modified Becke-Johnson exchange potential was used with the GGA approach (GGA-TBmBJ) to calculate the band structure with high accuracy. The structural properties, namely the lattice parameter, the bulk modulus, and the pressure derivative of the bulk modulus were determined and found to be generally in good agreement with other research findings. Furthermore, the energy band gaps, the Density Of States (DOS), the static and high-frequency dielectric constant, along the refractive index were addressed and analyzed. These results could be useful for hydrogen storage purposes.

Keywords-Hydrogen storage; LiH; NaH; *ab initio*; mBJ-GGA

I. INTRODUCTION

The energy transition is necessary in order to meet the increasing energy needs and cope with global warming. The main drivers for this transition are the adoption of responsible consumer practices and the increased use of renewable sources of energy. This transition also requires efficient processes for production, conversion, storage, and transport of energy. Many scientific and technological challenges exist in each of those axes. As the problem of suitable materials is ubiquitous, materials science is at the heart of this research. The challenge is to obtain and optimize materials having specific properties to fulfill the requirements of renewable energy.

Hydrogen is a transportable, storable, and convertible energy medium and has great potential to become the ultimate solution that combines energy security, resource availability, and environmental compatibility. However, the greatest challenge in the development of hydrogen-based technologies

is how to store hydrogen safely, effectively, and economically [1-5]. Depending on the physical state of hydrogen, three different routes are currently used for its storage: compressed gas, liquid, and solid-state. Hydrogen stored as a solid-state material has potential advantages in terms of volumetric density and safety, compared to compressed gas or liquid [6-11]. In the case of solid-state, the bonds between hydrogen and the host material can be of different kinds and strengths. Both van der Waals weak and chemisorptive strong bonds can be involved [11]. It is possible to increase the density of hydrogen, as it is packed with H-H distances up to 170kg/m³ in many hydride-type materials. This value is higher than the density of hydrogen in a liquid state [12]. Numerous studies have been conducted to determine and design the most suitable materials with convenient gravimetric and volumetric densities for hydrogen storage. These materials span a large class, from conventional metal hydrides to complex hydrides, microporous materials, and clathrate hydrates. This study addresses some fundamental properties of LiH and NaH using the first principles calculations to utilize the Density Functional Theory (DFT). Such calculations are of great interest before the synthesis procedure, which is a very time-consuming effort. The structural properties along with their electronic and optical features are explored and analyzed for the materials under load in the rock-salt (B1) structure. The comparison with experimental and theoretical data, when possible, shows satisfactory agreement in general.

II. COMPUTATIONAL METHODOLOGY

This study used the Full Potential Linearized Augmented Plane Wave (FP-LAPW) method, based on the DFT [13] that constitutes the core of the WIEN2k code [14]. Exchange-correlation energy was calculated using the WC-GGA [15] when dealing with structural properties. The exchange-correlation functional mBJ [16] was applied to determine the electronic and other optical characteristics. In the FP-LAPW

method, the wave function and the potential are developed as sums of spherical harmonic functions inside non-overlapping spheres, surrounding the atomic sites (muffin-tin spheres), and a set of plane waves in the interstitial region. A plane wave cut-off of $R_{MT.kmax}=7$ (where R_{MT} is the smallest muffin-tin radius in the unit cell) was used. R_{MT} 's were chosen to be 1.7, 2.1, and 2.5 a.u. for H, Li, and Na, respectively. The k-sampling over the Brillouin zone was performed up to a $13 \times 13 \times 13$ Monkhorst-Pack [17-20] mesh for both considered materials. The number of k-points and the plane wave cut-off energy varied in such a manner as to obtain total energy convergence. The convergence of these self-consistent calculations was considered to be obtained within an error of 10^{-5} Ry on the total energy of the crystals studied.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The total energy was calculated from the WC-GGA approach as a function of the volume of LiH and NaH in the rocksalt structure. At first, the total energy for some selected lattice parameter values was calculated. The results obtained were then written according to Murnaghan's equation of state [21]. This allowed determining the equilibrium lattice parameter a_0 , the zero pressure bulk modulus B_0 , and the first-order pressure derivative of the bulk modulus B' for the ground-state. These results are summarized in Table I with experimental and theoretical data from other researches for comparison. The WC-GGA lattice parameter in this study is generally closer to the experiment than those of the GGA or LDA approaches [27-29]. The a_0 , calculated for both LiH and NaH from WC-GGA, agrees quite well with those reported in [22, 23]. The same remark can be drawn for the bulk modulus B_0 , which agrees within a few percent with other experimental or theoretical values [22, 24-26].

TABLE I. a_0 , B_0 , AND B' FOR LiH AND NaH IN B1 STRUCTURE USING GGA AND WC-GGA ALONG WITH THE VALUES REPORTED IN THE LITERATURE.

Material	a_0 (Å)	B_0 (GPa)	B'
LiH	3.9934 ^a	38.1840 ^a	3.9913 ^a
	4.0153 ^b	41.1635 ^b	3.0976 ^b
	4.012 ^c	36.228 ^c	3.51 ^c
	3.92 ^d	36.60 ^e	3.40 ^e
NaH	4.8051 ^a	25.9068 ^a	4.1001 ^a
	4.8347 ^b	23.0855 ^b	6.560 ^b
	4.833 ^c	23.546 ^c	3.90 ^c
	4.775 ^d	19.40 ^f	4.40 ^f
		22.9 ^g	

a. Present calculation using WC-GGA, b. Present calculation using GGA, c. [22], d. [23], e. [24], f. Experimental value quoted in [25], g. [26]

The formation energy is an important thermodynamic quantity that permits one to characterize and classify hydrogen storage materials. Formation energy is defined as the difference between the sum of the total energies of the products and the reactants:

$$\Delta H = \sum E_{tot}(\text{products}) - \sum E_{tot}(\text{reactants}) \quad (1)$$

The formation of MH (M=Li, Na) materials from their constituting elements is given as:

The formation energy can be written as:

$$\Delta H = E_{tot}(MH) - E_{tot}(M) - E_{tot}(H) \quad (3)$$

The total energies of LiH, NaH, Li, Na, and H were calculated. The formation energies of LiH and NaH were found to be -88.91 kJ.molH_2 and $-109.054 \text{ kJ.molH}_2$, respectively. The desorption temperature of hydrides was estimated using the standard Gibbs energy:

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad (4)$$

where ΔH and ΔS are the enthalpy of formation and the standard entropy of the reaction respectively. At equilibrium, the standard Gibbs energy ΔG is zero. Therefore, the desorption temperature can be expressed as:

$$T = -\frac{\Delta H}{\Delta S} \quad (5)$$

The calculated desorption temperature was 680.33K for LiH and 834.38K for NaH. The gravimetric hydrogen storage capacity can be determined as:

$$C_{wt} \% = \left(\frac{\left(\frac{H}{M}\right) M_H}{M_{Host} + \left(\frac{H}{M}\right) M_H} \times 100 \right) \quad (6)$$

where H/M is the hydrogen to material atom ratio, M_H is the molar mass of H, and M_{Host} is the molar mass of the host material. The hydrogen storage capacities calculated for LiH and NaH were 22.5% and 8.06%, respectively.

Fig. 1. Electron band structure calculated using TB-mBJ-GGA along high symmetry directions for (a) LiH and (b) NaH.

The electronic and optical properties of the materials are classically described by their electronic band structure [30-33]. Accurate knowledge of the band parameters of a given material provides precious information regarding its synthesis and devices fabrication [34-37]. The results of using the GGA-TBmBJ approach to compute the electronic band structure of rocksalt LiH and NaH are plotted in Figure 1. It should be noted that, from a qualitative point of view, the same picture is observed for all the reported band structures. The Fermi level energy does not cross any energy bands for all questioned crystal materials. Therefore, LiH and NaH in the rocksalt structure can be considered respectively as semiconductor and insulating materials. According to Figure 1, the valence band maxima and the conduction band minima are located at the same high symmetry point X in the Brillouin zone. The band gaps of these materials are direct in nature, agreeing with the results of [22]. The fundamental difference between the band structures arises from the magnitude of their fundamental energy band gap, which differs from one band structure to another. The calculated fundamental direct band gap (X-X) for the rocksalt LiH and NaH were 3.05 and 3.65eV respectively.

Fig. 2. Density of states (DOS) calculated using TB-mBJ-GGA for (a) LiH and (b) NaH.

The properties of semiconductors can be related to the electron configuration shown by the molecules. The Densities Of States (DOS), total and projected, were computed for the rocksalt LiH and NaH using the TB-mBJ approach to show how the electrons are distributed on different orbitals. The results are shown in Figure 2. An inspection of LiH (Figure 2(a)) shows that the first region of the DOS is the most tightly bound energy band. The contribution of the Li-s electrons is

predominant for the energy bands near the Fermi level of the LiH crystal. Hence, the Li-s electrons are useful for the conductivity of the crystal of interest. The DOS at these regions consist essentially of Li-s and Li-p states. The contribution of the H-s states was remarkably weak. Figure 2a also shows that the bonding peaks ranged from about -5 to 0eV. These peaks were mainly formed by the Li-s state. For NaH (Figure 2b), it is observed that the intensity of the H-s orbitals in the valence band constitutes the dominant contribution to the DOS. The Na-p and Na-s states have a minor contribution to the DOS compared to the H-s orbitals. The bonding peaks ranged from about -3.75 to 0eV. Moreover, the optical properties, such as the dielectric function, were examined. The computed optical response functions, real $\epsilon_1(E)$ and imaginary $\epsilon_2(E)$, for LiH and NaH are displayed in Figures 3 and 4 respectively, where E is the photon energy. The main peak of the real parts of LiH and NaH occurs around $E=2.94$ eV and $E=4.58$ eV respectively.

Fig. 3. Real part of the dielectric function calculated using TB-mBJ-GGA.

Fig. 4. Imaginary part of the dielectric function calculated using TB-mBJ-GGA.

Based on the optical transition mechanisms, the optical spectrum of a given crystal is usually classified into several photon energy regions [38]. In general, three spectral regions are distinguished. The first one is known as the reststrahlen region and is characterized by the interactions between the radiation field and the fundamental lattice vibrations [38]. For very low energies, the real part of the dielectric function tends to the static or low-energy dielectric constant ϵ_0 . The ϵ_0 for LiH and NaH materials were determined as:

$$\varepsilon_0(\text{LiH}) = 4.55 \quad (7)$$

$$\varepsilon_0(\text{NaH}) = 3.21 \quad (8)$$

Regarding the ε_0 of LiH, this result is different from the quoted in [39]. To the best of our knowledge, no data regarding ε_0 for NaH has been reported so far. Thus, this result could serve as a reference. The optical constant that relates the so-called reststrahlen region to the near-infrared region is commonly known as the high-frequency dielectric constant ε_∞ . For these materials, the calculations gave:

$$\varepsilon_\infty(\text{LiH}) = 7.84 \quad (9)$$

$$\varepsilon_\infty(\text{NaH}) = 10.82 \quad (10)$$

The calculated ε_∞ for LiH shows reasonable agreement with the one reported in [34]. For NaH, the calculation in [40] gave a value of 3.71, which is too low compared to this result. The general shape of ε_l was expected for a harmonic oscillator with resonant frequencies of about 8.39 and 5.71eV for LiH and NaH, respectively. It is generally accepted that the resonance frequency is a fundamental property of a given material. This quantity allows the expression of the average energy that separates the levels of bonding and anti-bonding [30]. The absorption for the imaginary part of the dielectric function starts at about 2.04 and 3.09eV for LiH and NaH, respectively. Similar behavior was reported in [41, 42] for $\text{ZnTe}_{1-x}\text{O}_x$ alloys. Knowledge of the refractive index of semiconductors in the energy range below or near the fundamental absorption edge is mostly interesting in device design [43-48]. This refractive device (n) can be easily derived from the dielectric function $\varepsilon(E)$. The n values obtained for LiH and NaH were:

$$n(\text{LiH}) = 2.8 \quad (11)$$

$$n(\text{NaH}) = 3.29 \quad (12)$$

The n value for LiH is in reasonable agreement with the value of 1.47 reported in [49]. The calculated spectral dependence of $n(E)$ for LiH and NaH is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Refractive index calculated using TB-mBJ-GGA for LiH and NaH.

From this spectrum, it can be noted that clear peaks are present. These peaks are due to the excitonic transitions at the E_0 edges. Excitonic effects are believed to be responsible for the enhancement of the oscillator strength at the critical points M_0 and M_1 [50]. Since the total strength of the oscillator is

proportional to the number of valence electrons, it should be "conserved" in some way. This means that as the oscillator strength at the critical points M_0 and M_1 is enhanced due to excitonic interactions, some losses occur elsewhere to achieve strength conservation. The strongest peaks in the $n(E)$ spectra can be explained as the result of the 2D exciton transition (E_l).

IV. CONCLUSION

This study examined the structural, electronic, and optical properties of the alkali metal hydrides LiH and NaH, using the FP-LAPW technique within DFT in the WC-GGA for structural properties and TB-mBJ-GGA for electronic and optical features. The crystal structure of both investigated materials investigated was rocksalt (B1). Results regarding the lattice constant, bulk modulus, and pressure derivative for LiH and NaH were reported and compared, where possible, with the available experimental and theoretical data. In general, a reasonably good agreement was found between the results of this study and the literature. The electron band structure, the density of states, and the dependence of the real and imaginary parts of the dielectric function along the refractive index of the materials under load were also studied and analyzed. The results derived from the present study could be useful for hydrogen storage purposes.

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Designing an IoT Agriculture Monitoring System for Improving Farmer's Acceptance of Using IoT Technology

Siti Aisyah Binti Anas

Faculty of Electronics and Computer Engineering
Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka
Malacca, Malaysia
aisyah@utem.edu.my

Ranjit Singh Sarban Singh

Faculty of Electronics and Computer Engineering
Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka
Malacca, Malaysia
ranjit.singh@utem.edu.my

Nur Adilah Binti Kamarudin

Electrical Electronic Validation, Engineering Validation, R&D Engineering
Perusahaan Otomobil Nasional Sdn Bhd
Shah Alam, Selangor, Malaysia
NurAdilah@proton.com

Abstract-This paper describes Agri-Snaps, an Internet of Things (IoT) agriculture monitoring system designed to improve farmers' acceptance of using IoT technology in their farm field. Agri-Snaps consists of four dedicated sensor circuit modules that integrate magnetic pogo pin connectors for easier assembly with the controller circuit module. This work investigated how such a design can enable the farmers to understand how 1) to assemble, 2) self-troubleshoot, and 3) maintain the monitoring system independently without requiring expertise on the farm site. User-experience testing was conducted with ten participants to validate Agri-Snaps's viability. The results showed that those participants positively rated Agri-Snaps as attractive, easy to understand and assemble, exciting, and innovative compared to the typical agriculture monitoring systems.

Keywords-Internet of Things; agriculture; industrial design; sensors; embedded system; human-computer interaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Internet of Things (IoT) is driving change in agriculture. It enables sensors on a farm to remotely monitor and give real-time data to the farmer, such as detecting the current environmental conditions [1]. The implementation of IoT also allows the farmers to increase farm production effectively throughout the year. In line with the Fourth Industrial Revolution (IR 4.0), farmers are always encouraged to implement smart farming using IoT technology for better decision making [2, 3]. Unfortunately, most farmers are still hesitant to adopt IoT on their farm sites and prefer traditional farming practices, resulting in lower crop yields [4]. A deeper investigation revealed 4 main reasons why farmers were not ready to implement IoT in their farm fields [2, 5]: 1) the level of education required to become familiar with the technology, 2) the lack of engineering skills needed to install the system, 3)

the troubleshooting process required to sustain the system, and 4) the high cost of implementing the system. While previous studies focus on the benefits of implementing IoT in the agriculture sector, to the best of our knowledge, there are no studies on improving the farmers' acceptance of using IoT technology. Hence, this work focuses on how a typical IoT agricultural monitoring system can be enhanced to enable the farmers to implement the system without requiring particular skills. With an improved design, farmers can easily understand how to self-integrate, self-troubleshoot and self-maintain the IoT environmental monitoring system without requiring expertise on the farm site. As a result, it can increase the farmers' willingness to accept innovative IoT technology and help them gain control over growing crops. In the end, such technology will allow them to run a more predictable, efficient, and profitable agribusiness [4].

II. BACKGROUND

In previously conducted research, authors in [6, 7] developed an automatic IoT environmental control system to optimize mushroom production. The developed system enables the farmer to remotely monitor and analyze the environmental conditions of the mushroom production house. Based on the analyzed data, the system will automatically control the irrigation system to ensure the temperature level is optimum. This smart mushroom system has proven to optimize the mushroom's quality and productivity. Authors in [8] developed an automatic web-based IoT agriculture fertigation system that allows the farmers to remotely set the fertigation schedule. The system also enables the farmers to formulate the fertilizer composition. In this way, the farmers can virtually manage their automated fertigation system by accessing the website using their mobile devices. Authors in [9] proposed an IoT

Corresponding author: Siti Aisyah Binti Anas

smart farming framework of cotton crops that supports smart reasoning based on the data streams from the embedded sensors deployed inside the cotton field. As a result, the framework provided real-time results that helped farmers make efficient event detection decisions. In addition, authors in [10-12] developed an automatic IoT irrigation system that measured and maintained the moisture content in the soil. Through the system, the farmers can optimize the usage of water fertilizers while maximizing the yield of the crops. To summarize, all the mentioned IoT research related to agriculture enables the farmers to increase the crop yield compared to conventional methods. This nonetheless proved that IoT technologies help to improve agricultural and farming industries. While previous research focused on the benefits of implementing IoT technology, there are no studies on the willingness of the farmer to accept, adopt and sustain the IoT system. Therefore, this work focuses on designing and developing a simple and intuitive IoT agriculture monitoring system that allows the farmers to understand how to implement it without much effort. Such a design could improve the farmers' acceptance of IoT technology in their farm fields.

III. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

A typical IoT agricultural monitoring system is generally built with a complex architecture and is difficult for farmers to comprehend [13]. Therefore, the complex architectural design of the IoT agricultural monitoring system needs to be separated into two modules: 1) the controller module and 2) the sensor modules. The following sections will describe how the two modules are designed and developed to improve farmers' acceptance of implementing IoT technology in the farm field.

A. 3D Enclosure Design

One key design decision was to allow the farmers to clearly understand how to assemble and easily set up the IoT weather monitoring system independently. Figure 1 shows 3D enclosures uniquely designed to house the controller and the sensor modules. The controller enclosure is designed to fit the system's brain (ESP8266 Wi-Fi module). Four sensor enclosures were designed to fit: the humidity sensor, the rain index sensor, the light intensity sensor, and the temperature sensor (DS18B20). Color-coded schemes [14] and emboss sensor icons [15] were also integrated into the designed enclosure for easy differentiation and understanding. For example, the blue enclosure with the water drop emboss icon represents the humidity sensor. Slot joints were also added to create a joint between two modules. Therefore, by referring to the matched emboss icon, such a design allows the user to easily assemble the system by inserting the sensor module into the controller module slot joint, respectively. Screw-fastened covers were also integrated to protect the electronic circuits placed inside the enclosure. Figure 2 shows the microcontroller and the circuit sensor modules placed inside the 3D printed enclosures to ensure the electronic components are protected in any environment. However, putting the sensors inside the enclosures can result in an inaccurate sensor reading that might directly lead to substantial risks [16]. Therefore, each of the sensors used for this system is mounted outside of the enclosure to provide a better and more accurate sensor reading.

Fig. 1. 3D casing design of Agri-Snaps.

Fig. 2. Agri-Snaps's 3D printed enclosures.

B. Pogo Pins and Magnets

The electronic connection of Agri-Snaps was inspired by the work of Bdeir on littleBits [17]. Like littleBits, pogo pins were used, specifically at the slot joint, to allow the current/signal to flow from the controller module to the sensor module and vice versa (Figure 3). Strong magnets were also used to enable a solid connection between the controller and the sensor modules. Therefore the current/signal can flow smoothly throughout the system. Figure 3 shows the placement of the pogo pins and magnets that are embedded into the designed enclosure. Each sensor module enclosure is integrated with different magnetic poles combinations as a safety precaution. Such combinations will protect the system if the user accidentally inserts the sensor module at the wrong slot joint, damaging the system's circuit. For example, as shown in Figure 5, magnets will repel each other when inserting a light intensity sensor module at the temperature slot joint.

Fig. 3. Pogo pins and magnets as an enabler mechanism to allow current/signal to flow from the controller to the sensor module and vice versa.

Fig. 4. Integration of pogo pins and magnets into the 3D printed enclosures.

Fig. 5. Magnets will push the sensor module away if the user tries to insert the sensor module at the wrong slot joint.

C. Power Supply

A typical 5V DC power connector is used to power the Agri-Snaps. It operates at 3.3V and has a maximum current draw of 70mA with a power consumption of 231mW. Generally, Agri-Snaps will consume 2.024kWh over the year, and the electricity bill will only cost around 7 USD per year. Therefore, implementing Agri-Snaps will not going to break the user’s bank.

D. Assembling Procedures

Agri-Snaps can be easily assembled. First, the user needs to match the emboss icon on top of the enclosures (Figure 6(a)). Then, the magnets will snap the sensor module into the controller module’s joint slot (Figure 6(b–e)). Any 5V DC power supply can be used to turn on Agri-Snaps. As shown in Figure 6(f), a USB power supply cable connected to a waterproof solar power bank and plugged into the power slot is used to power up Agri-Snaps. Afterwards, the user can decide where to integrate the system appropriately, as shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 6. Assembling procedure of the Agri-Snaps.

Fig. 7. Agri-Snaps placed directly in the farm field.

E. IoT Data Visualizations

ThingSpeak is a web-based open API IoT source information platform that can store sensor data and graphically present it on the web. Agri-Snaps uses the ESP8266 NodeMCU microcontroller to send the humidity, rain index, light intensity, and temperature data to the ThingSpeak platform over the Internet. As shown in Figure 8, ThingSpeak allows the farmers to visualize a live data stream from any web browser or mobile device and help them make accurate and proactive decisions.

Fig. 8. Data visualization on ThingSpeak.

Another key design was allowing the farmers to easily troubleshoot the system when required. Suppose two of the sensor modules are not functioning properly due to broken, ageing or similar reasons (Figure 9). In that case, Agri-Snaps will alert the user through the ThingSpeak platform. Therefore, the user simply needs to snap out the broken sensor modules and buy new modules from the supplier. Apart from that, Agri-Snaps can be customized following the user’s requirements. For example, the system will understand and function accordingly if the user decides to use humidity and temperature sensors in a certain situation, as shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 9. Notification of defect sensor modules.

Fig. 10. Notification of unconnected sensor modules.

IV. USER-EXPERIENCE TESTING

Before testing, a typical IoT agriculture monitoring system (Figure 11) was developed to allow the users to use both the typical system and the Agri-Snaps. The user-experience testings for both system designs were compared and analyzed at the end of the testing.

Fig. 11. A typical IoT agriculture monitoring system.

A. Participants

Within-subjects testing was designed to involve 10 farmers (7 males, 3 females, age range: 25 to 45). The farmers were evenly separated into two groups of 5 participants, groups A and B.

B. Procedures

Each participant was required to experience using the typical system for group A for 7 days. After that, they were asked to fill out a set of questionnaires. Then, the procedure was repeated again by letting the participants in group A experience Agri-Snaps. After 7 days, they filled out the same set of questionnaires again. The same procedures were implemented for group B, except they were experiencing using Agri-Snaps initially and then the typical system. These procedures were designed to eliminate the ordering effects that might affect the testing’s outcome [18].

C. Measurement

The User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) [19] was used to measure the subjective impression of users towards a product (Figure 12). The UEQ questionnaire consisted of 26 items divided into 6 individual scales: 1) Attractiveness indicated the overall impression of the product, 2) Perspicuity which measured the difficulty of participants to get familiar and learned how to use the product, 3) Efficiency was the ability of participants to realize how to use the product without unnecessary effort, 4) Dependability refers to the predictability when using the product, 5) Stimulation shows participants’ excitement and motivation to use the product, and 6) Novelty indicated whether the product was innovative, creative, and able to catch the participant’s interest. Items 1, 12, 14, 16, 24, 25 were related to the Attractiveness scale, items 2, 4, 13, 21 were related to the Perspicuity scale, items 9, 22, 23 were related to the Efficiency scale, items 8, 11, 17, 19 were related to the Dependability scale, items 5, 6, 7, 18 were related to the Stimulation scale, and items 3, 10, 15, 26 were related to the Novelty scale. Participants must express their experience with both the typical system and Agri-Snaps by marking each item of the UEQ questionnaire with a 6-point Likert scale.

	-3	-2	-1	0	+1	+2	+3		Scale
annoying	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	enjoyable	1 Attractiveness
not understandable	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	understandable	2 Perspicuity
dull	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	creative	3 Novelty
difficult to learn	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	easy to learn	4 Perspicuity
inferior	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	valuable	5 Stimulation
boring	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	exciting	6 Stimulation
not interesting	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	interesting	7 Stimulation
unpredictable	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	predictable	8 Dependability
slow	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	fast	9 Efficiency
conventional	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	inventive	10 Novelty
obstructive	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	supportive	11 Dependability
bad	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	good	12 Attractiveness
complicated	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	easy	13 Perspicuity
unlikeable	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	pleasing	14 Attractiveness
usual	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	leading edge	15 Novelty
unpleasant	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	pleasant	16 Attractiveness
not secure	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	secure	17 Dependability
demotivating	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	motivating	18 Stimulation
does not meet expectations	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	meet expectations	19 Dependability
inefficient	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	efficient	20 Efficiency
confusing	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	clear	21 Perspicuity
impractical	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	practical	22 Efficiency
cluttered	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	organize	23 Efficiency
unattractive	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	attractive	24 Attractiveness
unfriendly	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	friendly	25 Attractiveness
conservative	o	o	o	o	o	o	o	innovative	26 Novelty

Fig. 12. The User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ).

D. Results and Discussion

All the measured items have been summarized according to the scale as tabulated in Table I. The unshaded rows were the percentage of the participants' rating towards Agri-Snaps. The shaded rows were the percentage of the participants' rating towards the typical circuit. To better understand the participants' responses, Figure 13 shows the overall mean values of the UEQ questionnaire for each scale. The UEQ scale mean ranges from -3 (horrible bad) to +3 (extremely good), with values between -0.8 and 0.8 indicating a neutral assessment [19].

TABLE I. PERCENTAGE OF PARTICIPANTS THAT RATED EACH OF THE ITEMS ACCORDING TO THE SCALE

Scales	Items	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3
Attractiveness	Annoying/Enjoyable	-	-	-	-	50%	50%	-
	Bad/Good	20%	10%	40%	10%	20%	-	60%
	Unlikeable/Pleasing	-	-	-	-	10%	90%	-
	Unpleasant/Pleasant	10%	10%	30%	50%	-	-	-
	Unattractive/Attractive	-	-	-	-	20%	40%	40%
	Unfriendly/Friendly	10%	30%	40%	20%	-	-	-
	Not understandable/Understandable	30%	10%	20%	10%	30%	-	-
	Difficult to learn/Easy to learn	30%	-	40%	30%	-	-	-
Perspicuity	Complicated/Easy	-	-	-	-	10%	60%	30%
	Confusing/Clear	10%	30%	30%	10%	10%	10%	-
	Slow/Fast	10%	10%	60%	20%	-	-	-
	Inefficient/Efficient	-	20%	30%	30%	20%	40%	40%
Efficiency	Impractical/Practical	10%	40%	-	40%	10%	60%	20%
	Cluttered/Organize	20%	20%	40%	10%	10%	-	-
	Unpredictable/Predictable	10%	20%	30%	40%	-	-	-
Dependability	Obstructive/Supportive	10%	10%	40%	30%	10%	50%	30%
	Not secure/Secure	10%	10%	40%	30%	20%	50%	10%
	Not meet expectation/Meet expectation	10%	20%	40%	-	30%	50%	20%
Stimulation	Inferior/Valuable	-	20%	60%	20%	-	60%	30%
	Boring/Exciting	20%	-	30%	40%	10%	-	-
	Not interesting/Interesting	-	-	-	-	-	50%	50%
	Demotivating/Motivating	10%	30%	30%	20%	10%	50%	20%
Novelty	Dull/Creative	40%	20%	20%	20%	-	50%	50%
	Conventional/Inventive	20%	10%	10%	10%	20%	60%	20%
	Usual/Leading-edge	20%	10%	30%	40%	-	-	-
	Conservative/Innovative	10%	30%	20%	20%	10%	80%	20%

Unshaded rows: the collected results for Agri-Snaps
 Shaded rows: the collected results for the typical system

Based on the results, the scales mean values show very positive impressions for Agri-Snaps, ranging from 1.53 to 2.38 for all aspects of user experience. This indicates that the participant's judgment of Agri-Snaps was that it was attractive, easy to understand, efficient, reliable, stimulating, and innovative. In contrast, the scales mean values for the typical IoT agriculture system leaned towards negative impressions, with the scores ranging from -0.83 to -1.23. This result

validates that although the typical system provided useful agriculture monitoring data, the participants seemed demotivated to depend on and use it when compared to Agri-Snaps. They felt the typical system was unattractive, difficult to understand, less efficient, unreliable, uninteresting and failed to grab their attention.

Fig. 13. Overall results for UEQ items, per scale.

For Agri-Snaps, Dependability was the least positively rated scale among the participants (M=1.53). The results suggested that participants may have difficulty predicting where the sensor modules should be snapped together with the controller module as 40% of participants rated Agri-Snaps as neither unpredictable nor predictable, 10% found it to be neither obstructive nor destructive and neither meet their expectation or not, and 20% felt Agri-Snaps as neither insecure nor secure. It can be speculated that the icon embossed on top of the controller and sensor module enclosures was not clearly visible to the user. Therefore, instead of referring to the embossed icon, the design of Agri-Snaps can be improved by changing the color of the controller module slot joint. Instead of using a white color scheme, the controller module slot joint should be matched with the color of the sensor modules. For example, the blue color slot joint at the controller module is to be attached with the blue color sensor module. This design approach will allow the user to instantaneously rely on the color scheme when assembling the Agri-Snaps. Nonetheless, 50% of the participants rated Agri-Snaps as supportive, secure, and meeting their expectations, whereas 60% of the participants found the design of Agri-Snaps as predictable.

In contrast, Stimulation was the most positively evaluated scale (M=2.40), in which 60% (+2) of the participants found it to be exciting and 50% (+2) of them rated Agri-Snaps as motivating. Also, half of the participants found the design of Agri-Snaps was positively interesting (+3). The results proved that Agri-Snaps has improved the way the participants perceived the IoT system as more valuable than the typical system. Although both systems were able to produce the same IoT data visualization, the enhanced design of Agri-Snaps made the participants feel more motivated and interested in implementing the IoT system in their farm field.

Perspicuity was the second most positively evaluated scale (M=2.38). 60% of the participants found Agri-Snaps as understandable and easy (+2). Whereas 50% of the participants rated Agri-Snaps as easy to learn and clear (+3). This indicated that when compared to the typical system, the intuitive design

of Agri-Snaps managed to develop a better understanding of how to assemble, self-troubleshoot, and maintain the system independently without much effort. It should be noted that allowing the farmers to have a thorough understanding and a firm knowledge of the system is critical in order to galvanize and sustain their interest in the use of IoT.

Attractiveness and Efficiency were the third and fourth positively evaluated scales with $M=2.28$ and $M=2.15$ respectively. These results indicated that the participants liked Agri-Snaps and could practically assemble the system without unnecessary effort. This was reflected when 60% of participants rated Agri-Snaps as fast to assemble and practical (+3). Also, 80% of the participants rated Agri-Snaps's design as efficient and organized (+2 to +3). Moreover, 90% of the participants found Agri-Snaps as pleasing (+3), whereas 60% rated the design of Agri-Snaps as friendly and good (+3).

Novelty was the participants' second least positively rated scale ($M=1.93$), in which 20% of the participants found Agri-Snaps's design as conventional (-1 to -2). The results suggested that despite Agri-Snaps's inventive design, only 4 sensors were integrated into the system, limiting its capability to detect other changes in environmental conditions. However, it is a good starting point to investigate whether the design of Agri-Snaps can improve the farmers' acceptance of using IoT technology in their farm field. Nonetheless, based on Figure 13 and Table I, the design of Agri-Snaps has been positively accepted among the participants compared to the typical IoT agriculture monitoring system.

V. FUTURE WORK AND CONCLUSION

Future work should further improve the design of Agri-Snaps by integrating more sensor modules, as illustrated in Figure 15. The variety of sensors allows the farmer to choose which sensor modules are required to cater the crop grown on their farm field. In conclusion, the design of Agri-Snaps successfully allows the user to easily understand how to assemble, self-troubleshoot, and maintain the system independently without requiring an extensive understanding of IoT technology and electronic concepts. These features enable the farmers to improve their acceptance towards implementing IoT technology in their farm fields.

Fig. 14. The design concept of Agri-Snaps with more sensor modules integration.

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Electromagnetic and Thermal Analysis of Interior Permanent Magnet Motors Using Filled Slots and Hairpin Windings

Dinh Bui Minh

School of Electrical Engineering
Hanoi University of Science and Technology
Hanoi, Vietnam
dinh.buiminh@hust.edu.vn

Hung Bui Duc

School of Electrical Engineering
Hanoi University of Science and Technology
Hanoi, Vietnam
hung.buiduc@hust.edu.vn

Nguyen Huy Phuong

School of Electrical Engineering
Hanoi University of Science and Technology
Hanoi, Vietnam
phuong.nguyenhuy@hust.edu.vn

Vuong Dang Quoc

School of Electrical Engineering
Hanoi University of Science and Technology
Hanoi, Vietnam
vuong.dangquoc@hust.edu.vn

Abstract—This paper analyzes the electromagnetic and thermal design of interior permanent magnet motors using filled slots and hairpin windings for electric vehicle applications. Two models of ∇ shape of the interior permanent magnet motors have been proposed to evaluate the temperature distribution and cogging torque performance. A narrow opening slot of the interior permanent magnet of 48 slots/8 poles with the filled winding has been designed to investigate the electromagnetic torque because the cogging torque depends on opening stator slots. A parallel-rectangle slot of the interior permanent magnet with the hairpin winding has been also implemented with finite element analysis to evaluate their performances. Normally, the slot opening of the interior permanent magnet stator equals the slot width, it is greater than the size of hairpin windings, and the cogging torque is increased significantly with a bigger slot opening. The main advantage of the hairpin winding design is the high slot fill factors. Hence, the lower the current density, the higher torque, and efficiency are, than the normal design with the same geometry parameters. To improve the cogging torque due to the wide slot opening, the step-skew rotor slices have been arranged to minimize the torque ripple with different skewing angles.

Keywords—interior permanent magnet; finite element analysis; Ansys Maxwell; SPEED software; hairpin windings

I. INTRODUCTION

Hairpin-type windings are gaining increasing popularity [1, 2], especially in automotive traction motors due to advantages which include reduced manufacturing time, high fill factor, shorter end-winding overhang, and better high voltage protection. Moreover, with respect to the random nature and the packing style of traditional distributed windings, hairpin windings consist of a plurality of accurately placed stator bars [1, 3]. However, the cogging torque is very high with a wider slot opening, and it is also very complicated to manufacture.

Corresponding author: Dinh Bui Minh

Thus, in order to improve the torque ripple, a novel design of a step-skew ∇ shape magnet has been presented for Interior Permanent Magnet (IPM) motors of 150kW (48 slots/8 poles). The stator stepped slot-openings with optimal shift angles have been implemented for the IPM motors in [4-6]. Cogging torque reduction has become an increasingly important issue in IPM motors. Effective methods for reducing the cogging torque, such as skewing slots, step-skewing rotor, and magnets are possible for the slot-filled windings. For the hairpin windings, only step-skewing rotor can be applied to improve the torque ripple. In this paper, a stepped skewing shift magnet rotor method for reducing the cogging torque of IPM motors, which can avoid the drawbacks of the wider slot opening of stator slots, is proposed. The electromagnetic torque and efficiency performance of the IPM motor are significantly affected by winding topology. The electromagnetic performance of multi-layered IPM motors keeping in mind their potential use in Electric Vehicle (EV) applications. The torque and back Electromagnetic Force (EMF) waveforms are verified with different step skewing models. The torque harmonics have been compared for different topologies. Finally, an IPM motor with a step-skewing magnet rotor is manufactured to verify the results of Finite Element Analysis (FEA) [9-12].

II. HAIRPIN AND SLOT FILL WINDING DESIGNS

The designed IPM motor with ∇ shape of permanent magnet rotor with slot filled and hairpin windings is presented in Figure 1. The stator slot parameters are pre-determined in and are shown in Table I. The slot-filled winding has an opening width of 1.2mm, which is greater than the wire diameter of 1mm (Figure 1(a)) and the stator slot opening of the hairpin winding is 5mm, bigger than the rectangle bar sizes of 4.3×3.3mm (Figure 1(b)).

Fig. 1. (a) Slot filled winding and (b) hairpin winding.

TABLE I. SLOT FILLED AND HAIRPIN WINDING PARAMETERS

Parameter	Unit	Slot filled winding	Harpin winding
Stator lamination diameter	mm	250	250
Stator bore D_s	mm	175	175
Airgap	mm	1	1
Stator slot opening width (t_s)	mm	1.2	5
Mechanical opening angle	($^\circ$)	0.55	2.22
Motor length	mm	240	240
Stator lam length	mm	120	120
Magnet length	mm	120	120
Magnet Segments		6	6
Rotor lam length	mm	100	100
EWG Overhang [F]	mm	55	37
EWG Overhang [R]	mm	55	37
Copper size	mm	Φ 0.85	4.3 \times 3.3
Number strands		15	1
Phases		3	3
Turns		6	6
Throw		5	5
Parallel paths:		2	2

The two IPM motors have 48 slot/8poles, the stack length is 51mm, the diameter of stator and rotor is 250mm and 175mm respectively, the air-gap length is 1mm, the thickness of the electrical steel sheet is 0.2mm, the continuous phase current amplitude is 400A, the continuous rated power is 150kW, and the maximum speed of the machines is 12000rpm. The main differences are winding overhang, slot opening, and the copper sizes of 15 (Φ 0.85) and 4.3 \times 3.3mm. The slot opening is 1.2mm in slot filled and 5mm in hairpin designs. In both models, the slot openings are arranged along the motor axis and the central position of the slots remains the same. The cogging torque of IPM motors results from the interaction between the stator teeth and rotor magnetic poles, which can be expressed in Fourier series [6-8]:

$$T_{cg} = \sum_{i=0}^n T_{c,i} \sin(iN\theta) \quad (1)$$

where i is the order of the cogging torque harmonics, T_{ci} is the amplitude of i order cogging torque component, and N is the least common multiple between the number stator slots and rotor poles. The mechanical angle of the stator opening θ is:

$$\theta = 360 \frac{t_s}{\pi D_s} \quad (2)$$

where t_s is slot opening width, D_s is the stator diameter.

The cogging torque of slot filled winding with 1.2mm (0.55°) opening is 2.8N.m, while the cogging torque of Hairpin winding with 5mm opening width (2.22°) is 8N.m, which is three times bigger than the slot filled winding designs.

Fig. 2. (a) Cogging torque of slot filled and (b) hairpin winding.

III. COGGING TORQUE AND THERMAL ANALYSIS

To eliminate the cogging torque by the stator slot-openings, the step-skewing rotor has a shift angle of β mechanical degrees. The cogging torque can be transformed as [6]:

$$T_{cog} = \sum_{i=0}^n T_{ci} \sin(iN(\theta - \beta)) \quad (3)$$

If the rotor is divided into segments along the motor axial direction, and the relative shift angle between the adjacent two rotor poles is δ_n mechanical degrees, the resultant cogging torque can be expressed as [6]:

$$T_{cog} = \sum_{i=1}^n T_{ci} \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \sin(iN(\theta - j\beta_n)) \quad (4)$$

The above equation can be simplified to:

$$T_{cog} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n T_{ci} \frac{\sin \frac{iN\beta_n n}{2}}{\sin \frac{iN\beta_n}{2}} \sin(iN(\theta - j\beta_n)) \quad (5)$$

Hence, for eliminating the i -th order cogging torque component, the theoretical shift angle β_n must fulfill the following requirements:

$$\sin \frac{iN\beta_n n}{2} = 0 \quad (6)$$

By applying the cogging torque for straight skewing and V-shape skewing magnet model, the conventional skewing model with straight skewing has a smaller shift angle than the V-shape skewing model with the same total skewing angle. The V shape magnet model has more advantages than the straight skewing because two harmonic orders can be eliminated together. For example, the harmonic orders with mechanical degrees of 1^0 or 3^0 are reduced to zero if they fulfill (6). The cogging torque of the 3 models is shown in Figure 3. The cogging torque of the V shape skewing design is the lowest value because the second order harmonics are eliminated in this model. The back EMF harmonic of the 3 models has been analyzed by Fourier transform from the electromagnetic force waveform with the harmonic order from the first to the 15th order. The back EMF amplitude versus harmonic order was implemented by the

Matlab function to obtain the results shown in Figure 5. From the back EMF harmonic result, the total harmonic distortion TDH of Model 3 with V skewing is the smallest about 4.2%.

designed with one guide pin to fix the correct position when all segments assembly together.

Fig. 3. (a) Straight skewing and (b) V-skewing.

Fig. 4. Cogging torque of the 3 models.

Fig. 5. Back EMF harmonic order analysis of the models.

The temperature distribution of slot fill and hairpin winding designs is depicted in Figure 6. The hot spot of Hairpin winding is 105.7°C, which is lower than 111.5°C. Based on these results, the IPM V skewing with the hairpin winding design is preferable for EV applications. The efficiency map of hairpin winding design is shown in Figure 7, with a speed range of 12000rpm and a current density of 8.9A/m².

IV. SKEWING ROTOR DESING

The prototype with the 6-segmented magnets has been manufactured and is shown in Figure 8. Each segment with a thickness of 20mm is skewed by 1.5 mechanical degrees. To insert the six segments simply, every segment block is

Fig. 6. (a) Slot fill, (b) hairpin winding designs temperature distribution.

Fig. 7. Efficiency map of hairpin winding design.

Fig. 8. (a) Rotor lamination, (b) Six step-V skew magnet slices assembly.

The whole hardware of the IPM motor has been assembled as in Figure 9. The high accurate torque transducer is used to measure the torque and speed values under different load conditions. The measured no-load phase EMF at 1500rpm of IPM is shown in Figure 10. To verify the electromagnetic performance, the 48 slot/8 pole proposed PM machine is built. Distributed windings were adopted. It should be noted that the PM motor is a prototype. The no-load back-EMF is carried out by using a voltage sensor. The simulated and measured results are exhibited in Figure 10. One circle of the back EMF has been measured by the oscilloscope and the data were recorded for plotting those curves.

Fig. 9. Back EMF measurement of the IPM motor system.

Fig. 10. Back EMF comparison of IPM motor system.

V. CONCLUSION

The obtained performance of IPM with slot filled and hairpin windings in the wide speed range has been presented in this paper and the effect of slot opening width on the cogging torque has been discussed. The thermal simulation of the two designs has been investigated to find out the hot spot or maximum temperature of hairpin and slot filled windings. A significant contribution of this study is the analytical calculation of the V skewing angle for the elimination of the second order harmonics of the cogging torque. A prototype of the V skewing magnet shape of the IPM hairpin winding has been manufactured and assembled. The simulation results achieved peak torque of 300N. m at the base speed of 5500rpm. The back EMF waveforms obtained from the FEA are close to the measured ones.

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A Simple and Fast Computation Equivalent Circuit Model to Investigate the Effect of Tape Twisting on the AC Loss of HTS Cables

Alireza Sadeghi

Department of Electrical Engineering
Shahrood University of Technology
Shahrood, Iran
alisadeghi380@yahoo.com

Seyyed Mesysam Seyyed Barzegar

Department of Electrical Engineering
Shahrood University of Technology
Shahrood, Iran
seyyedbarzegar@shahroodut.ac.ir

Mohammad Yazdani-Asrami

James Watt School of Engineering
University of Glasgow
Glasgow, UK
m.yazdaniasrami@gmail.com

Abstract-This paper aims to evaluate the AC loss of a High Temperature Superconducting (HTS) cable with respect to the twisting angle while considering mechanical constraints in an iterative approach. A 1km 22.9kV AC HTS cable was selected in this study to assess the impact of the twisting angle alterations. The electromagnetic behavior of the selected HTS cable was modeled using an Equivalent Circuit Model (ECM). After the implementation of this model in MATLAB/SIMULINK, a series of simulations were performed without the consideration of mechanical limits. They showed that the increase in the twisting angle leads to the decrease of the AC loss. Afterwards, simulations were conducted to reduce the AC loss, while mechanical limits were taken into account. This could reduce the AC loss by 27.41% with a much lower computation time than Finite Element Methods (FEMs).

Keywords-HTS cables; power cables; twisting; magnetic field; AC loss

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the discovery of superconductors in 1911 by H. K. Onnes, many investigations were initiated to enhance the critical temperature of superconductors. In 1986, J. G. Bednorz and K. A. Müller have introduced new superconductors with a critical temperature near 30K [1]. This has led to the rapid development in the manufacturing of High Temperature Superconducting (HTS) tapes and wires. Ever since the application of superconductors in power systems is gaining interest. Consequently, numerous investigations were funded to take the advantage of HTS materials in various apparatuses of power systems [2-9]. Among them, HTS cables are the most investigated components. They can be applied in common power systems as transmission or distribution lines [7]. They also play a significant role in future power systems with

renewable energy resources and even smart grids [10-14]. Accordingly, multiple studies have dedicated their efforts and funding to improve and model the electromagnetic and thermomechanical characteristics of HTS cables. Altogether, the main objective of these studies is to attain the proper behavior of HTS cables and increase their efficiency. One of the most significant parameters which could entirely impact the characteristic of cables is AC loss. Along with the passing of an AC current through HTS tapes of a superconducting cable, alternating magnetic fields are generated in the HTS cable [15]. The AC current and the generated fields induce losses in HTS cables which are known as transport current loss and hysteresis loss respectively [16]. These losses increase the heat load of the cooling system and consequently, the efficiency of the cable is reduced [17, 18]. To avoid such consequences, numerous attempts were conducted to reduce the AC loss of cables.

In [19] the AC loss of a 66kV HTS cable was studied and reduced by the variation in the topology of the HTS cable. This change is based on the increase of the radius of the former. By doing this, the number of HTS tapes is increased in each layer and a lower current passes through each tape. However, this method increases the total cost and weight of the cable. In [20], the AC loss is reduced by the reduction of tape thickness. The thickness of tapes directly impacts their engineering current density and so, AC loss. A sensitivity analysis was conducted in [21] to reduce the AC loss of the cable by the variation of the twisting angle. This method is very effective and can reduce AC loss significantly. Nonetheless, there is a lack of an iterative algorithm in this method to guarantee the certainty of the results. Authors of [22] have also used the twisting angle increase to suppress the AC loss. However, they did not consider any types of mechanical constrain on the HTS tapes. Twisting angle was also used for the sake of gaining a uniform

Corresponding author: Seyyed Mesysam Seyyed Barzegar

current distribution in HTS cables, without any attention to AC loss [23, 24]. The novelty of this paper is the reduction of the AC loss by varying the twisting angle in an iterative method while the mechanical limits of the HTS tapes are considered to avoid mechanical issues. A 22.9kV HTS cable with a length of 1km is opted to apply variations of twisting angle and the design improvement. All simulations were carried out in MATLAB/SIMULINK. The results show that the twisting angle has a significant impact on the value of the AC loss.

II. STRUCTURE OF THE HTS CABLE AND SIMULATION PROCEDURE

A. Description of the HTS Cable and ECM

To analyze the proposed method, a 22.9kV coaxial HTS cable was considered [25]. Figure 1(a) illustrates the structure of the chosen cable and Table I tabulates the most important parameters of the cable. According to Figure 1(a), the superconducting tapes of the cable are 2G HTS tapes. More detailed information about these tapes is listed in Table II. The selected HTS cable is a connection between the 22.9kV generation units and a 50 MVA load at 50Hz frequency. In this study, an ECM is put to work to simulate the behavior of the selected HTS cable.

Compared to FEMs, ECMs not only have a lower simulation time but also can provide a more complex test power system with different buses, lines, and generation units for the simulation of an HTS cable. So, an ECM for 22.9kV HTS cable was provided which is shown in Figure 1(b). In this Figure, the subscript "HTS" is devoted to the resistances and inductances of superconducting layers in each phase while "F" is related to former layers. There are also mutual inductances which are not shown in Figure 1(b) to avoid complexity. However, self-inductances, mutual-inductance, and capacitances were calculated according to [26].

TABLE I. INFORMATION OF THE SELECTED HTS CABLE

Item	Value and Type
Voltage/Power (kV/MVA)	22.9/50
Tape	YBCO
Operational Temperature (K)	70
Insulation Layer	PPLP
Primary pitch angle in each phase [A1 A2 B C]	[18.1° -16.3° 30.7° 45.8°]
Former Radiuses [A B1 B2 C] (mm)	[17 20 21 28]
Coolant	LN2

TABLE II. YBCO TAPE CHARACTERISTICS

Parameter	Value
Tape Type	YBCO
Width and Thickness (mm)	4.4 & 0.1
Stabilizer Thickness	50 (25 upper stabilizer and 25 lower stabilizer)
Upper Shield Thickness (μm)	2
Lower Shield Thickness (μm)	1.8
YBCO Thickness (μm)	1
Substrate Thickness (μm)	45.2

Fig. 1. The structure of (a) HTS cable, (b) equivalent circuit model of the understudied cable.

B. Modeling Formulation

The passing current through the cable induces a magnetic field with perpendicular and parallel components. These components vary with respect to the twisting angle and the pitch length. According to Biot-Savart law, these components of the magnetic fields are computed as follows [27]:

$$B_{iz} = \mu_0 \left(\sum_{k=i-1}^n a_k \frac{I_k}{l_{pk}} + a_i \left(\frac{r_{io}-r_{ip}}{r_{io}-r_{ii}} \right) \frac{I_i}{l_{pi}} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$B_{i\theta} = \mu_0 \left(\frac{1}{2\pi r_{ip}} \sum_{k=i-1}^{i-1} I_k + \left(\frac{r_{ip}-r_{ii}}{r_{io}-r_{ii}} \right) \frac{I_i}{2\pi r_{io}} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$B_{i\perp} = B_{iz} \cos \alpha_i + B_{i\theta} \sin \alpha_i \quad (3)$$

$$B_{i\parallel} = B_{iz} \sin \alpha_i + B_{i\theta} \cos \alpha_i \quad (4)$$

where $B_{i\perp}$ is the perpendicular component of the magnetic field in i th layer and $B_{i\parallel}$ is the parallel magnetic field, α_i is the twisting angle, B_{iz} states the axial magnetic field, and $B_{i\theta}$ expresses the azimuthal magnetic field.

Equations (5-8) represent the formulations of the pitch length in each layer of the cable [28]:

$$l_{a,1} = \varepsilon f_1(r_a, r_b, r_c) \quad (5)$$

$$l_{a,2} = -\varepsilon f_1(r_a, r_b, r_c) \quad (6)$$

$$l_{b,1} = \varepsilon f_2(r_a, r_b, r_c) \quad (7)$$

$$\ell_{c,1} = \varepsilon f_3(r_a, r_b, r_c) \quad (8)$$

where $\ell_{abc,i}$ is the primary twisting pitch of the i^{th} layer of the three phases and r_{abc} is the radii of the formers in each phase. As it can be seen, the twisting length is a function of the former radius. By accessing the pitch length of the phases, the calculation of the primary pitch angle of the HTS cable is conductible according to (9) [29]:

$$\alpha = \tan^{-1} \frac{\ell_i}{2\pi r_i} \quad (9)$$

The calculated twisting length and the twisting angle of the understudied cable based on (5-9) are tabulated in Table I as simulation initial values. By having the magnetic field and the current distribution in each tape, the AC loss could be attained according to [30-32]:

$$Q_{mag} = \begin{cases} \frac{2fB_i^2 \beta_i}{\mu_0} S_i & \beta_i < 1 \\ \frac{2fB_i^2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{1}{\beta_i} - \frac{2}{3\beta_i^3} \right) S_i & \beta_i > 1 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$B_i = \sqrt{B_{iz}^2 + B_{i\theta}^2} \quad (11)$$

$$\beta_i = \frac{B_i}{\mu_0 J_c b} \quad (12)$$

$$Q_{trans} = \frac{\mu_0 f I_{ci}^2}{2\pi} \{ (2 - F_i) F_i + 2(1 - F_i) \ln(1 - F_i) \} \quad (13)$$

$$F_i = \frac{I_{pi}}{I_{ci}} \quad (14)$$

where Q_{mag} is the magnetization loss in tapes, Q_{trans} is the transport current loss of superconducting layers, f is the frequency, μ_0 is the permeability of vacuum, S_i is a cross-section of layer i , J_c is critical current density, b is the half width of HTS tapes, I_{ci} is critical current of the i^{th} layer, and I_{pi} is the peak value of the current.

According to (10-14), twisting angle has a remarkable impact on the magnetic field and on AC loss [33]. As a matter of fact, the AC loss of a superconducting cable could be reduced by changing the initially calculated twisting angles. However, changing the twisting angle could jeopardize the mechanical stability of the tapes and this could lead to malfunctions in the HTS cable. To attain the mechanical limits, firstly strain must be calculated. The strain is a function of twisting pitch and the calculation point of strain. This could be conducted as expressed in (15). If the mechanical limits surpass the threshold value, the critical current abruptly becomes zero. The correlation between the strain and the critical current of tapes is expressed in (15-19) [34]:

$$\varepsilon(d, \ell) = 2\pi^2 \frac{(d^2 - \frac{\omega^2}{12})}{\ell^2} \quad (15)$$

$$I_c(T, \varepsilon) = I_{cm}(T) [1 - b(T) |\varepsilon - \varepsilon_m(T)|^2] \quad \forall \varepsilon \leq \varepsilon_{irr} \\ I_c(T, \varepsilon) = 0 \quad \forall \varepsilon > \varepsilon_{irr} \quad (16)$$

$$b(T) = b_0 + d \exp(eT) \quad (17)$$

$$\varepsilon_m(T) = FT - \varepsilon_{m0} \quad (18)$$

$$I_{cm}(T) = I_{cm0} \left(1 - \frac{T}{T_{C1}} \right)^m \quad (19)$$

In (16), ε_{irr} is the maximum strain value of tapes. The other parameters are tabulated in Table III [34].

TABLE III. PARAMETERS OF (16-19)

Parameter	Value
I_{cm0}	1282
T_{C1}	94
M	1.45
b_0	3122
d	4.3e-4
e	0.201
ε_{m0}	0.44
F	5.1e-5
ε_{irr}	1.1

Figure 2 illustrates the normalized value of the critical current in different locations while the strain is varied. As shown in Figure 2, the maximum value of strain in phase A is about 0.5%, while this value for phase B is about 0.95% and in phase, C is 1%. So, the angle of phase C should not be increased any further or the mechanical collapse will occur in this phase. On the other hand, in phases A and B, the maximum induced strain is lower than ε_{irr} and so, their angle can be changed. After analyzing the resulting critical current of different phases, it can be observed that the tapes of phase A are operating way lower than ε_{irr} and the angle of this phase could be further increased to reduce the AC loss of the system. The tapes of phase B have the maximum strain value of 0.95% and could be twisted a little further.

C. Simulation Procedure of the Proposed Method

To this section, the formulation, structure of the test system, the geometry of the HTS cable, and the structure of ECM are discussed. This section is presented to characterize the proposed modeling procedure and the AC loss reduction. Figure 3(a) represents the Simulink model of the test system. It can be seen that HTS cable with 1 km length is used to connect the upstream grid and the load. The HTS cable model is shown in Figure 3(b). Each phase of the cable is modeled by a variable resistance for HTS tapes, a constant resistance for the former layer, and a matrix of self and mutual inductances between all layers. Each variable resistance consists of multiple parallel superconducting tapes. One of these tapes is illustrated in Figure 3(c). In this Figure, RYBCO is the resistance of the superconducting layer of tape, RAg is the resistance of a silver layer of the tape, and RCu and Rsolder imply the resistivity of the copper stabilizer layer and solder, respectively. These resistances along with the resistivity of the former and the inductances are calculated in each iteration and inserted into the system. The procedure is shown in Figure 4. The first step is to feed the model with the former radii and to calculate the twisting characteristics as an initial value for the model. After that, the iteration number is set to 1 and after inserting the values of resistances and inductances, the Simulink model is run. After that, the strain for the calculated twisting angle is computed. In the next step, the computed strain is compared with the maximum irreversible strain of HTS tapes. If the strain is lower than this limit, a value as $\Delta\alpha$ is added to the last twisting angle and another time Simulink model is run. This procedure continues until the strain overpasses the irreversible

strain limit and that results in stopping the algorithm. $\Delta\alpha$ plays an important role in the speed of the proposed method. The smaller this value is, the higher the computation time would be.

Fig. 2. Normalized critical current value with respect to strain for the primary angle of tapes: (a) of phase A, (b) of phase B, (c) of phase C.

Fig. 3. Simulink model used as the test system of the proposed method: (a) system model, (b) cable model, (c) HTS tape model.

Fig. 4. The general flowchart for implementing the proposed method.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Sensitivity Analysis of Twisting in an HTS Cable without Consideration of Mechanical Limits

The twisting angle impacts the parallel and perpendicular components of the magnetic field. Figure 5 shows the changes of parallel and perpendicular components of the magnetic fields of each phase. According to Figure 5, the parallel component of the magnetic field is maximum for twisting angle of 0°, whereas the maximum perpendicular magnetic field occurs in 90°. The values of Figure 5 are calculated by neglecting the mechanical limits of the tapes.

Fig. 5. (a) Parallel, (b) perpendicular magnetic field variation with respect to angle.

AC loss reduction is the most important target of this paper. AC loss is reduced by the increase in twisting angle with respect to parallel and perpendicular magnetic fields. Figure 6 illustrates the behavior of AC loss with respect to pitch angle alterations. According to Figure 6, a twisting angle of 90° produces the minimum AC loss, near-zero, however, this led to the mechanical collapse of the tapes.

Fig. 6. AC loss variations with respect to twisting angle.

B. The Results of the Proposed Method in the Reduction of the AC Loss of the HTS Cable with Consideration of the Mechanical Limits

In order to reduce the AC loss of the HTS cable, the twisting angle of the HTS cable could undergo some changes. The proposed ECM in this paper can analyze the aforementioned electromechanical problems at a significantly faster time (than FEM) with high accuracy while the mechanical limits are considered. Firstly, the twisting angles of HTS tapes in phase A (two layers of tapes), phase B, and phase-C are increased according to the procedure of Figure 4 with a $\Delta\alpha$ step, and pitch lengths are recalculated. After gaining these parameters of the HTS cable, the strain is computed in each iteration to avoid the downgrading of the critical current to zero. The basic value of the AC loss without any changes in twisting angle is about 3.125W/m/ph. To reduce this value and change the twisting angle, multiple $\Delta\alpha$ are presented in Table IV. According to this Table, the smaller $\Delta\alpha$ leads to a more precise solution. However, the simulation time increases significantly. This means that for a 0.0644% further reduction in AC loss, computation time is 886.3333 times increased.

TABLE IV. ANGLE VARIATION IMPACT ON AC LOSS REDUCTION

$\Delta\alpha$ (degrees)	0.05	0.005	0.0005	0.00005
Final angle (degrees)	35.3612	35.2332	35.2292	35.2284
ε (%)	1.105761	1.099339	1.099065	1.099059
$\frac{I_c(\varepsilon)}{I_c(0)}$	0.899	0.8988	0.8965	0.8963
Maximum AC loss (W/m/ph)	2.25168	2.25043	2.25026	2.25023
Iteration	159	1593	15927	159263
Time (s)	0.03	0.32	2.72	26.59
Improvement (%)	27.9462	27.9862	27.9917	27.9926

Table V shows the comparison results between the proposed method and other previously published methods. The conducted studies in [21, 22] have also aimed to reduce the AC loss by the variation of the twisting angle. The maximum reduction of the AC loss in [21] is about 19.66% while the mechanical limits were also considered. However, the current paper uses sensitivity analysis to gain the results and does not

present any iterative method. On the other hand, in [22] the AC loss is reduced by 12 to 14%, but the mechanical limits were neglected.

TABLE V. COMPARISON BETWEEN THE PROPOSED METHOD AND [21, 22]

Reference	Maximum reduction	Mechanical limits	Iterative method
[21]	19.66%	yes	no
[22]	12-14%	no	no
Proposed	27.99%	yes	yes

IV. CONCLUSION

AC loss is investigated in this paper, as a significant parameter in the performance of superconducting cables, with its reduction being the main target. This paper has utilized an ECM to analyze the impact of the twisting angle increment on the efficiency improvement of the selected HTS cable. For this purpose, firstly a sensitivity analysis was conducted to analyze the electromagnetic behavior of the cable which results in:

- The parallel magnetic field was reduced along with the increment of twisting angle, while the perpendicular magnetic field was increased.
- The AC loss of the cable in all phases was either decreased to a minimum value for the angle of about 90 degrees.

In order to reduce the AC loss of the cable, another study was accomplished. According to this study:

- The AC loss in the improved design of the HTS cable is 0.356 times of the AC loss in the preliminary design.
- The AC loss could be further decreased if the reduction step of the twisting angle is selected to be smaller, but we would end up needing a much better computer system to handle the high computation cost.

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Investigation of Polycaprolactone/Carboxymethyl Cellulose Scaffolds by Mechanical and Thermal Analysis

Noppadol Sriputtha

Department of Advanced Manufacturing Technology
Faculty of Engineering
Pathumwan Institute of Technology
Bangkok, Thailand
Idol7877@gmail.com

Fasai Wiwatwongwana

Department of Advanced Manufacturing Technology
Faculty of Engineering
Pathumwan Institute of Technology
Bangkok, Thailand
fasaiw227@gmail.com

Nattawit Promma

Department of Mechanical Engineering
Faculty of Engineering
Chiang Mai University
Chiang Mai, Thailand
nano_504@hotmail.com

Abstract—The objective of this work was to learn more about three-dimensional porous scaffolds made from biomaterial based on polycaprolactone (PCL) containing different amounts of carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) nanoparticles. Composite material samples containing 0, 2, 6.5, 11, 15.5, and 20% w/w of CMC and PCL/CMC scaffolds were prepared with the use of the salt particle leached technique. The mechanical properties were evaluated with the compressive strength analysis method. The studied temperature range started at very low temperatures and ended at crosslinking temperatures. It was evaluated using the thermal analysis methods of Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) in the range 0°C-200°C. The results revealed that the compressive modulus of blended PCL/CMC scaffold was higher than the one of pure PCL scaffold (582.2±106.2 kPa for pure PCL scaffold and 612.2±296 kPa for blended scaffold which contained 20% of CMC). For DSC analysis, in addition to the 15.5% w/w CMC PCL/CMC composite scaffold, other proportions of composite materials showed a decrease in crystallization temperature. The crystallinity of PCL-20% CMC was higher than that of PCL scaffolds.

Keywords—polycaprolactone; carboxymethyl cellulose; compressive strength; thermal analysis; differential scanning calorimetry

I. INTRODUCTION

Damage or loss of tissue or a portion of the body is usually one of the most deadly and costly problems in health care [1]. Tissue engineering has grown in popularity as a result of the necessity to consider merging or engaging multi-skilled approaches in order to solve this medical problem. Medical progress, along with increasing interaction in a range of fields of knowledge such as materials science, biology, engineering,

and physics, has produced breakthroughs in the diagnosis, evaluation, and implementation of implant instruments and tissue transplantation. Extraction of isolated cells, execution with tissue-persuasion chemicals, and implantation of a cell into a scaffold composite are common approaches for tissue regeneration [3, 4]. In addition, the usage of composite scaffold typically yields more lucrative outcomes [2].

Nanotechnology has become one of the world's fastest expanding industrial sectors, influencing a wide range of scientific and technology industries [5]. Scaffolds are critical components in tissue engineering. When it comes to choosing scaffolds for tissue engineering however, researchers are usually presented with a confusing number of choices [6]. Polymers have been utilized as biomaterials in the manufacturing of medical devices and tissue-engineering scaffolds [7, 8]. The most recent scaffolds mimic biological processes in the extracellular matrix in order to capture the structure and functions of growing tissues and aid cell adhesion, growth, and dispersal [9]. Biodegradable polymers such as PCL, PLLA, PLGA, etc. are used as scaffolds in tissue engineering to foster cells until they are replaced by the Extracellular Matrix (ECM) [10-12]. An ideal scaffold should be extremely porous with linked pores, biodegradable, and made of components that are compatible. Even though most scaffolds comply with these parameters, their final features are mostly defined by their technique of construction. However, the approach is determined by the goal of the tissue engineering application [13-14]. Three-dimensional porous scaffolds can be prepared using a variety of processes, including 3D printing, phase separation, gas-foaming, solvent casting, salt particle leaching, and freeze-drying [15-17].

Corresponding author: Noppadol Sriputtha

Particulate leaching has been employed in tissue engineering since it is one of the simplest methods used to create porous materials using salt. The method of salt leaching is simple and does not need the use of high pressure or expensive equipment [18-20]. Controlling of porosity, pore structure, and pore size is as easy as changing the quantity and particle size of salt. In this work, scaffolds were fabricated using the salt particulate leaching method. Polycaprolactone (PCL) is a linear aliphatic polyester. It is a hydro-phobic, biocompatible, semi-crystalline, slowly disintegrating polymer which is simple to work with [21-24]. As a result, a PCL composite based material with tunable hydrophilicity is utilized. The changed hydrophilicity was achieved by offering different magnitudes of a highly hydrophilic biocompatible substance, such as carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) [21]. The current study investigated the properties of porous scaffolds made of PCL and CMC. The morphological, thermal, and mechanical characteristics of PCL/CMC composite material samples containing 0, 2, 6.5, 11, 15.5, and 20% w/w CMC were studied.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PART

A. Materials

PCL with an average molecular weight (M_w) of 45g/mol and melting temperature of 56–64°C, and CMC with a medium viscosity, were acquired from Sigma-Aldrich, USA. Sodium chloride (NaCl), which will be used as a porogen, was received from Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany). Trifluoroethanol (TFE) from Sigma-Aldrich was employed as a solvent for these composite polymers.

B. Scaffold Preparation

The scaffolds were fabricated using the salt leaching method. A polymer solution was made by combining a PCL pellet with CMC (PCL/CMC), with TFE as a solvent at a concentration of 30% (by mass). The PCL solution contained 3g of PCL and 7g of TFE [25, 26]. The mixture design parameter in the Minitab software was used to generate the design of the PCL and blended PCL with CMC mixing formulations, as shown in Table I. Codes were used to name the materials, with P0 being the pure base material of PCL produced by mixing a PCL pellet and TFE at a 30% concentration (by mass). The salt was mixed into the solution, which is utilized for 24g [27]. The pure PCL P0 sample (6g) was used for comparison. The weight ratios of the P1-P5 samples were 5.88:0.12, 5.61:0.39, 5.34:0.66, 5.07:0.93, and 4.80:1.20 respectively.

TABLE I. SOLUTION ABBREVIATIONS AND COMPOSITIONS

Sample	PCL % (w/w)	CMC % (w/w)
P0	100	-
P1	98	2
P2	93.5	6.5
P3	89	11
P4	84.4	15.5
P5	80	20

C. Porous Scaffold Fabrication

In this process, scaffolds were produced by casting a

mixture of polymer solution and salt particles. Following solvent evaporation, the scaffolds were fractionated in a suitable solvent, allowing particles to be leached off. Porous scaffolds were formed when these particles were completely eliminated from the mixture [19]. First, the PCL was melt on a stirrer at 55-65°C and then the TFE solvent was added to make a 30% PCL solution. The CMC was poured, stirred, and mixed into the PCL solution until the solution became homogeneous. The NaCl was then stirred into the mixed PCL/CMC solution. The solution was poured into a teflon mold, which produced 20mm edge cube molds. The molds were placed under a ventilation hood overnight to allow the solvent to evaporate. After the solvent evaporated, deionized water was used to leach off the salt particles. The scaffolds were then air dried for two days before being stored in a desiccator. The produced salt-leached PCL/CMC scaffolds revealed strongly linked porosity networks.

D. Morphological Characterization

Optical and electron microscopy were used to examine the morphology of the scaffolds. A COXEM model EM-30 Plus was used with 20kV acceleration voltage. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was utilized as a measurement technique to quantify the average pore size. The average pore size of each component was calculated after measuring at least 20 different pore sizes. The porosity of the scaffold was determined using a specific gravity bottle with ethanol as the fluid in motion, according to the Archimedes hypothesis [28-30]. Finally, the porosity of a scaffold was determined by:

$$\text{Porosity (\%)} = \frac{(W_2 - W_3 - W_s) / \rho_e}{(W_1 - W_3) / \rho_e} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where W_1 , W_2 , and W_3 represent the weights of specific gravity bottles containing ethanol, both ethanol and scaffold, and a taken out of ethanol-saturated scaffold respectively, W_s represents the weight of the scaffold, and ρ_e represents the ethanol density.

E. Mechanical Testing

PCL has been extensively researched in bone tissue engineering. Long bones respond better to compression stresses than other types of loads [31]. As a result, it was customary to investigate the compression properties of a material that was intended to be utilized for bone replacement [32-34].

The compressive mechanical properties of scaffolds were tested using a Zwick Roell universal testing machine. Five replicas of scaffolds were cut into rectangular pieces of 10mm length, 10mm width, and around 3mm thickness [31]. The crosshead speed was set at 1mm/min. The compression modulus was computed by taking the first part of the linear segment of the stress-strain curve and dividing it by the initial cross-sectional area. The parameters were computed in accordance with the processes outlined in the ASTM D3574 standard.

F. Thermal Analysis

To investigate the temperature behavior of the PCL/CMC composite scaffold, a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC 3+, Mettler Toledo, Switzerland) was used. The samples were

around 10mg in weight [4]. All samples were put in a hermetically sealed aluminum pan with a nitrogen flow rate of 50mL/min. The samples were heated for 5min at temperatures ranging from 0 to 200°C before being cooled to 0°C and reheated to 200°C. The ramp rate was 10°C/min during all heating and cooling cycles [35].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Morphological Analysis

After being coated with gold by an ion-sputter machine. (Ion-Coater, a COXEM SPT-20), the porous scaffold was studied for morphological characterization using SEM (COXEM model EM-30 Plus) at 20kV. The dimension of the pore size was measured for at least 20 pores [15, 26] and the average pore size was calculated as shown in Figure 1. Figure 1 shows the P0, P1, P2, P3, P4, and P5 occurring pore diameters of 227.35, 269.48, 348.28, 271.82, and 284.70mm respectively. The average porosity of the PCL (P0) scaffold was 81.44% and the porosities of the blended P1 to P5 scaffolds were 98.70, 98.30, 98.73, 98.06, and 98.88%. The porosity of blended PCL/CMC scaffolds was higher than that of the pure PCL scaffold, which might be due to CMC particles being dispersed throughout the PCL matrix surrounding the scaffold [27].

Fig. 1. SEM images of PCL and PCL/CMC composite scaffolds, (a) P0, (b) P1, (c) P2, (d) P3, (e) P4, and (f) P5.

B. Morphological Analysis

Adding CMC loading had a detrimental influence on the mechanical characteristics of the composite scaffolds [36]. As demonstrated in Table II, the compression modulus decreased as the additive concentration of CMC increased. The decreasing of CMC was not significantly different ($p > 0.05$) when compared to P0 scaffold as shown in Figure 2 which shows the apparent compressive modulus of PCL and composite scaffolds. P0, P3, P4, and P5 scaffolds demonstrated mechanical behavior with a consistent pattern within each

group. P1 and P2 scaffolds, on the other hand, exhibited mechanical behavior with more diversity. The P2 mixture showed the highest compressive modulus which was 789.6kPa, whereas the P3 mixture showed the lowest compressive modulus which was 509kPa. P1, P4, and P5 had compressive moduli of 706, 605.4 and 612.2kPa, respectively. The compression modulus values were compared with the reported results of previous studies. The results obtained in this work for PCL scaffold, as well as the values published in [31] were close to the lower limit of the homogeneous compression modulus range.

TABLE II. COMPRESSIVE MODULUS OF THE BLENDED SCAFFOLDS

Scaffolds	Compressive modulus (kPa)
P0	582±106
P1	706±39
P2	789.6±183
P3	509±225
P4	605.4±124
P5	612.2±296

Fig. 2. Comparison of the compressive modulus of PCL/CMC blended scaffolds.

C. Differential Scanning Calorimetry

Figure 3 shows the DSC results taken during the second heating, and Table III shows the measured parameters. With these data, melting temperature (T_m), and melting enthalpy (ΔH_m) were obtained. Crystallinity (X_c) was determined using (2). The considered melting enthalpy of the 100% crystalline PCL (ΔH_0) was 146J/g [37].

$$X_c = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\Delta H_0} \quad (2)$$

The sample P4 showed the greatest peak melting temperature, a melting enthalpy of 83.27J/g, and a crystallinity of 57.0%. Other authors discovered that the addition of CMC to PLC had no effect on melting temperature [38], however their experiments were restricted to increase of up to 20% by weight of CMC in particular. Authors in [2, 21, 31] reported that combining 20% CMC with PCL raised the melting temperature by 1°C. We observed that the 20% CMC scaffold exhibited a consistent melting temperature change of about

1°C. It was found that the melting temperature was 68°C with 10% CMC addition [22], and 67.31°C for 11% CMC addition in this investigation.

Fig. 3. Heating DSC scan for PCL and its composite scaffolds.

TABLE III. COMPRESSIVE MODULI OF THE PCL/CMC BLENDED SCAFFOLDS

Samples	T _m (°C)	ΔH _m (J/g)	X _c (%)
P0	67.31	59.35	40.65
P1	65.43	57.62	39.46
P2	67.79	23.13	15.84
P3	67.31	23.04	15.78
P4	69.53	83.27	57.03
P5	66.49	81.59	55.88

D. Discussion

According to the results of these experiments, the PCL/CMC mixture of 93.5/6.5 (P2) combined the maximum compressive modulus with a good porosity value and interconnected porous structures that reacted similarly to other circumstances. The presence of CMC mitigated the degradation temperature and decreased it continuously as the amount of CMC rised. The blended PCL/CMC scaffolds P1-P5 were fabricated using the salt leaching method which could be used for tissue engineering applications. However, the amount of CMC used should be sufficient to alter the hydrophilicity of the scaffold. The melting temperature of P4 was the highest (89.53°C), with a melting enthalpy of 83.27J/g and a crystallinity of 57.03%, whereas the melting temperatures of the other components were quite comparable. This might imply that the addition of MC to the PCL had no influence on the melting temperature.

IV. CONCLUSION

The salt leaching method was used in this work to effectively fabricate PCL/CMC composite scaffolds. Using the solvent cast salt leaching method, it was feasible to create homogeneous PCL/CMC composite scaffolds with efficiently distributed homogenous porous structure. The scaffold from salt leaching with the mixture of PCL-6.5% CMC (P2) ratio showed the greatest compressive modulus, which was

789.6kPa, whereas the combination of PCL-11% CMC (P3) ratio had the lowest compressive modulus, which was 509kPa. The ratios P4 and P5 were lower than P3, but they were higher than the PCL. In summary, adding CMC to PCL can improve the mechanical characteristics of the scaffold. With the exception of the 15.5% w/w CMC, the PCL/CMC composite scaffolds showed decreasing in crystallization temperature, enthalpy of crystallization, melting enthalpy, and crystallinity degree in DSC analysis. In addition, the crystallinity of PCL-20% CMC is higher than that of PCL. Because of their biocompatible and biodegradable properties, making them suitable for support materials in biomedical engineering and pharmacological applications, the PCL/CMC scaffolds exhibited characteristics that need further investigation.

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Circuit Modeling and Analysis of Wearable Antennas on the Effect of Bending for Various Feeds

Sandhya Mallavarapu

Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering
National Institute of Technology Warangal
Warangal, Telangana, India
sandhyamallavarapu@student.nitw.ac.in

Anjaneyulu Lokam

Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering
National Institute of Technology Warangal
Warangal, Telangana, India
anjan@nitw.ac.in

Abstract-The promising utilization of wearable antennas has experienced gigantic growth during the last decade. An antenna is one of the most significant and crucial components of wireless wearable devices. They need to be particularly designed to work while worn on and off the body. The wearable antenna embedded into clothing finds its use in wireless communications including tracking and navigation, mobile and wearable computing, and public safety and security. For user accessibility, there is a growing requirement for incorporating antennas on or in clothing. Determining the dielectric characteristics of the flexible substrates utilized in the design of the wearable antenna is also essential. In this paper, a Microstrip Ring Resonator (MRR) is employed to determine the dielectric properties of fabric substrates followed by state-of-the-art designs of wearable antennas and their bending effects at ISM band frequencies. An electrical equivalent model is designed to realize the potentials inside the geometry of an antenna under bending environment. This is followed by observing the effect of bending for different feeding methods on the wearable antenna's parameters when bending on a certain radius. The robustness of the proposed wearable antenna is examined by measuring the antenna under various bending curvatures for return loss, gain, and efficiencies. This will disclose the various contemplations for designing a wearable antenna from different feeding mechanisms with different materials and exemplifying the antenna's outcomes to dynamic moments of the human body. The performance of the proposed wearable antenna is acceptable even in a deformation environment, and there is a good agreement between the measured and the simulation results.

Keywords-wearable antenna; Wireless Body Area Networks (WBAN); Microstrip Ring Resonator (MRR); industrial; Scientific and Medical (ISM) band; Aperture Coupled Wearable Antenna (ACWA)

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution of wearable antennas originates from the concept of wearable computing systems as a part of clothing that enables the wearer continuous hassle-free data transfer. In recent times, a wearable antenna receives a noteworthy development in technologies such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, Wireless Local Area Networks (WLANs), and Wireless Body Area Networks (WBANs). In general, a wearable antenna is stated to have high flexibility and competence in a system connected with the human body. Well-being, health, and

lifestyle are the primary interests while implementing these systems [1-5]. Usually, wearable antenna desires for all modern applications must be lightweight, economical, almost maintenance-free, and do not require installation. Several specialized activity segments apply body area communication network systems, for instance, paramedics [6], firefighters [7], astronautics [8], military [9], and public safety. In addition, wearable antennas can also be applicable for teenagers, the elderly, and sportspersons to monitor vital signs such as temperature, heart rate, etc.

When worn on the body, wearable antennas can establish a wireless link between the body and the external world. The most appropriate topology for wearable antennas, ensuring the most favorable integration into clothing and wearer's ease, is the planar patch antenna [8, 9]. On-body antennas are preferably made of flexible textiles and wearable materials [12], which can naturally conform to the surface of the body. This involves information related to the dielectric characteristics, namely permittivity and loss tangent of the fabric. The measurement of the dielectric properties of flexible materials characterized by their complex values is a challenging task and special measuring instruments are required [13]. A simple but effective technique is considered to characterize the flexible substrates and electromagnetic properties of some fabrics [14, 15]. Wearable antennas are usually designed in the ideal flat state. Still, when integrated into clothing and worn they are likely to be subjected to deformations such as bending and stretching, which cause variations in the performance of the antenna, leading to potential performance degradation related to the resonant frequency, impedance bandwidth, and efficiency [16, 17]. Though the antenna is designed for a certain curvature, the variation of the radius of the curvature can influence the antenna's performance. Therefore there is a need to explore the influence of bending on various factors starting from scratch. The effect of bending on the antenna performance is sensitive to the different dielectric value of substrates [18], in which the dielectric constant near the air shows stable performance under bending. The impact of different thicknesses is explored in [19], and the influence of different radiator shapes is explored in [20]. Further, the wearable antenna undergoes the effect of being near to the body as the relative permittivity of the body changes [21]. To mitigate the human body coupling,

Corresponding author: n Sandhya Mallavarapu

Electromagnetic Bandgap (EBG) structures / AMC structures are placed on the backside of the wearable antenna, which can improve its FBR [22].

Therefore, the fundamental step in ensuring that the antenna can perform well is to ascertain the most suitable feeding method [23]. Mostly, any efficient antenna design involves a maximum power transfer between the end terminals, i.e. from the source to the antenna, where the antenna is fed at a point where the antenna impedance is 50Ω . By considering these conditions, the wearable antenna should be designed carefully in every aspect, including the feeding mechanism. However, the approach of estimating the antenna behavior using electromagnetic simulators has relatively high computational costs depending on the complexity of the radiating structure. Thus, an electrical equivalent circuit model is useful while characterizing such complex structures. In addition, the matching potentials of the antenna are estimated with the knowledge of equivalent circuit models. In this paper, the Advanced Design System (ADS) software is utilized to develop the equivalent circuit and predict the return loss, while the antenna is simulated in CST MW software before fabrication.

II. DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF FABRICS

Several techniques are available in the literature to identify the dielectric properties of fabrics. One simple technique adopted here is the Microstrip Ring Resonator (MRR), which is useful for analyzing the electromagnetic properties of the materials due to its feasible geometry, ease in prototyping, low price, small volume, and adaptability [24, 25]. The proper usage of the fabric material as substrate while designing wearable low-profile antennas makes them efficient. The MRR method uses the resonant frequency and the quality factor to calculate the permittivity and loss tangent of the substrate, which gives accurate results due to the absence of end effects and the high Q factor. This makes the proposed method advantageous compared to previously published [26, 27] methods. A straightforward resonant technique to characterize sample fabric's electromagnetic properties is based on the MRR and another method is based on the patch radiator, which is used to validate the results of the first. The geometry of the MRR involves the ring and two feed lines separated by a gap (Δ), which are placed on top of the substrate of size $50 \times 50 \text{mm}^2$. On the back of the substrate, ground plane is placed. Adhesive copper foil is utilized for the metal parts such as the ring and the two feed lines, whereas flexible jeans is the substrate as shown in Figure 1. The optimized dimensions are obtained with the help of traditional equations (Table I).

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic of the MRR, (b) prototype.

TABLE I. OPTIMIZED DIMENSIONS OF THE MRR MODEL

Ring dimensions	Mean radius (r)	Feed line width (W_f)	Feed line length (L_f)	Gap (Δ)
Value (mm)	8.5	3	14	1

Theoretically, the n^{th} resonance peak takes place at [28]:

$$F_n = \frac{nc}{2\pi R\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \quad (1)$$

where R is the average radius, c is the speed of light in the vacuum, and ϵ_r is the required dielectric constant.

Also, the Insertion Loss (IL) S_{21} (dB) is given by:

$$\text{IL} = 20 \log \left[1 - \frac{Q_l}{Q_u} \right] \quad (2)$$

where Q_l , Q_u represent the loaded and unloaded quality factors respectively.

From the S_{21} curve, the loaded quality factor given by:

$$Q_l = \frac{f_0}{\Delta f} \quad (3)$$

where f_0 is the resonance frequency, Δf is the difference between the upper and lower of the S_{21} (dB) curve.

The loss tangent can be calculated by determining the unloaded quality factor Q_u from (2) and substitute in (4):

$$\frac{1}{Q_u} = \frac{1}{Q_c} + \frac{1}{Q_d} \quad (4)$$

$$Q_c = h\sqrt{f_0\mu_0\pi\sigma_c} \quad (5)$$

where Q_d and Q_c are the quality factors of the dielectric and the conductor respectively.

Then, the loss tangent is calculated from:

$$\tan \delta = \frac{1}{Q_d} \quad (6)$$

Figure 2 shows the measurement setup on the network analyzer and the transmission coefficient of the proposed method. It is observed that there are two resonance peaks obtained at 4.27GHz and 8.9GHz, with a corresponding return loss of -35.94 and -22.48dB for the jeans textile. Based on the resonant peaks that appeared in S_{21} , the dielectric properties are calculated by substituting in (1)-(6) (Table II). The simulated and measured values are in good agreement. This result is also verified by the second method, which is focused on designing the patch antenna on the desired substrate [14].

In general, the fabric material is said to be lossless when the loss tangent is significantly small. According to the obtained results, the dielectric constant and loss tangent are 1.729 and 0.025 respectively [29-30]. Usually, the substrate's relative permittivity plays a substantial part in the design of the antenna, and variations in its value tend to change the operating

frequency of the antenna to more or less of the desired center frequency. However, the variation in loss tangent has a negligible effect on the antenna resonant frequency, affecting mostly the magnitude of return loss.

Fig. 2. S21 (dB) Vs. frequency of the MRR mode.

TABLE II. RESULTANT DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF JEANS SUBSTRATE USING THE MRR METHOD

Mode	Resonant frequency (GHz)	IL S21 (dB)	Dielectric constant (ϵ_r)	$\tan \delta$
$n=1$	4.2716	-35.94322	1.729	0.078
$n=2$	8.916	-24.9838	1.687	0.025

III. DESIGN AND ELECTRICAL EQUIVALENTS OF THE WEARABLE ANTENNA

Ideally, a wearable antenna should be highly flexible, lightweight, and small in volume. It should have no installation requirements, high durability, and support bending and stretching at certain strain levels, but simultaneously it must be able to still function efficiently without compromising its RF characteristics. Two wearable antennas were designed with different feeding mechanisms and their equivalent circuits were obtained.

A. Inset Fed Wearable Antenna

For the implementation of a textile antenna, a planar patch antenna of a rectangular shape is chosen because of its planar structure and compactness [31]. Substrate selection is the key parameter while designing a microstrip antenna. By proper selection of the substrate dielectric properties and dimensions, a good antenna design is possible. The elementary form of the microstrip patch antenna consists of two metallic layers and a dielectric layer sandwiched between them as shown in Figure 3. The full ground plane attached to the back of the substrate shields the user from unwanted radiation. The radiating patch and the feed line are attached to the top of the substrate. The patch antenna with the inset feed is designed with flexible jeans as substrate and adhesive copper foil as the radiating patch. The proposed wearable patch antenna is designed to resonate at 2.5GHz, which is suitable for Wi-Max applications. The transmission line model is used to find the input impedance of the inset-fed microstrip patch antenna. The microstrip patch antenna operates on the same principle, where the length of the patch has a greater influence in deciding the resonant

frequency. The fringing fields' forms at both the ends along the length of the patch tend to increase the effective length of the patch. Therefore, the impedance at the edges is very high and decreases as the inset distance moves towards the center of the patch. By adjusting the inset distance, proper impedance matching is achieved. The optimized dimensions are obtained from the standard equations [32] as shown in Table III. To get more insight, the textile antenna can be described in its electrical equivalent. Using the transmission line model in [32], the equivalent circuit of the inset-fed patch element is modeled as a parallel RLC resonant network with a series inductance representing the near field effect of the microstrip feed line. The electromagnetic fields' parameters L and C can be determined in the antenna's near field, where they can represent the ability to deposit magnetic and electric energy in the circuit throughout resonance. The circuit simulations were carried out in ADS software. The optimized parameter values are directly shown with the elements in the circuit in Figure 4.

TABLE III. DIMENSIONS OF THE INSET FED WEARABLE PATCH ANTENNA

Parameter	L_p	W_p	W	L	Feed width	Thickness
Dimensions (mm)	46.6	53.6	100	100	13	3.5

Fig. 3. (a) Schematic view, (b) fabricated prototype of the inset fed wearable patch antenna.

Fig. 4. (a) Simulated equivalent circuit in ADS, (b) S11 plot of the inset fed microstrip patch antenna.

From the circuit, the feed point impedance at the specific frequency band can be modeled as an inductance (L) at high-frequency and a capacitor at low-frequency (which is neglected and not shown in the circuit) in series. The circuit parameters R_a , L_a , and C_a are the equivalent resistance, inductance, and capacitance and are given by the standard relations given below [33]:

$$C_a = \frac{\epsilon_e \epsilon_0 L_p W_p}{2h} \cdot \frac{1}{\cos^2(\beta)}, \quad \beta = \frac{\pi Z_0}{L_p} \quad (7)$$

$$L_a = \frac{1}{2\pi f_r C_a} \quad (8)$$

$$R_a = \frac{Q}{2\pi f_r C_a} \quad (9)$$

The input impedance at the feed location from the circuit is noted as:

$$Z_{in}(f) = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{R_a} + \frac{1}{j\omega L_a} + j\omega C_a} + X_f \quad (10)$$

where L_p is the length of the patch, W_p the width of the patch, h the substrate thickness and Z_0 the feed location impedance.

From Figure 4(b), it is observed that there is a good agreement between the simulated and the measured values. However, a small discrepancy is accountable for fabrication errors. With a flexible substrate, it is always a challenging task to shape the material in the required dimensions with the help of scalpel/cutting tools. While cutting the edges of the substrate, due to parallax error, the slides and edges may not be straightly cut or some threads may come out. All these complications may affect the antenna matching and performance. Therefore the wearable antenna is fabricated with the right tools and with utmost care.

B. Aperture Coupled Wearable Patch Antenna

The present generation clothing can monitor the bio signals of the wearer and enables continuous communication between the attached antenna and the outer world regarding the person's state of health. Many of the existing models involve a single-layer design and regularly a coaxial feed [34, 35] is utilized to attach the antenna to the transceiver. This type of feed structure is firm and is often annoying to the wearer. Similarly, using microstrip feed to the antenna is not the greatest solution because of the unnecessary parasitic radiations from the feed line and the radiating element. However, these problems can be mitigated by situating the feed line beneath the antenna ground plane, which can protect the feed line and the transceiver from the radiating antenna. The power is transferred from the feed line to the radiating element through an aperture in the ground plane that leads to an aperture-coupled patch antenna. The Aperture Coupled Wearable Patch Antenna (AC-WPA) serves the purpose. Its structure involves a ground plane sandwiched between two different substrates. The radiating patch is placed on the antenna substrate and a feed line is seated on the base of the feed substrate as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. AC-WPA: (a) Scheme, (b) front view and (c) back view of the fabricated prototype, (d) experimental setup.

All the rigid cables are replaced with a simple transmission line, and the power is coupled through a small aperture of arbitrary shape in the ground plane, which justifies the name of the antenna. Flexible jeans and wash cotton were chosen as the feed and antenna substrates since they are typical, durable, inelastic, and of low cost. Design studies were carried out using the electromagnetic simulator CST MW Studio and the acquired optimized dimensions are tabulated in Table IV.

TABLE IV. OPTIMIZED DIMENSIONS OF THE AC-WPA

Patch	Adhesive copper	W_p (mm)		L_p (mm)	
		43		40	
Antenna substrate	Wash cotton	h (mm)	ϵ_r	$\tan\delta$	
		2.56	1.5	0.025	
Ground plane	Adhesive copper	W_g (mm)		L_g (mm)	
		65		65	
Aperture		W_{ap} (mm)		L_{ap} (mm)	
		3.5		20	
Feed substrate	Jeans	h (mm)	ϵ_r	$\tan\delta$	
		1.15	1.7	0.02	
Feed line	Adhesive copper	W_f (mm)		l_f (mm)	
		1.5		22.5	

The adopted feeding method produces a higher bandwidth than the other feeding methods because of its impedance transformation behavior. In practical applications, the transceiver is directly connected to the feed line which couples the power to the patch through an aperture placed exactly in the middle under it. The prototype is built according to the specifications and is shown in Figure 5.

The AC-WPA is represented in its electrical equivalent circuit model to gain insight into the underlying electromagnetic behavior. The equivalent circuit of AC-WPA practically is complex and consists of lumped RLC elements, ideal transformer, and transmission line segment to represent the radiating patch and coupling slot. A simple equivalent model is adopted here, in which the optimized parameter values are shown directly in the circuit. The circuit simulations were carried out in ADS, whereas the electromagnetic simulator CST MWS was applied to achieve the AC-WPA design and optimization, which are shown in Figure 6(a).

Fig. 6. (a) Circuit model, (b) reflection coefficient curve of AC-WPA.

It can be observed that there is a close relationship between the simulated and the measured values. However, proper care and attention must be given while assembling the multilayer structure manually, because even for small misalignment between the feed line, the slot, and the patch there is variation in the performance result. Moreover, high fabrication tolerances exist while working on textiles compared to the traditional substrates. All these circumstances lead to some measurement deviation in the resonance frequency as can be seen in Figure 6(b).

IV. BENDING CHARACTERIZATION AND ELECTRICAL MODELING

The bent wearable patch antenna's geometry is modeled as a cylindrical cavity [36]. The geometry of the foam cylinders upon which the textile antennas are wrapped around is shown in Figure 7(a). For both inset fed and aperture coupled antennas, patch and ground planes were modeled as perfect electric conductors and the remaining four sides as perfect magnetic conductors. Hence this arrangement forms a cavity bounded by electric and magnetic walls at:

$$\rho = r, \rho = r + h, \varphi = \pm \frac{\beta}{2}, \text{ and } Z = \pm L/2 \quad (11)$$

The Maxwell's field equations are:

$$E = -\nabla X F - j\omega\mu A + \frac{1}{j\omega\epsilon} \nabla(\nabla \cdot A) \quad (12)$$

$$H = -\nabla X A - j\omega\mu F + \frac{1}{j\omega\epsilon} \nabla(\nabla \cdot F) \quad (13)$$

The fields inside the cylindrical cavity are obtained by imposing the boundary conditions on Maxwell's equations. By solving these equations, one can get the relations for T.E. and T.M. modes, from which a relation between resonant frequency

and bending radius was found analytically. To give an outlook to WBAN applications, it is essential to explore certain bending radius/angles per antenna width/length. From the circuit analysis point of view, the bending of the patch antenna changes length, thereby altering the antenna's E-field, which can be validated by changing the capacitance between the antenna element and the ground plane. In general, bending of the antenna brings discontinuity, i.e. the electric field becomes strongest in that particular part while the magnetic field shows a minimal effect. This indicates that the inductive loading doesn't get affected. The capacitive loading, also known as tuning capacitor, is denoted by C_t . As the bending radius increases, the capacitive loading becomes small [37]. The simulated circuit parameters for the patch antenna bent in the E-plane are shown in Figure 7(b). Comparing the flat case with the bent cases, it is observed that the capacitance C_2 decreases and L_2 increases. The product $L \cdot C$ increases when bending becomes critical, which means that the resonance frequency shifts to a lower frequency band.

Fig. 7. (a) Antennas wrapped around foam cylinders in E, H-plane directions, (b) equivalent circuit of a bent patch antenna.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Although the performance of the flexible antennas can be upgraded with united solutions for wearable applications, the development and optimization of such materials still require further characterization and improvement. Here a comparison is made for bending variations for different feeds of patch antennas where four different scenarios are considered. These radii are sensibly considered to mimic the chest and arm sizes of the human body [38]. These deformations were conducted to test their capability to resist a certain amount of structural bending.

A. Effect on Resonant Frequency and Impedance Match

Simulations were carried out over the frequency range of 1.0–3.0GHz. The proposed textile antennas have been fabricated, and the resultant reflection coefficient is measured using the Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) Hewlett Packard 8719A. When these antennas are wrapped around the cylindrical foam surfaces, the simulated resonant frequency appears to be dependent on the antenna curvature, more particularly for the antenna bending in the direction of length as for a microstrip radiator the electric field lines are oriented

along the length and magnetic field lines along the width. Therefore a shift in resonant frequency appeared as the effective length of the patch is decreased when it is bent lengthwise.

Fig. 8. Return loss variations for different bending cases for (a) AC-WPA, on the E-plane, (b) inset fed patch antenna on the E-plane, (c) AC-WPA on the H-plane, and (d) inset fed patch antenna on the H-plane.

If the tendency of detuning of the simulated resonant frequency is considered and graphed for different bending cases, it is worth noting that the more the antenna is bent in the E-plane, in general, the more the effective length gets reduced, and so the resonant frequency gets shifted to the higher band as shown in Figure 8(a) and 8(b) for the AC-WPA and the inset fed patch antenna respectively [39]. On the other hand, the H-plane bending shows minute, almost negligible, variations in resonant frequency (Figure 8(c), 8(d)). It can be seen that the reflection coefficient increases as the bending becomes critical, i.e. the antenna operates ordinarily. For the AC-WPA, the frequency detuning is approximately 16% for severe bending in the E-Plane, and the deviation in the resonant frequency is small in the H-Plane. The return loss of the bent AC antenna is large, so a large amount of energy enters the antenna and hence efficient antenna performance is obtained. The same is applicable for any candidate antenna.

B. Effect on Electric Field Intensity

The electric field intensity can be better understood when the antenna bending occurs on a foam cylinder. The distribution of the E-field for both the proposed antennas under different bending radii is shown in Figure 9. It can be observed that the E-field is small at the center, and maximum at the sides of the patch for the flat antenna candidates. Instead, for both the antennas, there is an insignificant effect on their E-field behavior under bending situations, in which maximum occurs at the sides of the patch. Generally, for the inset fed patch antenna, the electric field, and thus the current flow, is associated with the length, whereas the magnetic field with the width. Exposing antennas to lengthwise bending, influences on the current flow and the electric field are expected, while there is marginal impact when the bending occurs in the width direction. The change in the distance traveled by the current between the opposing ends of the patch antenna due to the bending of the materials leads to a reduction in the length of the patch.

Fig. 9. Electric field variations of (a) inset fed antenna, (b) AC-WPA on different bending fixtures.

C. Effects on the Radiation Pattern

Figure 10 shows the E-plane 2D radiation patterns for the planar and bent antennas. Meanwhile, for all the bending cases, the forward gain shows slight variations due to the high bending radius, which gives some difficulties to the antenna to radiate appropriately. It is instinctively clear that antenna

bending widens the radiation pattern in the bending plane, which leads to gain reduction. Different bending radii do not have a significant effect on the antenna radiation pattern. However, the efficiency of the proposed antenna is marginally reduced as the antenna bending is increased, but the antenna still operates efficiently at an acceptable level as shown in Table V. Another main consequence was obtained in terms of 3dB angular beam width, which is experienced as an increment when bending becomes critical.

Fig. 10. 2D Radiation pattern variations of (a) aperture coupled, (b) inset fed wearable patch antenna in different bending situations.

TABLE V. GAIN AND EFFICIENCY VARIATIONS OF THE PROPOSED ANTENNAS FOR DIFFERENT BENDING RADII

Cylinder Radius(mm)	Gain (dBi)		Efficiency (%)	
	Inset fed	Aperture coupled	Inset fed	Aperture coupled
Flat	6.12	4.84	58.61	53.95
70mm	6.01	4.50	58.34	46.02
50mm	5.74	4.46	58.47	55.08
40mm	5.41	4.41	59.56	55.08
35mm	5.03	4.13	60.06	52.72

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper focused on developing electrical equivalents of bending and its feeding effects on wearable textile antennas

when bending occurs on a certain radius. Two exciting feed types were selected on the textile patch antenna and input impedance, resonance frequency, electric field intensity, and radiation pattern were investigated. These are the most significant parameters to be observed before focusing on the bending effects. It was found that the E-Plane bending has a dominant impact on the impedance matching for both textile antennas. This result holds for all antenna candidates because the resonant length changes when the antenna is bent. The results showed that the aperture coupled antenna has a minimal bending influence on the impedance matching and resonant frequency, proving the robustness of the antenna under these effects at the cost of complexity. Moreover, the feed type removes the usage of rigid cables and unnecessary radiation from the feeds. The less cross-polar level makes it a better candidate for wearable applications. Also, the electric field intensity and gain have minimal effect on bending for both the antenna candidates. Therefore, aperture coupled wearable antennas are far better regarding the bending performance despite their structural complexity.

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Illegal Construction Imposed by the Private Lands in Peripheral Urban Areas of M'sila, Algeria

Elhadj Benkhaled

Department of Urban Engineering
Institute of Urban Techniques Management
University of M'sila
M'sila, Algeria
elhadj.benkhaled@univ-msila.dz

Mohamed Mili

Department of Urban Engineering
Institute of Urban Techniques Management
University of M'sila
M'sila, Algeria
mohamed.mili@univ-msila.dz

Fateh Oudina

Department of Urban Engineering
Institute of Urban Techniques Management
University of M'sila
M'sila, Algeria
fateh.oudina@univ-msila.dz

Abstract-Urban building lands are considered a scarce resource, which forces us to rationalize their use and assignment. They play an important role in shaping the urban space with all its components and determine its characteristics. The impact on urban space depends on the legal nature of the land, the density of buildings, and the quality of social cohesion. Like all Algerian cities, the city of M'sila has experienced, since the '90s, an increasing demand for building plots, especially in the outskirts which are mostly private properties. This situation directly contributed to the spread of illegal constructions and as a result, districts lack basic living conditions. This phenomenon appeared in the peripheral district called La Rocade. In this paper, we will attempt to identify the impact of the legal nature of land properties, particularly private ones, on the proliferation of illegal constructions in the outskirts of the city of M'sila. We will try to find solutions and alternatives to limit or stop its spread and propose urban interventions to restructure this district and integrate it into the existing urban space.

Keywords-outskirts; land ownership; private land; urban space; illegal construction

I. INTRODUCTION

Following the example of the majority of Algerian cities, the city of M'sila underwent, after the independence of Algeria in 1962, an important process of urbanization due to the natural increase of the population and the phenomenon of rural exodus [1]. This urbanization has been accompanied by an accelerated increase in the rate of land consumption to meet the strong demand for housing and public facilities [2]. The urbanization phenomenon was amplified at the beginning of the '90s due to the poor political and security conditions that the country experienced during this period [3]. This has led to the emergence of new urban forms, particularly in the outskirts of the city [4]. As a result, two distinct forms of urbanization have

been developed: The first concerns urbanization through the planning instruments established by the public authorities and the second illegal (illicit) constructions on private properties to the detriment of agricultural land [5]. Faced with the worrying situation of the propagation of illicit constructions, the public authorities were obliged to regularize these areas [6]. Operations were conducted by the promulgation of a set of legislative texts [7] setting the rules for bringing constructions into conformity and their completion, aiming to achieve a balance between the interest and needs of inhabitants in terms of housing and the public interest in urban planning according to the economic, social, environmental, cultural, and aesthetic dimensions [7]. However, the application of the law faces a set of challenges, particularly in the district called La Rocade, where most of the buildings are built illegally. Built on private lands, this district constitutes one of the most important components of the urban space of the city due to its location along the national road number 40 (RN 40), its area of over 68 hectares, its density of 70 dwellings per hectare, and its population of more than 45,000 inhabitants. Over the last 10 years, the public authorities have spent more than 5 billion Algerian dinars to improve the living conditions of the inhabitants of this district.

The proliferation of constructions without a building permit in the La Rocade district has prompted us to ask a series of fundamental questions: What is the influence of private land properties in determining the urbanization arrangements of M'sila? How to limit the spread of this type of illicit constructions? How to reorganize and improve the living conditions of the inhabitants of this district? Despite the difficulty of mastering the phenomenon of the proliferation of illegal constructions on land of a private legal nature, the aim of this research is to try to answer these questions. This could

Corresponding author: Elhadj Benkhaled

be done through an evaluation of the urban and architectural characteristics of the studied district, the proposal of solutions that could contribute to stopping the propagation of the phenomenon, the improvement of the living conditions of the inhabitants, and finally by seeking ways to involve the multiple urban actors, particularly the citizen.

II. STUDY AREA

M'sila is a city in the North-Central part of Algeria. The city has experienced two types of urban extension. The first concerns the various collective housing, residential subdivision, and public facility programs carried out by the public authorities on public land [8]. The second concerns, essentially, individual housing in the eastern outskirts of the city made on privately owned land [4]. This outskirts contains more than 4 districts, the most important of which is the La Rocade. This district was chosen as the study area because of its strategic location along the NR 40, its large surface area, its high residential density, and the private legal nature of land ownership. The district is surrounded by private agricultural properties on the North, South, and East sides. The second reason is the significant number of observed illegal constructions (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Location of the study area (La Rocade district).

III. METHODOLOGY

The urban dynamic in the eastern outskirts of the city of M'sila was noticed during the '90s by the emergence of illegal dwellings on private lands. This situation has become worrying for the local public authorities. In the present research, the methodological approach used associates the diachronic comparison between the directives of the graphic planning documents, in particular, the master plan of development and town planning (PDAU), the land use plan (POS), and cadastral plans [9] along with in situ observation. This analysis was supplemented by an administrative survey through a series of semi-structured interviews with urban stakeholders. Our analysis is based on 3 elements, namely the legal nature of lands, the construction type, and the land market. To carry out our plans, we relied on architectural survey, taking photos, AutoCad software, and the Geographic Information System (GIS).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Evolution of the Nature of Land Ownership and its Effect on Urban Extension

The legal nature of land properties may change according to the different stages of the historical development of the city in relation to the nature of the political system, especially in administrative and legislative aspects, management strategies, and town planning instruments [10]. We found it useful to do a spatial reading through in which we highlight the stages of the urban development of M'sila through the nature of land properties, the emergence of different urban forms, and the direction of extension relative to each period of development.

At the beginning of the creation of M'sila, which dates back to 1015 AD, the land properties belonged to individuals or to the various tribes of the nearby agro-pastoral villages. During the French colonization, the administration proceeded to a restructuring of all the properties in order to be reassign and allocate them to European owners according to the plan of the senatus consulte of the city established in 1905 [12]. This plan played an important role in determining the directions of the urban extension of the city. The general shape of the urban tissue has been configured in an oval shape due to its location within large areas of private agricultural land and crossed by a natural element which is the El-Ksob River [8]. As for the lands intended for construction, they were very limited, which produced a contrast between the components of the urban tissue, where there were dwellings attached to each other. This succession of adjacent dwellings is due to the increasing evolution of members of the same family [11]. The French authorities carried out cadastral operations covering a total area estimated at 13,950 hectares where they counted more than 53% of land of private and tribal property, located mostly in the eastern part of the El-Ksob River. The area of public property was estimated at around 47%, of which 19% was owned by the state and 28% by the commune (communal property). The majority of these public properties are located in the western part of the city [12].

This radical change of property nature of all the lands of the city of M'sila, in particular in its western part had a direct and significant impact on the determination of the direction of urban growth towards the northwest side of the city. It allowed the emergence of new urban and architectural forms and typologies. The colonial city is structured by perpendicular streets and individual dwellings lined up in city blocks that are almost identical in terms of shape, area, and size. These constructions are aligned symmetrically along the main and secondary ways. Due to the oppressive colonial policy towards the natives of the villages and surrounding areas, and the modern facilities and services of the European district [11], most of their inhabitants sought to find stability near the existing urban core. The year 1958 marks the beginning of the appearance of the La Rocade district along the NR 40 which crosses the town of M'sila. This district appeared as an alternative urban area to the European district given the scarcity of building land in the western part of the city. In contrast, in the eastern part of the city, private land was easy to divide and sell under customary contracts.

After the independence of Algeria, the French left the city leaving behind vacant properties and many developed and constructible spaces in the northwest part of the city. At the same time, a significant rural exodus has taken place in the absence of regulatory and legislative texts to guide the city's growth. Public land ownership played a preponderant role in determining the orientation of the urban extension towards this direction, because it did not present an administrative or legal constraint, in addition to its subsequent allocation as a constructible area defined by the town planning instruments. At the beginning of the '90s, the urban space of M'sila experienced a new mode of operation and management through mechanisms and means adapted to the aspirations and requirements of this period. The law number 90/29, related to the development and town planning, was promulgated to organize and manage urban areas through two fundamental tools: PDAU and POS [13]. The guidelines for town planning and the directions of urban extensions of M'sila were defined by the PDAU plan. The whole urban area was divided into eleven (11) sectors. These sectors are areas that are already built up, building lands, or designated for future urbanization. Most of the sectors are oriented towards the western part of the city due to the existence and availability of public land properties [14] (see Figure 2-3).

Fig. 2. Division of the urban area of M'sila.

Fig. 3. Types of land ownership in M'sila.

According to the stages analysis of the urban development of the city of M'sila, we note that the nature of the land ownership was often at the origin of the determination of the general configuration of the city. This happened either directly in the production of the forms of buildings and districts, as we noted in the first core, or indirectly, after the conversion of the

nature of land ownership, as was the case of the buildings of the colonial era. On the other hand, the nature of land ownership played a major role in determining the direction of the city's extension. Thus there has been a planned urban development towards the northwest side, where most of the land belongs to the State and does not present any administrative or legal problems, accompanied by the illegal urban development caused by the existence of private land properties in the eastern part. As for the extension to the southern part of the city, it was stopped by the creation of the industrial area (Figures 3-4).

Fig. 4. Stages of urban expansion in the city of M'sila, 1985-2021.

B. Illegal Construction: A Response to the Constraints of High Land Prices and the Scarcity of Building Land

The free market economy policy adopted by the Algerian government after the promulgation of Law number 25/90 is seen as an explicit declaration of the new land policy. All restrictions on the willingness of individuals to buy or sell land have been lifted. Thus, the land market through supply and demand has become the only parameter determining the prices of real estate on the basis of the agreements concluded between the contracting parties [15, 16]. This change in land policy has had major repercussions on the urban space of M'sila due to the large, rapid, and continuous increases in the land, particularly building land, prices. Land transactions have become compliant with the current regulations and are carried out on the basis of notarial deeds in accordance with the approved urban plans. For example, we cite the subdivision of 924 plots located about 4km from the city center, where the price per square meter of building land exceeded 100,000 Algerian dinars in 2020 (or nearly 800 Euros). As for the city center (Ouaoua Madani district), the price per square meter has crossed 200,000 Algerian dinars (or nearly 1600 Euros) per square meter. Considering the excessive prices of building land on the one hand, and the persistent high demand for building plots due to the housing crisis on the other, it was mandatory for low-income citizens to seek the cheapest possible alternative to acquire a home. La Rocade district, located in the east of the city, offered them this basic need. The price of square meter is low (15,000 DA or nearly 75 Euros per square metre) and affordable, transactions were made by customary contracts in most cases and the land is sold without servicing or landscaping.

TABLE I. AVERAGE PRICE OF URBAN LAND, 1940-1985 COMMAND ECONOMY PERIOD

Command economy period					Designation
1985	1980	1975	1960	1940	Year
165	150	100	80	20	Urban extension (ha)
52.3	40.2	29.5	19.2	5	Population (thousands)
317	268	295	240	250	Habitat density (h/ha)
300	100	20	//	//	Cost of m ²

TABLE II. AVERAGE PRICE OF URBAN LAND, 1990-2018 FREE MARKET ECONOMY PERIOD

Free market economy period						Designation
2018	2008	2005	2000	1995	1990	Year
900	400	350	250	200	180	Urban extension (ha)
650	135	121	109	99.5	60.3	Population (thousands)
850	337	347	365	467	335	Habitat density (h/ha)
100000	30000	20000	5000	3000	1000	Cost of m ²

C. Descriptive Analysis of the Components of the Urban Tissue of the Study Case

The La Rocade district occupies an area of 68 hectares with an irregular geometric shape. The characteristics of this spatial configuration are determined by the nature of the land properties which are considered as private agricultural land. The NR 40 is the main road axis which crosses the district. The structure of all the streets of the urban tissue is organized perpendicular to this main axis. The majority of these streets are characterized by small, variable, non-uniform width and a tortuous alignment. As for the built plots, they are irregular in shape crossed by narrow dead-end streets [17]. The land areas range from 600m² to 8000m². Sometimes we find free spaces between the plots in the form of very small cavities not exceeding 200m². These free spaces are used for social exchanges, especially for women, between neighbors and for playgrounds. The owners of private lands seek to maximize the profitability of the sale of plots reserved for construction (see Figure 5).

Fig. 5. The general form of the division of the islands.

The dwellings lined up and juxtaposed along the winding streets are of irregular and variable shape and have surface area ranging from 100m² to 400m². The buildings have heights that vary from 6m (ground floor plus one floor) to 9m (ground floor plus two floors). The terracotta brick is the most used material given its availability and its affordable price (Figure 6).

Fig. 6. Building materials and heights.

Fig. 7. The road network.

The road network is a mix between the grid system and the tree system. Some alleys are primary with a width up to 12m and others are dead ends with a width not exceeding 2.5m. The various commercial activities are carried out mainly along the principal axis of the NR 40 (Figure 7).

V. CONCLUSION

Through the study of the district and the analysis of its land use plan, we can conclude that private properties, which are estimated to be more than 95% of the total land area, have played an important role in determining the shape of the urban tissue. A tissue characterized by irregular and varied plots in terms of shapes, geometries, and areas. This inconsistency and disorganization are the result of the system of division adopted by the owners of land which was initially agricultural and was later transformed into building land. Their principle was to sell most of the land and to leave only small alleys to ensure accessibility. This act of division of building land produced constructions lined up along the national road with significant commercial activity, while extensions were made behind this main axis. These extensions were characterized by the appearance of adjacent illegal constructions. The buildings form continuous blocks separated only by windings, dead ends, and narrow alleys, and an urban tissue that does not meet the modern daily needs. The logic of profitability and easy gain adopted by the private land owners also had a negative impact on the spaces reserved for public facilities.

From the above, it becomes clear that private land properties sold to poor housing seekers had a considerable effect on the emergence of particular architectural and urban forms. Consequently, a number of solutions must be proposed to possibly help limit the spread of illegal constructions in the outskirts of the city of M'sila. Among the solutions we can mention:

- The awareness aspect: An awareness campaign through the media while involving the various social institutions (associations, mosques, schools, etc.). During this campaign, we must educate citizens to proceed with the

regularization of their illegal construction according to the current regulations.

- The management aspect: It is a question of speeding up the diagnostic studies and the census of all illegal constructions. Then, the implementation of land use plans with continued control of urban space development follows. It is also necessary to work on the stability between housing supply and demand.
- The legal aspect: It is necessary to know the nature of the properties of the urban area by carrying out a global cadastral survey. It is also necessary to reform the legislative texts in order to adapt them to the current reality of the city. It is necessary to opt for the reduction of the documents requested in the constitution of building permit files and construction conformity certificates.
- The economic aspect: The development of an efficient and well-controlled system for subsidies intended for low-income families. Grants can be financial loans, without interest, repayable one the long term.

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Prestressing Effects on Full Scale Deep Beams with Large Web Openings

An Experimental and Numerical Study

Rafaa M. Abbas

Department of Civil Engineering
College of Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
dr.rafaa@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Lara T. Hussein

Department of Civil Engineering
College of Engineering
University of Baghdad
Baghdad, Iraq
l.hussein1001@coeng.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Abstract—Most studies on deep beams have been made with reinforced concrete deep beams, only a few studies investigate the response of prestressed deep beams, while, to the best of our knowledge, there is not a study that investigates the response of full scale (T-section) prestressed deep beams with large web openings. An experimental and numerical study was conducted in order to investigate the shear strength of ordinary reinforced and partially prestressed full scale (T-section) deep beams that contain large web openings in order to investigate the prestressing existence effects on the deep beam responses and to better understand the effects of prestressing locations and opening depth to beam depth ratio on the deep beam performance and behavior. A total of seven deep beam specimens with identical shear span-to-depth ratio, compressive strength of concrete, and amount of horizontal and vertical web reinforcement ratios have been tested under mid-span concentrated load applied monotonically until failure. The main variables studied were the effects of depth of the web openings and the prestressing location on deep beam performance. The test results showed that the enlargement in the size of web openings substantially reduces the element's shear capacities, while prestressing strands location above the web openings have more effect at increasing the element's shear capacities. The numerical study considered three-dimensional finite element models that has been developed in Abaqus software to simulate and predict the performance of prestressed deep beams. The results of numerical simulations were in good agreement with the experimental ones.

Keywords—deep beam; large web openings; pre-stressing; finite element; shear strength; static loading

I. INTRODUCTION

Shear behavior of reinforced concrete members (slender members that have span-to-depth ratios greater than 2.5) is a complex phenomenon influenced by a large number of parameters [1, 2]. This complexity is more pronounced in deep beams (members that have small span-to-depth ratios, less than 2.5) because the applied load is transferred mainly through the formation of arching which causes a highly nonlinear strain distribution in the cross section so that the shear strain is dominant [3]. In deep beams, the strain distribution is nonlinear and the load is transferred to the support by a compression strut

joining the loading point and the support [1, 4-7]. The creation of web openings is often required for the accommodation of electrical and mechanical conduits. Enlargement of openings due to architectural/mechanical requirements reduces the element's shear capacity [8]. Openings' configuration was investigated in [9] and an increase in ultimate load capacity when circular openings were used was reported. Many studies investigated the pre-stressing effects [10]. Pre-stressing a deep beam can increase significantly its load carrying capacity [11].

Finite Element Modeling (FEM) is a powerful tool in simulating structural elements in a variety of fields. In FEM, the successful simulation of specific elements relies upon the realistic representation of the material properties. However, due to the complexity of the constitutive material properties, modeling the behavior of reinforced concrete, shear in particular, has been, and still is, a challenging issue [12]. In the current study, 7 deep beams were tested and a comparison was made with the results of the numerical analysis (FEM) that was implemented with the aid of Abaqus/CAE program in order to investigate the effect of openings and pre-stressing locations. The comparison included load-deflection relation, load-strain relation at specific locations, crack pattern, and failure stage load. From the experimental results a significant decrease in load carrying capacity can be noticed when large web openings are introduced, and that agrees with the statement that the further the opening is located from what can be called the loaded quadrant and the nearer to the unloaded quadrant, the strength of the beam increases [13] and the deep beam acts as an ordinary beam. Also, pre-stressing location above the openings has more effect above the soffit in increasing load carrying capacity of the deep beam. The experimental results showed a good agreement with the numerical ones and can predict the pre-stressed deep beam strength accurately.

II. FEM DESCRIPTION

A. Geometry and Element Types

In order to investigate the pre-stress effects on the response and performances of full scale T-section deep beams with large web openings under monotonic loading, three-dimensional (3D) FE models of simple supports that have been partially pre-

Corresponding author: Lara T. Hussein

stressed and reinforced were constructed as a reference. The geometry, dimensions, and configuration of the FE beams were identical to the actual tested specimens. Four partially pre-stressed concrete deep beams with web openings, two reinforced deep beams with web openings, and one-solid beam were designed according to the strut-and-tie approach [14]. The full scale (T-section) deep beam specimens had the same geometry with dimensions of 1950mm length, 1000mm height, 750mm flange width, 125mm flange thickness, and 250mm web thickness, having 900mm span, 25Mpa concrete compressive strength, and the same main reinforcement with the shear reinforcement. The specimens were tested and analyzed under monotonic loading at mid-span. The main variable was the size of web openings, and pre-stressing location (above the openings or above the soffit). The adopted pre-stress level was selected so that it satisfied the limit of $0.62 f_{pu}$ [15]. The objective of this study is to investigate experimentally and numerically the:

- Location of pre-stressed strand across the height of the section: Case (1) – pre-stressed strand above the soffit of the beam at $0.07H$, where H is the height of the section Case (2) – pre-stressing strand above the top surface of openings at $0.07H$.

- Height of opening D , adopting ratios of the height of the opening to the height of section D/H equal to 0.48 and 0.6.

The constants were:

- Concrete's compressive strength.
- Span length to height of the section ratio (L/H).
- Two openings symmetrically located relative to the center-line of the beam.
- The width of the opening D .
- The center of each opening was located at $0.45H$ from the soffit of the beam.

The practical program of this study was to investigate four deep beams with large web openings that were partially pre-stressed at various locations ($0.07H$ mm) above the openings and above the soffit. The beams were designated with the DP-DE-OP symbols for partially pre-stressed deep beams with large web openings (480mm×480mm, 600mm×480mm) and different pre-stressing locations (OP- for above opening and SP- for above soffit). For more details of specimens and reinforcements properties, see Table I.

TABLE I. PROPERTIES OF THE REINFORCEMENTS OF THE POST TENSIONED DEEP BEAMS

Beam	Main reinf. A_s (mm ²)	Compression reinf. A_s (mm ²)	Pre-stressed A_p (mm ²)	Skin reinf. A_{sw} (mm ²)	ρ_w (%)	f_y (MPa)	Pre-stressing force F_{pe} (KN)
DP-48×48	3016	4010	---	50	0.2	430	286
DP-48×48-OP	3016	4010	2012.7	50	0.2	430	286
DP-48×48-SP	3016	4010	2012.7	50	0.2	430	286
DP-60×48	3016	4010	---	50	0.2	430	286
DP-60×48-OP	3016	4010	2012.7	50	0.2	430	286
DP-60×48-SP	3016	4010	2012.7	50	0.2	430	286
DP-Solid	3016	4010	2012.7	50	0.2	430	---

B. Numerical Modeling

The numerical investigations were carried out using the commercial FE tool Abaqus/Explicit finite element code. The concrete and the pre-stressed bars were modeled as three dimensional deformable bodies and the reinforcement as three dimensional truss. The interaction between concrete and steel was modeled using the constraint option available in Abaqus/CAE wherein the concrete was taken as the host region and the steel as the embedded region (Figure 1(a)). The element types that were used in the FE model for concrete were 8-noded linear bricks and 2-noded linear three dimensional trusses. The beam boundaries of the two ends were restrained with respect to all the degrees of freedom. The stresses for posttensioned strands were added in predefined fields as shown in Figure 1(b) and the loading applied was linearly varied to maximum, until failure occurred. Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP) modeling was used and the Johnson-Cook elastoviscoplastic material model available in Abaqus finite element code was employed for modeling the steel reinforcing bar material. The mesh sensitivity in concrete and steel was studied and the size of the elements was chosen based on the mesh convergence studied for concrete and reinforcements. The meshing of the elements of deep beams and reinforcement is shown in Figure 1(c)-(d).

Fig. 1. (a) Embedded regions, (b) applying prestress, (c) meshing of the model DP-48×48-OP, (d) meshing of the model DP-48×48-SP.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- The first crack appeared at the support regions toward the lower opening corner for the 48×48 and 60×48 specimens at 31% and 28% of the ultimate load respectively. The load-carrying capacity decreased as a result of the increasing opening depth [11].
- For the prestressed specimens 48×48-OP and 60×48-OP, the first crack was initiated at around 25%-26% of the ultimate load. The prestressing strands above the opening applied more compression stress and hence initial cracks above the openings appeared before the initiation of the first crack of the ordinary reinforced deep beams.
- At 48×48-SP and 60×48-SP specimens, the initial crack propagated at the upper corner of the openings toward the applied load region at 33%-34% of the ultimate load, as a result of the prestressing strand location at the tension zone [16].
- Flexure cracks appeared in all specimens, except specimens with prestressing above the soffit. There were no early flexure cracks as a result of tie action. They appeared at 34-44% whereas the flange shear cracks appeared at 33-52% of the ultimate load.
- As a result of large web openings, a typical crack pattern (column-beam) conjunction occurred. Horizontal cracks appeared at 32-47% of the ultimate load (Figure 2(a)-(b), crack number 3).
- The existence of web openings (480mm×480mm) can reduce the load carrying capacity by about 156KN (Figure 3).

Fig. 2. Specimen DP-48×48-SP: (a) Experimental and (b) simulated crack patterns.

Fig. 3. Comparison of reinforced and pre-stressed deep beams with the solid deep beam.

- The stresses paths and strut-and-tie configurations are shown clearly in Figure 2(a)-(b) [17].
- The comparison of the ultimate load according to the prestress location shows that the prestressing strands above the web openings increase the load carrying capacity by about 14% in the case of 480mm depth and by 22% in the case of 600mm depth (Figure 3). When the pre-stressing strands are above the soffit the load carrying capacity increases by about 2.38% and 17% for 480mm depth and 600mm depth respectively (Figure 3).
- Introducing web openings reduces the solid deep beam strength by about 136-209KN for 48×48 and 60×48 respectively (Figure 3). Increasing the web opening depth, from 480mm to 600mm, decreases the load carrying capacity by about 31% for reinforced deep beams and 15% for pre-stressed deep beams (Figure 3), as a result of intersecting the load path [8].
- Introducing large web openings in the deep beam transforms it into an ordinary beam-column (Figure 2(a)-(b), crack number 3) [17].

Fig. 4. Comparison of load versus deflection between experiments and simulations.

- The load-deflection curve behaves semi-linearly, which shows that the deep beams act as ordinary beams more than as deep beams, as a result of the large web openings at the shear zone which change their geometry (Figure 3) [17].
- The comparison of the load-deflection relation results of the tested specimens with the FEM results is shown in Figure 4. It is noted that the numerical load deflection responses are stiffer than the experimental ones and there is a good agreement in both trend and amplitude which varies from 5 to 10%.
- The deflection reaches 8mm-10mm and stresses at the failure stage (Figure 5).

Fig. 5. Specimen DP-48×48-OP: (a) Deflection counter, (b) stresses at the failure stage.

IV. CALIBRATION WITH THE PRESTRESSED SOLID MODEL

Based on the FEM results, a calibration of solid deep beams with a pre-stressed solid deep (pre-stress location at $d_p=930\text{mm}$) beam in finite element analysis using Abaqus was done. The obtained crack patterns of the pre-stressed solid deep beam are presented in Figure 6. The comparison with the simulated model shows that the existence of pre-stressing in the case of the solid deep beam increased the ultimate strength by about 37% than ordinary reinforced solid deep [16] (Figure 7).

Fig. 6. Showing the crack patterns of the solid deep beam.

The load-deflection curve for prestressed and ordinary reinforced solid deep beams is linear. As a result of the under-reinforcement, the steel reaches its yield strain before the concrete reaches the failure strain which is 0.0035. Figure 7 shows the significant crack patterns in tension. The

compression zone does not show any kind of failure which can lead to a ductile failure. The influence of the longitudinal reinforcement on ductility is defined by the relative neutral axis position along the cross section of the element. For lower values of neutral axis position, the beams have higher cross section heights and, consequently, lower longitudinal reinforcement rates, which grant more ductility to these beams at the ultimate limit state. When the concrete resistance increases, the amount of longitudinal reinforcement required to maintain the same ductility also increases. Therefore, a direct dependence between the ductility factor and the longitudinal reinforcement rate was observed [18].

Fig. 7. Load-deflection relations of simulated and experimentally examined pre-stressed solid deep beams.

V. COMPARISON OF NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The numerical models which simulate the actual tested specimens were able to predict the accurate shear capacity of each specimen with error varying around 10% (Table II). The highest shear capacity was observed with the solid deep beam (Figure 8).

Fig. 8. Experimental and numerical shear capacity results.

As the opening depth increased, the shear capacity will decrease simultaneously. The DP-60×48 deep beam has the lesser shear capacity. The enlargement of the opening size reduces the shear capacity [11]. Introducing prestressing strands can increase the load-carrying capacity by about 35% [16]. It is observed that a prestressed solid deep beam has greater load carrying capacity than ordinary reinforced solid

deep beams by around 37%. When the prestressing location is above the web opening, it provides greater shear capacity than when it is above the soffit. Adding prestressing strands above the openings increased the compression struts and hence increased the shear capacity [14]. Introducing web openings intersects the stresses paths and changes the geometry of the deep beam affecting its behavior and shear capacity [17]. The existence of web openings (480mm×480mm and 600mm×480mm) can reduce the load carrying capacity (by about 135 and 209KN respectively). More details about each specimen's simulated and experimentally tested shear capacity can be seen in Figure 8 and Table II.

TABLE II. EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL RESULTS

Specimens	Shear strength (kN)		
	Experimental	Numerical	Num/Exp ratio
DP-48×48	210	228	1.08
DP-48×48-OP	280	308	1.1
DP-48×48-SP	220	232	1.05
DP-60×48	160	176	1.32
DP-60×48-OP	260	267	1.02
DP-60×48-SP	200	227	1.13
DP-Solid	495	546	1.1
DP-Solid-SP	---	550	---

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, seven beam specimens with large web openings and different pre-stressing locations were examined. The numerical model predictions were compared with the experimental results and the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Introducing pre-stress at a location above the opening can increase the load carrying capacity by 14% and 22%, whereas when the pre-stressing location is above the soffit, the load carrying capacity is increased by 2.3% and 17% for DP-48×48 and DP-60×48 respectively.
- Pre-stressing on beams with larger opening depth increases more the ultimate load capacity.
- Introducing web openings can reduce significantly the load carrying capacity by at least 136KN (480mm×480mm web openings), in comparison with the solid beam.
- The solid deep beam has bigger strength than the pre-stressed deep beam with openings.
- The numerical results comparison showed that, in the case of pre-stressed solid deep beam, as the location of the pre-stressing d_p decreases, its effects on increasing the beam strength decrease. In the case of pre-stressed deep beams with openings, the load carrying capacity of deep beam increased when the pre-stressing location d_p decreased.
- From the FEM result analysis, it can be seen that the models are stiffer than the experimental specimens.

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Assessment of Groundwater Quality Using Water Quality Indices: A Case Study of Paliganj Distributary, Bihar, India

K. Praveen

Civil Engineering Department
National Institute of Technology Patna
Patna, India
praveen.ce17@nitp.ac.in

L. B. Roy

Civil Engineering Department
National Institute of Technology Patna
Patna, India
lbroy@nitp.ac.in

Abstract—Groundwater quality evaluation in the command area of Paliganj distributary of the Sone irrigation scheme in India was carried out during two different seasons in the year 2020, namely pre-monsoon, i.e. during March, and post-monsoon, i.e. during October. Forty groundwater samples were obtained from hand pumps and dug wells in the study area during the pre- and post-monsoon seasons. The chemical characteristics of groundwater samples were determined according to American Public Health Association approved process. Twelve parameters, namely, pH, EC, TDS, Ca, Mg, Na, F, SO₄, K, Cl, and HCO₃ were used to compute the water quality based on the weighted arithmetic water quality index method. In the study area, Ca²⁺-Mg⁺-HCO₃⁻, and Ca²⁺-Mg⁺-Na⁺-HCO₃⁻ were the dominant hydro-chemical facies. All the samples were found to belong to excellent to good category for drinking purposes during pre-monsoon period. However, during the post-monsoon season, only 75% of the samples fell into the excellent to good group, while the remaining 25% fell into the poor for drinking purposes category. By analyzing through the irrigation quality index, 80% of the samples are considered highly suitable for irrigation and the remaining 20% come under the medium category. Thus, it was seen that the majority of groundwater samples are suitable for drinking and irrigation purposes, although groundwater in some portions of the area had high salinity and the Sodium Adsorption Ratio (SAR), showing that it is unsuitable for irrigation and requires adequate drainage.

Keywords—chemical parameters; water quality index; weighted arithmetic index; irrigation water quality index

I. INTRODUCTION

The pressure on all natural resources to provide enough food and raw materials to meet the demand has increased as a result of the large increase in human population [1]. Drinking and irrigation water supplies will be further stressed. Increased demand may result in substantial changes in the hydrologic cycle, such as a decrease in the groundwater level or a reduction in groundwater quality [2, 3]. Water in sufficient quantity and of acceptable quality is a fundamental need, yet preserving that quality is difficult. The chemical, physical, and biological characteristics of water are referred to as water quality. If the values of these parameters exceed the stated

limitations, they are harmful to human health [4]. Water Quality Index (WQI) is a statistic for expressing the level of water quality in a single numerical statement. It summarizes numerous water quality criteria to determine the acceptability of a water source for drinking purposes. WQI is one of the most effective techniques to quantify water quality. It is commonly used to assess the acceptability of water sources for human consumption. Individual water quality factors have been shown to be difficult to understand when they are used to explain water quality for the general public [5-10].

The weighted arithmetic WQI was first proposed in [11] and further modified in [12]. In general, WQI is a technique for determining water quality conditions, and they, like any other tool, necessitate the understanding of water principles and basic ideas. WQI is a single, dimensionless number that is calculated by combining the major parameters that influence water quality. In general, WQI can avoid the challenges of drawing conclusions from vast amounts of water quality study data. The Irrigation Water Quality (IWQ) concept was implemented by using a model established in [13] to assess the appropriateness of groundwater for irrigation purpose. Authors in [14] investigated uranium and other water quality parameters in drinking water sources in 5 districts of Kerala, southern India, using the WQI method. Groundwater in some cities on the right bank of the river Ganges and in the vicinity of the study area, suffers from TDS, nitrate concentration and fluoride contamination. The result and analysis of the present study shows the current status of groundwater in the study area.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A total of 40 groundwater samples were collected from the Paliganj block during March, 2020 (pre-monsoon) and again at the same locations during October 2020 (post-monsoon) to analyze seasonal variation. New, clean 1000ml polyethylene bottles were used to collect the groundwater samples. At the time of collection, the bottles were thoroughly rinsed 3 times with the same collection of samples. All groundwater samples were taken from hand pumps and dug wells. The groundwater samples were collected from the hand pumps after 5min of pumping. This method removes the stored groundwater in the

Corresponding author: K Praveen

well. At the time of sample collection, pH, EC, and TDS readings were measured by a mobile field kit. These factors fluctuate with storage time [15]. The laboratory tests were conducted in the Central Groundwater Board (CGWB), Patna. By using a flame photometer, major cations like sodium and potassium were determined. Thermo-Orion bench top ion electrode was used to determine fluoride and chloride. The total hardness and total alkalinity were determined by titration. The methods and techniques used to analyze all water quality parameters are shown in Table I. The standard procedure given by APHA [16] was used.

TABLE I. METHODS AND TECHNIQUES USED

Chemical parameter	Method
pH	Mobile pH meter
Electrical Conductivity (EC)	Mobile EC meter
Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)	Mobile TDS meter
Chloride (Cl ⁻)	Ion chromatography
Sulphate (SO ₄)	Spectro photometer
Nitrate (NO ₃ ⁻)	Ion chromatography
Calcium (Ca ²⁺)	Titration method by using EDTA solution
Magnesium (Mg ²⁺)	Titration method by using EDTA solution
Sodium (Na ⁺)	Flame photometer 128
Potassium (K ⁺)	Flame photometer 128
Fluoride (F ⁻)	Ion chromatography
Bicarbonate (HCO ₃ ⁻)	Titration method by using H ₂ SO ₄ solution

A. The Study Area

The Sone command area aggregate catchment zone of the waterway is 71,259km², of which 17,651km² lie in Bihar. The remaining 53,608km² lie in Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, and Jharkhand states of India. The Paliganj Distributary is a part of the Sone Canal System in South Bihar. The Sone River flows north-eastward from the Deccan Plateau before joining the Ganges not far from the city of Patna. The Sone Canal System diverts water from the river to irrigate a design command area of over 700,000ha.

Fig. 1. Index Map of Paliganj Distributary, Sone canal system. (Source: Bihar State Second Irrigation Commission).

B. Water Quality Index Methodology

The Weighted Arithmetic WQI was used, considering 12 different chemical parameters. The World Health Organization (WHO) and the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) established standard values for several water quality indicators as shown in Table II.

TABLE II. CHEMICAL PARAMETERS CONSIDERED FOR WQI, THEIR STANDARD VALUES, AND RECOMMENDING ORGANIZATIONS

Chemical parameters (EC-µS/cm, all other parameters in mg/l)	Standard value	Recommending organization
pH	6.5-8.5	WHO
EC	400	WHO
TDS	500	WHO
F ⁻	1	BIS
HCO ₃ ⁻	244	BIS
Ca ²⁺	75	BIS
Mg ²⁺	30	BIS
Total Hardness (TH)	300	BIS
NO ₃ ⁻	45	BIS
SO ₄	400	BIS
Cl ⁻	200	BIS
Total Alkalinity (TA)	200	BIS

The weighted arithmetic index approach [12] was used to calculate the WQI:

$$WQI = \left[\frac{\sum Q_n \times W_n}{\sum W_n} \right] \quad (1)$$

where W_n is the unit weight of the n th water quality parameter and Q_n is its quality rating. Based on the WQI value, the status of water quality is divided into 5 categories, i.e. WQI value between 0 and 25 is Excellent, a value between 26 and 50 comes under Good, a value between 51 to 75 comes under Poor, a value between 76 and 100 comes under Very Poor, and a value above 100 is unsuitable for drinking purposes.

The equation used to compute the quality rating Q_n is:

$$Q_n = \left(\frac{V_n - V_i}{V_s - V_i} \right) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where V_n is the observed parameter's actual value and V_i denotes the parameter's ideal value. Except for pH ($V_i = 7$), V_s is the maximum permitted value for the n th water quality parameter.

The formula for calculating W_n is:

$$W_n = \frac{k}{V_s} \quad (3)$$

where k is the proportionality constant, which is derived by:

$$k = \left(\frac{1}{\sum_{s=123...n} \frac{1}{V_s}} \right) \quad (4)$$

C. Irrigation Water Quality Index Methodology

IWQ [17, 19] is based on a linear combination of 5 sets of irrigation water quality indicators that have the ability to affect soil quality and crop output significantly. Throughout this method, the 5 groups were analyzed at the same time and then merged to provide a single index value, which is subsequently reviewed to find the suitability of irrigation water. Authors in [18] proposed the guidelines for the selection of water quality parameters given in Tables III and IV. These water quality parameters not only reflect best the related risk, but they also interact with others to form the resource's basic water quality pattern. Moreover, these parameters are set up in such a way that a non-technical policy maker could understand the tool's results and use the procedure without difficulty.

TABLE III. IWQ INDEX PARAMETER CLASSIFICATION [19]

Hazard	Unit weight	Chemical parameter range	Rating	Suitability
Salinity	5	EC > 3,000	1	Low
		700 ≤ EC ≤ 3,000	2	Medium
		EC < 700	3	High
Infiltration and permeability	4	Details are given in Table IV		
Specific ion toxicity	3	SAR > 9	1	Low
		3.0 ≤ SAR ≤ 9.0	2	Medium
		SAR < 3	3	High
		B < 0.7	3	High
		0.7 ≤ B ≤ 3.0	2	Medium
		B > 3.0	1	Low
		CI < 140	3	High
		140 ≤ CI ≤ 350	2	Medium
CI > 350	1	Low		
Trace element toxicity	2	Details are given in Table V		
Effects on sensitive crops	1	NO ₃ < 5.0	3	High
		5.0 ≤ NO ₃ ≤ 30.0	2	Medium
		NO ₃ > 30.0	1	Low
		HCO ₃ < 90	3	High
		90 ≤ HCO ₃ ≤ 500	2	Medium
		HCO ₃ > 500	1	Low
		pH < 6.5 or pH > 8.5	1	Low
		6.5 ≤ pH < 7.0 and 8.0 < pH ≤ 8.5	2	Medium
7 ≤ pH ≤ 8	3	High		

$$IWQ\ index = \sum_{i=1}^5 G_i \quad (5)$$

where G represents the contribution of each of the five risk factors that are important in determining the irrigation system's quality and i represents the incremental index. The salinity is the first considered parameter:

$$G_1 = w_1 \times r_1 \quad (6)$$

where w is the hazard group's weight value and r represent the parameter's rating value, as shown in Table III.

The permeability hazard and infiltration, which is represented by the EC – SAR combination and is formulated as:

$$G_2 = w_2 \times r_2 \quad (7)$$

where w is the weight value, and r represents the parameter's rating value as shown in Table IV. The third category is specific ion toxicity, which is defined as a weighted average of the three ions in water (SAR, chloride, and boron ions):

$$G_3 = \frac{w_3}{3} \sum_{j=1}^3 r_j \quad (8)$$

where j represents an incremental index, w is the group's weight value as shown in Table IV, and r represents each parameter's rating value as shown in Table IV.

The trace element toxicity category is calculated as the weighted average of all the ions available for analysis:

$$G_4 = \frac{w_4}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N r_k \quad (9)$$

where w is the group's weight and N is the total number of trace elements that can be analyzed. As shown in Table V, k is the incremental index, and r represents the rating value of each parameter.

The 5th and final category is the weighted average of several influences on sensitive crops, which are represented by NO₃⁻ and HCO₃⁻ ions, and the pH of water.

$$G_5 = \frac{w_5}{3} \sum_{l=1}^3 r_l \quad (10)$$

where l represents the incremental index, w represents the group's weight value, and r is each parameter's rating value, as shown in Table III.

TABLE IV. INFILTRATION AND PERMEABILITY HAZARD CLASSIFICATION [19]

	SAR					Rating	Suitability
	<3	3–6	6–12	12–20	> 20		
EC	<200	<300	<500	<1300	<2900	3	Low
	700–200	1200–300	1900–500	2900–1300	5000–2900	2	Medium
	>700	>1200	>1900	>2900	>5000	1	High

TABLE V. TOXICITY CLASSIFICATION

Factor	Range	Rating	Suitability
Fluoride (mg/l)	F > 15	1	Low
	1.0 ≤ F ≤ 15.0	2	Medium
	F < 1	3	High

TABLE VI. IWQ INDEX CLASSIFICATION

IWQ Index	Water suitability for irrigation
< 22	Low
22–37	Medium
> 37	High

For the computation of the index's total value, suitability analysis has been performed using the 3 categories listed in Table VI. The values in the Table were derived by providing different rating factors (i.e. 1, 2, and 3) to each parameter while keeping the weighted coefficient constant, resulting in 3 different index values. The upper and lower limits for each category in Table VI are determined by the medians of these values.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The current study involves the estimation of WQI for water samples obtained from 20 sampling locations during pre- and post-monsoon season. A total of 40 groundwater samples of WQI were considered and the weighted arithmetic index method was used. The results are shown in Figure 2. The methods that were employed in the analysis of various water chemical parameters are given in Table I. Table VII shows the calculated SAR values of the study area. It should be noted that the SAR value of four locations is more than 10, which indicates salinity hazard, requiring adequate drainage. The different water quality parameters were compared to the international standards recommended by WHO [15, 20] and BIS-2012 [21] (Table VIII).

After analyzing the water quality index during the pre-monsoon season, 35% of the samples came under the Excellent

category and the remaining 65% under the Good category for drinking purposes. During the post-monsoon season, 15% of the samples come under the Excellent category, 60% under the Good category, and the remaining 25% are Poor to Very Poor.

TABLE VII. CALCULATED SAR VALUES OF THE STUDY AREA

Location	Pre-monsoon SAR	Post-monsoon SAR
Paipura	5.4	2.5
Fathepur	5	2.6
Kurkuri	3.1	2.6
Sarsi	2.7	3.1
Shiyarampur	2.8	5.6
Bara	3	2.4
Satpura	3.2	2.6
Pipardah	2.7	8.8
Lalganj	10.5	4.4
Gulitar	11	7.8
Makmilpur	10.2	4.1
Baratpura	3.4	11.2
Achhua	17.4	12.3
Dulhin Bazar	2.8	11.1
Ular Pond	8.4	6.1
BhimniChak	3.2	6.4
Harpura	3.2	4.3
Nabi Nagar	4.6	2.7
Aktiyarpur	2	6.6
Khapura	3.5	5

TABLE VIII. INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS USED TO COMPARE VARIOUS WATER QUALITY PARAMETERS

Parameter	WHO/BIS -limit	Pre-monsoon		Post-monsoon	
		No. of samples	% of samples exceeded	No. of samples	% of samples exceeded
pH	6.5-8.5	20	0	20	0
EC	400	20	65	20	60
TDS	500	20	20	20	15
F ⁻	1	20	0	20	0
Cl ⁻	250	20	0	20	0
HCO ₃ ⁻	244	20	50	20	45
SO ₄ ⁻²	400	20	0	20	0
NO ₃ ⁻	45	20	10	20	0
Ca ⁺²	75	20	5	20	5
Mg ⁺²	30	20	20	20	10
TA	200	20	70	20	55
TH	200	20	35	20	25

IWQ index [13] was used for groundwater assessment for irrigation purposes in the command area of Paliganj Distributary of the Sone Irrigation scheme in India. By analyzing the groundwater samples showed in Table IX with the IWQ index, 80% of the samples came under the Highly suitable for irrigation purposes category and the remaining 20% under the Medium suitable category. Therefore, overall, all groundwater samples in the study area are considered suitable for irrigation purposes, but some areas have high sodium percentage and SAR value, indicating irrigation unsuitability. Therefore, adequate drainage is required to overcome this problem.

TABLE IX. IWQ INDEX WITH IRRIGATION WATER STATUS IN THE STUDY AREA

Location	G-1	G-2	G-3	G-4	G-5	IWQ	Status of water for irrigation
Paipura	15	4	18	6	1.98	44.98	High
Fathepur	15	4	12	6	2.31	39.31	High
Kurkuri	15	8	18	6	2.31	49.31	High
Sarsi	15	4	18	6	2.31	45.31	High
Shiyarampur	15	8	18	6	2.31	49.31	High
Bara	15	8	18	6	1.98	48.98	High
Satpura	15	8	18	6	1.98	48.98	High
Pipardah	15	8	27	6	2.64	58.64	High
Lalganj	10	8	9	6	2.31	35.31	Medium
Gulitar	10	8	9	6	1.65	34.65	Medium
Makmilpur	10	8	9	6	1.65	34.65	Medium
Baratpura	15	8	12	6	2.31	43.31	High
Achhua	15	4	6	6	2.64	33.64	Medium
Dulhin Bazar	10	12	27	6	1.98	56.98	High
Ular Pond	15	8	12	6	2.31	43.31	High
BhimniChak	15	8	12	6	2.31	43.31	High
Harpura	15	8	12	6	2.31	43.31	High
Nabi Nagar	15	8	12	6	2.31	43.31	High
Aktiyarpur	15	8	18	6	2.31	49.31	High
Khapura	15	4	18	6	2.64	45.64	High

IV. RESULT COMPARISON

Authors in [22] analyzed groundwater samples from 14 different stations of Patna city based on WQI and the results placed the water in the Good category. However, none of their samples was found suitable for drinking purposes as they were all found to have high concentration of total and fecal coliform. Also, they found that TDS and nitrate concentration at some locations were above the standards' limits for drinking water. Authors in [23] studied groundwater quality for samples collected from different locations of Sabour block in Bhagalpur district, Bihar using WQI. They found that around 7% of the samples had WQI score greater than 100, the limit for drinking water. Based on this, they suggested water safety and remediation measures.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The WQI is a single value calculated from a set of water quality parameters that can be used to determine the quality and drinkability of a water sample. WQI estimation can help us save time and effort while dealing with groundwater data. It can also facilitate to communicate the data-driven decision with only one value. By analyzing WQI through the weighted arithmetic index method, during the pre-monsoon season, all

Fig. 2. Pre- and post- monsoon WQIs.

samples were either excellent or good for drinking purposes. However, during the post-monsoon season, only 75% of the samples fell into the excellent to good range, while the remaining 25% fell were poor to extremely poor. By analyzing the samples through the IWQ index, 80% of them fell in the highly recommended for irrigation category and 20% were medium suitable for irrigation purposes. Therefore, the overall groundwater quality is considered satisfying with respect to the standard values given by WHO and BIS, but in some parts of the study area the groundwater has high salinity and SAR, indicating that it is unsuitable for irrigation and requires adequate drainage. A collaborative multi-agency approach is recommended in order to ensure that agencies responsible for the study area are involved in the management of water quality. The outcome of this study may be used for the effective monitoring of water quality for drinking and irrigation purposes in the study area and elsewhere in the state and the country.

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Improving the Curvelet Saliency and Deep Convolutional Neural Networks for Diabetic Retinopathy Classification in Fundus Images

Vo Thi Hong Tuyet

Department of Information Systems
Faculty of Computer Science and Engineering
Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology (HCMUT)
Vietnam National University-Ho Chi Minh City
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
vhtuyet.sdh19@hcmut.edu.vn

Nguyen Thanh Binh

Department of Information Systems
Faculty of Computer Science and Engineering
Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology (HCMUT)
Vietnam National University-Ho Chi Minh City
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
ntbinh@hcmut.edu.vn

Dang Thanh Tin

Information Systems Engineering Laboratory
Faculty of Electrical and Electronics Engineering
Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology (HCMUT)
Vietnam National University-Ho Chi Minh City
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
dttin@hcmut.edu.vn

Abstract-Retinal vessel images give a wide range of the abnormal pixels of patients. Therefore, classifying the diseases depending on fundus images is a popular approach. This paper proposes a new method to classify diabetic retinopathy in retinal blood vessel images based on curvelet saliency for segmentation. Our approach includes three periods: pre-processing of the quality of input images, calculating the saliency map based on curvelet coefficients, and classifying VGG16. To evaluate the results of the proposed method STARE and HRF datasets are used for testing with the Jaccard Index. The accuracy of the proposed method is about 98.42% and 97.96% with STARE and HRF datasets respectively.

Keywords-saliency; VGG16; classification; diabetic retinopathy; retinal blood vessel

I. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a condition that occurs when the pancreas does not produce enough insulin or when the body loses its ability to metabolize insulin. Manifestations of diabetic retinopathy include microaneurysms, intraretinal hemorrhage, hard exudates, macular edema, macular ischemia, neovascularization, vitreous hemorrhage, and traction retinal detachment. The fundus complication of diabetes is called diabetic retinopathy, which damages the small blood vessels in the retina. The retina is the light-sensitive area of the eyeball, where nerve cells receive images and send them to the brain for processing. The macula is most important for the most delicate images. Diabetic retinopathy is the leading cause of vision loss or blindness in developed countries. Therefore, the

identification of diabetic retinopathy through retinal images is very important. Recent advances in computer science, focused on machine learning to detect data patterns, can provide solutions for diabetic retinopathy disease detection through retinal imaging. The detection of bright lesions in the retinal blood vessels is hard work, but can help doctors in diagnosis and treatment. Retinopathy is widely researched [1-5] and many different methods such as image saliency analysis [6, 7], machine learning techniques [8-10], wavelet and support vector machine [11], segmentation [12, 13], morphology [27], etc., are used.

Authors in [10] proposed a method to identify diabetes from retinal images using the DiaNet model with a multi-stage Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). Authors in [14] proposed a method for the detection of fundus image lesions by using a CNN to search with the shuffled frog leaping algorithm. Authors in [15] used the discrete image clustering technique to separate the image foreground and background of the input image in order to classify the lesion results. Authors in [16] proposed a method to segment premature infant retinal images to achieve an extracted retinal image with a map of blood vessels. Authors in [17] suggested a contour detection method. They computed the image gradient value by applying Type- 2 fuzzy rules to detect edges. Authors in [18] used a CNN model to design a learning method for grading fundus images. However, the system was validated on a small dataset. Authors in [19] proposed a method for diabetic retinopathy detection based on U-Net and ResNet-18. In their experiments, they assessed two segmentation images. This method gives

Corresponding author: Nguyen Thanh Binh

results with accuracy, but its complexity is high. Authors in [20] proposed a method for retina image recognition. This method includes two phases: finding features for healthy retinal image recognition and using vascular and lesion-based features for diabetic retinopathy retinal image recognition. Their experimental results were 100%, 96.67% and 97.78% for the considered databases.

This paper proposes a method for diabetic retinopathy classification based on the improvement of the second general wavelet transform with the VGG-16 CNN. To evaluate the results of the proposed method and compare them with the results of other known methods, two (STARE and HRF) open datasets were used for testing and the evaluation criterion of Jaccard Index (JI) was utilized. The accuracy of the proposed method is about 98.42% and 97.96% for STARE and HRF datasets respectively.

The main contributions of this study are:

- The proposal of the deep VGG16 to classify diabetic retinopathy in fundus images.
- Increased accuracy of classification by curvelet saliency combined with VGG16.

II. CLASSIFYING DIABETIC RETINOPATHY WITH CURVELET SALIENCY AND VGG16

The quality of retinal blood vessel images is affected by a wide range of reasons such as: noise, motion which creates blur images, and overlapping. The diabetic classification based on feature extraction is a popular state-of-the-art approach. This section presents the proposed method for diabetic retinopathy classification with curvelet saliency and VGG16 which is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The proposed method for diabetes classification.

The proposed method can be divided into 3 stages which depend on the characteristics of each step: pre-processing, curvelet saliency, and classification. The input data are the retinal blood vessel images of the system. Green is the color

channel chosen to be processed. The CLAHE redistributes the lightness values of the objects. The top-hat transform for mask making creates the morphology for the next stages. The 3 above steps are the preprocessing of the proposed method. The aim of preprocessing is to enhance the quality of the blood vessels in fundus images. Secondly, the curvelet coefficients are calculated based on the curvelet transform with DB4 in the decomposition steps. This value is applied in each level of the top-hat transform to form the threshold for saliency levels. The output is the curvelet saliency map for the final periods. Finally, the VGG16 model classifies the images as diabetic or not.

A. Improving the Features of Retinal Blood Vessel Images

The aim of this step is to improve the features of fundus images. The thickness of blood vessels varies from 1 to 5 pixels. Enhancing quality starts from the similar color and the approximation of the surrounding pixels. The color of fundus images includes three color channels, i.e. Red-Green-Blue. Among them, Red is the saturated channel, Green is the lighting, and Blue is the contrast of vessels with the background. In our method, the Green color is chosen because of the necessary lighting in blood detection. Then, CLAHE is performed with the following steps:

- Not overlapping contextual areas and preserving 8×8 pixel blocks.
- Calculating the average number of pixels for preparing the division as in (1):

$$N_{avg} = (NrX \times NrY) / N_{gray} \quad (1)$$

where N_{avg} is the average number of pixels, N_{gray} represents the gray levels of the divided areas, NrX and NrY are the number of pixels for the X- and Y-dimension respectively.

- From the average number of pixels, their product with the clipped pixels can be created with the i -th gray level. These values are the histogram of the clipped pixels. Then, the conditions for histogram level setup are compared to the average to keep the better value.
- Applying the condition and probability density as in (2):

$$p(y(i)) = \frac{(y(i) - y_{min})}{\alpha^2} \times \exp\left(-\frac{(y(i) - y_{min})^2}{2\alpha^2}\right) \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha = 0.04$ is the scaling parameter of Rayleigh distribution, $y(i)$ is the Rayleigh forward transform, and y_{min} is the lower bound of the pixel value.

- Updating the artifacts with the average histogram and probability density.
- The final step in pre-processing is the top-hat transform. This transform creates the mask making and the subtraction process. The proposed method is divided into 2 levels (high and low) based on the number of distances between the gray levels of these pixels and the average histogram in the CLAHE step. The output of this step is the high-level and low-level curvelet coefficients.

B. Curvelet Coefficients for Choosing the Saliency Map

The input of this step is the high and low level of the previous step. In each level, this approach uses the stages as in Figure 2. The decomposition is done with DB4 for division and subband creation.

Fig. 2. The curvelet coefficients for choosing saliency.

The subband w_j with a block size b_j in each level of fundus images f is noted as Δ_i . An appropriate scale of sidelength $\sim 2^{-s}$ and w_Q is a collection of smooth windows localized around dyadic squares of fundus images as in (3):

$$Q = [k_1 / 2^s, (k_1 + 1) / 2^s] \times [k_2 / 2^s, (k_2 + 1) / 2^s] \quad (3)$$

Then, the curvelet coefficients are calculated as follows:

- Renormalizing in each unit scale.
- Analyzing via the discrete Ridgelet transform in each unit scale.
- Update the subbands of blocks based on the double value if their number is odd. However, if the block's number is even, the updates do not work.
- In reversion, the curvelet domain with coefficients K depends on the number of scales in the list of subbands. The saliency level $R(x)$ at pixel x is presented with level K .

The curvelet saliency for final saliency prediction will be done with the algorithm described below:

Input: $R(x)$ and K

Output: the saliency prediction

Function `cal_curveletSaliency(R(x), K)`

The superpixel centers S = the average pixel i in grid while iteration t from 1 to v do:

The association between pixel p and superpixel i is:

$$Q_{pi}^t = e^{-\|r_p - s_i^{t-1}\|^2}$$

superpixel centers = \sum association in K

end while

return distance(pixel x with superpixel centers)

End function

The final output of this period is the saliency map of the areas of blood vessels in fundus images. The curvelet coefficient K is the condition for the association of superpixel centers in a map.

C. VGG16 in the Curvelet Saliency Map for Diabetes Classification

The stage after the feature extraction of image segmentation from curvelet saliency is the classification by VGG16 with the architecture shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Applying VGG16 for feature extraction in the curvelet saliency map.

In this architecture, each level of the curvelet saliency will be submitted to the following procedures:

- Block 1: 2 convolution + 1 pooling
- Block 2: 2 convolution + 1 pooling
- Block 3: 3 convolution + 1 pooling
- Block 4: 3 convolution + 1 pooling
- Block 5: 3 convolution + 1 pooling
- Block 6: Dense with 3 fully connected + ReLU
- Softmax at the end.

At first, each input image is downsized with a 3×3 channel. The channel of the second block is 64×64 and the size is doubled for the below blocks. Therefore, the channels of block 3, 4 and 5 are 128×128 , 256×256 , and 512×512 . The padding is 2 pixels for 3×3 convolution layers. This size is the smallest size for the notion of left/right, up/down, and center. The stride of the convolution layer is also 2 pixels with the above padding. Then, the pooling layer (max pooling) has a window size of 2×2 pixels and the stride has also 2 pixels. In block 6, the first and second fully connected layers have $1 \times 1 \times 4096$ channels. However, the final fully connected layer is $1 \times 1 \times 1000$ channels. The softmax (ranging from 0 to 1) gives the final classification as diabetes or non-diabetes in each level of the curvelet saliency. The differences between VGG16 in this paper with the traditional VGG16 are the stride and the multi-model applied in each level of the curvelet saliency. The synthesis of the multi-model (multi-results of softmax) is the max value.

III. EXPERIMENTATION AND EVALUATION RESULTS

$$JI(A, B) = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} \quad (4)$$

A. Datasets Used

The proposed method is actualized in the STARE [21] and HRF (High-Resolution Fundus) [22] datasets. These datasets contain images of normal or diseased retinal blood vessels. These 2 datasets are public and free to be used in research and academic tasks. During the experiments 70% of the STARE dataset was used for training and 30% for testing. The HRF dataset was used for testing (100%). The STARE dataset [21] consists of 402 images (91 diabetes and 311 non-diabetes). Their size is 605×700 pixels with 24 bits per pixel (standard RGB). In this dataset, a wide range of diseases are diagnosed based on retinal blood vessels. In this paper, the focused disease is diabetic retinopathy. The HRF dataset [22] includes 45 images (15 diabetes images of glaucomatous patients and 30 non-diabetes).

The language used to develop the proposed method is Python 3.9 and the configuration of the system is: 2.7GHz Quad-Core Intel i7 processor and 16GB 2133MHz LPDDR3 RAM.

B. Evaluation Metric and Experimental Results

The main idea of the proposed method is based on the segmentation with curvelet saliency. Therefore, the evaluation applies to the JI value. If A is the image segmentation and B is the ground truth image, the $JI(A, B)$ is calculated by (4). The higher the JI value is, the better.

To define the curvelet coefficients that adapt with the salient map more than others, Table I shows the comparison of saliency segmentation by superpixels and other coefficients. It can be seen that the proposed curvelet coefficients give segmentation results near the ground truth of the retinal blood vessels in the HRF dataset. Table II exhibits the comparison results between the proposed method and matched filtering and fuzzy C-means clustering with integrated level set [23] and fully convolutional deep learning [24]. We can see that the average JI of the proposed method is better than the others. This experiment is practiced in HRF with 45 images for evaluation. The ground truth of each fundus image is given clearly in the dataset. Therefore, the JI values are easy to compare.

Figure 4 presents some segmentation results of curvelet saliency in the HRF dataset and compares the proposed method with [23] and [24].

TABLE I. AVERAGE JI FOR SALIENCY SEGMENTATION BASED ON OTHER COEFFICIENTS

Method	Average JI
Saliency based on superpixels	85.1
Saliency based on Gaussian filter	90.42
Saliency based on contourlet coefficients	91.37
Proposed method (saliency based on curvelet coefficients)	98.25

Fig. 4. Segmentation result comparison in the HRF dataset.

TABLE II. AVERAGE JI OF THE PROPOSED METHOD AND OF OTHER SEGMENTATION METHODS

Method	Average JI
[23]	92.03
[24]	96.13
Proposed	98.25

From Tables I-II and Figure 4, the curvelet saliency adapts with segmentation in diabetic diseases. The next evaluation is the input of curvelet saliency for other deep learning models for diabetes classification. Figure 5 shows the comparison chart of the results. In Figure 5, we can see that VGG16 performs better than the other methods known, in terms of classification accuracy for classifying diabetic retinopathy in curvelet coefficients. The comparison was carried out between the proposed method with CNN, Fully Convolutional Network (FCN), and U-Net with VGG16. In the two datasets, the accuracy of VGG16 is higher for classifying diabetic retinopathy. Table III shows the classification results of VGG16 in detecting diabetes and non-diabetes images using Deep CNN VGG-16 and GoogLeNet [25], ResNet50 and VGG-16 pretrained networks [26], and VGG16 in curvelet saliency.

Fig. 5. Classification results of diabetic retinopathy of deep learning models based on curvelet saliency.

TABLE III. DIABETIC RETINOPATHY CLASSIFICATION RESULTS RESULTS OF VGG16 COMPARISON

Dataset	Deep CNN VGG-16 and GoogLeNet for diabetic retinopathy detection [25]	Diabetic retinopathy classification using ResNet50 and VGG-16 pretrained networks [26]	VGG16 in curvelet saliency
STARE	94.36	96.01	98.42
HRF	94.1	95.74	97.96

The curvelet coefficients are the main reason for the better results because they enhance the quality and divide the saliency levels. The curves adapt with the curvelet transform. These values make a condition for choosing saliency maps. Therefore, the segmentation of fundus images is better. On the other hand, the multi-level curvelet coefficient for saliency

consists of continuing the input of VGG16 with changing the stride and synthesis of multi-model VGG16. As a result, the classifying results are improved. The authors in the other works applied deep learning for classification based on the number of layers or by improving the parameters of the dataset. However, the input parameters are not easy to enhance. If we only focus on information on the surface, it is not enough. The proposed method offers multi-level processing with curvelet coefficients for salient map. The levels of fundus image quality are shown clearly. The deep VGG16 in each saliency level calculates a value for disease classification.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Diabetes can reduce the red blood cell rate, increase the ability of platelets to agglomerate, and increase blood viscosity. As a result, the capillaries become clogged, causing retinal ischemia. Diagnosis in medicine is a vital task. Any disease prediction or classification system must adapt to the medical images. The retinal vessel images give a wide range of abnormal pixels. Therefore, classifying the diseases from fundus images is a popular research topic. This paper proposes a new method for classifying the diabetic retinopathy in retinal blood vessel images based on curvelet saliency for segmentation. Our approach includes 3 steps: pre-processing of the input images, calculating the saliency map based on curvelet coefficients, and utilizing VGG16 for classification. The choice of the Green color channel combined with enhancement and division level saliency by curve condition of the curvelet transform gave the best segmentation results. The stride and multi-model of the VGG16 was proposed for each saliency level to enhance the results. In future work, configuration and updating the number of layers or blocks in the deep learning models will be considered.

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Efficient Hybrid Algorithm Solution for Optimal Reactive Power Flow Using the Sensitive Bus Approach

Zahir Sahli

QUERE Laboratory
Electrical Engineering Department
University Ferhat Abbas Setif 1
Setif, Algeria
sah_zah@yahoo.fr

Samir Sayah

QUERE Laboratory
Electrical Engineering Department
University Ferhat Abbas Setif 1
Setif, Algeria
samir.sayah@univ-setif.dz

Abdellatif Hamouda

QUERE Laboratory
Optics and Fine Mechanics Institute
University Ferhat Abbas Setif 1
Setif, Algeria
a_hamouda1@yahoo.fr

Damien Trentesaux

LAMIH-UMR CNRS
University of Valenciennes
Valenciennes, France
damien.trentesaux@univ-valenciennes.fr

Abdelghani Bekrar

LAMIH-UMR CNRS
University of Valenciennes
Valenciennes, France
abdelghani.bekrar@univ-valenciennes.fr

Abstract-This paper presents the design and application of an efficient hybrid algorithm for solving the Optimal Reactive Power Flow (ORPF) problem. The ORPF is formulated as a nonlinear constrained optimization problem where the active power losses must be minimized. The proposed approach is based on the hybridization of Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Tabu-Search (TS) technique. The proposed PSO-TS approach is used to find the settings of the control variables (i.e. generation bus voltages, transformer taps, and shunt capacitor sizes) which minimize transmission active power losses. The bus locations of the shunt capacitors are identified according to sensitive buses. To show the effectiveness of the proposed method, it is applied to the IEEE 30 bus benchmark test system and is compared with PSO and TS without hybridization, along with some other published approaches. The obtained results reveal the effectiveness of the proposed method in dealing with the highly nonlinear constrained nature of the ORPF problem.

Keywords-optimal reactive power flow; active power loss minimization; hybrid methods; particle swarm optimization; tabu search; sensitive bus

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to their complex construction and operation, electrical power networks encounter several challenges. In modern power

system operation and planning, Optimal Reactive Power Flow (ORPF), which is a specific Optimal Power Flow (OPF) and a highly constrained large-scale non-linear optimization problem, has emerged as one of the major problems and intensively explored topics. The goal of ORPF is to find the optimal settings for a power system under some imposed equality and inequality constraints, in order to optimize its active power loss objective [1, 2].

The objective of ORPF in power systems is to minimize real power losses while satisfying a given set of operating and physical constraints. The ORPF then provides optimal control variables settings such as generator bus voltages, output of static reactive power compensators, transformer tap-settings, shunt capacitors, etc. [3, 4]. Due to its influence on the secure and economic operation of power systems, ORPF has attracted increasing interest from electric power suppliers. Many classical approaches for solving the ORPF problem have been reported such as the gradient based approach [5, 6], linear programming [7], non-linear programming [8, 9], quadratic programming [10], and interior point [11]. However, these methods have some disadvantages in solving complex ORPF problems, namely premature convergence, algorithmic complexity, and the local minima entrapment [12]. In order to overcome these drawbacks, researchers have applied

evolutionary and meta-heuristic algorithms such as the Genetic Algorithm (GA) [13], Differential Evolution (DE) [14], Artificial Physics Optimization (APO) [15], Sunflower Optimization (SFO) [16], Evolutionary Programming (EP) [17], Stud Krill Herd Algorithm (SKHA) [18], Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA) [19] and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [20, 21]. PSO in particular has received increased attention from researchers because of its searching capability. It was developed through simulations of a simplified social system, and has been found to be robust in solving continuous non-linear optimization problems. Generally, PSO has a more effective global searching ability at the beginning of the run and a local search near the end of the run [1]. PSO can generate high-quality solutions and has a more stable convergence than other stochastic methods. However, when solving complex multimodal problems, PSO can be trapped in local optima [22]. To overcome this drawback, PSO performance can be enhanced with a few adjustments. Hybridization is one of these modifications or techniques which, is applied to evolutionary algorithms in order to increase their efficiency and robustness [23].

Hybrid PSO has provided promising results for problems such as the power loss minimization problem [24, 25]. The novelty of this paper is that an efficient hybrid PSO with Tabu Search (PSO-TS) method is implemented to solve the ORPF problem by minimizing active power losses. The optimal locations of shunt capacitors have been identified based on sensitive buses.

To demonstrate the superiority of the proposed technique, the obtained results were compared to those given by standalone PSO and TS and some other published approaches. Simulations were performed with MATLAB using the IEEE 30-Bus benchmark system.

II. ORPF PROBLEM FORMULATION

The purpose of ORPF in a power system is to find the optimal settings of the reactive power control variables, which mainly include the generator voltages (V_G), the transformer tap-settings (T), and the shunt capacitors/reactors (Q_{sh}), to minimize the real power loss (P_{Loss}) while satisfying a given set of constraints. These comprise the power flow equations, the upper and lower limits of the control variables and the dependent variables, including mainly the PQ-bus voltages (V_{PQ}) and the reactive power out-puts of generators (Q_G). The ORPF mathematical model can be written as [14]:

$$\begin{cases} \min J(x,u) \text{ subject to} \\ g(x,u) = 0 \\ h(x,u) \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $J(x,u)$ represents the transmission active power losses, g and h are the sets of equality and inequality constraints respectively, x is the state or dependent variables vector, and u is the control or independent variables vector.

In this study, all control variables have been considered as continuous variables. The objective to be minimized is the system transmission active power losses. This objective function is expressed as [1]:

$$J(x,u) = \sum_{k=1}^{N_L} g_k (V_i^2 + V_j^2 - 2V_i V_j \cos \theta_{ij}) \quad (2)$$

where N_L is the number of transmission lines, V_i and V_j represent the voltage magnitude at buses i and j respectively, g_k is the conductance of branch k between buses i and j , and θ_{ij} is the voltage angle difference between bus i and bus j .

The elements of the state variables vector x are load bus voltage (V_L), generators' reactive power output (Q_G), and lines' apparent power flow (S_L). The control variables vector u includes the generation buses voltage (V_G), the transformer tap settings (T), and the shunt VAR compensators (Q_C). Accordingly, the x vector can be written as:

$$x^T = [V_{L_1} \dots V_{L_{N_{PQ}}}, Q_{G_1} \dots Q_{G_{N_G}}, S_{L_1} \dots S_{L_{N_L}}] \quad (3)$$

where N_G is the number of generators, N_{PQ} is the number of PQ buses (load buses). u can be expressed as:

$$u^T = [V_{G_1} \dots V_{G_{N_G}}, T_1 \dots T_{N_T}, Q_{C_1} \dots Q_{C_{N_C}}] \quad (4)$$

where N_T is the number of tap regulating transformers and N_C is the number of shunt VAR compensation.

The minimization of the above function is subject to a number of equality and inequality constraints [1] which will be detailed below:

A. Equality Constrains

These constraints reflect the physical laws governing the electrical system, known as power flow equations. They are the expression of the balance between load demand (power loss included) and generated power. The power flow equations are:

$$P_{Gi} - P_{Di} - V_i \sum_{j=1}^{N_B} V_j (G_{ij} \cos \theta_{ij} + B_{ij} \sin \theta_{ij}) = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$Q_{Gi} - Q_{Di} - V_i \sum_{j=1}^{N_B} V_j (G_{ij} \sin \theta_{ij} - B_{ij} \cos \theta_{ij}) = 0 \quad (6)$$

where P_{Gi} , Q_{Gi} are the active and reactive power of the i^{th} generator, P_{Di} , Q_{Di} are the active and reactive power demand at bus i , N_B is the total number of buses, and B_{ij} , G_{ij} are the real and imaginary parts of the $(i,j)^{th}$ element of the bus admittance matrix.

B. Inequality Constraints

1) Inequality Constraints on Security Limits

Some limits are imposed for security purposes:

- Active power generated at the slack bus:

$$P_{G,slack}^{min} \leq P_{G,slack} \leq P_{G,slack}^{max} \quad (7)$$

- Load bus voltage:

$$V_{L_i}^{min} \leq V_{L_i} \leq V_{L_i}^{max} \quad i \in N_{PQ} \quad (8)$$

- Generated reactive power:

$$Q_{G_i}^{min} \leq Q_{G_i} \leq Q_{G_i}^{max} \quad i \in N_G \quad (9)$$

- Thermal limits: the apparent power flowing in line "L" must not exceed the maximum allowable apparent power flow value (S_L^{max}):

$$S_L \leq S_L^{max}, \quad L \in N_L \quad (10)$$

2) Inequality Constraints on Control Variable Limits

The different control variables are bounded as follows:

- Generator voltage limits:

$$V_{G_i}^{\min} \leq V_{G_i} \leq V_{G_i}^{\max} \quad i \in N_{PV} \quad (11)$$

- Transformer tap limits:

$$T_i^{\min} \leq T_i \leq T_i^{\max} \quad i \in N_T \quad (12)$$

- Shunt capacitor limits:

$$Q_{C_i}^{\min} \leq Q_{C_i} \leq Q_{C_i}^{\max} \quad i \in N_C \quad (13)$$

where $P_{G,slack}$ is the real power generation at the slack bus, V_{G_i} is the voltage magnitude at generator bus i , T_i is the tap ratio of the transformer i , Q_{C_i} is the reactive power compensation source at bus i , and N_{PQ} is the number of PQ bus. $(\cdot)^{\max}$ and $(\cdot)^{\min}$ are the upper and lower limits of the considered variables respectively.

The objective functions of equality and inequality constraints, are non-linear functions and they depend on control variables. Therefore, ORPF is a constrained non-linear optimization problem with multiple local minima [26]. The equality constraints given by (5) and (6) are met by solving the load-flow problem. The inequality constraints given by (11)-(13) should be maintained during the solution evolution, while (7)-(9) should be handled by additional techniques.

III. THE PROPOSED HYBRID ALGORITHM

Hybridization is a way of combining two techniques in a judicious manner, so that the resulting algorithm contains the positive features of both algorithms. The success of the meta-heuristic optimization algorithms depends to a large extent on the careful balance between the two conflicting goals: exploration (diversification) and exploitation (intensification). In order to achieve these two goals, the algorithms use local search techniques, global search approaches, or integrations of both, commonly known as hybrid methods [23]. For the ORPF problem, different hybridizations with PSO have been used to improve the algorithm's performance by avoiding premature convergence. For instance, PSO has been hybridized with the linear interior point method [27], fuzzy logic [28, 29], Pareto optimal set [30], Grey wolf technique [31], DE [32], multi-agent systems [1], imperialist competitive algorithm [33], GA [34], and chaotic bat algorithm [35]. Tabu search was used to solve OPF [36] and it is hybridized with harmony search algorithm to solve the reactive power flow problem [37]. Both algorithms (PSO, TS) and their hybridization (PSO-TS) for solving the ORPF problem are discussed below.

A. Particle Swarm Optimization

PSO is a population-based evolutionary computation technique. The main idea is to evolve the population (particles) of initial solutions in a search space in order to find the best solution. This evolution is an analogy of the behavior of some species as they look for food, like a flock of birds or a school of fish [38]. These particles move through the search domain with a specified velocity in search of the optimal solution. Each particle maintains a memory which helps it in keeping the track

of its previous best position. The positions of the particles are distinguished as personal best and global best. The swarm of particles evolves in the search space by modifying their velocities according to the following equations [23]:

$$v_i^{k+1} = w_i v_i^k + c_1 rand \times (pbest_i - x_i^k) + c_2 rand \times (gbest - x_i^k) \quad (14)$$

where v_i^k is the current velocity of particle i at iteration k , w_i is the inertia weight, $rand$ is a random number between 0 and 1, c_1 and c_2 are the acceleration coefficients, $pbest_i$ is the best position of the current particle achieved so far, $gbest$ is the global best position achieved by all informants, and x_i^k is the current position of particle i at iteration k .

The new position of each particle is given by:

$$x_i^{k+1} = x_i^k + v_i^{k+1} \quad (15)$$

The inertia weighting factor for the velocity of particle i is defined by the inertial weight approach [24]:

$$w_i = w_{max} - \frac{w_{max} - w_{min}}{iter_{max}} \times k \quad (16)$$

where $iter_{max}$ is the maximum number of iterations, k is the current iteration number, and w_{max} and w_{min} are the upper and lower limits of the inertia weighting factor.

The efficiency of PSO has been proved in a wide range of optimization problems. However, constrained non-linear optimization problems have not been widely studied with this method. The authors in [39] were the first to try to adapt PSO to constrained non-linear problems. The penalty function approach is used in this paper due to its simplicity of implementation and its proven efficiency for many constrained non-linear optimization problems. The ORPF objective function is then modified as follows [22]:

$$F_T = F + K_P (P_{G,slack} - P_{G,slack}^{lim})^2 + K_V \sum_{i=1}^{N_{PQ}} (V_{L_i} - V_{L_i}^{lim})^2 + K_Q \sum_{i=1}^{N_G} (Q_{G_i} - Q_{G_i}^{lim})^2 + K_S \sum_{i=1}^{N_L} (S_{L_i} - S_{L_i}^{lim})^2 \quad (17)$$

where F is the total active power loss given by (2), K_P , K_V , K_Q and K_S are the penalty factors of the slack bus generator, bus voltage limit violation, generator reactive power limit violation, and line flow violation respectively.

$P_{G,slack}^{lim}$, $V_{L_i}^{lim}$, $Q_{G_i}^{lim}$ and $S_{L_i}^{lim}$ are defined as follows:

$$P_{G,slack}^{lim} = \begin{cases} P_{G,slack}^{\min} & \text{if } P_{G,slack} < P_{G,slack}^{\min} \\ P_{G,slack}^{\max} & \text{if } P_{G,slack} > P_{G,slack}^{\max} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

$$V_{L_i}^{lim} = \begin{cases} V_{L_i}^{\min} & \text{if } V_{L_i} < V_{L_i}^{\min} \\ V_{L_i}^{\max} & \text{if } V_{L_i} > V_{L_i}^{\max} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

$$Q_{G_i}^{lim} = \begin{cases} Q_{G_i}^{\min} & \text{if } Q_{G_i} < Q_{G_i}^{\min} \\ Q_{G_i}^{\max} & \text{if } Q_{G_i} > Q_{G_i}^{\max} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

$$S_{L_i}^{lim} = \begin{cases} S_{L_i}^{\max} & \text{if } S_{L_i} > S_{L_i}^{\max} \\ 0 & \text{if } S_{L_i} \leq S_{L_i}^{\max} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

B. The Tabu Search Method

TS is a meta-heuristic proposed in 1986 that guides a local heuristic search procedure to explore the solution space beyond

local optimality. This technique uses an operation called "move" to define the neighborhood of any given solution. One of the main components of TS is its use of adaptive memory, which creates a more flexible search behavior [40]. The simplest of these processes consists in recording in a tabu list the features of the visited regions on the space search, which provides a means to avoid revisiting already inspected solutions and thus avoid becoming trapped in local optima.

C. The Hybrid PSO-TS Approach Applied to ORPF

Several arguments support the hybridization of PSO with TS. Firstly, PSO is a global population-based algorithm while TS proposes a fast local search mechanism. Secondly, the incorporation of TS into PSO enables the algorithm to maintain population diversity. Finally, TS is integrated to prevent PSO from falling into local optima. To this end, TS is proposed to serve as a local optimizer of the best local solutions (*pbest*). The *pbest* solutions of PSO are the inputs of the TS diversification procedure. For each solution *s*, a neighborhood list is defined. Candidate solutions from the list are examined and the best one becomes the new current solution that replaces *s*. The move leading to the solution *s* is saved in the tabu list, called *best_list*. This process is repeated to produce successive new solutions until a defined stopping criterion is satisfied. The neighborhoods of a solution *s* are defined by hyper-rectangles introduced in [41]. A hyper-rectangle of *s* with a radius *r* is the space containing solutions *s'* such that the distance between *s* and *s'* is less than *r*. To generate *m* neighbors for the solution *s*, *m* hyper-rectangles centered on *s* are created, and a point is randomly chosen from each of them. The best of the *m* chosen points then replaces *s*. The search procedure of PSO-TS algorithm will terminate whenever the predetermined maximum number of generations is reached, or whenever the global best solution does not improve over a predetermined number of iterations. The diversification procedure is outlined in the algorithm in Figure 1, while the general flowcharts of the proposed PSO-tabu search are given in Figure 2.

```

Inputs
  pbest; // best historical solution of particles
  pbestval; solutions values
  m; //neighborhood size
  r; //radius of hyper-rectangles
  eps; //threshold for accepting new solution
  best_list = (pbest, r); // Initializing the tabu list best_list
Repeat
  For each solution s(VGi, Ti, Qci) in pbest
  //generation of m neighbors
  i=1
  While i <= m
  Generate the hyper-rectangle of radius r*i around s,
  choose randomly a solution NS in the hyper-rectangle
  If NS ∉ best_list then
    add the move to best_list;
    if eval(NS)-pbestval(s) ≤ eps then update
    pbestval and pbest
    s = NS;
  End if
  i=i+1;
End While
Until (stopping criteria)
    
```

Fig. 1. Tabu search procedure (diversification).

Fig. 2. Flowchart of the proposed PSO-TS algorithm.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this study, the proposed PSO-TS based reactive power optimization approach was applied to the IEEE 30-bus power system shown in Figure 3 with 12 control variables. Two cases were considered. In the first case, we kept the shunt capacitors on their initial buses [24]. In the second case, the capacitors were installed at the most sensitive buses. A sensitive bus is a load bus which requires the installation of a shunt capacitor. To identify this type of buses and their number, we removed the load from each load bus and calculated the active power losses (P_{Loss}) each time. The bus giving the least active power losses was considered as the most sensitive bus. Table I shows the classification of the sensitive buses according to the new values of the active power losses when the loads of these buses were eliminated. From this Table we can see that the most sensitive buses are: 7, 21, 30, 24, and 19. Therefore, the 2 available shunt capacitors will be installed at buses 7 and 21. All inequality constraints (7)-(13) were taken into consideration. The simulations were carried out in Matlab 7.3 on a Pentium® 3.4GHz computer with 1GB total memory. The PSO-TS parameter selection is a challenging task not only for this algorithm but also for other meta-heuristic algorithms. The parameter settings used in the proposed PSO-TS algorithm, namely initial inertia weight, acceleration factors, number of generations, swarm size, tabu list length, total number of neighborhoods, and neighborhood radius are shown in Table II.

Fig. 3. Single-line diagram of the IEEE 30 bus test system.

TABLE I. CLASSIFICATION OF THE SENSITIVE BUSES

Load bus	New P_{Loss} (MW)	Load bus	New P_{Loss} (MW)
7	4.787	10	5.696
21	4.816	14	5.707
30	5.040	23	5.769
24	5.271	18	5.771
19	5.306	16	5.838
17	5.487	20	5.850
15	5.517	3	5.944
12	5.670	29	5.944
4	5.691		

TABLE II. CONTROL PARAMETER SETTINGS

Parameters	Value
Initial inertia weight w	0.9 and decreased to 0.4
Acceleration factor c_1	2
Acceleration factor c_2	2
Maximum number of generations (PSO)	200
Swarm size	20
Tabu list length	7
Number of neighborhoods	3
Neighborhood radius	0.1
Maximum number of generations (TS)	1000

This system contains 6 generator units connected to buses 1, 2, 5, 8, 11, and 13. Four regulating transformers are connected between the line numbers 6–9, 6–10, 4–12, and 27–28 and two shunt compensators were connected to buses 10 and 24. The transmission feeder number is 41. The generator voltages, transformer tap settings, and VAR injection of the shunt capacitors were considered as control variables. The voltage magnitudes of all the buses were between 0.95 and 1.1pu, transformer tap settings were within the range of 0.9-1.1pu and shunt capacitor sizes were within the interval from 0 to 30MVAR [24]. There are 12 control variables in this case, namely 6 generator voltages, 4 transformer taps and 2 capacitor banks. The initial total P_{Loss} before optimization was 5.2783MW. In the first case study, the shunt capacitors are installed at buses 10 and 24 as in [24]. In the second case study, the shunt capacitors are placed at the most sensitive buses, namely 7 and 21. Table III summarizes the results of the optimal settings and the system power losses obtained by the proposed PSO-TS approach, standalone PSO and TS, and the methods reported in [24, 25], namely CA, IP-OPF, LPAC, GPAC, and BBO. For the case 1, the results show that the dispatch optimal solutions determined by the PSO-TS led to better results. The achieved active power losses are lower than

those found by the other methods. Using the PSO-TS algorithm, power losses decrease from 5.2783MW to 4.6304MW, indicating a reduction of 12.27%, while standalone PSO and standalone TS reduce power losses by only 1.03% and 5.61% respectively. For the other optimization algorithms, the best result is given by the BBO algorithm [25] which reduces losses by 5.93%. The convergence characteristic of power loss objective function for this case is plotted in Figure 4. From Figure 5, it is clear that the results obtained in case 2 are better than those obtained in case 1. This amelioration is due to the installation of shunt capacitors at the most sensitive buses. The active power losses obtained by the PSO-TS method in case 2 decrease from 5.2783MW to 4.6095MW, indicating a reduction of 12.67% which is better than the reduction obtained in case 1. It can be concluded that the proposed PSO-TS method is able to determine a near-global optimal solution. At the same time, the proposed method succeeded in keeping the dependent variables within their limits. The convergence characteristics of power loss objective function for this case is plotted in Figure 6.

As the hardware and the software environment significantly affect the computational time, it is not possible to compare the computational time requirements of the different methods unless all the methods are run on the same hardware and are programmed using the same environment. As a rough guide, however, the average time taken by PSO-TS is 19s.

Fig. 4. Convergence characteristic of the power losses (case 1).

Fig. 5. Comparative graph of the power losses.

TABLE III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS OF THE PROPOSED AND OTHER KNOWN ALGORITHMS

Control variables	CA	IP-OPF	LPAC	GPAC	BBO	TS	PSO	PSO-TS (case 1)	PSO-TS (case 2)
V_1	1.02282	1.10000	1.02342	1.02942	1.1000	1.0684	1.1000	1.0992	1.0990
V_2	1.09093	1.05414	0.99893	1.00645	1.0943	1.0933	1.0943	1.0948	1.1000
V_5	1.03008	1.10000	0.99469	1.01692	1.0804	1.0893	1.1000	1.0766	1.0687
V_8	0.95000	1.03348	1.01364	1.03952	1.0939	1.0853	1.1000	1.0977	1.1000
V_{11}	1.04289	1.10000	1.01647	1.03952	1.1000	1.0017	0.9505	1.0837	1.1000
V_{13}	1.03921	1.01497	1.01101	1.04870	1.1000	1.0780	1.1000	1.0754	1.1000
T_{6-9}	1.07894	0.99334	1.04247	1.04225	1.1000	0.9979	1.0547	0.9257	0.9072
T_{6-10}	0.94276	1.05938	0.99432	0.99417	0.9058	0.9008	1.1000	1.0291	0.9399
T_{4-12}	1.00064	1.00879	1.00061	1.00218	0.9521	1.0337	0.9000	0.9265	0.9000
T_{27-28}	1.00693	0.99712	1.00694	1.00751	0.9638	0.9441	0.9468	0.9422	0.9149
Q_{sh10}	0.15232	0.15253	0.17737	0.17267	0.2891	0.1395	0.3000	0.2864	-
Q_{sh24}	0.06249	0.08926	0.06172	0.06539	0.1007	0.1838	0.0000	0.1363	-
Q_{sh07}									0.1285
Q_{sh21}									0.2052
P_{loss} (MW)	5.09209	5.10091	5.09212	5.09226	4.9650	5.2240	4.9819	4.6304	4.6095

Fig. 6. Convergence characteristic of the power losses (case 2).

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a new efficient hybrid PSO-TS strategy was successfully implemented to solve the ORPF problem. This problem was formulated as a highly constrained non-linear optimization problem where all realistic constraints were taken into consideration. The proposed hybrid algorithm combines the exploration ability of the PSO algorithm and the exploitation ability of TS technique. In order to illustrate the application of the proposed method, it has been tested and examined on the standard IEEE 30-bus test system. Two case studies were considered. In the first case, we kept the shunt capacitors on their initial nodes. In the second case, the capacitors were installed at the most sensitive buses. The computational results show that the proposed hybrid approach, with a judicious choice of control parameters, has the ability to converge to high quality solutions with stable convergence characteristic and good computation efficiency. The comparison of the results with TS, PSO, and with various techniques reported in the literature, confirms the superiority of the proposed method and its potential to find accurate and feasible optimal solutions for the ORPF problem.

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Challenges in the Numerical Analysis of Centrifugal Pumps

Energetic, Cavitation, and Dynamic Characteristics

Andrej Lipej

Faculty of Mechanical Engineering

University of Novo Mesto

Novo Mesto, Slovenia

andrej.lipej@fs-unm.si

Abstract-Pumps are energetic devices that are present in a wide range of industries. Their installed power varies from a few tens of watts up to hundreds of megawatts. As the energy consumption is connected with global warming and climate change, the development of pumps that have good characteristics is very important. Theoretical and experimental methods have long been utilized in the development of pumps, but recently much research has been carried out with the help of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) analysis. Certain numerical analyses can be of high quality and accurate, but special operational phenomena still occur, where special attention is required when performing analysis. This category includes operating regimes outside the Best Efficiency Point (BEP), the formation of inlet recirculation, cavitation, and the influence of wall roughness on all the above characteristics. The current paper presents the main problems that developers face when numerically analyzing the above-mentioned special operating regimes. Both numerical and experimental results are considered.

Keywords-pump; computational fluid dynamics; operation characteristics; cavitation

I. INTRODUCTION

Pumps are used in all branches of industry. Depending on the different requirements for the basic characteristics of the head (H) and the flow rate (Q), piston pumps [1] or centrifugal pumps [2] are used. Centrifugal pumps are developed to operate at a calculation point, but in reality, they operate over a wider range. The service life of a pump and the probability of various damages depend on its operating range [2]. Pumps have a theoretically defined recommended operating range, but it is not always feasible for this condition to be met. From the efficiency point of view, the pump is recommended to operate most of the time near the Best Efficiency Point (BEP). For accurate knowledge of the kinematics of the flow conditions in the pumps, the best option is to use Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD). The use of numerical methods is an indispensable tool for the development of pumps. Numerical simulations of flow conditions are more or less accurate, depending on the operating range. At the same time, high accuracy of calculations and analysis of various characteristics in the widest possible range of operation must be achieved during the development. Stationary calculations are sufficient

for some characteristics, but in some special cases, it is necessary to use non-stationary calculations. The current article aims to present various problems that arise when using numerical methods in the development phase of centrifugal pumps and reversible pump turbines. The problems are mainly related to instabilities in pump operation and numerical instabilities. Comparisons between the measured results and the CFD analysis results are needed to better understand the problems and validate non-standard numerical procedures. The results of model measurements for most presented cases in the paper were done based on international standards [3].

In some cases, it was necessary to analyze specific properties that are rarely discussed in the literature. One such example is the consideration of wall roughness, which may be due to different influences in the operation of the pumps [4]. To the best of our knowledge, there is no literature relevant to the link between roughness and the use of a suitable turbulent model with a proper computational grid. In such cases, certain studies need to be performed for fairly fundamental properties, such as boundary layer flow analysis [5]. The influence of wall roughness on pump operation is presented in [6]. The research in the paper was focused on issues where it is necessary to perform non-usual procedures in numerical simulations. The first example is related to the instability of $H(Q)$ characteristics of different types of pumps. The stability of pump characteristic is the most important and complex design criterion. Some research has already been done in this area. A detailed description of the numerical simulation of a reversible pump turbine in pump mode is presented in [7]. A similar topic is addressed in [8], where more focus is given on the analysis of guide vanes geometry. There have been quite a few articles dealing with experimental research [9]. Another example is associated with unstable operation as a consequence of inlet recirculation. A numerical simulation of the causes and consequences of inlet recirculation is presented in [10]. Inlet recirculation has various consequences, including cavitation [11] and rotating stall [12], which can occur regardless of favorable standard cavitation characteristics. Input recirculation analysis in most cases requires the selection of a suitable turbulent model for nonstationary calculations, which is presented in [13].

The numerical analysis results presented in this paper are the result of the author's many years of research in the field of centrifugal pump development.

II. INSTABILITY OF PUMP CHARACTERISTICS

Centrifugal pumps operate under different operating conditions, depending on the magnitude of the flow Q and the head H . The relationship of the two variables is given by a function known as the H-Q characteristic. Theoretically, this function decreases with increasing flow. The shape of the function is influenced by many operating parameters, so it is not trivial to identify possible instabilities in the operation of the pump. By measurements on the model or prototype, it is possible to determine very precisely the shape of the above characteristic, but without detailed measurements of the kinematics, it is not possible to determine the possible causes of unstable areas during pump operation. By using CFD it is possible to determine the exact characteristic and also predict the causes for the formation of the so-called unstable regions in the H-Q characteristic. Since the flow conditions in the pumps are very demanding, mainly due to the diffuser effect in the fluid flow through the impeller, it is necessary to be very careful when preparing computational grids, choosing a turbulent model, determining boundary conditions, and deciding on stationary or nonstationary analysis. All numerical analyses are based on the solution of Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes system of equations, i.e. continuity equation and momentum equation. Since a region of instability in the H-Q characteristic occurs in areas where the flows are smaller than the QBEP, the flow conditions in this region are associated with several different causes of instability. The inlet angles and consequently the velocity triangles at the inlet to the pump indicate a mismatch of kinematic and geometric angles, which affects the flow conditions inside the impeller and also in the area in front of the impeller.

Fig. 1. Axial velocity component at the inlet of the impeller.

In the front of the impeller, the so-called inlet recirculation can occur, which continues downstream through the runner. The recirculation area can be detected accurately enough if quality computational grids are used. A sufficiently dense computational grid must be considered, one that provides orthogonality and all recommendations regarding the individual relationships between sides within elements and regarding the size of the adjacent elements.

Since the above phenomena are always associated with temporal changes, it is necessary to determine whether the stationary calculation is sufficiently accurate or whether a much more time-consuming non-stationary calculation needs to be used. In the presented case, it was found that stationary calculations are not the most appropriate, because they cannot describe all the effects of operating conditions on flow conditions. Cavitation and inlet recirculation of the centrifugal pumps have a significant impact on the operation and the service life of the pump. Partial flow recirculation directly affects the reliability of the pump and limits the operating range. Damage to the pressure side of the inlet blade rotor due to cavitation due to recirculation may occur. The hydraulic design of the pump should prevent many of the negative effects of cavitation due to recirculation in the pumps. The basic criterion for free-range recirculation is the suction Specific Speed (SS) of the pump.

Fig. 2. Hump zone analysis. Measurement, steady and unsteady state simulation results.

Figure 2 shows the measurement and numerical analysis results in the case where the pump characteristic has a well-defined area of instability. The results of numerical analysis differ considerably if we perform a stationary or nonstationary calculation. A comparison of the results shows that in this case, it is very important to use a non-stationary calculation that predicts the characteristics of the pump with sufficient accuracy, which is also confirmed by the comparison with the measurement results. In the case of efficiency analysis, there are no such pronounced differences between stationary and non-stationary calculations, but a slightly better result can still be observed compared to the measurement results if a non-stationary calculation is used (Figure 3). Since the numerical and experimental results agree quite well in stationary calculations, such results can mislead us and it is possible to obtain a bad result for the H(Q) characteristic. If the kinematics of the flow at the inlet to the impeller is monitored in parallel, it can be roughly determined when non-stationary calculations should be started.

The turbulent model $k-\omega$ SST is recommended for stationary calculations and the Scale-Adaptive Simulation (SAS-SST) for non-stationary analysis.

Fig. 3. Efficiency comparison.

III. NUMERICAL INSTABILITY

The numerical simulations according to different operating conditions can basically be divided into 3 main areas. The first area is near the BEP. The two others are at part load and at full load. Large differences can be observed between these 3 results if continuous monitoring of the efficiency convergence during the calculation is running. Due to the favorable flow conditions at the impeller inlet, the convergence is very stable in the optimal mode, which can be seen well in the upper curve in Figure 4. The other 2 curves represent the operating range at partial and at maximum flows. At partial flows, a small fluctuation in the efficiency of about 2% is observed and at maximum flows the instability of convergence is more than $\pm 15\%$. In particular, this must be taken into account when it is necessary to accurately predict numerically the efficiency characteristic in the wider operating range of the pump. By simultaneously monitoring the convergence of different variables, it can be determined when it is necessary to use non-stationary instead of stationary calculation. In any case, this is not always the same for all types and specific rotating pump speeds, so continuous monitoring can greatly simplify and shorten the development time of a new pump. From these results, it can be concluded that standard convergence monitoring with residual monitoring can lead to erroneous conclusions. Therefore, it is advisable to always monitor the convergence of individual variables that are important for the calculation.

Fig. 4. Efficiency comparison.

IV. INLET RECIRCULATION IN PUMPS

Inlet recirculation (Figure 5) in the pumps can cause many side effects with harmful consequences such as vibration, noise, and erosion damage. The probability of damage depends on the specific rotational speed, cavitation characteristics, and the suction energy level at the inlet.

Fig. 5. Inlet recirculation.

Fig. 6. NPSH characteristics of pump with safe range of operation.

By improving the characteristics associated with the inlet recirculation, the area where the pump operates without the risk of cavitation is increased. The maximum flow that determines non-cavitation operation is determined where the $NPSH_a$ and $NPSH_r$ curves intersect. However, by reducing the inlet vortices, it can be determined what the minimum flow must be such that there is no danger of cavitation due to the inlet recirculation. The results of the safe area of the pump, in which there will be no cavitation are presented in Figure 6. With the optimized geometry, in the case shown above, the NPSH characteristic is slightly worse, but the area at part load is significantly increased.

The flow conditions at the inlet vary greatly depending on the operating regime of the pump. Figure 7 shows two situations - without and with inlet recirculation. Under unfavorable conditions at the inlet, this is also transferred to the space between impeller blades, where various vortices are observed (Figure 8). A novelty in the numerical analysis of the inlet recirculation is the cognition that in terms of cavitation

characteristics it is not enough to analyze the NPSH parameters but the parameters related to the inlet recirculation must be also considered. Only in this way it is possible to obtain a correct assumption about the interval of the operating area without cavitation.

Fig. 7. Flow conditions in front of impeller – without (left) and with inlet recirculation (right).

Fig. 8. Flow inside the impeller – vortices.

V. WALL ROUGHNESS

The pumps are made of different materials and with different technological processes. As a result, wetted surfaces have different roughness values. In most cases, this fact does not greatly affect the performance characteristics, but there are cases where the surface roughness of the rotor blades can affect the performance characteristics. Since numerical flow analysis (CFD) has been widely used in the development of pumps in recent times, it is necessary to determine how accurately it is possible to numerically analyze the influence of wall roughness on the energy and cavitation characteristics of pumps. The first step in the numerical analysis of the flow along rough surfaces is to determine which turbulent model enables satisfactory results and how the characteristics of the computational grids affect these results (Figure 9). Figure 9 shows the difference between the theoretical and the numerical results when using different sizes of the non-dimensional parameter y^+ . It is known that the influence of roughness is closely related to the

modeling of the fluid in the boundary layer and therefore such a preliminary analysis is very welcome. From the obtained results, it was seen that the values of y^+ significantly influence the final calculation results. To analyze the use of appropriate parameters of computational grids, a numerical analysis of 2 simple examples was performed, where it was possible to compare the numerical with the theoretical results. The need to consider roughness in numerical simulations can be seen in Figure 10, where a comparison of numerical and experimental results for two smooth and rough walls is shown. These findings were used in the analysis of various pumps, where it was confirmed that even with numerical analyzes, where surface roughness is considered, it is possible to obtain useful results in the analysis of energy and cavitation characteristics.

Fig. 9. Influence of y^+ on the numerical analysis accuracy.

Fig. 10. Comparison of numerical and experimental results – smooth walls and rough walls.

In numerical analysis, the so-called sand grain equivalent should be considered instead of the classical roughness data. Another problem is the appropriate definition of computational networks in the roughness range. For the appropriate selection of the y^+ parameter, a method based on a comparison with the theoretical results was presented, which differs from the classical comparison between measurements and numerical analysis.

VI. CAVITATION

Cavitation is a physical phenomenon that occurs during the operation of various energy and working machines. This can be a particular problem with centrifugal pumps, as cavitation characteristics are very important when choosing a suitable machine in a particular system. Since cavitation also affects many other characteristics, such as operation stability, maintenance costs, and the service life of pumps, it is necessary to pay close attention to this phenomenon during the development of new machines. As engineers increasingly use CFD analysis, it is necessary to know the main pitfalls that arise in the numerical predictions of all the operating characteristics of centrifugal pumps. Qualitative numerical prediction of cavitation is performed almost routinely, which means that numerical simulations can predict the position, the size of the area, and the intensity of cavitation, but it is not always possible to accurately obtain quantitative results of certain characteristics as a result of cavitation. Determining the critical cavitation coefficient can be an even more challenging task. Figures 11 and 12 show the location and intensity of the cavitation cloud, for two different values of suction height. It can be observed that the sizes of the steam clouds vary, as at higher suction heights (Figure 12) the risk of cavitation formation is higher. In both images, it can also be observed that the cavitation intensity varies from individual impeller blades, although the geometry of the blades is identical.

Fig. 11. Cavitation inside the impeller – low suction head.

This means that there are no uniform conditions at the pump inlet or that the situation changes greatly over time. The consequence of the above-mentioned observations is the fact that it is not always possible to obtain concretely useful results using stationary calculations, but we have to use non-stationary calculations. These require significantly longer computational times, thus extending the entire development cycle. The influence of wall roughness on cavitation characteristics was also considered during the research. When predicting the efficiency by considering roughness, the obtained numerical results were quite satisfactory. A larger problem arises in the numerical simulation of cavitation considering the roughness of the walls. Figure 13 shows the results of numerical analysis of cavitation at 3 different suction heights for smooth and rough walls.

Fig. 12. Cavitation inside the impeller – high suction head.

Fig. 13. Influence of roughness on the cavitation intensity – smooth wall (top), rough wall (bottom).

Fig. 14. Comparison of NPSH characteristics for two different roughness – numerical analysis and experimental results.

In the case of rough walls, a slightly larger size of the cavitation cloud is observed, which is not observed in all similar situations. In some cases, the ground plan size of the cloud remained the same or even decreased, but the thickness of the cavitation cloud increased. In the Figure, the color scale indicates the thickness of the cavitation cloud. Roughness also

affects the NPSH characteristic. Figure 14 shows a comparison between the measurement results and the numerical results. The absolute results do not match very well, but the right trends of considering roughness in the numerical calculations are observed on the graph. In linking cavitation and roughness, it was found that it is important to consider the thickness of the cavitation area and not only the size of the cavitation clouds.

VII. CONCLUSION

The pump is one of the most important working machines in the industry. Pumps are major energy consumers and therefore special attention needs to be paid to their development phase. The pumps should operate to as high as possible efficiency without significant energy losses. They must also operate reliably with the lowest possible operating cost and their service life must be reasonably long. As numerical methods are increasingly used in the development of pumps, development engineers are facing various problems. The current article presents some of the problems that arise in the development phase when CFD analysis is used in the design. For accurate instability analysis in pump characteristics, it is recommended to analyze the kinematics of the flow at the pump inlet. When the first input vortices are observed, nonstationary calculations must be used. The $k-\omega$ SST turbulent model is recommended for stationary calculations and the SAS-SST for non-stationary analysis. Where operating conditions are far from optimum, numerical instabilities occur. It can be concluded that standard convergence monitoring with residual monitoring cannot lead to the right conclusions. Therefore, it is recommended to monitor the convergence of several variables that are important for the qualitative result in numerical analysis.

The often-overlooked consideration of wall roughness in numerical calculations has proven to be an important factor to consider at the development stage if the properties of the materials and the surface treatment technology are known. Detailed analysis revealed which computational grids are suitable for the numerical simulation of rough surfaces. Instead of the classical roughness parameters, the so-called sand grain equivalent should be considered in CFD analysis. For the appropriate selection of the y^+ parameter, a method based on the comparison with the theoretical results should be used, which differs from the classical comparison between the experimental and the numerical results. The results show that the roughness affects the efficiency and the NPSH characteristics of the pumps. The surface roughness increases the wall shear stress in the turbulent boundary layer. Sometimes the numerical results match very well with the experimental ones but in many cases the difference is still relatively big. The comparison of the numerical and experimental results shows a slight improvement of the results if wall roughness is considered. In linking cavitation and roughness, it was found that it is important to consider the thickness of the cavitation area and not only the size of the cavitation clouds. In fact, all the above phenomena are intertwined and interdependent, so in most cases, consideration and analysis of all the physical phenomena presented in the article should be done during the development phase of a new centrifugal pump. By presenting the results of individual

numerical analyses and some recommendations on how to perform them most optimally, we are far from covering all the problems that arise in numerical analysis of centrifugal pumps. However, it can be concluded that any contribution that enables development engineers to work more successfully in the development process is very welcome.

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A Novel Approach for the Modeling of Electromagnetic Forces in Air-Gap Shunt Reactors

Hung Bui Duc

School of Electrical Engineering
Hanoi University of Science and Technology
Vietnam
hung.buiduc@hust.edu.vn

Tu Pham Minh

School of Electrical Engineering
Hanoi University of Science and Technology
Vietnam
tu.phaminh@hust.edu.vn

Tuan Phung Anh

School of Electrical Engineering
Hanoi University of Science and Technology
Vietnam
tuanphunganh1@hust.edu.vn

Vuong Dang Quoc

School of Electrical Engineering
Hanoi University of Science and Technology
Hanoi, Vietnam
vuong.dangquoc@hust.edu.vn

Abstract-Shunt reactors are usually used in electrical systems to imbibe reactive powers created by capacitive powers on the lines when the system is operating on low or no loads. Moreover, they are also used to balance reactive powers and maintain the stability of a specified voltage. In general, the air gaps of a magnetic circuit shunt reactor are arranged along the iron core to reduce the influence of fringing and leakage fluxes. Therefore, non-magnetic materials made of ceramics or marbles are often used in air gaps to separate the iron core packets. The direction of the fringing flux is perpendicular to the laminations, so the core packets of the shunt reactor are generally made from radially laminated silicon steels. Due to the alternating electromagnetic field through the core, a periodically altered electromagnetic force is produced between the core packets, tending to compress the ceramic spacers. This electromagnetic force causes vibration and noise in the core. In this research, a finite element approach based on the Maxwell stress tensor was developed to compute the magnetic flux density and the electromagnetic forces appearing in a shunt reactor.

Keywords-shunt reactor; air gaps; magnetic flux density; electromagnetic force; Maxwell stress tensor

I. INTRODUCTION

A Shunt Reactor (SR) is an important component widely used in power transmission systems to improve stability and efficiency. Parasitic capacitance occurs in a line when the system is working under low or no load. Especially for a long line, its value is very large and leads to a voltage increase, causing an overvoltage at its end. Hence, to maintain voltage stability according to the regulations and balance the reactive power in electrical systems, the SR is proposed to absorb the excess reactive power created by the line capacitance [1-4]. In addition, in order to reduce the magnetic flux and to avoid the saturation of the magnetic circuit, air gaps are added in the iron core of the SR to increase the reluctance values. On the other hand, fringing fluxes appear around the air gaps [6-9],

increasing the winding inductance and causing nonuniform magnetic fields in the iron core packets of the SR. Nonmagnetic materials such as ceramic or marble are often used in air gaps to separate the iron core packets. The fringing flux departs and reenters the lamination perpendicularly, so the core packets of the SR are generally made from radially laminated silicon steels. Because of the alternating electromagnetic field through the core, a periodically altering electromagnetic force is produced between the core packets, tending to compress the ceramic spacers. The force on the core packets is a Maxwell force that causes vibration and noise. Maxwell forces are acting at twice the power frequency due to the sinusoidal flux passing through the windings at the power frequency.

Many researchers have investigated transient situations and magnetic fields in SR or calculated the air-gap reluctance and -inductance of winding for magnetic circuits [6-12]. In [13], a method was introduced to calculate the leakage fields in air-core reactors using a 3D reluctance network. Testing problems of gapped-core reactors were presented in [14, 15]. Some researchers investigated the temperature field distribution [16, 17]. In this research, a Finite Element Method (FEM) based on Maxwell stress tensor theory [18] was developed for an iron core gapped SR to compute the magnetic flux density and the electromagnetic force on the core packets. These fields are the inherent reason for the vibration and noise and tend to compress the ceramic spacers.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. The Structure of a Gapped-Core Shunt Reactor

The structure of an SR is illustrated in Figure 1. The mid limb with the non-magnetic gaps is enclosed by the winding. The winding is also enclosed by a frame of core steel providing the return path for the magnetic field. Three single-phase SRs are connected to provide a three-phase transmission line. A

Corresponding author: Hung Bui Duc

three-phase SR can also be used, having 3 or 5 limbed cores. Figure 1(b) shows a three-limbed core SR having a strong magnetic coupling between the 3 phases. A 5-limbed core is shown in Figure 1(c), where the phases are magnetically independent due to the enclosing magnetic frame formed by the two yokes and the two unwound side-limbs. The gapped core limbs are built of core packets. The core packet type is further classified into parallel and radially laminated core types by the core packet laminating methods. The parallel laminated core type has steel plates in parallel in the same direction as the power transformer core, and the radially laminated core type is constructed as a cylindrical core packet by laminating steel plates in the radial direction arranged in a wedge-shaped pattern [14]. The core packet is filled with epoxy resin and molded into one solid unit.

Fig. 1. Modeling of the shunt reactor: (a) single-phase, (b) 3-phase 3-limbed core, (c) 3-phase 5-limbed core [6].

The vibration in the SRs is usually higher than in transformers as a result of the magnetic forces between the consecutive core packets. Therefore, the core is designed to eliminate excessive vibrations. The non-magnetic gaps are established by using cylindrical spacers to take the large magnetic forces appearing between the discs in a gapped core SR. The height of the distance spacer is equal to the height of the air gap. The core packets are stacked and cemented together to form a core limb column. Dimensional stability and core tightness can be fixed by an epoxy impregnated polyester material and a fiberglass cloth of a few millimeters between the last limb packet and the top/bottom yoke. The yokes and side limbs, normally with a rectangular cross-section, make up the magnetic circuit.

B. Parameters of the Shunt Reactor

A single-phase SR of 35MVA_r (500/√3kV and 50Hz) was considered to calculate the electromagnetic force in the core packets. A simple model of this single-phase SR is shown in Figure 2. The volume of the air gaps was determined by the equations describing the magnetic circuit model. It should be noted that this volume depends on the main parameters of the shunt reactor, i.e. reactive power, magnetic inductance, winding inductance, frequency, and energy storage in the winding space air gap. Iron materials have usually a high magnetic permeability ($\mu = \mu_r \mu_0$) compared to the air gap permeability (μ_0). Therefore, the reluctance of the magnetic core is very small, compared to the reluctance of the air gaps, and can be neglected in the equivalent magnetic circuit. In addition, the winding resistance is normally very small compared to the inductance and can be neglected when defining the parameters of the electric circuits. From the relationship between the Magnetomotive Force (MMF), magnetic flux, and reluctances of the magnetic circuit, the magnetic flux density on the core can be determined via the reactive power and the volume of the air gap as:

$$B_m = \sqrt{\frac{Q}{\frac{\pi}{\mu_0} \cdot f \cdot V_g}} \quad (1)$$

where B_m , V_g , and μ_0 are the maximum flux density, the air gap volume, and air permeability respectively. The obtained results of the SR of 35MVA_r are shown in Table I [10]

Fig. 2. Model of the shunt reactor.

TABLE I. SR RESULTS BY THE ANALYTIC METHOD

Parameters	Notation	Results
Reactive power	Q (MVA _r)	35
Rated voltage	U (kV)	$500/\sqrt{3}$
Rated current	I (A)	121,24
Total inductance	L (H)	7.5788
Core dimension	D_c (mm)	673
Height of core	H_c (mm)	1758
Total air gap length	l_g (mm)	363
Turn number	N (turn)	2166
Width of winding	W_w (mm)	248
Height of winding	H_w (mm)	1488

C. Calculation of the Electromagnetic Force

In the gapped core of the SR, vibrations can be very high due to the magnetic forces between the consecutive core packets. Thus, the ceramic spacers and any other gap materials should tolerate these forces without any significant shrinkage. The electromagnetic force acting on the core packets can be computed by either the Maxwell stress tensor approach or the virtual work method [20]. This force is given by:

$$F = \frac{\Delta W}{\Delta x} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{B^2}{\mu_0} A_c, \quad (2)$$

where A_c is the cross-sectional area, and Δx is the translation of a body. The surface force density is therefore given by:

$$F_s = \frac{F}{A_c} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{B^2}{\mu_0} \quad (\text{N/m}^2) \quad (3)$$

The higher the operating flux density, the higher the attractive force is. Therefore, the operation flux density is typically lower than the value used sometimes in power transformers. According to (2), it is necessary to increase the total volumic air gap to reduce the magnetic flux density. The force between the core packets can be calculated by (3) if the flux distribution is uniform. However, as the flux distribution in the SR is non-uniform, the finite element approach is generally applied with the virtual work principles. The magnetic flux density can be determined through the MMF and the air gap parameters as:

$$B = \frac{F}{A_c} = \mu_0 \frac{I \cdot N}{l_g} \quad (4)$$

The surface force density can also be calculated by:

$$F_S = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\mu_0 I^2 N^2}{l_g} \quad (\text{N/m}^2) \quad (5)$$

The Maxwell stress tensor approach is widely used for computing electromagnetic forces. When ignoring the magnetostriction, the distribution of the magnetic forces in the core packets can be defined as:

$$F_v = -\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{H} \cdot \mathbf{H} \nabla \mu \quad (6)$$

On the material surface, F_v can be written in terms of normal and tangential components as:

$$\begin{aligned} F_v &= -\frac{1}{2} (H_t^2 + H_n^2) \nabla \mu \\ &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(H_t^2 + \frac{B_n^2}{\mu^2} \right) \nabla \mu \quad (7) \\ &= -\frac{1}{2} (H_t^2 \nabla \mu - B_n^2 \nabla v) \end{aligned}$$

since $\frac{\nabla \mu}{\mu^2} = -\nabla v$, where reluctivity is $v = \frac{1}{\mu}$.

The force density at the surface can be defined as:

$$F_s = -\frac{1}{2} (H_t^2 (\mu_0 - \mu) - B_n^2 (v_0 - v)) n \quad (8)$$

where n is the unit normal vector to the surface. In the gapped-core SR, the force density between two packets can be determined by (8), which when the fringing effect is negligible ($H_t=0$) becomes:

$$F_s = \frac{1}{2} (B_n^2 (v_0 - v)) n \quad (9)$$

The reluctivity v of the core material in (9) is negligible. Thus, the magnitude of the force per unit area perpendicular to the surface can be expressed as:

$$F_s = \frac{1}{2} \frac{B^2}{\mu_0} \quad (\text{N/m}^2) \quad (10)$$

This force is a function of the square of the flux density. The higher the operating flux density, the higher the forces of attraction are.

D. Modeling of the Shunt Reactor via a Finite Element Approach

Maxwell's equations and the constitutive laws of the problem are written as [10-13]:

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \quad (11)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{J} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t} \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A} \quad (14)$$

The value of the magnetic flux density B corresponding to the magnetic field intensity H is:

$$B = \mu H \quad (15)$$

The magnetization forces were calculated by applying the Maxwell stress tensor locally. The Maxwell stress tensor for magnetic fields is a 3×3 matrix and has a unit of N/m²:

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} B_x H_x - \frac{1}{2} BH & B_x H_y & B_x H_z \\ B_y H_x & B_y H_y - \frac{1}{2} BH & B_y H_z \\ B_z H_x & B_z H_y & B_z H_z - \frac{1}{2} BH \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_x \\ n_y \\ n_z \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

This is also a suitable approach for computing the force distributions. The divergence of the stress tensor f_v is defined by the volume force density in (16a), while the volume force is defined in (16b):

$$f_v = \nabla \cdot T \quad (16a)$$

$$F_v = \int_v \nabla \cdot T dv \quad (16b)$$

The force on the surface of the core packets can be obtained by:

$$F_s = \int_s T ds \quad (17)$$

The tangential F_t and the normal F_n components of the force F per unit area on an elemental surface can be expressed in terms of the tangential and normal field components as:

$$F_t = B_n H_t \quad (18a)$$

$$F_n = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} B_n^2 - \mu_0 H_t^2 \right) \quad (18b)$$

Both the normal component of B and the tangential component of H should be determined. In this part, the FEM was used to determine the modeled SR parameters, utilizing the Ansys Maxwell software [20]. The accuracy and the validity of FEM have been proven in recent studies [10, 12, 19]. Due to the anisotropy of the magnetic properties, a set of 3D laminated coordinate systems was defined considering the anisotropy of magnetic properties for laminated silicon steel in the Rolling Direction (RD), the Transverse Direction (TD), and the Lamination Direction (LD). The models of all parts (yokes, core packets, windings) in the 3D coordinate system were created, and core packets are shown in Figure 3(a). Then, the lamination direction of the yokes and all core packets was chosen in the 3D laminated coordinate systems. The core packet of the SR was generally made from radially laminated silicon steels, as shown in Figure 3(c). The mapping between the laminated and the rectangular spatial coordinate systems is presented in Table II.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mapping distributions of the magnetic flux density in the SR core are presented in Figure 4. The magnetic flux density in the SR model is shown in Figure 4(a)-(b). The distribution of the magnetic flux density on a core packet, generally made from radially laminated silicon steels as Figure 3(c), is presented in Figure 4(c). The magnetic flux density is unevenly distributed, especially in the core packets. The magnetic flux density around the core's corner is larger than in its interior due to the characteristics of the SR, which has air gaps between the core packets to increase the reluctance of the magnetic circuit. However, the fringing flux around the air gaps

increases the magnetic flux around the iron core packets. Together with the fringing flux, it is directed to the laminated silicon steel in the transverse direction, which has worse magnetic properties than the rolling direction. The magnetic flux density along the lines Y1-Y2 and Y3-Y4 is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 3. 3D model of the single-phase SR and the radially laminated silicon steels.

TABLE II. MAPPING BETWEEN THE TWO COORDINATE SYSTEMS

Part	RD	TD	LD
Core packets	z-axis	Perpendicular z-axis	Radial as a fan-shaped
Top and bottom yokes	x-axis	z-axis	y-axis
Side yokes	z-axis	x-axis	y-axis

Fig. 4. The magnetic flux density on the magnetic circuit and iron core packets.

Fig. 5. Magnetic flux density along the lines Y1-Y2 and Y3-Y4 on the surface of a core packet.

In the same way, the magnetic flux density around the outermost edge is highlighted in Figure 5. It is significantly larger than the rest, while this magnetic flux density is directly related to the electromagnetic force acting on the core packets. This electromagnetic force component will act on the ceramic plates that separate the core packets. The distribution of the force density on the surface of the core packets is shown in Figure 6. In the gapped-core SR, the magnetic force acts between the core packets like close electromagnets and can be interpreted as attractive forces that try to minimize the gap length. Due to the very high magnetic attraction forces between the core packets, the ceramic spacers and any other air gap material should tolerate these forces without any significant

shrinking. As shown in (14), these forces are a function of the square of the flux density, and thus the higher the operating flux density, the higher the forces of attraction are. The operating flux density is typically lower than the value usually used in power transformers. The cut values of the electromagnetic force density on the lines Y1-Y2 and Y3-Y4 on the core's surface are shown in Figure 7. It can be observed that these forces have the same value but in the opposite direction.

Fig. 6. Distribution of the force density on the surface of the core packets.

Fig. 7. Distribution of force density along the lines Y1-Y2 and Y3-Y4 on the core surface.

Figures 5 and 7 show that the electromagnetic force results are similar to the magnetic field results. The electromagnetic force around the outermost edge is also significantly larger than in the rest. Figure 8 shows the post-processing normal forces acting on the top and bottom surfaces of the core packets. The positive normal forces are linked to the top surfaces of the core packets, whereas the negative normal forces are linked to the bottom surfaces. As shown in Figures 6 and 8, the forces acting on the top and bottom surfaces of each core packet are in the opposite directions and have approximately the same magnitude, resulting in a net force acting close to zero on each core packet. The ceramic spacers are in contact with the bottom surfaces of the upper core and the top surfaces of the lower core packets. Due to the two surface forces acting on the ceramic spacer in the opposite directions, these spacers suffer huge compression forces and should withstand approximately 257.5kN/m² or 26.3Ton/m². If the flux density on the iron cores is doubled, these forces will increase 4 times to over

100Ton/m². To withstand the very high forces acting on the ceramic spacers, their height has to be precisely uniform to ensure a uniform force distribution on all the ceramic spacers. Usually, the spacers are first glued to the core packet and then grinded to be equal. This result explains why during the design of shunt reactors, the flux density of their core should be smaller than the core of the power transformer, even using the same magnetic material.

Fig. 8. Force density distribution along the lines Y1-Y2 and Y3-Y4 on the surface of the core packets.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the electromagnetic forces on the core packets of a shunt reactor by both the virtual work method and the Maxwell stress tensor approach. In both methods, the normal forces are a function of the square of the flux density. Finite element approach, using Ansys Maxwell software, was applied to compute the magnetic flux density distribution and the normal surface forces density on the core packets. The forces acting on the top and bottom surfaces of each core packet are in opposite directions and have approximately the same magnitude, resulting in a near-to-zero net force acting on each core packet. However, as the surface forces act on the ceramic spacers in opposite directions, they become huge compression forces. Therefore, these results will be useful to researchers, design engineers, and manufacturers when choosing the appropriate magnetic flux density on the core in order to control the electromagnetic forces acting on the spacers between the core packets.

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